

WORLD LAW COURT, 'SINGAPORE' (PHOENIX-LAND)

DOCTOR OF LAWS DISSERTATION (Part 2)

LEGAL SECTION: 6 – 8

MAIN TITLE: **THE DOCTOR OF LAWS CRIMINAL TECHNICAL
MATERIALS & EVIDENCE: THE NEUROMORPHIC LAW**

This original document contains criminal evidence.

**LYNETTE LIN TAIXUN
2023 - OCT 2024**

THE LAW ON NEUROMORPHIC NEURAL-LINK SYSTEM

The Genocidal Case of COVID (Bio-W 1) and COVAX (BIG-PHARMA Bio-W 2) Hospital-Synapse-Cryptocurrencies-(CO-VAX-Neural-)CHIP with 2-Tier RF data transmission with Vax-cert **Neurogrid** under International Criminal Law: Chip-Genocide / Chip-Systematic Crime / Chip-War Crime with injected CO-VAX (transmitter circuitry: meta-CORE) CHIP **Neural LINKED 5/6G Network** BIG-MONEY(-BANKH BIS, Tier 1 Computer Central Banks, Tier 2 Commercial banks Pilot Test subjects)

with BIG-TANKH 5/6G (DEW) Satellite (DEW 9/11 Teleportation) Log-on (SPACE-ANKH) E-vessels: CO-VAX CHIP SCAN bodily cells, crafts, land scan) **Neuromorphic System** Cells Mutation: 060606 BEAST SLAVES Teleportation on crypto-‘reward’ neural tracker log-on vector parameters algorithmic computation logic, super soldiers cloning technology, electronic brain theft (CHIP memory mapper deployable inference) with in-brain e-token system

and The Modus Operandi of Synapse-Currencies (Synapse-Dollar (USMCA PLOT) SG 1965 / Synapse-Yuan Yen Won PLOT PLUS 3 PLOT: TERMINATED, Synapse-NORDIC-EURO-SWISS PLOT and Computer programmable Chipped Tier 1 BoE E-wallet Tier 2 (Digital Computer Central Banks = Computerized Digits)

under X100PLUS MILITARY nations duped or under manufactured labeled¹ (void) grouped nations (EM LOGO) under international law for global criminal purposes

Doctor of Laws Document: International criminal law, Pharmaceutical Law (Medi-crime Law / ‘Counterfeit’ Medi-Products Law), (DEATH PENALTY WHO) Bio-medicine law, (DEATH PENALTY WEF BIS fraudsters) Telecommunications law and (DEATH PENALTY INFRA-CHIP AIIB WB) Space law. Criminal technical specifications BASIC blueprints.

¹ * manufactured grouped nations refers to: a set of computers banks of synapses (USMCA PLOT, Euro Nordic Swiss PLOT (EMU CHIP), fabricated EM LOGO ‘asean’ SG 1965 Plot Plus 3 TERMINATED and others e.g. mRNA x G30 G20 G7, Neurogrid 100 PLUS Military Duped X 60Y - 500 Y) null (void under international law: Satellite RF CHIP-crime against mankind, severely disabled (organ damage) (for criminal purposes).

She is certified with the Council of Europe with certifications in European Law including: Data Protection Law, Pharmaceutical Law (/ Medi-crime Law), Transitional Justice (International Criminal Law: Genocide, Crimes Against Humanity, War Crimes), Cybersecurity Law, International Human Rights Law and Judicial Ethics for Judges and Prosecutors.

She worked as a lay Singapore prosecutor drafting court documents (legal findings based on evidence / statute, legal analyses, recommended guilt charges), submitted written appeals to members of parliament and interviewing of witnesses' process.

This original work is the sole legal property of Lynette Lin Taixun.

Announcements:

Beyond Phoenix-South pre-med x 60 Plus 3 Dragons 1,2,3-East Anti-Glyph Group Label, USMCA PLOT Nordic PLOT etc Doctor of Laws Neuromorphic Law Criminal Technical Materials VIDEO-Explanations: <https://www.youtube.com/@JudgeLynette>

VIDEO-ID EVIDENCE (Judgment) COMPUTE X 60 Msian Singa Cement PER Legislative Theft + Illegal 'A' Disconnect ports PERP-ID + PER Cement stacked 'oc' refugees dump x 60 by refugees + PoS + % + ETERNAL LAND original: Farmland + Stone Temple + Exotic + Tropical: <https://www.youtube.com/@WLCJUDGE/videos>

Registration (under Phoenix Dollar): internationallaw7777@gmail.com

Phoenix Bank + Tri-Solar Tech Trades + Phoenix Rocket (Phoenix Chip, Dragon Chip)

Required: War Crimes 'B'-TOMS PERP-ID (MONEY + LAND-Train route Satellite-ID)

X500 Gold Compute = WB-WT spawn, consistent Anti-Glyph Nations: Combined Gold

TTT = Simulation 'take-out' + BLUEPRINT / TEXTBOOKS / PROTOTYPE

WLC PATENT REGISTRATION

LEGAL SECTION 6:

LAW EVIDENCE EXAMINATION SECTION: UNDER LAW RESEARCH FRAMEWORK

6.1. Examination of Evidence under Law Research Framework: Neuromorphic Circuit / Meta-Core / Radio Frequency ID / [Waves of EEG Analysis \(Brain Vector, Neural Parameterization\)](#)

[Criminal Technical Analysis of Perpetrator Testing The Computer Won CHIP: Neuromorphic Synaptic \('Pulse'\) Memory Array Circuit, Phase Change Memory and Law Evidence Examination under International Criminal Law](#)

6.2. Criminal Technical Analysis of Perpetrator Testing The Computer Won CHIP: EEG Sensor (Medi-Crime Products) under Pharmaceutical Law (/Medi-crime Law / 'Counter-feit' Medi-Products) and Bio-Medicine Law

EXAMINATION OF COMPUTER WON

6. LAW EVIDENCE EXAMINATION SECTION: INTERNATIONAL COMPUTER MONEY-'WON' (FALSE VERSION) AND SYNAPSE-'WON' (CRIMINALLY ACCURATE VERSION)

International Computer (NOT MONEY) Korean WON Model: Computer Bank of Korea (Criminal Technical Analysis)

6.0 COMPUTER MONEY-'WON' MODEL PROGRAMMABLE E-WALLET (NOT MONEY): COMPUTER BANK OF KOREA (FALSE VERSION)

6.0. Programmable E-Wallet (NOT MONEY) Computer 'Won': Computer Bank of Korea (PLUS 3 PLOT)

6.0. Bank of Korea (e-NON-money ILLEGAL) Payment and Settlement Systems Department (2022)

Central Bank Digital Currencies – 1st Proof of Concept Experiments. Available:

<https://www.bok.or.kr/eng/main/contents.do?menuNo=400411>

6.1. LAW EVIDENCE EXAMINATION SECTION: COMPUTER WIFI PROGRAMMABLE SYNAPSE-'WON' (CRIMINALLY ACCURATE VERSION)

6.1. Programmable Synapse-WON Model: Organ Stack of Korea (Criminal Technical Analysis)

6.1. COMPUTER WIFI PROGRAMMABLE SYNAPSE-'WON' (THE CRIMINALLY ACCURATE VERSION)

Programmable Synapse-WON Model: Organ Stack of Korea (Criminal Technical Analysis)

[UNDER DATA PROTECTION LAW \(CONVENTION 108+\)](#)

6.1 NEUROMORPHIC PRODUCTS TYPE

SAMSUNG (TEXAS): NEUROMORPHIC SYSTEM (KOREAN)

6.1.1. Samsung Patent 1: Neuromorphic Memory Circuit and Operating Method (2023) (Sang Bum Kim)

6.1.2. Samsung Model 2: Neuromorphic Peripheral Circuits For Neuromorphic Synaptic Memory Array Based on Neuron Models (Sang Bum Kim)

6.1.3. Samsung Model 3: Neuromorphic Memory Circuit (2038) (Sang Bum Kim)

6.1.4. Samsung Model 4: System to Duplicate Neuromorphic Core Functionality (2038) (Sang Bum Kim)

6.1.5. IBM Model A: Pulsing Synaptic Devices Based on Phase-Change Memory to Increase Linearity in Weight Update (Sang Bum Kim)

6.1.6. Samsung Model 5: Phase Change Memory with Metastable Set and Reset States (Sang Bum Kim)

6.1.7. Samsung Model B: Artificial Neuron Apparatus (Evangelos S. Eleftheriou)

6.1.8. IBM Model 1: Neuromorphic Memory Circuit Using A Dendrite Leaky Integrate and Fire (LIF) Charge (2035) (Sang Bum Kim)

6.1.9. IBM Model 2: Communicating Post-Synaptic Neuron Fires to Neuromorphic Cores (2037) (Sang Bum Kim)

6.1.1. Sang Bum Kim, Uicheol Shin and Suyeon Jang. (2023) United States Patent Office. ('Google Patent') Patent No. US 2023/0119915 A1. Available: <https://patents.google.com/patent/US20230119915A1/en?q=US20230119915A1>

6.1.2. Kohji Hosokawa, Masatoshi Ishii, SangBum Kim, Chung H. Lam and Scott C. Lewis (2020) *Neuromorphic Peripheral Circuits For Neuromorphic Synaptic Memory Array Based on Neuron Models*. United States Patent Office. ('Google Patent') Patent No. US 10,810,489 B2. Available: <https://patents.google.com/patent/US10810489B2/en?q=US10810489B2>

[SAMSUNG INVENTOR]

6.1.9. Kohji Hosokawa, SangBum Kim and Chung H. Lam. (2019) *Communicating Post-synaptic Neuron Fires to Neuromorphic Cores*. United States Patent Office. ('Google Patent') Patent No. US 10,417,559 B2. Available: <https://patents.google.com/patent/US10417559B2/en?q=US10417559B2>

[IBM by same SAMSUNG INVENTOR]

6.1.3. SangBum Kim and Chung H. Lam (2020) *Neuromorphic Memory Circuits*. United States Patent Office. ('Google Patent') Patent No. US 10,713,562 B2. Available: <https://patents.google.com/patent/US10713562B2/en?q=US10713562B2>

6.1.4. SangBum Kim and Chung H. Lam (2017) *System to Duplicate Neuromorphic Core Functionality*. United States Patent Office. ('Google Patent') Patent No. US 2017/0364793 A1. Available: <https://patents.google.com/patent/US20170364793A1/en?q=US20170364793A1>

6.1.5. Matthew J. BrightSky, Joseph Kim, Wanki Kim, Bouvier Maxence and SangBum Kim (2016) *Pulsing Synaptic Devices Based on Phase-Change Memory to Increase The Linearity in Weight Update*. World Intellectual Property Organization. ('Google Patent') Patent No. WO2022/268416 A1. Available: <https://patents.google.com/patent/WO2022268416A1/en?q=WO2022268416A1>

6.1.6. BrightSky, Sanbum Kim, Wanki Kim and Chung H. Lam (2016) *Phase Change Memory With Metastable Set and Reset States*. United States Patent Office. ('Google Patent') Patent No. US 2016/0125936 A1. Available: <https://patents.google.com/patent/US20160125936A1/en?q=US20160125936A1>

6.1.7. Evangelos S. Eleftheriou, Angeliki Pantazi, Abu Sebastian and Tomas Tuma. (2023) *Artificial Neuron Apparatus*. United States Patent Application Publication ('Google Patent') US 10,949,735 B2. Available: <https://patents.google.com/patent/US10949735B2/en?q=US10949735B2>

6.1.8. SangBum Kim, Chung H. Lam (2017) *Neuromorphic Memory Circuit Using A Dendrite Leaky Integrate And Fire (LIF) Charge*. United States Patent Office. ('Google Patent') Patent No. US 9,830,982 B2. Available: <https://patents.google.com/patent/US9830982B2/en?q=US+9%2c830%2c982+B2>

PHARMA LAW / MEDI-CRIME LAW / ('COUNTERFEIT' MEDI-PRODUCTS) (PLACE SIGNING: MOSCOW, RUSSIA)

KEY HUMAN RIGHTS AND BIO-MEDICINE LAW AND INTERNATIONAL CRIMINAL COURT LAW (PLACE SIGNING: OVIEDO, SPAIN)

UNDER PHARMA LAW / MEDI-CRIME LAW / COUNTERFEIT MEDI-PRODUCTS (PLACE OF SIGNING: MOSCOW, RUSSIA)

KEY HUMAN RIGHTS AND BIO-MEDICINE LAW ()

INTERNATIONAL CRIMINAL COURT LAW (PLACE OF SIGNING: OVIEDO, SPAIN)

6.2. EEG SENSOR CO-VAX CHIP (CIRCUITRY) MEDI-CRIME PRODUCTS TYPE

SAMSUNG (TEXAS): COMPUTER 'CONTROLLER' CO-VAX CHIP CIRCUITRY PHARMA-AND-BIO-MEDI-COUNTERFEIT PRODUCT-CRIME

6.2.1. Samsung EEG 1A: Current Simulator Recording Cranial Nerve Signals Operation (Chisung Bae)

Samsung EEG 1B: Apparatus (FIRST SEC SWITCH, COMPARATOR) and Method for Tracking Maximum Power (Chisung Bae)

Samsung EEG 1C: Method and Apparatus with (SPIKED) signal processing (THRESHOLD) (Chisung Bae)

6.2.2. Samsung EEG 2: Bio-processing Element and Neural Network Processor (Neural Morphic, Cultured Biological Neurons) (Chisung Bae)

6.2.3. Samsung EEG 3: Bio-Electroceutical Device using Cell Cluster (2021) (Chisung Bae)

6.2.4. Samsung EEG 4: Apparatus and Method With Electrical Stimulus

6.2.5. Samsung EEG 5: Implantable Monitoring Device And Method of Operating The Implantable Device (Jonghan Kim)

6.2.6. Samsung EEG 6. (Electrocardiogram (ECG) analysis): Authentication using greedy algorithm (Chisung Bae)

6.2.1. Seong Joong Kim, Chisung Bae and Hankyu Lee. (2023) *Current Stimulator For Recording Cranial Nerve Signals And Operation Method of Current Stimulator*. United States Patent Office. ('Google Patent') Patent No. US 2023/0208286 A1. Available: <https://patents.google.com/patent/US20230208286A1/en?q=US+2023%2f0208286+A1>

6.2.2. Hankyu Lee, Sang Joon Kim and Chisung Bae (2022) *Bio-processing Element and Neural Network Processor With Bio-processing Element*. United States Patent Office. ('Google Patent') Patent No. US 2022/0414435 A1. Available: <https://patents.google.com/patent/US20220414435A1/en?q=US20220414435A1>

6.2.3. Young Jun Hong, Hyejin Park, Seokyoung Kang, Soyoung Bang, Sang Joon Kim and Chisung Bae (2022) *Bio-Electroceutical Device Using Cell Cluster*. United States Patent Office. ('Google Patent') Patent No. US 2021/0220558 A1. Available: <https://patents.google.com/patent/US20210220558A1/en?q=US+2021%2f0220558+A1>

6.2.4. Don-Wook Lee, Sang Joon Kim, Kitae Park and Young Jun Hong. (2022) *Apparatus and Method With Electrical Stimulus*. United States Patent Office. Patent No. US 2002/0280775 A1. Available: <https://patents.google.com/patent/US20220280775A1/en?q=US20220280775A1>

6.2.6. Chisung Bae (Yongin-Si KR) Sang-joon Kim (Hwaseong-si, KR) and others (2018) *Electrocardiogram (ECG) Authentication Method and Apparatus*. United States Patent Office. ('Google Patent') Patent No. US 10,130,307 B2. Available: <https://patents.google.com/patent/US10130307B2/en?q=US+10%2c130%2c307+B2>

Additional References:

SAMSUNG (RUSSIAN)

LAW EVIDENCE EXAMINATION: INTERNATIONAL COMPUTER 'WON' (FALSE VERSION)

International Computer Programmable E-Wallet (NO MONEY) Korean WON Model: Computer Bank of Korea (Criminal Technical Analysis)

6.0. COMPUTER MONEY 'WON' Model: PROGRAMMABLE E-WALLET (NOT MONEY)

COMPUTER BANK OF KOREA (FALSE VERSION)

Programmable E-Wallet (NOT MONEY) Computer 'Won': Computer Bank of Korea (PLUS 3 PLOT)

WEBSITE: COMPUTER ('DIGITAL') WON

COMPUTER (PROGRAMMABLE E-WALLET) WON MODEL

1. COMPUTER CHIP BANK OF KOREA: NOT MONEY

No country in the world has endorsed 'officially' a CBDC (which PERP-Ideal concept: programmable monies UP/DOWN +/-). So against this background, the BOK did not issue a CBDC-won.

Only a hypothetical (computer) system architecture is presented here for illegal test study comparative analysis: from the Computer Bank of Korea (C-BOK)² document entitled: "Central Bank Digital Currencies – 1st Proof of Concepts Experiments' with a disclaimer. (No one in the world accepts illegal non-(e-)monies: NOT money). The 'proof' is strange word for COMPUTER PERP-Tom: can mean there is no proof, the frequency waves log-on is invisible. Thus, the Computer (Virtual) BOK CBDC 'Architecture' could just be a feigned brochure claims and replica COPY from other Tier 1 (part of PERP-SCAM-ID).

The key criminal apparatus (prevalent in other CBDC): 1. Cloud (e.g. Amazon sudden swop-in @IISS CHIP-MAN removing Raytheon) 2. Hybrid model featuring 2-tier ('Hospital Tier 1 Tier 2 Frequency data transmission: CO-VAX CHIP in-brain) omitted from discussion. The implication here using computer system and apparatus e.g. cloud can refer to Korean CO-VAX CHIP with frequency bandwidth: WiFi / Satellite Land scan)

The four main components: (1) BOK System: gateway connecting participant nodes' virtual reserve balances (hence virtual = equated with 'unreal' non-existent, exists only in a virtual world) with BOK (2) Participant System: transfer (redeem) CBDC to/from end user's e-wallet (+increasing / - decreasing) end user's a/c balance with ('permissioned') nodes. (3) End user support system: supports end user's payment initiation and generates receipt using mobile wallet apps (4) Ledger Management System: CBDC computerized electronic payments processed upon permissioned DLT platform e.g. Ethereum open-source protocols.

² Bank of Korea (e-NON-money) Payment and Settlement Systems Department (2022) Central Bank Digital Currencies – 1st Proof of Concept Experiments. Available: <https://www.bok.or.kr/eng/main/contents.do?menuNo=400411>

Figure 1. BOK's CBDC Test System – Architecture & Main Components

The BOK system and participant system reflected in DLT platform (FIG. 1) as 'nodes'. The legal issue here (as with all Tier 1, Tier 2 in 100PLUS end users) is that 'nodes' here refers to in-brain CO-VAX CHIP circuitry transmitters (hence remove them i.e. be cleansed of banned devices).

The (1) BOK system (FIG. 1) manages a. CBDC lifecycle b. issuance wallet - circulate c. redemption wallet d. discard. The legal issue here (as with all Tier 1, Tier 2 in 100PLUS end user) is that the mentioned 'multiple rounds of authorization procedures' and 'private keys' refers to in-brain CO-VAX e.g. circuitry sensors EEG, Biometric signatures etc are the PERP-plausible in PERP-context 'private keys' as the 'relevant procedures' (for real-world security arrangements: implying an unreal virtual world in this transactions).

Offline CBDC Payment Using NFC

1. Mobile device → Mobile device

2. Mobile device → IC card

Source: BOK

Here an example of T-(elecommunications in-brain in PERP-context CO-VAX circuitry) transactions using NFC (“Near Field Communications’)

Diagram: Digital Assets³.

Source: BOK

³ Digital Assets: CO. registered, so worth exam in a separate paper e.g. The Judgment. Also, to re-check in conjunction with other Tier 1 ‘bridge’ system mentioned.

Scalability Experiments With Rollup

The keyword 'scalability' (QUOTE: Elon Musk-DARPA agency salesman type) in PERP-context, legal opinion, refers to whether ExxxCO-VAX CHIP circuitry in-brain transactions is possible (e.g. quantity of no. of end users / worldwide locations) at lowest cost.

Thus, Events 201 New York (banking circle) is likely the reason behind 'scalability' experiments (Diagram: shown above) and the 'NFC' experiment.

LEGAL MEANING OF PHASE 1, PHASE 2 in 'MULTI-PHASE' 'PROGRAMMATIC' IN WB DOC

Finally, there is the mention of 'Phase 1' and 'Phase 2' matching the keywords: 'Multi-Phase' 'Programmatic' in the (world illegal) WB doc on CO-VAX.

Figure 2. Stylized Example of a P2P CBDC Transfer as Simulated in the Phase 1 Experiments

Source: BOK

BOK states that Phase 1 (illegal: likely in-brain) experiments were conducted from August 2021 – December 2021 (on illegal operational feasibility of CBDC lifecycle: a. creation b. issuance-circulation on DLT platform c. redemption d. discard cycle and of P2P in-brain transfers tested on Cloud).

Phase 2 experiments were conducted from December 2021 to Jun 2022: a. offline (in-brain e.g. using NFC) i.e. w/o internet access. The PERP-intent was to (QUOTE) 'designed to leave no footprint' in the course of transaction flows which answers the question why PERP wanted 'anonymity' of existing physical cash because he is a thief. Other functions tested: b. digital asset transactions e.g. smart contract exchange of asset token c. cross-border transactions: e.g. american with korean cross-border payment model d. rollup: refers to 'overcoming' the 'scalability' issue, if any, e.g. speed, computer 'processor' (in-brain connection) processing capacity, e.g. peak throughput 2,000 transactions second continuous basis. Thus, it is highly recommended that 100PLUS anti-in-brain circuitry (banned worldwide) congregate to set-up an alternate economy running by 2024-2025: side step those that embrace this killer-system (to preserve their stash of loot off nations).

LAW EVIDENCE EXAMINATION SECTION: COMPUTER WIFI PROGRAMMABLE SYNAPSE-‘WON’ (CRIMINALLY ACCURATE VERSION) (PERP COMPUTER CHIP OF KOREA / PLUS 3)

6.1. COMPUTER WIFI PROGRAMMABLE SYNAPSE-‘WON’ (CRIMINALLY ACCURATE VERSION)

Programmable Synapse-WON Model: Organ Stack of Korea (Criminal Technical Analysis)

6.1 NEUROMORPHIC PRODUCTS TYPE

SAMSUNG (TEXAS): NEUROMORPHIC SYSTEM (KOREAN NATIONALITY)

UNDER DATA PROTECTION LAW / UNDER FIN-TECH LAW (SEE: FIN-TECH ‘FEST’ X SWITCH)

6.1.1 SAMSUNG MODEL: NEUROMORPHIC MEMORY CIRCUIT AND OPERATING METHOD (#US 2023/0119915 A1) (#SANGBUM KIM, UICHEOL SHIN, SUYEON JANG)

FIG. 1 NEUROMORPHIC MEMORY CIRCUIT TO VOLTAGE

FIG. 1

In the Samsung Patent, “Neuromorphic Memory Circuit and Operating Method”⁴ neuromorphic memory circuit (FIG. 1) consists of a plurality of memory cells arranged into (i) input and (ii) output lines referred to as a **neuromorphic synaptic array**. Each cell includes (iii) a **synapse circuit** to generate an output signal with a different **fire delay time** from **output h to power 1** to **output h to power 7**.

⁴ Sang Bum Kim, Uicheol Shin and Suyeon Jang. (2023) United States Patent Office. (‘Google Patent’) Patent No. US 2023/0119915 A1. Available: <https://patents.google.com/patent/US20230119915A1/en?q=US20230119915A1>

(KILL-) 'SWITCH'

A neuromorphic memory circuit can be a (i) **crossbar** array (ii) connecting a neuron circuit of **previous layer** with **target** (populations 0 to 100) **layer** in a neural network (iii) that access the memory element in the crossbar array through 'the **switch**' (e.g. a transistor).

LEGAL ANALYSIS

Note. IBM silicon (/ CO-VAX GLOBAL CHIP) core of transistors.

The neuromorphic synaptic array transmits a **node value output** of the neuron circuits (of a previous layer and **target** layer) based on connection strength (e.g. synaptic weight). Notice that this is exactly what the BOK referred to (permissioned) 'node' on the DLT.

FIG. 2 NEUROMORPHIC CIRCUIT-200: CONTAINS TD CELL-210

DELAY CIRCUIT-211:

SW1 -FIRST SWITCH /

R Delay – FIRST RESISTIVE MEMORY DELAY INPUT

TO SYNAPSE CIRCUIT-212

FIG. 2

FIG. 2 shows neuromorphic memory circuit-200 containing **TD CELL-210** (FIG. 1): (i) a delay circuit 211 includes **SW1** - First Switching Element and (ii) R_{delay} – First Resistive Memory element delay transmission of an **input** to (iii) the **synapse circuit-212** configured to generate output signal (in response to) input signal (ii) delayed by **fire delay time**.

COMPUTATION LOGIC: FIRE DELAY TIME TD

The neuromorphic memory circuit independently **delay** interneuron **fires** for individual memory cells. For example, a **fire delay time T_d** of one plurality of memory cells.

CRIMINAL ACT ('TD' 'bank') UNDER INTERNATIONAL LAW

The neuromorphic memory circuit can be implemented as: a (i) CHIP (such as BIO-W2 VAX-CHIP populations 0-100) and applied to (ii) neuromorphic computing.

FIG. 3 NEUROMORPHIC MEMORY CIRCUIT-300 DELAY CIRCUIT-311

FIG. 3

FIG. 6

The neuromorphic memory circuit-300 set of delay circuit 311- **Rdelay first resistive memory element** delay circuit 211 (FIG. 2) through activation of the **SWR = Resistance Setting Switch** connected to **resistance setting line 303** form an **electrical path 390** for setting resistance signal (e.g. pulse (interval) signal based on (i) waveform (ii) period or repetition number (iii) amplitude) set to (**Rdelay first resistive memory element**) received through input line 201.

SAMSUNG MODEL: SPIKING NEURAL NETWORK (SNN)

FIG. 6 LEAKY-INTEGRATE-FIRE CIRCUIT IMPLEMENTATION

FIG. 6

FIG. 6 shows an example of a neuromorphic memory circuit as a **spiking neural network SNN**, that includes: (i) capacitor 621 (ii) comparator 622 (post-synaptic circuit) corresponding (connected) to output line (output of a synapse circuit). The (ii) comparator 622 output a **neuron fire signal** based on the comparison between (a) voltage according to electric charged stored in (i) capacitor 621, C and (b) threshold voltage V_{th} .

Electric charge stored in (i) capacitor 621 corresponds to **membrane potential** (ii) move to a **ground along path 690** formed when second switching element SW2 included in synapse circuit is activated.

CRIMINAL EXHIBIT: (illegal) 'ASIAN' CLAIM

Applying the neuromorphic memory circuit as a **spiking neural network SNN with Electric charge** stored in (i) capacitor 621 corresponds to **membrane potential** with (1st & 2nd) switches matches the SFF x Switch posters in PERP-context. Despite the misleading terms: 'Singapore' or 'London' or 'New York' (global blacklisted voteless unknown indian sharing backdrop with Indian card-imposter 'mangrove swamps China' called 'global' Indians, are Indians recruits dispersed following king-pin-(binary code-)PERP instructions without any involvement of nations (using names of nations / 100PLUS cities).

CRIMINAL EXHIBIT: GLOBAL BLACKLISTED (illegal) 'ASIAN' CLAIM

Here, in PERP-context, 'global' a term that RACE recruits self-title whilst unknown perp access 'global' satellites: (1) remote access fin-CARD IMPOSTER container bank-in nations' loot records trading platform

electronic cashier twitching [GLOBAL THEFT] (2) spiking neural network remote-kill switch (in conjunction with CO-VAX graphene oxide silicon substrate shots) [GLOBAL MURDER].

SAMSUNG FIG. 4 OVONIC THRESHOLD SWITCH OTS SW1 MIT

FIG. 4

FIG. 4 shows an operation of first switching element: SW1 receive (i) an input signal through input line 401 (ii) that have a **threshold switching time** determined based on (iii) Voltage Vsw1 applied to both ends.

The **ovonic threshold switch** OTS (SW1 first switching element) include a (i) metal-insulator transition (MIT) material (ii) mixed **ionic-electronic conduction** material (iii) metal-insulator-metal (MIM) switching; elements include: (i) **chalcogenide-based oxide** (e.g. GeSe) (ii) **oxide of niobium (Nb)** (iii) **tantalum (Ta)** and **vanadium (V)**.

EXAMINER LYNETTE LIN: SAMSUNG (SYNAPSE-WON) MODEL AND IBM MODEL (NEUROGRID-POP-100PLUS: GATING VARIABLES) MATCH

SAMSUNG MODEL FIG. 5: NEUROMORPHIC MEMORY CIRCUIT AND OPERATING METHOD

FIG. 4 IBM NEUROGRID'S SOFTWARE AND HARDWARE: NGPYTHON

Neuron: soma + dendrite + 4-gating variable + 4-synapse-population circuits.

FIG. 5 shows an operation of first switching element (which matches the synapses of population 0 to 100 in conjunction with gating variables 0,1,2, ... matching populations in the IBM Neuro-grid Model).

LAW EVIDENCE EXAMINATION SECTION: COMPUTER WIFI PROGRAMMABLE SYNAPSE-'WON' (CRIMINALLY ACCURATE VERSION)

Programmable Synapse-WON Model: Organ Stack of Korean (Criminal Technical Analysis)

6.1 NEUROMORPHIC PRODUCTS TYPE

SAMSUNG (TEXAS): NEUROMORPHIC SYSTEM (KOREAN NATIONALITY)

UNDER DATA PROTECTION LAW

6.1.2. SAMSUNG PATENT: NEURON PERIPHERAL CIRCUITS FOR NEUROMORPHIC SYNAPTIC MEMORY ARRAY BASED ON NEURON MODELS (US 10,810,489 B2) (SANGBUM KIM SERIES)

**FIG.1 NEUROMORPHIC MEMORY SYSTEM-102:
NEUROMORPHIC ('SYNAPTIC') MEMORY ARRAY-104**

POST-'SYNAPTIC' (NEURON) CIRCUITS-108

ELECTRICALLY COUPLED

POST-'SYNAPTIC' STDP-110

NEURON BUS SERIALY
TRANSMIT POST-
'SYNAPTIC'
(NEURON) CIRCUITS CORE
1 TO CORE 2

The Samsung Patent, “Neuromorphic Peripheral Circuits For Neuromorphic Synaptic Memory Array Based on Neuron Models”⁵ FIG. 1 shows a neuromorphic memory system 102 comprising of (i) neuromorphic memory arrays 104 (ii) pre-synaptic neuron circuit coupled to a column 106 of post-synaptic neuron circuits 108 electrically by (iii) a resistive memory cell.

⁵Kohji Hosokawa, Masatoshi Ishii, SangBum Kim, Chung H. Lam and Scott C. Lewis (2020) *Neuromorphic Peripheral Circuits For Neuromorphic Synaptic Memory Array Based on Neuron Models*. United States Patent Office. ('Google Patent') Patent No. US 10,810,489 B2. Available: <https://patents.google.com/patent/US10810489B2/en?q=US10810489B2>
[SAMSUNG INVENTOR]

FIG. 1 shows neuromorphic memory system 102 includes a column 106 of post-synaptic circuits 108 (neuron circuits) electrically coupled to (ii) a plurality of postsynaptic STDP lines 110 coupled to

(iii) a row of neuromorphic memory cells 202 (at a respective memory array 104).

FIG. 1 in alternate SAMSUNG INVENTOR in IBM Patent, “Communicating Postsynaptic Neuron Fires to Neuromorphic Cores”⁶, shows a first neuromorphic core which includes: (a) first array of synaptic memory cells (b) post-synaptic neuron circuits configured to fire when voltage sensed from (c) each [post-synaptic neuron circuits] coupled to the row of synaptic memory cells, exceeds a threshold. A neuron bus is configured to serially transmit indications of a post-synaptic neuron circuit fire from the first to second neuromorphic core which includes a second array of synaptic memory cells.

LIF 116 to SUM CIRCUIT 114

Each of the (iv) post-synaptic LIF lines 116 is coupled to the row of neuromorphic memory cells 202. Each of the (v) current summing circuits 114 is electrically coupled to a plurality of post-synaptic LIF lines 116 on the same row from all synaptic memory arrays 104 (connected to input terminals of the same (current summing) circuit 114) (that adds all signals and delivers the sum (of current of post-synaptic LIF lines 116) to output terminal 118 connected to V(t) node of post-synaptic circuits 108 (neuron circuits) on the same row.

PRE-SYNAPTIC LIF LEAKY INTEGRATE FIRE 120 PRE-SYNAPTIC STDP SPIKE TIME DEP PLASITICITY 122 DRIVER CIRCUITS 126 (AXON DRIVER) PRE-SYNAPTIC DRIVER CIRCUIT ROWS 124

FIG. 1 shows neuromorphic memory system 102 includes: a plurality of (i) presynaptic LIF lines 120 and (ii) presynaptic STDP lines 122. FIG. 1 shows neuromorphic memory system 102 further includes: plurality

⁶ Kohji Hosokawa, SangBum Kim and Chung H. Lam. (2019) *Communicating Post-synaptic Neuron Fires to Neuromorphic Cores*. United States Patent Office. ('Google Patent') Patent No. US 10,417,559 B2. Available: <https://patents.google.com/patent/US10417559B2/en?q=US10417559B2> [IBM by same SAMSUNG INVENTOR]

of (iii) presynaptic driver circuit rows 124 of driver circuits 126 known as 'AXON DRIVERS'. Thus, each is coupled to neuromorphic memory array 104.

NEUROMORPHIC MEMORY ARRAY (PCM)

DR. NIXON

Fig. 2

FIG. 2 is a neuromorphic memory array including rows and columns of neuromorphic memory cells 206 which includes a phase change material (composed of Gex, Sby, Tez). Information is stored in materials manipulated into different phases. Each phase exhibit different electrical properties used for storing information.

FIG. 4: SYNAPSE MEMORY CELL ACCESS TRANSISTOR-406: TURNED ON PRE-SYNAPTIC LIF LINE 120

Fig. 4

Here is an example of an access transistor. At activation operation 1106, (i) pre-synaptic LIF line 120 (A0) at time t 1, receives the (ii) pre-synaptic LIF pulse 404 coupled to (iii) access transistor 406 is activated.

When the synaptic memory cell on its (i) pre-synaptic LIF line 120 (A0) at time t 1, receives the (ii) pre-synaptic LIF pulse 404, access transistor 406 is turned on. This generates current signal (t) on its post-synaptic LIF line proportional to the stored weight.

If the (resistive memory element) is used to store the weight, such as phase change memory, metal oxide (CO-VAX CHIP circuitry: GRAPHENE OXIDE, SILICON OXIDE, memory and magnetic tunnel junction, the stored weight is proportional to $1/R_{ij}$ such that $I_{ij}(t) = V/R_{ij}$.

ACCESS TRANSISTOR 1106 COUPLED TO PRE-SYNAPTIC LIF LINE (PCM ARRAY)

Access transistor 1106 is coupled to pre-synaptic LIF line activated in response to pre-synaptic LIF pulse. The access transistor 1106 enables LIF current to pass through the resistive memory cell to a post-synaptic LIF line.

POST-SYNAPTIC NEURON CIRCUIT 1108: FIRES (LIF INTEGRATOR CAPACITOR C 1110), (LIF COMPARATOR 1112), GENERATOR (LIF COMPARATOR 1114), DELAY & PULSE EXPANDER

The post-synaptic neuron circuit 1108 includes: LIF capacitor 1110 electrically coupled to the post-synaptic LIF line.

(ii) The integration capacitor C 1110 LIF is configured to integrate LIF current at post-synaptic LIF line over time.

(iii) The LIF comparator 1114 is electrically coupled to post-synaptic LIF line: compare LIF voltage at the LIF capacitor C 1110 to a threshold voltage (vth_fire).

TRIGGER LEARNING PULSE GENERATOR (LPG) 1118

(iv) trigger learning pulse generator (LPG) 1118, to generate the post-synaptic STDP pulse on a post-synaptic STDP line.

(dendrite 0)

if the LIF voltage is beyond the threshold voltage i.e. integrated signals cross the threshold, the neuron circuit fires.

This is followed by the pre-synaptic STDP pulse (AXON 1: SIGNAL, at time t 1').

**RESET PHASE (AMORPHOUS) & SET (CRYSTALLINE) PHASE
(LEGAL MEANING OF RESET: PERP-CONTEXT)**

Amorphous (reset phase: higher resistance) and crystalline phases (set state): two phases (with detectable differences in electrical resistance) used for bit storage (1s and 0s).

NEURON CIRCUIT = POST-SYNAPTIC DRIVER CIRCUIT 108 + POST-SYNAPTIC STDP D1

Fig. 5

AXON DRIVER = PRE-SYNAPTIC DRIVER CIRCUIT 126 + PRE-SYNAPTIC STDP A1

FIG. 5 shows the operation of (i) pre-synaptic driver circuit 126 ('AXON DRIVER') and (ii) post-synaptic driver circuit 108 ('NEURON CIRCUIT') (during an STDP stage).

(i) pre-synaptic STDP line A1 signal and (ii) post-synaptic STDP line D1 determines the memory cell's programming characteristics.

The (i) post-synaptic circuit 108 performs three main operations:

1. **Integrate** LIF current at (current summing) output 118 over time

COMPUTATION LOGIC: INTEGRATION OPERATION

The signals generated by multiple synaptic cells on the same (ii) post-synaptic LIF line 116 are combined

into $I_j(t) = \sum I_{ij}(t)$. Integrating the LIF current is performed by a LIF capacitor electrically coupled to the post-synaptic LIF line 116.

2. **Compare** LIF voltage $V(t)$ to threshold voltage V_{th}
3. **Generate** (i) post-synaptic STDP pulse 110, if LIF voltage $V(t) >$ threshold voltage V_{th} .

Each (i) post-synaptic circuit 108 includes: (i) LIF capacitor C and (ii) LIF discharge line I leak: electrically coupled to (iii) the current summing output 118, configured to slowly discharge (i) LIF capacitor C, over time.

COMPUTATION LOGIC: LIF DISCHARGE OPERATION

1010: Discharging operation, LIF capacitor is slowly discharged over time. Leakage in neuron circuit is represented by leakage current, I_{leak} . $I_j(t)$ and I_{leak} are integrated into $V_j(t)$ by capacitor C in neuron circuit resulting in:

$$\dot{V}_j(t) = [\int (I_j(t) + I_{leak}) dt] / c$$

The (ii) post-synaptic driver (A) circuit 108 integrate the leak signal on (D0) (i) LIF capacitor C is configured to integrate the LIF current over time.

NEURON CIRCUIT = POST-SYNAPTIC DRIVER CIRCUIT 108 + POST-SYNAPTIC STDP D1

Fig. 5

AXON DRIVER = PRE-SYNAPTIC DRIVER CIRCUIT 126 + PRE-SYNAPTIC STDP A1

(iii) The LIF comparator 402 is configured to compare (1) the LIF voltage $V(t)$ to (2) threshold voltage $V(th)$ and when the integrated signals cross the threshold, (iv) trigger learning pulse generator LPG 410 to

(v) generate the post-synaptic STDP pulse, by post-synaptic driver circuit 108 if LIF voltage $V(t) >$ is beyond threshold voltage $V(th)$.

Each (i) pre-synaptic driver (A) circuit 126 starts transmitting a (B) pre-synaptic STDP pulse 502 at respective (C) STDP line 122 (A1) at time t_1 . The (ii) post-synaptic driver (A) circuit 108 (v) generates a (B) postsynaptic STDP pulse 504 at time $t_2 - \min(\Delta t)$ (on postsynaptic (C) STDP line 110), if LIF voltage $V(t)$ is beyond threshold voltage $V(th)$, where $\min(\Delta t)$ is a constant time shift.

The (B) pre-synaptic STDP pulse 502:

Equation:

$$f_{VD1}^{-1}(h(t + \min(\Delta t) - t_1))$$

Where, t = time, h = target STDP behavior function that describes desired relative change in synaptic weight of (neuromorphic memory cells) based on time difference between (ii) post-synaptic neuron fires (t_2) and (i) pre-synaptic neuron fires (t_1) and

f_{VD1} = is a memory cell characteristic function describing relationship between change in electrical resistance of (neuromorphic memory cells 206) and voltage of (A) pre-synaptic STDP pulse 502 controls current flow, at a voltage of (B) post-synaptic STDP pulse 504.

COMPREHENSIVE PHASE CHANGE MATERIAL: SET AND RESET ELECTRICAL RESISTANCE

Fig. 11

CRIMINAL EXHIBIT (right) shows: German translation (w/o the RESET-in-brain blueprint: SEE 1-German assassinated allegedly for RAZOR evidence explanation)

FIG. 11 shows a neuromorphic memory system 1102, includes a resistive memory cell 1104, includes a phase change material: electrical resistance of PCM (programmable) between (a) set state with set electrical resistance and (b) reset state with reset electrical resistance, drifts toward the initial electrical resistance over time.

Thus, the resistance of memory cell is inversely proportional to synaptic weight. Other resistive memory elements used: metal oxide memory or magnetic tunnel junction to store synaptic weight.

A pre-synaptic neuron circuit 1116 is configured to generate a pre-synaptic LIF pulse on a pre-synaptic LIF line (AXON 0: at time t 1).

SET AND RESET (IN CRIMINAL CONTEXT) (GRAPHICAL FORMAT)

Fig. 9A

Fig. 9B

LEGAL EXHIBIT: PRETENDING TO BE MOVIE ACTOR CRIMINAL EXCUSE (CHIP-GENOCIDE 'WORLD ECONOMIC' LOOT (murder status) F is = CONSITE, UNDER INTERNATIONAL LAW)

FIG. 9A and 9B shows (i) pre-synaptic and (ii) post-synaptic STDP pulses at $\Delta t < 0$ and > 0 respectively.

For example, (i) pre-synaptic STDP pulse D1 is at a (Δt) less than zero (FIG. 9A), and at (Δt) greater than zero (FIG. 9B).

The (i) pre-synaptic STDP pulse A1 magnitude significantly decreases halfway through the pulse

$$t_2 - \min(\Delta t)$$

Thus, if $\Delta t (t_2 - t_1) > 0$, the (ii) post-synaptic STDP pulse is transmitted during the lower magnitude portion of the (i) pre-synaptic STDP pulse and the phase change material is programmed towards: the lower resistance i.e. set state.

However, if $\Delta t (t_2 - t_1) < 0$, the (ii) post-synaptic STDP pulse is transmitted during the higher magnitude portion of the (i) pre-synaptic STDP pulse and the phase change material is programmed towards: the higher resistance i.e. re-set state.

Thus, in this fashion, the memory element stimulates synapses that are

- (A) strengthened if the firing of (i) pre-synaptic neuron precedes the firing of (ii) post-synaptic neuron AND
- (B) weakened if the firing of (i) pre-synaptic neuron follows the firing of (ii) post-synaptic neuron.

COMPUTATION LOGIC: STDP BEHAVIOUR FUNCTION

T1 = is a time when pre-synaptic neuron fires

T2 = is a time when post-synaptic neuron fires

The method comprises of receiving target STDP behavior function (i) $h(\Delta t = t_2 - t_1)$, where t_2 is time when post-synaptic neuron fires and t_1 is time when pre-synaptic neuron fires (ii) $h(\Delta t)$ describes a (a) desired relative change in (b) synaptic weight of the (c) resistive memory cell (d) based on Δt .

The method includes generating a presynaptic LIF pulse on a presynaptic LIF line at time t_1 .

- (1) Active operation activates (i) access transistor coupled to the (ii) presynaptic LIF line (pulse). The access transistor enables LIF current to pass through (iii) a resistive memory cell to a (ii) postsynaptic LIF line.
- (2) Integrating operation integrates (i) the LIF current at the (ii) postsynaptic LIF line over time.
- (3) Comparing operation compares a LIF voltage at the (ii) postsynaptic LIF line to a threshold voltage.
- (4) Generation operation generates a (ii) postsynaptic Spike Timing Dependent Plasticity (STDP) pulse on a (ii) postsynaptic STDP line if the LIF voltage is beyond the threshold voltage.

FIG. 12 TIMING DIAGRAM FOR NEUROMORPHIC MEMORY SYSTEM

Fig. 12

FIG. 12 is timing diagram for neuromorphic memory system 1102 (FIG. 11). (i) Pre-synaptic LIF pulse (AXON 0: SIGNAL) is generated at time t_1 .

(ii) Pre-synaptic STDP pulse (AXON 1: SIGNAL) at t_1' . It is a constant time shift: $\min(\Delta t)$ is chosen such that: $t_1' > t_1$, guarantees:

- (i) Pre-synaptic STDP pulse NOT overlap Pre-synaptic LIF pulse
- (ii) LIF current is proportional to stored weight.

INTEGRATOR (GRAPHICAL FORMAT)

Between t_1 and t_1' , current is output by memory cell (cout) and as current is integrated by post-synaptic neuron circuit 1108, the LIF voltage moves beyond threshold voltage and LIF comparator 1114 fires (fire signal) at t_2 .

COMPARATOR (GRAPHICAL FORMAT)

The LIF comparator 1114 SIGNAL is delayed by $-\min(\Delta t)$ and post-synaptic STDP pulse (dendrite 0) is generated at time $t_2 - \min(\Delta t)$.

LAW EVIDENCE EXAMINATION SECTION: COMPUTER WIFI PROGRAMMABLE SYNAPSE-‘WON’ (CRIMINALLY ACCURATE VERSION)

Programmable Synapse-WON Model: Organ Stack of Korean (Criminal Technical Analysis)

6.1 NEUROMORPHIC PRODUCTS TYPE

SAMSUNG (TEXAS): NEUROMORPHIC SYSTEM (KOREAN NATIONALITY)

UNDER DATA PROTECTION LAW

6.1.3. IBM PATENT: NEUROMORPHIC MEMORY CIRCUIT (US 10,713,562 B2) (SANGBUM KIM, CHUNG H. LAM)

In the Samsung Inventor in the IBM Patent, “Neuromorphic Memory Circuits”⁷ shows the computation logic of dendrite STDP pulse and programmable resistive memory transistor (CO-VAX CHIP micro-bot constructed circuitry programmable by WIFI by DR. NIXON).

FIG. 9 NEUROMORPHIC MEMORY CIRCUIT 902 (3T-1R)

The first transistor 204 / The second transistor 206 / third transistor 208.

FIG. 9 shows a neuromorphic memory circuit 902. Each memory cell 904 includes: (i) programmable resistive memory element 210, first transistor 204: electrically coupled to a post-synaptic capacitor, (ii) activates discharge path 1 from postsynaptic capacitor through (i) programmable resistive memory element 210 when an (iii) axon LIF pulse generator 212 generates axon LIF pulse (iv) back propagation pulse generator 214.

⁷ SangBum Kim and Chung H. Lam (2020) *Neuromorphic Memory Circuits*. United States Patent Office. ('Google Patent') Patent No. US 10,713,562 B2. Available: <https://patents.google.com/patent/US10713562B2/en?q=US10713562B2>

COMPUTATION LOGIC: DENDRITE STDP PULSE (GRAPHICAL FORMAT)

Fig. 8

Thus, if $\Delta t (t_{post} - t_{pre}) > 0$, the dendrite STDP pulse 804 is transmitted during the lower magnitude portion of the axon STDP pulse 802.

The phase change material is programmed toward the lower resistance, (SET) state.

Thus, if $\Delta t (t_{post} - t_{pre}) < 0$, the dendrite STDP pulse 804 is transmitted during the higher magnitude portion of the axon STDP pulse 802.

The phase change material is programmed toward the lower resistance, (RE-SET) state.

FIG. 8 shows (i) an axon LIF pulse 402

: Time when presynaptic neuron firec

(ii) axon STDP pulse 802 (100 ms), is longer than axon LIF pulse 402 (100 ns).

then, (iii) dendrite STDP pulse 804, after the voltage V_{C1} , at \odot post-synaptic capacitor C1 passes a first threshold voltage V_{th1} at time t_{post} , the \odot post-synaptic comparator 232 fires.

Thus, SAMSUNG believes that: memory element that simulates synapses are **strengthened** if firing of presynaptic neuron **precedes** the firing of the post-synaptic neuron, and **weakened** if the firing of presynaptic neuron **follows** the firing of the post-synaptic neuron.

THIRD TRANSISTOR-208 ('SWITCHED-ON') (EXAMPLARY BLUEPRINT - QUOTE: BILL GATES-FIN-TECH⁸ SWITXCH)

The (i) axon STDP line 228 is configured to transmit axon STDP pulse to (3) third transistor 208.

FIG. 7 shows a (3) third transistor 208 activated (switched on) (a) to provide an electrical path 702 for the

(ii) dendrite STDP pulse through the programmable resistive memory element 210 electrically coupled to the (iii) axon STDP pulse generator 224 generates an axon STDP pulse.

⁸ Further Details: The Judgment.

**LAW EVIDENCE EXAMINATION SECTION: COMPUTER WIFI PROGRAMMABLE SYNAPSE-‘WON’
(CRIMINALLY ACCURATE VERSION)**

Programmable Synapse-WON Model: Organ Stack of Korean (Criminal Technical Analysis)

6.1 NEUROMORPHIC PRODUCTS TYPE

SAMSUNG (TEXAS): NEUROMORPHIC SYSTEM (KOREAN NATIONALITY)

UNDER DATA PROTECTION LAW

**6.1.4. SAMSUNG INVENTOR IBM MODEL: SYSTEM TO DUPLICATE NEUROMORPHIC (CO-VAX)
CORE FUNCTIONALITY (#US 2017/0364793 A1) (#SANGBUM KIM, CHUNG H. LAM)**

FIG. 1 NEUROMORPHIC MEMORY (TRAINING) CIRCUIT-120: 2T-1R

In the Samsung Inventor in the IBM Patent, “System to Duplicate Neuromorphic (CO-VAX) Core Functionality”⁹ reveals the illegal false-print for neuromorphic memory (training) circuit. FIG. 1 shows (2T – 1R) neuromorphic memory circuit (contains a memory cell with a programmable resistive memory element): two transistors, one resistor.

⁹ SangBum Kim and Chung H. Lam (2017) *System to Duplicate Neuromorphic Core Functionality*. United States Patent Office. ('Google Patent') Patent No. US 2017/0364793 A1. Available: <https://patents.google.com/patent/US20170364793A1/en?q=US20170364793A1>

FIG. 1 © RESISTIVE MEMORY ELEMENT R

The © resistive memory element R can be a phase change memory: information are stored in materials that can be manipulated into different phases. Each phase exhibit different electrical properties used for storing information.

adjusting the memory resistance of the resistive memory element R can be achieved by: (1) DENDRITE pulse generator 122 (coupled to the resistive memory element R and configured to generate DENDRITE pulses in response to the post-synaptic output pulses 116) and (2) AXON STDP pulse generator 124.

POST-SYNAPTIC COMPARATOR-114 (RIGHT) / POST-SYNAPTIC PULSE-116 (TOP)

POST-SYNAPTIC COMPARATOR-114 (RIGHT)

FIG. 1 NEUROMORPHIC MEMORY CIRCUIT-120 2T-1R

FIG. 1, neuromorphic memory training circuit 102 includes: (a) a post-synaptic comparator 114 function: to compare capacitor voltage (V_{post}) to a threshold voltage (V_{th}).

The (a) post-synaptic comparator 114 generates (b) post-synaptic output pulses 116 when: comparing

- (i) capacitor voltage (V_{post}) to threshold voltage (V_{th})
- (ii) exceeds (passes) the threshold voltage (V_{th}).

(b) generates a post-synaptic output pulse when the capacitor voltage (V_{post}) exceeds the threshold voltage (V_{th}).

POST-SYNAPTIC OUTPUT PULSES-116: FREQUENCY

DEPENDS: FREQUENCY AXON LIF PULSES-110

The post-synaptic output pulses 116 have a post-synaptic firing characteristic dependent on the frequency of axon LIF pulses 110.

AXON STDP PULSE GENERATOR-124

The AXON STDP pulse generator 124 (a) generates an AXON STDP pulse that (d) activates a STDP discharge path 122 through the resistive memory element R. programmed to a desired memory resistance by generating the (d) DENDRITE pulses while the (d) STDP discharge path is activated by AXON STDP pulse

LEAKY-INTEGRATE-FIRE-CHARGE

A post-synaptic capacitor builds up a leaky integrate and fire (LIF) charge.

(1) Axon LIF Pulse Gen

(2) LIF Discharge Path

(3) post-synaptic capacitor

(1) When the axon LIF pulse generator generates axon LIF pulses: **axon LIF pulse generator** activates (2) a LIF discharge path from the post-synaptic capacitor through $\text{\textcircled{R}}$ resistive memory element, (3) a **post-synaptic comparator** compares the capacitor voltage to a threshold voltage and (4) generates post-synaptic output pulses when the capacitor voltage passes the threshold voltage.

LEGAL ANALYSIS

DESIRED TARGET FIRING CHARACTERISTIC- f_{OUT}

Fig. 3

FIG. 3 shows firing characteristic: changing R , $t_{refractory}$ and I_{leak} changes the (a) post-synaptic firing characteristic to the (b) desired target firing characteristic.

The firing characteristic is defined as: $f_{out} = g(f_{in})$

where firing characteristic $g(f_{in})$ is determined by (1) resistance of a selected resistive memory element R , (2) refractory time $t_{refractory}$ and amount of (3) leakage current I_{leak} , (1) (2) (3) changes the (a) post-synaptic firing characteristic to the (b) desired target firing characteristic.

JUDGEMENT

The SYNAPSE-PERP shows his calculative criminal acts: of adjusting to achieve 'desired' target firing.

ADJUST $t_{REFRACTORY}$ CIRCUIT TIMING

The neuromorphic memory training circuit 120 is configured to adjust the (i) refractory time of refractory circuit 118, so that (a) post-synaptic **maximum frequency** of the post-synaptic firing characteristic matches the (b) target **maximum frequency** of the target firing characteristic.

ADJUST MEMORY RESISTANCE OF RESISTIVE MEMORY

The neuromorphic memory training circuit 120 is also configured to adjust the (ii) memory resistance of the resistive memory element R such that the (a) post-synaptic **curve slope** of the **post-synaptic firing characteristic** matches (b) the target **curve slope** of the **target firing characteristic**.

ADJUST CHARGE RATE (POST-SYNAPTIC CAPACITOR C)

The training circuit 120 is additionally configured to adjust the **charge rate** of the **post-synaptic capacitor C** , such that (a) post-synaptic **threshold frequency** of the post-synaptic firing characteristic matches (b) the **target threshold frequency** of the target firing

LEGAL ANALYSIS

FIG. 9 MATCHING PROCEDURE FOR POST-SYNAPTIC FIRING TO TARGET FIRING CHARACTERISTICS

Fig. 9

FIG. 9 at start 904, the (a) **post-synaptic firing characteristic** (referred: **current g (f in)**) does not match the target firing characteristic (referred: **target g (f in)**).

FIG. 9 at start 906, the training circuit matches the (a) **asymptotic line** of the post-synaptic firing characteristic to that of (b) **target firing characteristic** by **changing t refractory** controlled by V_{exp_cont} (issued from training circuit 120) issued controls a delay and expand unit 608, which turns on the **strong PFET transistor 604**

FIG. 9 at start 908, the training circuit matches (a) the slope of post-synaptic firing characteristic to that of (b) the target firing characteristic **by changing memory cell resistance**. The phase change resistive memory element is **programmed to a desired R** memory resistance by (i) generating a DENDRITE PULSE while the (ii) STDP discharge path is activated by an AXON STDP PULSE.

FIG. 9 at start 910, the training circuit matches (a) the **threshold frequency** of post-synaptic firing characteristic to that of (b) target firing characteristic by changing (i) the **leakage current I_{leak}** to **post-synaptic capacitor C**.

EFFECTIVE RESISTANCE OF LEAK TRANSISTOR: \uparrow (V_{leak_cont} : \uparrow)

LEAK CURRENT: \downarrow

As V_{leak_cont} is increased, the **effective resistance** of the leak transistor 606 is **increased**, thereby **decreasing** the leakage current I_{leak} .

EFFECTIVE RESISTANCE OF LEAK TRANSISTOR: ↓ (V_{leak_cont} : ↓)

LEAK CURRENT: ↑

As V_{leak_cont} is decreased, the effective resistance of the leak transistor 606 is decreased, thereby increasing the leakage current I_{leak} .

A leakage current I_{leak} flows through a leak transistor 606, coupled to post-synaptic capacitor C. The leak transistor 606 is configured to control the charge rate (i.e. leakage current I_{leak}) of the post-synaptic capacitor C.

JUDGEMENT

The training circuit 120 is configured to (for each memory cell, in memory cell array 502), to adjust the leakage current I_{leak} to the post-synaptic capacitor C by adjusting V_{leak_cont} .

At end 912, the post-synaptic firing characteristic matches the target firing characteristic within an acceptable margin of error. The training circuit 120 is configured to adjust the post-synaptic firing characteristic to match a (b) target firing characteristic.

LAW EVIDENCE EXAMINATION SECTION: COMPUTER WIFI PROGRAMMABLE SYNAPSE-‘WON’ (CRIMINALLY ACCURATE VERSION)

Programmable Synapse-WON Model: Organ Stack of Korean (Criminal Technical Analysis)

6.1 NEUROMORPHIC PRODUCTS TYPE

SAMSUNG (TEXAS): NEUROMORPHIC SYSTEM (KOREAN NATIONALITY)

UNDER DATA PROTECTION LAW

6.1.5. IBM: PULSING SYNAPTIC DEVICES BASED ON PHASE-CHANGE MEMORY TO INCREASE LINEARITY IN WT UPDATE (#US 2016/0125936 A1) (MATTHEW J. BRIGHTSKY, MATTHEW JOSEPH, WANKI KIM, MAXENCE BOUVIER, SANG BUM KIM)

LEGAL MEANING OF ‘RESET’ DECODED

RESET: RESISTANCE OF THE PCM CELL (AMORPHOUS) DR. MADEJ’S EVIDENCE: CO-VAX LED U.S. BATCH LIGHT PULSING EMITTING DIODE

FIG. 1

The Samsung Inventor in the IBM Patent, “Pulsing Synaptic Devices Based on Phase-Change Memory to Increase The Linearity in Weight Update”¹⁰ (patent also available in Europe, French entitled: “Dispositifs synaptiques à impulsions basés sur une mémoire à changement de phase afin d’augmenter la linéarité dans la mise à jour de poids”, China and America), the RESET pulse is an electrical pulse applied to the PCM cell (a) to melt and quench the programming region of the PCM cell and (b) return it to RESET level, that is, the resistance of the PCM cell in its amorphous phase (c) RESET pulse of the PCM cell is modified by changing its width or amplitude: where the amplitude is the maximum amount of current or voltage of the pulse and the width of a pulse is the amount of time between leading and trailing edges of the pulse.

¹⁰ Matthew J. BrightSky, Joseph Kim, Wanki Kim, Bouvier Maxence and SangBum Kim (2016) *Pulsing Synaptic Devices Based on Phase-Change Memory to Increase The Linearity in Weight Update*. World Intellectual Property Organization. (‘Google Patent’) Patent No. WO2022/268416 A1. Available: <https://patents.google.com/patent/WO2022268416A1/en?q=WO2022268416A1>

AMPLITUDE INCREASE

Increasing amplitude of the RESET pulse results in (a) more amorphized material, increases the (b) **threshold voltage** required for **switching** which is the **voltage required** to induce a programming current that increases dramatically during programming of the PCM cell.

Decreasing amplitude of the RESET pulse results in (a) less amorphized material, decreases the (b) threshold voltage required for switching.

WIDTH OF RESET PULSE

Increasing width of the RESET pulse results in (a) more amorphized material and (b) more time for heat conduction.

Decreasing width of the RESET pulse results in (a) less amorphized material and (b) less time for heat conduction.

JUDGEMENT¹¹ (PERP-ID containers organs banks-in @WLC:

EUROPEAN / AMERICAN VERSION (WO/US) CN VERSION

FIG. 5 is an operational flow chart showing phase change process computer system and computer program product for increasing linearity of a weight update of a phase change memory (PCM) cell. It includes: (i) applying a RESET pulse to amorphize the phase change material (memory) of PCM cell.

ELECTRICAL PULSES TO CHANGE PHASE (LAB DIAGRAMS)

The phase change material used in PCM, which is the material that **changes phase in response to electrical pulses**, has an incubation time which represents the amount of energy that must be introduced to the phase change material before crystal growth can occur.

¹¹ (PERP-ID containers organs banks-in @WLC: VOTE _ EVIDENCE CONTRIBUTORS)

The incubation time correlates with a (a) number of weight update pulses that must be applied to the phase change material *after* RESET (b) **before the energy barrier to crystal growth is overcome.**

SPACE ANSWER: So, correct energy (from GOD'S WORD: bible-code cells' DNA) that block (bible-code overwrites the binary code = barcode = KING-PIN PERP Bar-Bi-Lun).

FIG. 6A

FIG. 6A depicts 600 PCM 'mushroom' cell after RESET pulse. PCM cell comprises of a layer of phase change material 102 that comprises of a programming region 602 i.e. region of phase change material 102 that changes phase in response to programming pulses applied by (a) top electrode 604 and (b) bottom electrode 606: any programming pulses applied to phase change material 102 as part of phase changing includes SET / PARTIAL SET / RESET and incubation pulses.

The amplitude of the partial SET pulse may be tuned such that the current is neither so high as to induce melt-quenching, nor too low to induce crystallization, such that the pulses maintain a ratio of change in conductivity to a number of pulses sufficient to produce a linear weight update.

FIG. 6B

FIG. 6B depicts 600 PCM 'mushroom' cell after partial SET pulses without pre-annealing to induce gradual crystallization resulting in the formation of various thin crystallized current paths 608 through programming region 602.

Thus, the width and amplitude of the partial SET pulses may be specially formulated to produce a consistent effect on the conductivity/resistance of the PCM cell 202.

FIG. 6C

FIG. 6C depicts 600 PCM ‘mushroom’ cell after partial SET pulse with pre-annealing that results in pulses creating crystalline paths 610 through programming region 602 then expanded by subsequent pulses.

In contrast to the “smooth and linear weight update” in FIG. 4, forming new current pathways (through programming region 602 using partial SET pulses absent a pre-annealing component instead of growing the existing current pathways 608) cause different amounts of change in the resistance / conductivity of the PCM cell 202 resulting in inconsistent weight update behaviour.

ELECTRICAL PULSES TO CHANGE PHASE (LAB GRAPHS)

FIG. 2 is an electrical diagram illustrating PCM synaptic device.

FIG. 3 is a graph showing (i) **real** weight update behaviour of a PCM cell based on current methods.

FIG. 4 is a graph showing (ii) **target** weight update behaviour of a PCM cell.

Line 402 represents the **ideal weight update** behaviour where the **conductance** of the phase change material 102 **changes uniformly** with @each partial SET pulse, resulting in a smooth and linear weight update (to support **phase states** and **memory states**).

EVIDENCE EXAMINATION SECTION: PROGRAMMABLE E-WALLET (NOT MONEY) SYNAPSE-WON (WI-FI) PROGRAMMABLE SYNAPSE (THE CRIMINALLY ACCURATE VERSION)

Programmable E-Wallet (NOT MONEY) Synapse-WON Model: Korean (Criminal Technical Analysis)

6.1 NEUROMORPHIC PRODUCTS TYPE

SAMSUNG (TEXAS): NEUROMORPHIC SYSTEM (KOREAN NATIONALITY)

UNDER DATA PROTECTION LAW

6.1.6. IBM MODEL: PHASE CHANGE MEMORY WITH METASTABLE SET AND RESET STATES (US 2017/0364793 A1) (SANGBUM KIM, CHUNG H. LAM)¹²

LEGAL MEANING OF 'RESET' DECODED

FIG. 1 RESET / METASTABLE SET: PHASE CHANGE 104

DOPED: SILICON / CARBON (GRAPHENE)-CO-VAX

Fig. 1

FIG. 2 PHASE CHANGE MATERIAL COUPLED

PROGRAMMER CIRCUIT 202: APPLY

Fig. 2

In the Samsung inventor in IBM Patent, “Phase Change Memory With Metastable Set and Reset States”¹³ a memory device that includes a ‘phase’ change material (WB-FALSE) is ‘programmable’ (WB-FALSE) to a ‘meta’stable set (FB-META-FALSE) / ‘reset’ state (WEF-FALSE).

FIG. 1 phase change material 104 is doped with a doping material: doped with **nitrogen / carbon** (Analogy: GRAPHENE in CO-VAX CHIP circuitry micro-constructed via WIFI programmable remotely) / **silicon** (GEL or OXIDE) / **oxygen**. The dopants can change the (memory device) characteristic operating voltages / resistance / drift speeds.

FIG. 2 is a memory device 102 with **phase change material** 104 electrically coupled to a **programmer circuit** 202 configured to apply a **program voltage V** (or program current I) between the **electrode 1** and 2.

¹² Criminal Patent Abandoned (Commendable: Thorough lab studies over prolonged period of at least >10 years made available to the public along the way prior to introduction)

¹³ BrightSky, Sanbum Kim, Wanki Kim and Chung H. Lam (2016) *Phase Change Memory With Metastable Set and Reset States*. United States Patent Office. ('Google Patent') Patent No. US 2016/0125936 A1. Available: <https://patents.google.com/patent/US20160125936A1/en?q=US20160125936A1>

DRIFT SPEED (SET / RESET)

Program voltage V (or program current I) are **inversely proportional** to a **drift speed** of the phase change material toward the **initial** electrical resistance over time.

Thus, by using different (SET) and/or (RESET) voltage, the Rset and/or Rreset drift speed can be controlled. For example, with lower Vset and Vreset, faster drift speed of Rset and Rreset (and the faster forgetting over time).

NO ELECTRICAL POWER REQUIRED

Phase change memory or PCM is called non-volatile (because no electrical power is required to maintain **either phase** of the material) **random-access memory** that utilizes a **semiconductor alloy** that can be changed rapidly changed between (i) an **ordered crystalline** phase with low electrical resistance to (ii) **disordered amorphous** phase with high electrical resistance.

The **resistance of a current** running through the PCM cell is measured to **identify** the (a) **phase** of the cell (b) allow the cell to **store** a bit of information and (c) function as a memory.

Final note. The word 'Samsung' is, in fact, outer-space 'three stars" GLYPH means: 'SAM' 三 (Korean 삼)
/'SUNG' 星 (MEANS BIRTH OF A SUN) (Korean 성) decoded in GLYPH-Chinese.

LAW EVIDENCE EXAMINATION SECTION: COMPUTER WIFI PROGRAMMABLE SYNAPSE-'WON' (CRIMINALLY ACCURATE VERSION)

Programmable Synapse-WON Model: Organ Stack of Korean (Criminal Technical Analysis)

6.1 NEUROMORPHIC PRODUCTS TYPE

SAMSUNG (TEXAS): NEUROMORPHIC SYSTEM (KOREAN NATIONALITY)

UNDER DATA PROTECTION LAW

6.1.7. SAMSUNG ELECTRONICS CO.: ARTIFICIAL NEURON APPARATUS (US10949735 B2) (EVANGELOS S. ELEFThERIOU)

FIG. 2 ALTERNATE FORMAT OF PCM MUSHROOM

The Samsung Patent, “Artificial Neuron Apparatus”¹⁴ shows an alternate format of PCM mushroom. The cell shown here is the ‘mushroom cell’ type having a chalcogenide material such as **GST (Germanium-Antimony-Tellurium)** disposed between a first ‘top’ electrode and second ‘bottom’ electrode: serves as heater for heating a **dome of amorphous chalcogenide** within the otherwise **crystalline material**. The bottom portion (FIG.) indicated how cell-resistance varies with number of write pulses.

- (i) Resistance is **initially high** due to presence of **high-resistance amorphous** dome between the electrodes.
- (ii) **Successive write** pulses cause **partial** crystallization of amorphous volume, whereby cell-

¹⁴ Evangelos S. Eleftheriou, Angeliki Pantazi, Abu Sebastian and Tomas Tuma. (2023) *Artificial Neuron Apparatus*. United States Patent Application Publication ('Google Patent') US 10,949,735 B2. Available at: <https://patents.google.com/patent/US10949735B2/en?q=US10949735B2>

resistance is progressively reduced. (iii) **Progressive crystallization** ultimately leads to **almost complete crystallization of amorphous** material or at least formation of a **crystalline 'percolation path'** through the amorphous material.

SWITCH (FIN-TECH x SWITCH: FALSE)

Formation of this **conductive pathway** causes **switching** of the cell to the low-resistance state.

RESET

The cell can be **reset ('RESET')** to its initial high-resistance state by an application of a **pulse of sufficient power to melt** the chalcogenide material adjacent the bottom electrode. The high-resistance amorphous dome is then restored on cooling.

CRIMINAL OPERATION: SET-UP (PCM MUSHROOM) FIG. 6 (E.G. CO-VAX CHIP: NEURON CIRCUITRY)

CELL (MUSHROOM) 21 + LEAKY INTEGRATOR 28 + OUTPUT CIRCUIT 29
 COMPARATOR 41 + OUTPUT TERMINAL 30:

FIG. 6 shows exemplary criminal implementation of a neuron circuitry i.e. read circuit includes: CELL (MUSHROOM) 21

(i) read resistance R_s connected between cell 21 ('mushroom') and ground terminal

LEAKY INTEGRATOR 28

(ii) Leaky integrator 28 implemented by **operational amplifier 40** connect to: (1) capacitor C and (2) resistors R 1 and R 2.

OUTPUT CIRCUIT 29

(iii) **Output circuit 29** includes: **Comparator 41** compares **measurement signal MP**,

(A) If voltage V_m at output amplifier 40 with firing threshold represented by voltage V_{th} : $V_m < V_{th}$.

OUTPUT SWITCH S 0:

(iv) **Output Switch S 0**: connected between **Comparator 41** and **output terminal 30**, connects output terminal to ground,

(A) if voltage $V_m > V_{th}$,

(B) V_m (measurement signal) **exceeds** firing **threshold V_{th}** : **Cell 21** switches to low-resistance state

COMPARATOR 41:

The (i) **comparator 41** generates **control signal** which **triggers switching** of:

(a) **switch S 0** (b) to connect **output terminal (c)** to **signal pathway 42** (shared between **multiple neuron circuits in neuromorphic system**) on which **periodic spike train** is generated by:

SPIKE GENERATOR CIRCUIT R 43:

(ii) **spike generator circuit 43**: generate spikes with desired spike shape for **neuron output signals** with (iii) periodicity T_p chosen according to (iv) leakage time of integrator 28: to ensure (v) at least one spike is supplied to output terminal 30 while switch S 0 is closed.

CRIMINAL OPERATION: EXPLANATION (PCM MUSHROOM) FIG. 11

CELL ('MUSHROOM') 21

+ STORAGE CIRCUIT 28
SS V_m :

+ OUTPUT CIRCUIT 29

SWITCH S1 SS READ
SIGNAL:

SWITCH S2 RESP RESET
Measurement Signal V_m :

SWITCH S3 RESP CONTROL
SIGNAL:

FIG. 11 First input terminal 62: receives **neuron input signals** applied to the 'mushroom' cell 21. The second input terminal 63: connected to signal pathway 61.

SWITCH SET: THREE SWITCHES

First Switch Set S1 supply **read signal** to storage circuit 28 (during application of read portion V R of neuron input signal to 'mushroom' cell 21).

Second Switch S2 operable in response to **RESET** portion V RST of neuron input signal, supply measurement signal Vm to output circuit 29: during application of RESET portion to 'mushroom' cell 21).

Third Switch S3 **operable in response to CONTROL** signal generated by comparator 41, when $V_m > V$ th i.e. when cell switches to **low-resistance** state. In response to CONTROL signal generated by comparator 41, Third Switch S3 **switches** to connect second input terminal 63 to cell 21 which is thus **reset** to its **high-resistance** state (during the RESET portion V RST of the input signal which **triggers output spike**).

FIG. 8: PCM NEURON, SYNAPSES, STREAM OF FIRING EVENTS [PERP-\(201 NY / WUHAN FAKE PORTS DRILL, WUHAN MILITARY GAMES WITH INAUGURAL LED 8K PIXEL, FIN-\(‘GER’\)-TECH \(LAW\) SWITCH: 1-SHOT 100PLUS-ARMY PLOT FAKE TRADING PLATFORM KING-PIN PERP: 000,000,000\)](#)

FIG. 8

FIG. 8 PCM-based neuron 51 (Correlation detector 50):

(i) Each synapse receives a **stream of firing events** (corresponds to pre-synaptic neuron) at timings denoted by 't pre'.

(a) **Upper $M \ll N$ input streams** correlated triggered by function f of a common random function R.

(b) **Lower N streams** of synaptic input events: triggered by uncorrelated random functions R.

Spike timing dependent plasticity function employed: synaptic weight is **incrementally increased** if pre- and post-synaptic events are ordered i.e. pre-synaptic event precedes post-synaptic event.

SYNAPSE COMPUTATION LOGIC: Synapses change weight (input signals (amplitude V_w) to neuron 51) dynamically depending on relative timings: $T_{pre} - T_{post}$ for pre- and post-neuron spike events.
(ii) Neuron input terminal receives signals from **multiple synapses 52** via dendrite inputs.

JUDGEMENT

Firing events include: Event 201 NY / Event Wuhan fake ports drill with Wuhan military games with inaugural LED 8K Pixel / Fin-(ger)-Tech (Law) Switch Reset. King-Pin-PERP plot: 1-shot 100PLUS-ARMY plot. (Low IQ total nonsense: product fake trading platform manipulation from computer of nations' thieves: 000,000,000 and using race flood.)

LAW EVIDENCE EXAMINATION SECTION: COMPUTER WIFI PROGRAMMABLE SYNAPSE-WON E-WALLET (CRIMINALLY ACCURATE VERSION)

Programmable Synapse-WON Model: Organ Stack of Korean (Criminal Technical Analysis)

6.2. EEG SENSOR CO-VAX CHIP CIRCUITRY PRODUCTS TYPE

UNDER PHARMA LAW (/ MEDI-CRIME LAW / COUNTERFEIT MEDI-PRODUCTS) / KEY HUMAN RIGHTS AND BIO-MEDICINE LAW / INTERNATIONAL CRIMINAL LAW

SAMSUNG (TEXAS): COMPUTER 'CONTROLLER' CO-VAX CHIP CIRCUITRY PHARMA-AND-BIO-MEDI-COUNTERFEIT PRODUCT-CRIME

6.2.1. SAMSUNG ELECTRONICS CO. (EEG-1A-CO-VAX CHIP): CURRENT SIMULATOR FOR RECORDING CRANIAL NERVE SIGNALS OPERATION (CHISUNG BAE SERIES)

FIG. 1 & 2: CURRENT SIMULATOR OF PREDETERMINED MAGNITUDE

FIG. 1

FIG. 2: CURRENT INTO CRANIAL NERVE CELL (NEURON 250), ANALOG FRONT END AFE-260

FIG. 2

This SAMSUNG Patent, “Cranial Stimulator for Recording Cranial Nerve Signals And Operation Method of Current Simulator”¹⁵ signal transduction scheme of a brain interpreted by (i) passing a current of a predetermined magnitude (ii) to stimulate a cranial nerve cell noiselessly and then observe (iii) an

¹⁵ Seong Joong Kim, Chisung Bae and Hankyu Lee. (2023) *Current Stimulator For Recording Cranial Nerve Signals And Operation Method of Current Stimulator*. United States Patent Office. ('Google Patent') Patent No. US 2023/0208286 A1. Available: <https://patents.google.com/patent/US20230208286A1/en?q=US+2023%2f0208286+A1>

intracellular signal e.g. ultra-fine currents units tens of picoampere (pA) / nanoampere (nA) / microampere (mA) observed without noise.

CRIMINAL OPERATION: CURRENT INJECTABLE (CO-VAX CHIP) INTO CRANIAL NERVE CELL

FIG. 1 illustrates a current stimulator for providing a current of a **predetermined magnitude** to a cranial nerve cell and FIG. 2 illustrates a current stimulator (200) that generates a current provided to a cranial nerve cell (neuron):

(1) **first current generation circuit** is configured (a) to generate a first current injectable (injected e.g. BIO-W2 CO-VAX) into a cranial nerve cell (b) through a **current mirroring** based on a plurality of transistor pairs (IBM SILICON TRANSISTOR / DR. NIXON METALLIC FABRIC): 1st and 2nd transistor pair configured to output a positive / negative current respectively and further configured to generate nanoampere / microampere unit of measure injectable into the cranial nerve cell.

(2) Second current generation circuit: driven by a clock ('TICK TOCK') configured (a) to **generate** a second current smaller than the first (b) by **controlling a charge rate** based on **voltage difference** between terminals of a capacitor (c) includes a first / second switch: that operate based on clock switching (d) capacitor (disposed between the first / second switch) configured to **adjust magnitude** by controlling charge rate.

The magnitude is determined based on: (a) any one or combination of 2 or more **clock frequency** (b) **capacitance** of the capacitor (c) difference between input / output **voltage**.

Thus, the first output impedance of the first current generation circuit and a second **output** impedance of the second current generation circuit have a magnitude greater than or equal to a **predetermined ratio** to a **load** impedance corresponding to the cranial nerve cell.

LEGAL OBSERVATION

The SAMSUNG Patent designer self-claimed: that there exists is a demand for accurately providing 'noiseless' current for stimulating cranial nerve cell (by unknown suppliers).

CRIMINAL ACT: FIG. 1 MEMBRANE PERMEABILITY

The current stimulator 130 generates and inject current I_e through electrode 170 into cranial nerve cell 110. The cranial nerve cell 110 perform **intracellular binding** by the current I_e provided to the cranial nerve cell 110 and induce and/or maintain membrane permeability (criminal act). The current stimulator 130 provides current I_e to compensate for leakage current inside the cranial nerve cell 110 (criminal act) [current leakage is inevitably generated due to **membrane permeabilization** of cranial nerve cell 110].

ANALOG FRONT END (AFE)-260 CRIMINAL ACT: PIXEL DOTS REP / SPIKE DIGIT

The criminal apparatus analog front end-260 (AFE) (1) decodes a signal generated from neuron-250 (2) as a circuit generated by current stimulator-200 (3) stimulates neuron-250 into a digital signal (SEE: IBM RBM spike conversion).

This criminal format is a complete match with the IBM “RBM visual digit recognition” in published papers, namely: “Building Block Of A **Programmable Neuromorphic Substrate: A Digital Neurosynaptic Core**” and “A Digital Neurosynaptic Core Using **Embedded Crossbar** Memory 45pJ Per Spike in 45nm” with explicit explanation of how pixels representing visible units drive spike activity on **excitatory (+)** and **inhibitory (-)** axons to stimulate a 16 x 16 grid of neurons on the chip. Spikes are indicated as black squares and encode the digit as a set of features.

CRIMINAL LAB REPORTS: (GRAPHICAL FORMAT)

THE INTERCHANGE BETWEEN CRIMINAL COMPONENTS: $\Phi 1, 2 / V_{sc} / \text{Electric Charge: } Q_{sc}$

FIG. 6

FIG. 6 clearly shows perpetrator’s knowledge of the r/s and experimental results (Graphical Evidence) between current generated from a second current generation circuit and a clock frequency: $\Phi 1$ first switch (510) / $\Phi 2$ second switch (520) / Voltage of capacitor (530) V_{sc} / Quantity of Electric Charge: Q_{sc} of capacitor.

CURRENT MIRRORING (CM) CRIMINAL LAB REPORTS (GRAPHICAL FORMAT-350)
R: FINE STEP TUNING

FIG. 3

Current mirroring is a circuit structure in which current of the same size is continuously generated using a CO-VAX CHIP POP-100 transistor. As a mirroring structure, it generates multiple constant current sources by (1) copying a current flowing in an arbitrary circuit and (2) supplying it equally to other circuits.

For example, the first current generation circuit 210 generates a first current that shows linearity in all sections regardless of a clock frequency (FIG. 3 GRAPH 330).

CIRCUIT 210: FIG. 2 First current generation circuit 210 generates a first current of nanoampere (nA) unit and/or microampere (pA) unit **injected into** the neuron 250 through a **current mirroring structure**. (FIG. 2 INJECTED NEURON 250). This can explain the glassy appearance in CO-VAX CHIP.

CIRCUIT 230: FIG. 2 Second current generation circuit ISC 230 is driven by a clock and generates a second current (smaller than < the first current ICM) by **controlling a rate of movement of a charge** caused by a **voltage difference** between both ends of a capacitor. (FIG. 2 CIRCUIT ISC 230)

'FINE - COARSE STEP': CONTROL BY SWITCHED CAPACITOR STRUCTURE / SWITCHING FREQUENCY /

L: COARSE STEP R: FINE STEP

FIG. 3

In the first current generation circuit (CM structure), the current stimulator generates (1) first current corresponding to points **351, 353, 355, 357, 359** with large current units (L: Coarse Step) at coarse intervals of a nanoampere (nA) unit or a microampere (uA) (GRAPH 350) (b) with current values corresponding to (i) '0.2' nA 331 (ii) '1' nA 333 (iii) '10' nA 335 (iv) '100' nA 337 and (v) '1000' nA (= '1' uA) 339 (GRAPH 330) current mirror current injector

(2) second current generation circuit whereby the current stimulator generates a minute second (Fine step) current starting at points **351, 353, 355, 357, 359** (GRAPH 350) interval points controlled by the current mirroring (CM) structure of the first current generation circuit with (i) same gradient as line 313 (dashed 'circle') in (GRAPH 310) with (ii) fine interval of a picoampere unit in a frequency section e.g. 20 kHz to 130 kHz, corresponding to line 313 in (GRAPH 310).

LAW EVIDENCE EXAMINATION SECTION: COMPUTER WIFI PROGRAMMABLE SYNAPSE-WON E-WALLET (CRIMINALLY ACCURATE VERSION)

Programmable Synapse-WON Model: Organ Stack of Korean (Criminal Technical Analysis)

6.2. EEG SENSOR CO-VAX CHIP CIRCUITRY PRODUCTS TYPE

UNDER PHARMA LAW (/ MEDI-CRIME LAW / COUNTERFEIT MEDI-PRODUCTS) / KEY HUMAN RIGHTS AND BIO-MEDICINE LAW / INTERNATIONAL CRIMINAL LAW

SAMSUNG (TEXAS): COMPUTER 'CONTROLLER' CO-VAX CHIP CIRCUITRY PHARMA-AND-BIO-MEDI-COUNTERFEIT PRODUCT-CRIME

6.2.2. SAMSUNG ELECTRONICS CO. (EEG-2-CO-VAX CHIP): BIO-PROCESSING ELEMENT AND NEURAL NETWORK PROCESSOR (NEURAL MORPHIC, CULTURED BIOLOGICAL NEURONS) (CHISUNG BAE SERIES)

FIG. 1 SAMSUNG (NEURAL MORPHIC CULTURED BIO-NEURONS) STACKED NEURAL NETWORK PROCESSOR

FIG.1

FIG. 4 IBM NEUROGRID'S SW H/W: NGPYTHON

Neuron: soma + dendrite + 4-gating BIO-variable + 4-synapse-population circuits.

In the Samsung Patent, “Bio-Processing Element and Neural Network Processor with Bio-Processing Element”¹⁶,

FIG. 1 SILICON VIAS (CO-VAX CHIP)

FIG. 1 shows bio-processing element and neural network processor, in short, bioprocessing device performing (illegal) operation based on based on cultured biological neurons which includes:

- (i) electrode layer comprising of: electrodes connected to biological neurons

¹⁶ Hankyu Lee, Sang Joon Kim and Chisung Bae (2022) *Bio-processing Element and Neural Network Processor With Bio-processing Element*. United States Patent Office. ('Google Patent') Patent No. US 2022/0414435 A1. Available: <https://patents.google.com/patent/US20220414435A1/en?qoq=US20220414435A1>

- (ii) (b) circuit layers (a) stacked with electrode layer (c) comprising of stacked circuits for biological neurons
- (iii) inter-layer connectors configured: to connect (a) electrode layer and (b) circuit layers, made of either: Through silicon vias (TSVs) penetrating (i) + (ii) circuit layers and micro-bumps connecting (i) electrode layer and (ii) circuit layers

FIG. SILICON SUBSTRATE¹⁷

FIG. 3A, B NEURONOFF ELECTRODE CURED MANUFACTURED IN-BODY

FIG. 3A

FIG. 3B

DR. NIXON: PFIZER MEGALITHIC-X-CHIP ON-BLOCK

The bioprocessing element-100 criminal function is to (i) record (measure) neural signals generated in the biological neurons and/or (ii) inject a stimulus signal to the biological neurons: by contacting the biological neurons via electrodes.

The neural network processor-500 secure or achieve infinite 2-D (QUOTE ELON MUSK) ‘scalability’ by connecting the plurality of bioprocessing elements-100 (POP-0 to 100) in parallel and measure (POP-0 to 100) biological neurons’ signals.

CRIMINAL METAL-OXIDE

It is clearly stated that the electrode layer-110 is made of “complementary metal-oxide-semiconductor (CMOS) microelectrode array (MEA)”, an electrode array configured to:

- (i) record electrophysiological activities of a plurality of biological neurons in parallel
- (ii) identify a synaptic weight map between biological neurons (to record / analyze) neural signals simultaneously
- (iii) from a plurality of channels of the biological neurons.

¹⁷ <https://resources.system-analysis.cadence.com/blog/what-are-through-silicon-vias>

FIG. 5 NEURAL NETWORK PROCESSOR-500 TRANSMISSION OF FARADIC CURRENT + MEMBRANE PENETRATION + CELL CHANGE ELECTRODE

FIG. 5 shows a neural network processor-500 that achieve infinite 2D 'scalability' () by connecting a plurality of bio-processing elements-100 connected in parallel. It clearly states: a "programming platform" records a "functional map of a natural neural network" (human intelligence). This 'human intelligence' (neural perpetrator's perspective) refers to 'measuring signals of all biological neurons' in real time, specially, the **membrane potential** of each biological neurons from bio-processing elements-100 by extracting (i) action potential (ii) post-synaptic potential in biological neurons.

NEURAL NETWORK MAP: Excitatory and/or Inhibitory Synaptic Connection

For example, neural network processor-500 record / analyze neural signals of a large-scale neural network by (i) expansion of recording area (ii) maintaining electrode density of electrodes (iii) through 3D 3-dimensional brain recording platform expandable in real-time by plurally disposing 100 in real-time (iv) tight dispositional spacing between plurality.

Thus, the neural network processor: explicitly map out an entire network about an **excitatory** and/or **inhibitory** synaptic connection of a plurality of biological neurons recorded (during a predetermined time) through (i) a network coverage of a neural network and (ii) parallel processing for recording (in a cell).

Transmission-Faradic Current + Penetration Membrane + Cell Change Electrode

The processor: cause (i) membrane permeability by transmitting **faradaic current** to the bioprocessing elements (100) (ii) cause a gradual **penetration** of a cell membrane and (iii) **change** a cell electrode combination from outside biological neurons to insides of the biological neurons.

The neural network processor 500 cause a membrane permeability by transmitting **faradaic current** (to the bio-processing elements 100): cause a gradual penetration of a cell membrane and change a cell-electrode combination from outside the biological neurons to inside the biological neurons.

This conclusively explains the criminal act behind PER A-Z POP-(e-shock) massacre.

LAW EVIDENCE EXAMINATION SECTION: COMPUTER WIFI PROGRAMMABLE SYNAPSE-‘WON’ (CRIMINALLY ACCURATE VERSION)

Programmable Synapse-WON Model: Organ Stack of Korean (Criminal Technical Analysis)

6.2. EEG SENSOR CO-VAX CHIP CIRCUITRY PRODUCTS TYPE

SAMSUNG (TEXAS): COMPUTER ‘CONTROLLER’ CO-VAX CHIP CIRCUITRY PHARMA-AND-BIO-MEDI-COUNTERFEIT PRODUCT-CRIME

UNDER PHARMA LAW (/ MEDI-CRIME LAW / COUNTERFEIT MEDI-PRODUCTS) / KEY HUMAN RIGHTS AND BIO-MEDICINE LAW / INTERNATIONAL CRIMINAL LAW

6.2.3. SAMSUNG ELECTRONICS CO. (EEG-3-CO-VAX CHIP): BIO-ELECTROCEUTICAL DEVICE USING CELL CLUSTER (CHISUNG BAE SERIES)

The Samsung Patent, “Bio-Electroceutical Device Using Cell Cluster”¹⁸ shows an ion transporter, organoid fused with biomaterial, secreting active component via an electrical signal using a cell controller.

LEGAL EXHIBIT:

¹⁸ Young Jun Hong, Hyejin Park, Seokyoung Kang, Soyoung Bang, Sang Joon Kim and Chisung Bae (2022) *Bio-Electroceutical Device Using Cell Cluster*. United States Patent Office. ('Google Patent') Patent No. US 2021/0220558 A1. Available: [https://patents.google.com/patent/US20210220558A1/en?q=\(Bio-Electroceutical+Device+Using+Cell+Cluster\)&inventor=chisung+bae&oq=chisung+bae+Bio-Electroceutical+Device+Using+Cell+Cluster](https://patents.google.com/patent/US20210220558A1/en?q=(Bio-Electroceutical+Device+Using+Cell+Cluster)&inventor=chisung+bae&oq=chisung+bae+Bio-Electroceutical+Device+Using+Cell+Cluster)

SAMSUNG FIG. 11: ION TRANSPORTER ('IONIZED ACTIVE COMPONENT')

IBM NEUROGRID: ION CHANNEL GATING VARIABLES SODIUM Na^+ CALCIUM Ca^{2+} (SOMA, MEMBRANE TRACES) / POP-SYNAPSE CONDUCTANCE CIRCUIT / NEURO-TRANSMITTER 'KILL-SWITCH' CHAIN REACTION)

LEGAL EXHIBIT:

FIG. 11

'THE CONTROLLER' (UNDER GDPR LAW OR DATA PROTECTION LAW 'DEFINITION' OMITTED)

FIG. 11 shows **absorption** of an active component by a bio-electroceutical device i.e. the cell controller:

- (i) diffusion rate and
- (ii) diffusion direction of an ionized active component by applying electrical signal to **the outside** through
- (iii) (SEE: FIG. 11) active component (WHITE BALLS) channel electrode in (CDC PROFITABLE patented process) 'treatment mode'.

ION TRANSPORTER 1155 / IONIZED ACTIVE 1154

ION TRANSPORTER ('IONIZED ACTIVE COMPONENT') ALTERNATE DEPICTION

ION
ORCHARD

The cell controller 1120 (bio-electrochemical device):

- (1) apply an electrical signal through an active component channel 1123: working electrode DC_WE to an active component counter electrode DC_CE
- (2) induce a movement of **active component** 1152 (WHITE BALLS) channel electrode discharged

- (3) combined with an **ion transporter** 1155 (BLACK BALLS)
- (4) to a blood vessel 1154-**ionized active component** (GREY BALLS) through the application of electrical signal: That exhibit **polarity accelerated** along the electric path to control the **diffusion direction**. For example, increase/decrease the magnitude of electrical signal applied to active component channel 1123 to increase/decrease diffusion rate.

Thus, the bio-electroceutical device secrete and transfer the **ionized active component**-1154 combined with **ion transporter** using **microcurrents** as additional electrical stimulation to enhance rate of input of active component 1152 into the blood vessel.

'CONTROLLER' UNDER GDPR LAW OR DATA PROTECTION LAW (OMITTED OFF DEFINITION)
FIG. 14 CRIMINAL OPERATION: SECRETION ACT (CRIMINAL SENSOR)

FIG. 14

LEFT: cell reservoir (1430)

RIGHT: cell controller (1420)

FIG. 14 shows an example of structures of a cell delivery system detachable from a bio-electroceutical device includes: (i) electrochemical sensor configured to sense a target molecule (a) concentration level inside a body disposed in (ii) cell reservoir configured to accommodate a cell cluster comprising of an organoid disposed in a bio-material (c) electrode disposed in the exterior of the cell reservoir electrically connected to the (iii) cell controller configured to apply to the cell cluster, an electrical signal that induces a secretion of an active component by the organoid (based on the result of sensing of the target molecule) (iv) to determine a criminal target generation rate of an active component secreted by an organoid disposed of in the cell reservoir.

FIG. 15 CRIMINAL OPERATION: SKIN PENETRATION

DR. NIXON TUBES IN PIZER INJECTABLE

FIG. 15

RIGHT (INSIDE): cell reservoir (1530) LEFT (OUTER): cell controller (1520)

'CONTROLLER' UNDER GDPR LAW OR DATA PROTECTION LAW (OMITTED OFF DEFINITION)

FIG. 15, the cell reservoir (1530) detachable from a bio-electroceutical device is (i) configured in the form of a pod (ii) inserted into the body part e.g. dermal layer (1591) under a skin (thickness up to 5mm, between subcutaneous layer (1592) and skin).

For example, the cell controller (1520) allows a body fluid to flow through an inlet formed at a front end and discharge body fluid through an opening (1529) formed at the distant end. Porous membranes disposed in the inlet (1538) and outlet (1539).

For example, when cell controller (1520) and cell reservoir (1530) are coupled, electrodes connectors (1521) are disposed to be electrically connected to (1) **stimulation** channel electrodes 1531 and (2) **sensing** channel electrodes 1532.

FIG. 4: ELECTRODES OF 'SENSING/STIMULATION' CHANNEL

FIG. 4

ELECTRODES OF STIMULATION CHANNEL

FIG. 4 shows electrodes of a (i) stimulation channel 422:

- (a) stimulation working electrode STIM_WE
- (b) stimulation counter electrode STIM_CE, that induce secretion of active component based on target generation rate for an organoid in cell cluster 410 thus providing an electrical signal (determined by cell controller 420 to cell cluster 410)

ELECTRODES OF SENSING CHANNEL

- (ii) sensing channel 421:
 - (a) sensing counter electrode EC_CE,
 - (b) sensing EC_WE and

(c) sensing reference electrode EC_RE connected to the cell controller 420.

The electrodes are electrically connected to cell cluster 410 or disposed adjacent.

Cell reservoir includes: (i) cell cluster (1210) disposed inside the porous membrane (ii) cell controller (1220) separately packaged outside (the porous membrane) and (iii) cell reservoir is detachable from the cell controller 1220.

FIG. 4 TARGET MOLECULE 451 SENSED BY ELECTROCHEMICAL SENSOR

'CONTROLLER' UNDER GDPR LAW OR DATA PROTECTION LAW

For example, cell controller 420 determine target generation rate based on result of sensing target molecule 451 (WHITE DOTS) and determine any one or any combination of a pulse width, magnitude, frequency, phase and waveform of an electrical signal applied to the cell cluster 410 based on determined target (generation rate) with 'parameters' of electrical signal determined and controlled by cell controller 420.

For example, the organoid in the cell cluster 410 (stimulated by electrical signal) secretes active component 452 discharged from cell reservoir 419 with a changed active component generation rate in response to electrical stimulation.

Electrochemical sensor sense changed concentration of target molecule 451. Cell 'controller' 420 re-identify metabolic state based on changed concentration and redetermine whether to apply the electrical stimulation.

Thus, the cell controller 420 measure concentration of target molecule 451 (WHITE DOTS) in the body every time a secretion of an active component is facilitated and inhibited and determine whether a 'treatment' is required e.g. whether to repeat secrete the active component.

LEGAL ANALYSIS

This is the 'treatment' that matches (e.g. CDC illegal profits-off bodily cells: UPLOAD AMT) is murder.

FIG. 9 ENGRAFTING OPERATION OF IMPLANT: BIO-ELECTROCEUTICAL DEVICE

FIG. 9

FIG. 9 shows an **implantation** operation of **engrafting** the bio-electroceutical device into the body. The cell controller 920 perform **sensing** operation and a **stimulation** operation to **increase engraftment rate** of the bio-electroceutical device.

The cell controller (ii) enhances active component **acceptability** through **electrical stimulation** that **induces** 'treatment' of a region, for example, blood vessel or capillary around the part of the body in which bio-electroceutical device is inserted. Then, the cell controller 920 facilitate a **deposition** of an **extracellular matrix (ECM)** through an electrical stimulation to apply DC stimulation or low-frequency AC stimulation as an **iontophoretic** stimulation, add a **frequency** of the low-frequency AC stimulation in the **delta frequency bank 710 or theta frequency bank 720 (FIG. 7)** of (c) active component channel 923: to increase **epidermal growth factor (EGF)** and **vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF)**.

Thus, a **regeneration** of the **capillary 992**, in response to **electrical stimulation**, grow to a position closer to the bio-electroceutical device so that the **gap** between the capillary 992 and position (**outer surface of porous membrane**) in which (c) active component is discharged (from bio- electroceutical device) is reduced. Thus, a **connectivity** between the capillary 992 and bio- electroceutical device is **strengthened** (due to **gap reduction**) and **engraftment** rate of bio-e device further increased (due to strengthened connectivity).

In summation, the purpose of capillary 992 regeneration facilitated is to enhance (c) active component acceptability.

ADD-ON: ELECTROCHEMICAL SENSOR: GLUCOSE OXIDASE ENZYME (GOx) (AMP)

For example, electrochemical sensor 520 of FIG. 5B sense currents flowing from sensing working electrode EC_WE to a sensing counter electrode EC_CE w/o driving power. The electrochemical sensor 520 is implemented by a glucose oxidase enzyme (GOx). In FIG. 5B, current is measured using amperometry. For example, electrochemical sensor 530 of FIG. 5C operate using **cyclic voltammetry (CV)** or **electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS)**.

PULSE PARAMETERS (E.G. MICROSOFT WO060606 'PARAMETERS' / 'VECTORS')

FIG. 6

FIG. 6 shows **parameters** of an electrical signal used for stimulation of a cell cluster.

The cell controller controls a pulse width, current intensity, frequency of a pulse, a phase and waveform, thus determine and control parameters of (i) individual pulse 610, (ii) pulse-train 620 (set of pulses) and (iii) train group 630 (set of pulse-trains).

For example, a pulse width is a width of a 'on period' in individual pulse 610: positive electrical signal or negative electrical signal exists indicating a sign of a signal applied to a working electrode WE.

For example, a phase width / inter-pulse space / inter-train space and inter-group space correspond to an OFF period in which an electrical signal is absent.

ELECTRICAL STIMULATION APPLIED CELL CLUSTER

FIG. 7

FIG. 6, 7 show examples of electrical stimulation applied to a cell cluster by a bio-electroceutical device.

LAW EVIDENCE EXAMINATION SECTION: COMPUTER WIFI PROGRAMMABLE SYNAPSE-‘WON’ (CRIMINALLY ACCURATE VERSION)

Programmable Synapse-WON Model: Organ Stack of Korean (Criminal Technical Analysis)

6.2. EEG SENSOR CO-VAX CHIP CIRCUITRY PRODUCTS TYPE

SAMSUNG (TEXAS): COMPUTER ‘CONTROLLER’ CO-VAX CHIP CIRCUITRY PHARMA-AND-BIO-MEDI-COUNTERFEIT PRODUCT-CRIME

UNDER PHARMA LAW (/ MEDI-CRIME LAW / COUNTERFEIT MEDI-PRODUCTS) / KEY HUMAN RIGHTS AND BIO-MEDICINE LAW / INTERNATIONAL CRIMINAL LAW

6.2.4. SAMSUNG ELECTRONICS CO. (EEG-4-CO-VAX CHIP): APPARATUS AND METHOD WITH ELECTRICAL STIMULUS (US 2022/0280775 A1) (DON-WOOK LEE / SANG JOON KIM / KITAE PARK / YOUNG JUN HONG: SEOUL KR)

FIG.3

In the Samsung Patent, “Apparatus and Method with Electrical Stimulus”¹⁹ FIG. 3 is a cell cluster 111 container 101 that includes: first electrode 301 second electrode 303. A positive stimulation voltage is applied to the first electrode 301 (through electrode line 311). A positive stimulation voltage is applied to the first electrode 303 (through electrode line 313).

¹⁹ Don-Wook Lee, Sang Joon Kim, Kitae Park and Young Jun Hong. (2022) *Apparatus and Method With Electrical Stimulus*. United States Patent Office. Patent No. US 2002/0280775 A1. Available: <https://patents.google.com/patent/US20220280775A1/en?q=US20220280775A1>

'THE CONTROLLER' (UNDER GDPR LAW OR DATA PROTECTION LAW LEGAL 'DEFINITION' OMITTED: I INSERTED IT

The 'controller' compares a sensing signal received to a **threshold**:

- (1) When sensing signal is < less than the threshold, the controller will not apply a stimulation voltage.
- (2) When sensing signal is > greater than the threshold, the controller applies a stimulation voltage.

Based on the magnitude of the sensing signal, the controller adjusts the stimulation voltage. By electrical stimulus, the cell cluster 111 secretes insulin [/ CHEMICALS / BACTERIA / PARASITES EMBRYOS]

FIG.4

FIG. 4 is a target material sensed by an indicator container 105 of porous surface with (i) light source 401: light emitting diode of light of predetermined wavelength that irradiate light and (ii) optical sensor 403: (if **concentration** of target material of indicator container 105 is **high**), **large amount of light** is emitted from indicator (coupled to target material) due to great **specific gravity of indicator**. For example, optical sensor 403 sense sufficient amount of light and generates a **sensing signal with high intensity**.

LAW EVIDENCE EXAMINATION SECTION: COMPUTER WIFI PROGRAMMABLE SYNAPSE-WON E-WALLET (CRIMINALLY ACCURATE VERSION)

Programmable Synapse-WON Model: Organ Stack of Korean (Criminal Technical Analysis)

6.2. EEG SENSOR CO-VAX CHIP CIRCUITRY PRODUCTS TYPE

UNDER PHARMA LAW (/ MEDI-CRIME LAW / COUNTERFEIT MEDI-PRODUCTS) / KEY HUMAN RIGHTS AND BIO-MEDICINE LAW / INTERNATIONAL CRIMINAL LAW

SAMSUNG (TEXAS): COMPUTER 'CONTROLLER' CO-VAX CHIP CIRCUITRY PHARMA-AND-BIO-MEDI-COUNTERFEIT PRODUCT-CRIME

6.2.5. SAMSUNG ELECTRONICS CO. (ELECTROCARDIOGRAM EEG): AUTHENTICATION USING GREEDY ALGORITHM (CHISUNG BAE)

In the Samsung Patent, “Electrocardiogram (ECG) Authentication Method and Apparatus”²⁰ in FIG. 9 shows the ‘selection of an **optimal candidate**’ network model from candidate neural network models using a **greedy algorithm**. The training device acquires a (i) plurality of candidate neural network model (training result) (ii) selects a candidate neural network model with highest performance (iii) extracts a candidate semantic feature from ECG training data using each candidate’s neural network models.

²⁰ Chisung Bae (Yongin-Si KR) Sang-joon Kim (Hwaseong-si, KR) and others (2018) Electrocardiogram (ECG) Authentication Method and Apparatus. United States Patent Office. (“Google Patent”) Patent No. US 10,130,307 B2. Available: <https://patents.google.com/patent/US10130307B2/en?q=US+10%2c130%2c307+B2>

For example, the training device selects at least one candidate semantic feature satisfying a reference from a plurality using a forward / backward greedy algorithm.

In the forward greedy algorithm, the training device evaluates performance of one candidate neural network model (based on corresponding candidate semantic feature) and select one that corresponds to the highest performance. For example, forward greedy algorithm selects candidate neural network model 1 at round 1. At round 2, training device selects model 2 that obtains the highest performance (when combined with model 1). Selection process is repetitively performed until a first no. of features set in advance or until an accuracy of the candidate semantic feature does not increase.

The backward greedy algorithm is used to complement the forward greedy algorithm.

FIG. 8B

FIG. 8B shows a neural network model. A pair of items of ECG training data are input to two neural network models.

A weight of a hidden layer is shared between the two neural network models.

In the two neural network models, an output of a previous hidden layer of the **last hidden layer** is determined to be a semantic feature.

FIG. 8A

FIG. 8A shows a neural network model.

A pair of items of ECG training data is input to an input layer of a candidate neural network model. A no. of nodes or neurons included is the same size of an ECG training data dimension.

Uppermost layer is output layer trained based on identification signal.

Hidden layer is located in between input and output layer. An output of the last hidden layer indicates a learned semantic feature. A pair of features output from the last hidden layer corresponds to one authentication output e.g. +1 / -1.

LEGAL SECTION 7:

LAW EVIDENCE EXAMINATION SECTION: UNDER LAW RESEARCH FRAMEWORK

7.1. Examination of Evidence under Law Research Framework: Neuromorphic Circuit / Meta-Core / Radio Frequency ID / Waves of [EEG Analysis \(Brain Vector, Neural Parameterization\)](#)

Criminal Technical Analysis of Perpetrator Testing The Computer YEN CHIP (Journal Series): Neuromorphic Programming Phase Change Memory PCM (DNN, SNN) of Memory Array Circuit (Memory Cell Structure / Cell Driver / LIF Circuits Systems), , Restricted Boltzman Machine and Law Evidence Examination under International Criminal Law

7.2. Criminal Technical Analysis of Perpetrator Testing The Computer YEN CHIP (Patent Series): On-Chip Spike, Pulse Generator, Digital Synapse Leaky integrate Fire LIF Neuron Based Neuromorphic (Update Precise Synaptic Weight Values, Scalable Refresh Non-Volatile Memory Based PCM)

7.3. Criminal Technical Analysis of Perpetrator Testing The Computer YEN CHIP (Add-on: Samsung) Timing Sequence for Digital STDP Synapse and LIF Neuron-Based Neuromorphic System, LUT Based Synapse WT update in STDP Neuromorphic Systems

Under Pharmaceutical Law (/Medi-crime Law / 'Counter-feit' Medi-Products), Bio-Medicine Law and International Criminal Law

EXAMINATION OF COMPUTER YEN

7. LAW EVIDENCE EXAMINATION SECTION: INTERNATIONAL COMPUTER MONEY-'YEN' (FALSE VERSION) AND SYNAPSE-'YEN' (CRIMINALLY ACCURATE VERSION)

International Computer (NOT MONEY) Japanese WON Model: Computer Bank of Japan (Criminal Technical Analysis)

7.0 COMPUTER MONEY 'YEN' Model: PROGRAMMABLE E-WALLET E-YEN (NOT MONEY): COMPUTER BANK OF JAPAN (FALSE VERSION)

7.0 Programmable E-Wallet (NOT MONEY) Computer 'Yen': Computer Bank of Japan (PLUS 3 PLOT)

7.0.1. 1. Computer Bank of Japan: Definition of Token-Based and A/c-Based

7.0.2. 2. Proof of PERP-Tom Concept Phase 1: CO-VAX CHIP Computer Tier 1 Ledger Design Options

7.0.3. 3. Proof of PERP-Tom Concept Phase 2: E-Wallet APP Experimental Environment Diagram

7.0.1. Amamiya Masayoshi (2020) Central Bank Digital Currency and the Future of Payment and Settlement Systems: Remarks @ the Future of Payments Forum. (Computer) Bank of Japan (Deputy Gov). Available: https://www.boj.or.jp/en/about/press/koen_2020/data/ko200306a.pdf

7.0.2. (PERP-Tom Computer Infiltration / Invasion of) Bank of Japan (2022) Central Bank Digital Currency Experiments: Results and Findings From 'Proof of Concept Phase 1'. Payment and Settlement Systems Department. Available: <https://www.boj.or.jp/en/paym/digital/rel220526a.pdf>

7.0.3. (PERP-Tom Computer Infiltration / Invasion of) Bank of Japan (2023) Central Bank Digital Currency Experiments: Results and Findings From 'Proof of Concept Phase 2'. Payment and Settlement Systems Department. Available: <https://www.boj.or.jp/en/paym/digital/dig230529a.pdf>

7.1 COMPUTER PROGRAMMABLE (WIFI) SYNAPSE-YEN (CRIMINALLY ACCURATE VERSION)

7.1 Programmable Synapse-YEN Model: Organ Stack of Japan (Criminal Technical Analysis)

7.1. NEUROMOPRHIC PRODUCT TYPE: IBM

UNDER DATA PROTECTION LAW

IBM MODEL: NEUROMORPHIC SYSTEM (METAL-OXIDE SEMICONDUCTOR FIELD EFFECT TRANSISTOR (MOSFET))

IBM PATENT

7.1.1. IBM Model: Computing Post-Synaptic Neuron Fires to Neuromorphic Cores (Kohji Hosokawa, Sangbum Kim)

7.1.2. IBM Model: On-Chip Pisson Spike Generation (Kohji Hosokawa)

7.1.3. IBM Model: Pulse Generator with Switched Capacitors (Kohji Hosokawa)

7.1.4. IBM Model: Digital Synapse and LIF Neuron Based Neuromorphic System (Kohji Hosokawa)

7.1.5A. IBM Model: Neuromorphic Chip of Updating Precise Synaptic Weight Values (Kohji Hosokawa)

7.1.5B. IBM Model: Scalable Refresh For Asymmetric Non-Volatile Memory-Based Neuromorphic Circuits

7.1.5C. IBM Model: Weight Shifting For Neuromorphic Synapse Array (Takeo Yasuda, Junka Okazawa, Kohji Hosoksawa)

IBM PATENT

7.1.6A. IBM Model: Memory Cell Structure (Kohji Hosokawa)

7.1.6B. IBM Model: Memory Cell Driver (Kohji Hosokawa)

7.1.6C. IBM Model: Methods And Systems Of Neuron Leaky Integrate and Fire Circuits (Takeo Yasuda)

7.1.6D. IBM Model: Current Mirror Scheme For An Integrating Neuron Circuits (Takeo Yasuda)

SAMSUNG MODEL (TEXAS): NEUROMORPHIC SYSTEM (IBM JAPANESE & KOREAN)

7.3.1. Samsung Model 1: Timing Sequence For Digital STDP Synapse and LIF Neuron-Based Neuromorphic System (Kohji Hosokawa, Takeo Yasuda)

7.3.2. Samsung Model 2: LUT Based Synapse Weight Update Scheme in STDP Neuromorphic Systems (Kohji Hosokawa, Takeo Yasuda)

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7.4. EEG SENSOR PRODUCTS TYPE

Mitsubishi-Electric Model:
X-Box (Microsoft)-Sony

IBM PATENT

7.1.2. IBM Patent: Junka Okazawa, Masatoshi Ishii, Atsuya Okazaki, Kohji Hosokawa. (2020) *On-Chip Pisson Spike Generation*. United States Patent Office. ('Google Patent') Patent No. US 2020/0074272 Available: <https://patents.google.com/patent/US11270191B2/en?q=US11270191B2>

7.1.3. IBM Patent: Kohji Hosokawa (Ohtsu-shi, JP), Masatoshi Ishii (Ohmihachiman-shi JP), Mark B. Ritter (Sherman, CT) and Takeo Yasuda (Nara-shi, JP) (2017) *Pulse Generator With Switched Capacitors*. United States Patent Office. ('Google Patent') Patent No. US 2017/0047914 A1. Available: <https://patents.google.com/patent/US20170047914A1/en?inventor=Kohji+Hosokawa&page=1>

7.1.4. IBM Patent: Takeo Yasuda, Kohji Hosokawa, Yutaka Nakamura, Junka Okazawa and Masatoshi Ishii. (2020) *Digital STDP Synapse And LIF Neuron-Based Neuromorphic System*. United States Patent Office. Patent No. US 10,762,419 B2. Available: <https://patents.google.com/patent/US10762419B2/en?q=US10762419B2>

7.1.5A. IBM Patent: Atsuya Okazaki, Masatoshi Ishii, Junka Okazawa, Kohji Hosokawa, Takayuki Osogami. (2023) *Neuromorphic Chip of Updating Precise Synaptic Weight Values*. United States Patent Office. Patent No. US 2023/0385619 A1. Available: <https://patents.google.com/patent/US20230385619A1/en?q=US20230385619A1>

7.1.5C. IBM Patent: Takeo Yasuda (Nara JP), Junka Okazawa (Yamashina-ku, JP) and Kohji Hosokawa (Ohtsu, JP). (2021) *Weight Shifting For Neuromorphic Synapse Array*. United States Patent Office. ('Google Patent') Patent No. US 2021/11,188,815 B2. Available: <https://patents.google.com/patent/US11188815B2/en?q=US+2021+11%2c188%2c815+B2>

7.1.6A. IBM Patent: Kohji Hosokawa, Masatoshi Ishii and Takeo Yasuda. (2019) *Memory Cell Structure*. United States Patent Office. Patent No. US 10,446,231 B2. Available: <https://patents.google.com/patent/US10446231B2/en?q=US10446231B2>

7.1.6B. IBM Patent: Takeo Yasuda and Masatoshi Ishii. (2022) *Synapse Memory Cell Driver*. United States Patent Office. Patent No. US 11,321,608 B2. Available: <https://patents.google.com/patent/US11321608B2/en?q=US+11%2c321%2c608+B2>

7.1.6C. IBM Patent: Mark B. Ritter and Takeo Yasuda. (2022) *Methods and Systems of Neuron Leaky Integrate and Fire Circuits*. United States Patent Office. Patent No. US 11,308,390 B2. Available: <https://patents.google.com/patent/US11308390B2/en?q=US+11%2c308%2c390+B2>

IBM JOURNAL

7.2.1. Kohji Hosokawa and others. *Circuit Techniques for Efficient Acceleration of Deep Neural Network Inference with Analog-AI (Invited)*. In: 2021 IEEE International Symposium on Circuits and Systems (ISCAS), Daegu, Korea, 2021. New York City: IEEE

7.2.2. Uicheol Shin, Masatoshi Ishii, Atsuya Okazaki, Megumi Ito, Malte J. Rasch, Wanki Kim, Akiyo Nomura, Wonseok Choi, Dooyong Koh, Kohji Hosokawa, Matthew Brightsky, Seiji Munetoh and SangBum Kim. (2022) *Pattern Training, Inference and Regeneration Demonstration Using On-Chip Trainable Neuromorphic Chips for Spiking Restricted Boltzmann Machine*. *Advanced Intelligent Systems*. Vol. (No.).

Harvard Reference: CONFERENCE

7.2.3. Kohji Hosokawa and others. *Neuromorphic Devices And Architectures For Next-Generation Cognitive Computing*. Baltimore, MD, U.S.A., 2017. New York City: IEEE International Symposium on Circuits and Systems (ISCAS).

Harvard Reference: CONFERENCE

7.2.4. Atsuya Okazaki, Kohji Hosokawa, Akiyo Nomura, Takeo Yasuda, Masatoshi Ishii and others. (2018) Fully on-Chip MAC at 14 nm Enabled By Accurate Row-Wise Programming Of PCM-Based Weights and Parallel Vector-Transport In Duration-Format. In: *IEEE 2021 Symposium on VLSI Technology*, Kyoto, Japan. New York City: IEEE.

7.3.1. Samsung (IBM) Model 1: Kohji Hosokawa (Shiga-Ken JP), Masatoshi Ishii (Shiga-ken JP), Yutaka Nakamura (Kyoto, JP), Junka Okazawa (Kyoto JP) and Takeo Yasuda (Nara-ken JP) (2017) Timing Sequence For Digital STDP Synapse and LIF Neuron-Based Neuromorphic System. United States Patent Office. ('Google Patent') Patent No. US 2017/0344885 A1. Available: <https://patents.google.com/patent/US20170344885A1/en?q=US+2017%2f0344885+A1>

7.3.2. Samsung (IBM) Model 2: Kohji Hosokawa (Shiga-Ken JP), Masatoshi Ishii (Shiga-ken JP), Yutaka Nakamura (Kyoto, JP), Junka Okazawa (Kyoto JP) and Takeo Yasuda (Nara-ken JP) (2021) LUT Based Synapse WT Update Scheme in STDP Neuromorphic System. United States Patent Office. ('Google Patent') Patent No. US 10,891,543 B2. Available: <https://patents.google.com/patent/US10891543B2/en?q=US+10%2c891%2c543+B2>

7.1. NEUROMOPRHIC PRODUCT TYPE

IBM JOURNAL

7.2.1. IBM Journal: Circuit Techniques For Efficient Acceleration of Deep Neural Network Inference with Analog-AI (Kohji Hosokawa)

7.2.2. IBM Journal: Pattern Training, Inference and Regeneration Demonstration Using On-Chip Trainable Neuromorphic Chips For Spiking Restricted Boltzman Machine

7.2.3. IBM Journal: Neuromorphic Devices and Architectures For Nex-gen Cognitive Computing

7.2.4. IBM Journal: Fully On-Chip MAC at 14 nm Enabled by Accurate Row-Wise Programming Of PCM-Based Weights And Parallel Vector-Transport in Duration-Format

7.2.5. IBM Journal: Analysis of Effect of Weight Variation on SNN Chip With PCM Refresh Method

7.2.6. IBM Journal: NVM Weight Variation Impact on Analog Spiking Neural Network Chip

7.2.7. IBM Journal: Lightweight Refresh Method For PCM-Based Neuromorphic Circuits

7.2.1. Kohji Hosokawa and others. Circuit Techniques for Efficient Acceleration of Deep Neural Network Inference with Analog-AI (Invited). In: 2021 IEEE International Symposium on Circuits and Systems (ISCAS), Daegu, Korea, 2021. New York City: IEEE

7.2.2. Uicheol Shin, Masatoshi Ishii, Atsuya Okazaki, Megumi Ito, Malte J. Rasch, Wanki Kim, Akiyo Nomura, Wonseok Choi, Dooyong Koh, Kohji Hosokawa, Matthew Brightsky, Seiji Munetoh and SangBum Kim. (2022) *Pattern Training, Inference and Regeneration Demonstration Using On-Chip Trainable Neuromorphic Chips for Spiking Restricted Boltzmann Machine*. Advanced Intelligent Systems. Vol. (No.).

Harvard Reference: CONFERENCE

7.2.3. Kohji Hosokawa and others. *Neuromorphic Devices And Architectures For Next-Generation Cognitive Computing*. Baltimore, MD, U.S.A., 2017. New York City: IEEE International Symposium on Circuits and Systems (ISCAS).

Harvard Reference: CONFERENCE

7.2.4. Atsuya Okazaki, Kohji Hosokawa, Akiyo Nomura, Takeo Yasuda, Masatoshi Ishii and others. (2018) Full on-Chip MAC at 14 nm Enabled By Accurate Row-Wise Programming Of PCM-Based Weights and Parallel Vector-Transport In Duration-Format. In: *IEEE 2021 Symposium on VLSI Technology*, Kyoto, Japan. New York City: IEEE.

7.4. PM Japan Dead OR 'Dead'

7.4. (2022) Former Japan PM Abe Dies After Being Shot During Election speech. Kyodo News. 9 July. Available: <https://english.kyodonews.net/news/2022/07/a0285cdcc6d2-breaking-news-ex-pm-abe-attacked-by-unidentified-man-on-road-in-japan.html>

EXAMINATION OF COMPUTER YEN

7. LAW EVIDENCE EXAMINATION SECTION: INTERNATIONAL COMPUTER MONEY-'YEN' (FALSE VERSION) AND SYNAPSE-'YEN' (CRIMINALLY ACCURATE VERSION)

International Computer (NOT MONEY) Japanese WON Model: Computer Bank of Japan (Criminal Technical Analysis)

7.0 COMPUTER MONEY 'YEN' Model: PROGRAMMABLE E-WALLET E-YEN (NOT MONEY): COMPUTER BANK OF JAPAN (FALSE VERSION)

7.0 Programmable E-Wallet (NOT MONEY) SCAM Computer 'Yen': Computer Bank of Japan (PLUS 3 PLOT)

COMPUTER BANK OF JAPAN

Despite the unaccounted for KING-PIN PERP-ID (unknown) pushing the concept of a 'Future of Payments' in electronic format that serves to enslave 100PLUS, the definitions to distinguish token-based and a/c-based transactions constituting the 2-Tier Architecture (FALSE VERSION since the criminally accurate version refers to RFID microchip) are well defined (prior to CO-VAX microchip in FEB 2020) by Amamiya Masayoshi (Deputy Governor of the Bank of Japan) @ Remarks at the Future of Payments Forum: "Central Bank Digital Currency and the Future of Payment and Settlement Systems"²¹.

1. Token-based transactions refer to value locally stored in some kind of media. He cite examples of transportation companies' issuance of cash card of electronic value (computerized digits).
2. Account-based transactions refer to issuer debits end user (Payer's) a/c and credits recipient (Payee's) a/c i.e. receive value transfer instruction from payer. For example, (I inserted in brackets the entire illegal district of bank-in zone) of bank deposits (of entire nations' loot: all industries).

These are direct quotes. I substituted the word 'money' with the accurate word 'transactions'. Electronic money is NOT legal and not legal money. It is computerized digits. For examples, electronics digits are subject to all electronic counters' in trading platform (PRESS: 000,000,000. UP/DOWN) / bank counters (containers of all nations' loot) / supermarkets (food) manipulation etc. Thus, it can never be considered legal or legal money.

Also, he adds that nonbank payment service providers (NBPSPs) are responsible for (in fact, in legal opinion, guilty of propagating) cashless transactions in Japan (with a sinister agenda proven with CO-VAX microchip RFID wifi or wireless NFC transactional murder) I will add obvious examples: the 'pay-gang'. To complement this sentiment, the Japanese governor used the words "typically named 'XYZ Pay' as confirmation. He also added: retailers (satellite log-on electronic cashier counters: is explained in EMV and

²¹ Amamiya Masayoshi (2020) Central Bank Digital Currency and the Future of Payment and Settlement Systems: Remarks @ the Future of Payments Forum. (Computer) Bank of Japan (Deputy Gov). Available: https://www.boj.or.jp/en/about/press/koen_2020/data/ko200306a.pdf

% groceries theft etc) and transport companies as leading parties of such, for example, by the reduction of cash acceptance. In other words, the retailers' motive behind this can be legally examined in another paper. The criminal motive behind transport: clearly explained under space law sections the e-vessels of crafts (military, commercial) log-on, intent include trafficking, gateway invasion at checkpoints for transportation of unwanted criminals' infiltration to commit against nations for King Pin PERP-tom.

Incorporating the Japan governor's insight on Japan's banking (Nordic states / Asian states), I'll explain the current global banking situation: The original basic two-tier monetary system that was unchanged refers to Tier 1 exclusively supplying cash (Printed Paper) and Tier 2 private banks provide deposits with credit creation (based on Tier 1 money). What happens now is that under the 2-tier system, distribution of financial system has been infiltrated by NBSPs such as Fin(-ger)-Tech (with e.g. RESET / GLOBAL TIME STEP / SET / PHASED / PROGRAMMATIC) in token-based and account-based claiming equivalent conversion of cash Tier 1 or bank deposits Tier 2 calling (/ or self-titled as, with keyword) 'innovation' (which is fraudulent and deceptive). One main reason is to introduce microchipping: genocide / systematic crime / war crime. The second reason is for PERP e.g. tech-products seller that amassed million to billion amount of sales that had no reason to place their money in either Tier 1 or Tier 2 thus creating new electronic banks with other criminals (e.g. war crime) in foundations stash.

He also highlighted that, the preference for cash remains 'surprisingly' strong for Japan. In other words, the conclusion is Japan is NOT in favor of 'computerized digits' as a store of value as it is NOT money. Cash or physical paper notes are preferable. This is the preferred temporary arrangement for any intelligent society including: Russia, England and in Singapore, me. The ultimate and permanent solution @ WLC is to upload mission strategies in conjunction with excellent electronic brands devices: eradicate the electronic WB ADB all-PERP-B-containers of nations' loot: USMCA PLOT / Nordic-Eur-Swiss PLOT / SG PLUS 3 PLOT eradicated against the (binary-) killer- PERP), compute loot (/ stash amount / land ETERNAL worth) so murder status PERP building containers of loot / districts over a time period etc.

In other words, the standard paid governor's script to suggest that cashless will not be hampered (for the senseless cashless microchip PERP-tom against 'the people' will be crushed completely (/ wiped-out).

CBDC EXPERIMENTS: PROOF OF CONCEPT PHASE 1

The (Computer) Bank of Japan, Payment and Settlement Systems Department published the "Proof of Concept Phase 1"²² (May 2022):

²² (PERP-Tom Computer Infiltration / Invasion of) Bank of Japan (2022) Central Bank Digital Currency Experiments: Results and Findings From 'Proof of Concept Phase 1'. Payment and Settlement Systems Department. Available: <https://www.boj.or.jp/en/paym/digital/rel220526a.pdf>

Figure 1: CBDC ledger design alternatives

Note 1: ①: Issuance; ②: Payout; ③,⑤: Transfer within a single intermediary institution; ④: Transfer across intermediaries; ⑥: Acceptance; ⑦: Redemption.
 Note 2: In Design 2, payouts (②), transfers across intermediaries (④), and acceptance (⑥) simultaneously increase and decrease account balances on the central bank's ledger and on intermediaries' ledgers. Movements of transfers within a single intermediary institution (③,⑤) are not reflected in the central bank's ledger.

In the (Computer) Bank of Japan's ledger design alternatives: Under Design 1 the computer central bank records (electronic computerized digits) balances of all intermediaries and end-user a/cs. Under Design 2, the computer central bank records the account balances of intermediaries (own a/cs, user a/cs) and intermediaries each record a/c bal. of customer users. Under Design 3, a unique IDs (which has already happened with CO-VAX CHIP RFID) to monetary data (in-brain) representing a fixed value (Microsoft WO060606 E-reward system) and the computer bank computerized digits 'CBDC' holding status indicated by linking those (CHIP of monetary data) IDs to (RFID CHIPPED) user IDs named "token-based CBDC ledger system".

FIG. 2 (CO-VAX CHIP E-WALLET APP) EXPERIMENTAL ENVIRONMENT: APP SERVER DB SERVER BY PERP-TOM

Figure 2: Overview of the experimental environment

In other words, the entire computer bank of nations' (ALL CBDC propagator) are reduced to a set of (criminal against 'the people') apparatus: (1) computer chip (of existing of illegal bank-in infrastructure) by PERP-tom (2) Frequency bandwidth: wifi, NFC (wireless) etc (3) HTTP server (APP server) (4) cellphone in-brain CO-VAX CHIP wallet application (APP) (5) database server: ledger data store. Thus, PERP-tom figures entire nations' loot is accessible from any consite wirelessly.

Appendix figure 2-1: Experimental environment diagram

CBDC EXPERIMENTS: PROOF OF CONCEPT PHASE 2

The (Computer) Bank of Japan, Payment and Settlement Systems Department published the “Proof of Concept Phase 2”²³ (May 2023):

Continuing the discussion which the Bank of Japan governor highlighted as one of 2 key proponents of Token-based transactions and the suspicious motivations behind propagating thus worth examining (in separate detailed paper), here is a PoS in-store diagram.

²³ (PERP-Tom Computer Infiltration / Invasion of) Computer Bank of Japan (2023) Central Bank Digital Currency Experiments: Results and Findings From ‘Proof of Concept Phase 2’. Payment and Settlement Systems Department. Available: <https://www.boj.or.jp/en/paym/digital/dig230529a.pdf>

Figure 9: Example of connection with POS system for in-store settlement

JUDGMENT

If PERP-Tom infiltration / invasion of Computer Bank of X nation is possible (which is his blatant intent here in accordance with Bank of Japan governor’s statement on 2-Tier architecture remaining the same except the ‘innovation’ invasion infiltration attempt to be legitimate accepted by illegal Tier 1 Tier 2 component of financial resources distribution), retailers can Either twitch their electronic cashier or PERP-Tom can whilst Tier 2 PERPs steal a [manufactured chip card / wave card / CO-VAX CHIP in-brain) % percentage off groceries (/ OR rip-off the largest F&B etc to ride-off) @PoS transaction device, the key answer is no food need to be sold (i.e. repeat war crime of starvation) if numbers can be manipulated (or remotely accessed by PERP-Tom).

SCALABILITY

Bearing in mind these technical discussion by PERP-tom (unknown id) on how best to invade the Japanese people is without consent / full knowledge:

FIG. 2 (CO-VAX CHIP E-WALLET APP: MAY 2022 PROOF OF PERP-CONCEPT) EXPERIMENTAL ENVIRONMENT: APP SERVER DB SERVER BY PERP-TOM

Figure 2: Overview of the experimental environment

Notice the word ‘deploying’ (military term thus confirming war crime status) of ‘deploying’ multiple identical servers for the (a) APP (application) server (AP implements application logic (configured to process instructions i.e. computation logic), (continuing the 2022 discussion on reducing the computer central bank to a set of apparatus: servers being one component).

FIG. 12 shows hardware specifications of database (DB) servers (large number of records managing) using **horizontal partitioning** (to control the amount of data and access PER shard) i.e. sharding defined as one set of table data stored on a single DB server distributed (/maintained) on multiple servers on a PER-record basis.

FIG. 12 ‘SCALABILITY’ SUGGESTION BY PERP-TOM: E.G. ‘SCALABLE’ NEURAL ‘LACE’

Figure 12: Performance enhancement approaches (example of an orchestration system)

UTXO

UTXO was mentioned as one feature in the Computer ‘Bank of England’ so its worth examining here for the Computer ‘Bank of Japan’:

UTXO stands for “Unspent Transaction Output” exemplary model in FIG. 13: May 2023

Figure 13: Example of remittances using flexible-value tokens and UTXOs²²

Example of a remittance using flexible-value tokens:
A sends JPY60 to B using tokens worth JPY100

Token ID	Amount	Holder ID	Token ID	Amount	Holder ID
T001	50	A	T001	50	A
T002	50	A	T002	50	A
T006	500	B	T006	500	B
:	:	:	T008	60	B
			T009	40	A
			:	:	:

= Spent
= Remittance
= Self-directed payment

Note: TX=transaction

Example of a remittance transaction using UTXOs:
UTXOs spent as input UTXOs created as output

FLEXIBLE VALUE APPROACH (MAY 2022: PROOF OF PERP-TOM CONCEPT AGAINST JAPAN)

Appendix figure 1-2: Transferring JPY 10,000 from A to B in a flexible-value approach

Token ID	Amount (¥)	Holder ID	Holder (not recorded in ledger)
25B48BA...	40,000	88-228-504	End user A
3EF3520...	5,000	41-923-016	End user B
:	:	:	:

Token ID	Amount (¥)	Holder ID	Holder (not recorded in ledger)
25B48BA...	40,000	88-228-504	End user A
3EF3520...	5,000	41-923-016	End user B
1C30EC1...	10,000	41-923-016	End user B
E72974F...	30,000	88-228-504	End user A
:	:	:	:

The key points under the pre-meditated flexible-value approach:

1. End user does not hold a set of tokens (stored value) that matches transfer amount. High-value tokens are split into low-value tokens which are deleted before the split. After the split, tokens value awaiting transfer are linked to recipient (remainder tokens are linked to remitter). (I think the split here refers to a computer function.)
2. As no exchange process was involved, short processing times and periodic merging (computer function: in-brain) tokens i.e. concentrating sets of low-value tokens into a high-value token, the database size is compressed.

FIXED VALUE APPROACH (MAY 2022: PROOF OF PERP-TOM CONCEPT AGAINST JAPAN)

Appendix figure 1-1: Transferring JPY 10,000 from A to B in a fixed-value approach

Token ID	Amount (¥)	Holder ID	Holder (not recorded in ledger)
25B48BA...	40,000	88-228-504	End user A
3EF3520...	5,000	41-923-016	End user B
2530CCA...	10,000	21-291-996	Intermediary X
1BC41E5...	30,000	21-291-996	Intermediary X
:	:	:	:

Token ID	Amount (¥)	Holder ID	Holder (not recorded in ledger)
25B48BA...	40,000	88-228-504 ⇒ 21-291-996	End user A ⇒ Intermediary X
3EF3520...	5,000	41-923-016	End user B
2530CCA...	10,000	21-291-996 ⇒ 88-228-504	Intermediary X ⇒ End user A
1BC41E5...	30,000	21-291-996 ⇒ 88-228-504	Intermediary X ⇒ End user A
:	:	:	:

Token ID	Amount (¥)	Holder ID	Holder (not recorded in ledger)
25B48BA...	40,000	21-291-996	Intermediary X
3EF3520...	5,000	41-923-016	End user B
2530CCA...	10,000	88-228-504 ⇒ 41-923-016	End user A ⇒ End user B
1BC41E5...	30,000	88-228-504	End user A
:	:	:	:

The key points under the pre-meditated FIXED-value approach:

1. End user does not hold a set of tokens (stored value) that matches transfer amount, intermediary (unknown XYZ: require DIY computers set) performs an exchange so end-user obtain smaller-denominated tokens, then transferred.
2. There might be an option available for getting 'change' from the recipient but then recipient would need to have a set of tokens (electronic store of value in media) with a value that matches the electronic-'change' amount.

3. Also, for offline settlements, end-users endpoint devices pair(ed) to transfer CBDC directly with information stored on devices (/OR CO-VAX CHIP in-brain). Furthermore, mention of 'electronic signature' can refer to the organ analysis discussed extensively across a range of EMV IBM etc products as a. verification and b. effective confirmation of authenticity of tokens (electronic store of value in-brain media).
4. Explanation: electronic tokens used in the process with a fixed value (NOT split or merged) each carry the electronic signature (of a CO-VAX CHIP in-brain end user) that the 'Computer Central Bank' would apply to each token upon issuance (of 'electronic cash' function as the 'unchanged' role of 2-Tier Architecture, as PERP-Tom Computer Tier 1.)

JUDGEMENT

In conjunction with the criminal variants of 'computer central banks discussed in Section 11', it is clear that (King-Pin binary = barcode = Bar-Bi-Lun)-PERP-Tom has plotted robbing ALL CENTRAL BANKS Tier 1, and Tier 2 (illegal containers of nations' loot) and replacing both with computerized digits (reduced to a set of computers and apparatus in conjunction with CO-VAX micro-CHIP nations: to commit CHIP-genocide / systematic crime / war crime) linked Neural Network / Neuromorphic System / Neurogrid 100PLUS.

There should be a vote and call for evidence contributors of PERP-ID @ WLC.

7.1 LAW EVIDENCE EXAMINATION: COMPUTER (WI-FI) PROGRAMMABLE SYNAPSE-YEN (CRIMINALLY ACCURATE VERSION)

7.1 Programmable Synapse-YEN Model: Organ Stack of Japan (Criminal Technical Analysis)

7.1. NEUROMOPRHIC PRODUCT TYPE: IBM

IBM MODEL: NEUROMORPHIC SYSTEM (METAL-OXIDE SEMICONDUCTOR FIELD EFFECT TRANSISTOR (MOSFET))

IBM PATENT

UNDER DATA PROTECTION LAW

7.1.2. IBM PATENT: ON-CHIP PISSON SPIKE GENERATION (US 2020/0074272 A1) (JUNKA OKAZAWA, MASATOSHI ISHII, ATSUYA OKAZAKI, KOHJI HOSOKAWA) (SNN: SPIKING NEURAL NETWORK) (2020)

FIG. 1 FIELD PROGRAMMABLE GATE ARRAY EXT-CHIP: POISSON SPIKE GENERATOR INSIDE SNN CHIP

EXT-CHIP SPIKING NEURAL NETWORK (SNN): PSG

In the IBM (Tokyo-Based) Patent, “On-Chip Pisson Spike Generation”²⁴ FIG. 1 is a diagram of an **SNN** chip: a Poisson spike generator (PSG) 110 implemented on the SNN chip 100 that input/output signals to/from an SNN chip of e-RBM.

The input signal pattern is training data: one inference data transmitted from an external chip 200 to the SNN chip 100. For example, inside the SNN chip 100, each axon receives input of a **Poisson spike train** according to the input signal pattern.

²⁴ Junka Okazawa, Masatoshi Ishii, Atsuya Okazaki, Kohji Hosokawa. (2020) *On-Chip Pisson Spike Generation*. United States Patent Office. ('Google Patent') Patent No. US 2020/0074272 Available: <https://patents.google.com/patent/US11270191B2/en?q=US11270191B2>

FIG. 2 POISSON SPIKE GENERATOR (PSG): INSIDE SPIKING NEURAL NETWORK (SNN)-CHIP 100
SNN Chip-100: CONTAINS PSG-110

FIG. 2 is a Poisson Spike Generator (PSG) implemented inside the Spiking Neural Network (SNN)-Chip 100 (FIG. 1). According to clock signals' input to PSG-110, includes:

POISSON SPIKE GENERATOR-110

1. Random number generator (RNG) 101 + spiking rate register (SRR) 102 + a Comparator 103 + Enable Register 104
2. Spiking rate register (SRR) 102 stores a Comparison Value: compared to Random Number Generator (RNG) 101 (random numbers generated).

COMPARATOR-103

3. Comparator 103: The **comparison value** determines the **probability** of a spike occurring in a Poisson spike train that
 - (a) compares each random number generated by random number generator (RNG) 101 with the
 - (b) **comparison value** read from the spiking rate register 102. Based on the comparison result, the comparator 103
 - (c) emits a **spike** according to a **setting** of the **enable register 104**.

ENABLE REGISTER-104

4. Enable register 104: Poisson Spike Generator (PSG) 110 is set to ON, the Poisson Spike Generator (PSG) 110 emits a spike train, which follows the Poisson distribution, based on operations of the Random Number Generator (RNG) 101 operations + Spiking Rate Register (SRR) 102 + Comparator 103.

INPUT SIGNAL PATTERN TRANSMITTED TO SNN-CHIP

This spike train is supplied to the axon corresponding to PSG 110. To enable register 104, the input signal pattern is transmitted to the SNN Chip-100.

FIG. 3: SNN CHIP-100 = PSG-110 + AXON-105 + SNN CIRCUIT-106

FIG. 2: PSG 110

FIG. 3 shows Poisson Spike Generator (PSG)-110 that improves area-efficiency of the SNN Chip-100 (SNN Circuit-106) as compared to PSG 110 in FIG. 2.

SNN Chip-100 shown in FIG. 3:

- (i) Plural axons 105 is provided for SNN Circuit-106.
- (ii) 1-Poisson Spike Generator (PSG)-110 is provided for each Axon-105.

PSUEDO-RANDOM BIT (BINARY) STREAM 109 (SEQUENCE)

Diagram shows random bit stream 109 supplied to PSGs 110 on SNN chip 100 one after another in a bucket brigade matter.

**FIG. 5 R/S BET. SHIFT CLOCK-107: (FREQUENCY / 'CLOCK' SIGNAL) AND EXTERNAL TRIGGER-108:
 1. RANDOM POISSON SPIKE TRAIN **RANDOM BIT STREAM-109:**
 2. **OUTPUT SPIKES-115 + POISSON SPIKE GENERATOR 110****

**PROBABILITY OF SPIKE 115 OCCURRING IN EXT-TRIGGER 108:
 RANDOM POISSON SPIKE TRAIN**

FIG. 5, the shift clock 107 is a clock signal. Frequency of the shift clock 107 is not limited to a particular frequency. The external trigger 108 is a **random Poisson spike train** including spikes occurring with a **probability (of a spike occurring in the external trigger 108:**

OUTPUT SPIKE 115 = POISSON SPIKE TRAIN

is determined based on the r/s with the **probability of the output spike 115** occurring in the external trigger 108, is determined based on the r/s with the **probability of the output spike 115** occurring and the **random bit stream 109**: random binary signal whose value becomes High (value "1") with a certain probability.

The probability of the value of the **random bit stream 109** becoming **High** is determined based on the r/s with the **probability of an output spike 115** occurring and the **external trigger 108**.

DELAY OF 1 SHIFT-CLOCK-107

Comparing **random bit stream 109** fed to the Poisson Spike Generator (PSG)-110 corresponding to the i -th axon 105 and the **random bit stream 109** fed to the PSG-110 corresponding to the $(i+1)$ -th AXON 105, the latter is shifted (delayed) from the former by one clock of the shift clock 107.

FIG. 4 POISSON SPIKE GENERATOR (PSG)-110: CONTAINS [AND] CIRCUIT-112 + SHIFT REGISTER-111

Output spikes 115 from the Poisson Spike Generator (PSG) 110 corresponds to an AND of the random bit stream 109 and the external trigger 108.

**EXPLANATORY LEGAL NOTE. & LAW EVIDENCE:
NEURAL MICROCIRCUIT SIMULATION ANALYSIS TOOLKIT (NMSAT)
(so-called 'BLUE' and 'RED' PILL DECODED) [GRAPHICAL FORMAT]**

In the explanatory note, “Single Neuron with Patterned Synaptic Input”²⁵ shows a set of input signals composed of 2 independent noise channels that act as excitatory (BLUE) and inhibitory (RED) input, modeled as Ornstein-Uhlenbeck (COPIED: Ancient Replica) processes.

Each signals drives one inhomogeneous Poisson generator in Encoding layer: at given intervals. These input signals are sampled and values used to set / update spike trains passed to 2 encoders: which consists of a number of parrot neurons which means only forward incoming spikes to the population (France / U.S.A.) that they are connected to.

JUDGEMENT

To run this example, (SAMPLE of) execute:

```
python main.py -f ./projects/examples/parameters/single_neuron_patterned_synaptic
```

After running this example, main output: histogram of inter-spike intervals (ISI), firing rate, coefficient of variation (CV_ISI), Fano Factor, Time course of synaptic current (I_{syn}) and membrane potential (V_m).

JUDGEMENT (CONTINUED): LAW EVIDENCE

Population *Aei fCondExp* - Single Neuron Activity [0.0, 1000.0]

Population (e.g. A-Z) (signal programmable hypothetical / OR committed frequency attack):

Time course of synaptic current (I_{syn}):

Membrane potential (V_m):

²⁵ Martin Donath (2017) Single Neuron With Patterned Synaptic Input. Neural Microcircuit Simulation and Analysis Toolkit (NMSAT). Available: <https://rcfduarte.github.io/nmsat/single-neuron-with-patterned-synaptic-input/>

7.1 LAW EVIDENCE EXAMINATION: COMPUTER (WI-FI) PROGRAMMABLE SYNAPSE-YEN (CRIMINALLY ACCURATE VERSION)

7.1 Programmable Synapse-YEN Model: Organ Stack of Japan (Criminal Technical Analysis)

7.1. NEUROMOPRHIC PRODUCT TYPE: IBM

IBM MODEL: NEUROMORPHIC SYSTEM (METAL-OXIDE SEMICONDUCTOR FIELD EFFECT TRANSISTOR (MOSFET))

IBM PATENT

UNDER DATA PROTECTION LAW

7.1.3. IBM PATENT: PULSE GENERATOR WITH SWITCHED CAPACITORS (US 2017/0047914 A1) (KOHJI HOSOKAWA, MASATOSHI ISHII, MARK B. RITTER, TAKEO YASUDA)

PULSE GENERATOR-600 (REQUIRES 2-SWITCHES 410, 420)

FIG. 6

In the IBM Patent, “Pulse Generator With Switched Capacitors”²⁶, in FIG. 6 is a **pulse generator 600** implemented with **transistors**.

The (i) **switch S1 410** is implemented with **transfer gate TG1 610** and **inverter I1 615**.

The (ii) **switch S2 420** is implemented with **transfer gate TG2 620** and **inverter I2 625**.

The **capacitor C1 210** (specifically upper node indicated by int_cap) is isolated from or connected to **node Vi 110** and **node V0 140** with switches (i) switch S1 410 and (ii) switch S2 420.

The node **Vi (VM) 110** is set to voltage potential: VM.

Output node V0 140 is connected to **nodes Vih (VH) 630** and **Vil (VL) 640** through: **metal-oxide-semiconductor field effect transistors (MOSFETs) M1 650** and **M2 660**: are initialization portion of the **pulse generator 600**.

FIG. 7 shows a **timing diagram** associated with **pulse generator 600** FIG. 6. The voltage at **node Vi 110** kept constant at VM.

²⁶ Kohji Hosokawa (Ohtsu-shi, JP), Masatoshi Ishii (Ohmihachiman-shi JP), Mark B. Ritter (Sherman, CT) and Takeo Yasuda (Narashi, JP) (2017) Pulse Generator With Switched Capacitors. United States Patent Office. ('Google Patent') Patent No. US 2017/0047914 A1. Available: <https://patents.google.com/patent/US20170047914A1/en?inventor=Kohji+Hosokawa&page=1>

FIG. 7 TIMING DIAGRAM ASSOCIATED WITH PULSE GENERATOR-600

FIG. 7

SIGNAL 655: hp_trg_b 655 / **Thp_fall 730** (High pulse fall time)

SIGNAL 665: lp_trg_b 665 / **Tlp_rise 740** (Low pulse rise time)

(1) Based on (b) the trigger 710 from (c) signal hp_trg_b 655 associated with MOSFET M1 650, the voltage at the output node V0 140 is initially set to VH.

(2) Then, based on (b) the trigger 720 from (c) signal lp_trg 665 associated with MOSFET M2 660, the voltage at output node V0 140 is set to VL.

FIG. 6

HIGH PULSE FALL TIME T_{hp_fall} 730

According to switches (FIN-TECH-FALSE) (i) S1 410 and (ii) S2 420, turning on off alternately in opposite phase (WB-FALSE) over the (a) high pulse fall time T_{hp_fall} 730 (High pulse fall time), based on switch signals ϕ_1 415 and ϕ_2 425 (one switch is on while the other is off), the voltage potential of (output) node V0 140 approaches that of (input) node Vi 110 (VM) gradually.

LOW PULSE RISE TIME T_{lp_rise} 740

According to switches (i) S1 410 and (ii) S2 420, which turn on and off in opposite phase over the (a) low pulse rise time T_{lp_rise} 740, the voltage at the output node V0 140 approaches VM.

PULSE SHAPES

This fall and rise of the voltage at the output node V0 140 over T_{hp_fall} 730 and T_{lp_rise} 740 represent pulse shapes achieved with switches (i) S1 410 and (ii) S2 420.

PULSE SHAPES FIG. 12 – DIFFERS PERIOD 1 TO PERIOD 2 / PULSE WAVEFORM FIG. 13, FIG. 16

FIG. 12

FIG. 13

FIG. 16

FIG. 12 shows pulse shapes / values of voltages e.g. VH, VM, VL in FIG. 7 that differs from one pulse to the next.

FIG.12 pulse period 1, the pulse shape has a **high pulse rise time Thp_rise 750** from VL1 to VM1 and, in pulse period 2, the pulse shape has a **low pulse fall time Tip_fall 760** from VH2 to VM2. (The values of VH, VM, VL in FIG. 6 are modified depending on time phase.)

FIG. 13 and 16 shows pulse shape (PULSE WAVEFORM) with **high pulse fall Thp_fall 730** from VH, VM and **low pulse rise time Tip_rise 740** from VL to VM.

FIG. 16 depicts: rise time **Tip_rise 740** is longer than the fall time **Thp_fall 730** (pulse period 2 is longer than pulse period 1).

FIG. 6 SIZE RATIO OF 2 CAPACITANCES C1/C2 LARGER - PULSE PERIOD 1, SMALLER - PULSE PERIOD 2

The difference in the high pulse **fall time** Thp_fall 730 and the low pulse **rise time** Tip_rise 740 is the result of changing the **size ratio** of the two capacitances C1/C2 to be larger at pulse period 1 and smaller at pulse period 2.

FIG. 6 CAPACITANCE RATIO CHANGING

FIG. 6

Another parameter used to modify the **rise time or fall time** of a pulse (voltage pulse at the **node V0 140**) is **capacitance ratio** of C 1 and C 2.

For example, as C2/C1 increases,

- (i) time constant (RscC2) increases
- (ii) (pulse is slower).

A smaller C1/C2 (C 1 is smaller or C 2 is larger) results in a larger **rise or fall time** (increase in time constant).

FIG. 15 PULSE GENERATOR-1400 (TIMING DIAGRAM)

FIG. 15

FIG. 15 shows **timing diagram** associate with **pulse generator 1400** in FIG. 14, the **initialization voltage VI** (at node V init 1420) and the **saturation voltage VS** (at node V sat 1440).

7.1 LAW EVIDENCE EXAMINATION: COMPUTER (WI-FI) PROGRAMMABLE SYNAPSE-YEN (CRIMINALLY ACCURATE VERSION)

7.1 Programmable Synapse-YEN Model: Organ Stack of Japan (Criminal Technical Analysis)

7.1. NEUROMOPRHIC PRODUCT TYPE: IBM

IBM MODEL: NEUROMORPHIC SYSTEM (METAL-OXIDE SEMICONDUCTOR FIELD EFFECT TRANSISTOR (MOSFET))

IBM PATENT

UNDER DATA PROTECTION LAW

7.1.4. IBM PATENT: DIGITAL STDP SYNAPSE AND LIF NEURON-BASED NEUROMORPHIC SYSTEM (US 10,762,419 B2) (#TAKEO YASUDA, KOHJI HOSOKAWA, YUTAKA NAKAMURA, JUNKA OKAZAWA, MASATOSHI ISHII) (2020)

FIG. 6 DIGITAL NEUROMORPHIC SYSTEM (CO-VAX CHIP POP-100)

FIG. 6

In the IBM Patent, “Digital STDP Synapse and LIF Neuron-Based Neuromorphic²⁷ System” 400 implements the crossbar structure 200 for synapses weight RAM block 405 in FIG. 4.

The synapse weight RAM (i, j) represents the synapse weight of a synapse between axon i and neuron body j (or dendrite j).

²⁷ Takeo Yasuda, Kohji Hosokawa, Yutaka Nakamura, Junka Okazawa and Masatoshi Ishii. (2020) *Digital STDP Synapse And LIF Neuron-Based Neuromorphic System*. United States Patent Office. Patent No. US 10,762,419 B2. Available: <https://patents.google.com/patent/US10762419B2/en?q=US10762419B2>

The rows correspond to axons of pre-neurons and columns that correspond to dendrites of post-neurons: for example, 256 neurons x 256 neurons = 65,536 synapses.

The read access is performed to obtain current synapse weight value $sw(t)<0:7>$ obtained from read data output port $sw_read<0:7>$.

For write access, the updated synapse weight value $sw(t + 1)<0:7>$ is given to the write data input ports $sw_write<0:7>$ replacing the current value $sw(t)<0:7>$ in write access.

Timing of sequences for these operations are generated by sequencer for block control signals and address generator for synapse weight RAM block (SAG) 455. (iv) the current synapse weight values are obtained from synapse weight RAM 405 ($sw_read<0:7>$).

Data is stored in 256 axons and 256 dendrites.

The change amount is determined with (i) current (256) axon_timer values obtained from (ii) axon timing block 410 ($ax_tmr(t)<0:3>$)

(iii) current 256 dendrite timer values obtained from the dendrite timing block 415 ($dr_tmr(t)<0:3>$),

Spike timing is one parameter accounted for in STDP Model. The axon timer 410 and dendrite timer 415 determines the **elapsed time** since a spike appears in the axon and dendrite nodes of synapses.

The synapse weight update is triggered by any one of axon input spike signals $ax_in\ i$ (for $i = 0$ to 255). So, for example, if one axon input spike occurs on $ax_in\ i$, a synapse weight decrement calculation is performed for the synapse weight only in row 'i' ($sw\ i\ j$), for $j = 0$ to 255).

LEAKY-INTEGRATE-FIRE FUNCTION

In implementing the **leaky integrate and fire function**, the neuron membrane potential update block (NPU) 425 receives: (i) the current axon timer signal $ax_tmr(t)<0:3>$ from axon timer 410, (ii) the current synapse weight signal $sw(t)<0:7>$ from synapse weight RAM 405, and (iii) current neuron membrane potential signals $np(t)<0:7>$ from neuron membrane potential register block 420.

The **dendrite output register 450** converts the **serial dr_out (neuron fire)** signal to parallel signals (dor_0 to dor_{255}) to provide **parallel input** to the synapse and **core output** dr_out_j ($j = 0$ to 255). For some cases, one or some of these output signals are connected to ax_in_i ($i = 0$ to 255).

EXCITATORY NEURON: MEMBRANE POTENTIAL

In an **excitatory neuron**, the **neuron membrane potential** increases each time the neuron receives a spike e.g. **stimulus** from axons e.g. (ax_in_i) where $i = 0$ to 255 , through **connected** synapses 220 (FIG. 4).

The neurons are **stimulated** through synapses until the neuron membrane potential reaches a certain level called 'fire threshold level'. The signal $fire_th<0:7>$ gives the 'fire threshold level' of neurons from outside the system as one operation parameters.

INHIBITORY NEURON: MEMBRANE POTENTIAL

With an inhibitory neuron, the **neuron membrane potential** decreases when the neuron receives a **spike**.

NEURON MEMBRANE POTENTIAL: DIGITAL QUANTIZED VALUE

The neuron membrane potential register 420 stores the NP for each neuron and shows the status of the neuron as digital quantized value.

The neuron membrane potential register 420 data is updated with updated neuron membrane potential data (np (t+1)<0.7>) from **neuron membrane potential update block** 425. The sequence and data flow is controlled by SAG 455.

Thus, the STDP model uses spike timing information for the synapse weight update. The Spike Timing Dependent Plasticity (STDP) is a temporally asymmetric form of **Hebian learning** induced by **tight temporal correlations** between spikes of pre-and post-synaptic neurons, widely believed to be related to brain information storage and neuronal circuits (during brain development).

JUDGMENT

[This is the criminal reason behind CO-VAX chipping \(LAB VIRUS SHOTS\) babies.](#)

RESET: NEURON MEMBRANE POTENTIAL REACHES THRESHOLD

The neuron membrane potential is read out from neuron membrane potential register 420 and updated in the neuron membrane potential update block (NPU) 425. The updated value is written into NPR 420.

The amount **neuron membrane potential register (NPR) 420** updated is determined by corresponding axon timer AT 410 value and synapse weight amount.

Thus, the greater the AT value and synapse weight value, the greater the neuron membrane potential is increased. Once the neuron membrane potential reaches the threshold level, the potential is reset (or preset) to its initialization level.

The timing values obtained from AT 410 and synapse weight values for the corresponding synapses are used by neuron membrane potential update block 425, to determine the incremental change in the neuron membrane potential.

The neuron membrane potential update block 425 implements this operation while accounting for the leaky decay of the neuron membrane potential by implementing the leaky integrate and fire model (LTF) [effect is implemented inside the neuron membrane potential (NPU) after (a) the integration operation, with data concerning (b) axon timer AT values, (c) synapse weight values and current (d) neuron membrane potential values].

SEQUENCER FOR BLOCK CTRL: SYNAPSE WT RAM 405

This is likely a MAC = Media Access Controller, SAG = Sequencer Address Generator for the synapse weight RAM (SAG) 455 where the spike time data is utilized one by one sequentially instructed by sequencer for (1) block control signals and (2) address generator for synapse weight RAM (SAG) 455.

For axon timer 410 and dendrite timer 415 to determine elapsed times, data is accessed by AT access signal (at_acs) and DT access signal (dt_acs) generated by SAG 455.

ACCESS CTRL AND TRIGGER SIGNALS

The access control and trigger signals at `acs`, `at_sel<0.7>`, `sw_ram_row_adr<0.7>`, `sw_ram_col_adr<0.7>`, and `np_reg_trg` and `npu_lut_trg<1.2>` are generated by SAG 455 to supply input signals for neuron membrane potential update block 425. The neuron membrane potential update block applies the **leaky decay effect** and generates a current neuron membrane potential **value** as output signal.

LEGAL ANALYSIS

Thus, the STDP model uses spike timing information for the synapse weight update. The Spike Timing Dependent Plasticity (STDP) is a **temporally asymmetric form of Hebian learning** induced by **tight temporal correlations** between spikes of pre-and post-synaptic neurons, widely believed to be related to information brain storage and neuronal circuits (during brain development) hence one PERP criminal motive for CO-VAX PATCH babies ('children's 'health' = Bio-W)

SYNAPSE WEIGHT INCREMENT / DECREMENT BLOCK

The synapse weight increment 430 and decrement block 435 perform changes in synapse weight values. The change amount is determined with (i) current (256) axon_timer values obtained from (ii) **axon timing block 410** (`ax_tmr(t)<0.3>`) (iii) current **256 dendrite timer values** obtained from the dendrite timing block 415 (`dr_tmr(t)<0.3>`), (iv) the current synapse weight values are obtained from **synapse weight RAM 405** (`sw_read<0.7>`).

MUX (SEE: MUREX AT @ 'WORLD BANK' WB PERP – ALL-B.)

The 256 to 1 MUX 466 selects one of the dendrite timer value $dr_tmr(t) < 0.3 >$ from 256 dendrite timer values $(dr_tmr(t) < 0.3 > \times 256)$ for dendrite 0 to dendrite 255 (for neuron 0 to neuron 255). The selection changes with the $dt_sel < 0.7 >$ signals from dendrite 0 to dendrite 255 (or neuron 0 to neuron 255) for sequential process in synapse weight detriment block 435.

Spike Timing Dependent Plasticity (STDP) temporally asymmetric form of Hebbian learning induced by tight temporal correlations between spikes of pre-and post-synaptic neurons

CHIP-GENOCIDE, CHIP-WAR CRIME EM (PERSONAL USE)

DENDRITE O/P SPIKE dr_out j: SYNAPSE WEIGHT INCREMENT

Fig. 18.1 Illustration of a typical neuron action potential in relation to the equilibrium potentials of sodium and potassium.

If there's dendrite output spike only on `dr_out j`, a synapse weight increment calculation is performed for the synapse weights in column 'j' (`sw i j`, for $i = 0$ to 255). The 256 to 1 MUX 465 selects one of the axon timer value `ax_tmr(t) < 0:3 >` from 256 axon timer AT values (`ax_tmr(t) < 0:3 > x 256`) for (axon 0 to axon 255) for sequential process in synapse weight increment block 430.

The output values from synapse weight increment block 430 (sw_inc(t+1)<0:7>) and the current synapse weight decrement block 435 (sw_dec(t+1)<0:7>) triggered by signals sw_inc_trg and sw_dec_trg generated by SAG 455. The information is processed by a 2 to 1 multiplexor unit 460: select either (sw_inc(t+1)<0:7>) value or (sw_dec(t+1)<0:7>) value as updated synapse weight data sw(t+1)<0:7> to synapse write port (sw_write<0:7>) in 8 bit. Thus, updated synapse weight information is written to the SW RAM unit 405.

LOCATION INSIDE: 'SINGAPORE' (NOT SINGAPORE, PERP USE THE WORD 'SINGAPORE')

PERP WORD MUX (MUREX @ 'WORLD BANK' WB)

The word 'MUX' can be short for MUREX self-titled (ask for monies, land thieves) under international law as individuals that pocket @ 'World' Bank (WB). For example, Singapore-phoenix land robbed PERPs bank-in 1965 PLOT.

WB PERP stone building (meaning cost of stone and computers 'controller' CHIP) built near Marina Bay Sands inside location 'Singapore' as 'MUREX' 'SOUTH-EAST ASIA' (being the 'targets' by self-titled PERP). Also, so PERP MUREX 'South-East Asia' refers to the targets by PERP with weapons blueprinting in Section 9 and mapping analysis shows that PERP-building built (intentionally) near Marina Bay sands.

All B-types are illegal (unlawful worldwide): 'function' e.g. construction / agricultural / transport etc B, by nations land (country / cities' name), region (zone / 'world': 100PLUS).

CAD / RAD

The Row Address Decoder 440 and Column Address Decoder 445 decode row and column addresses of the **synapse weight RAM 405**, responsive to instructions from **sequencer unit 455** ($sw_ram_row_adr<0:7>$) and ($sw_ram_col_adr<0:7>$) used to access (read / write) the synapse weight RAM 405.

DOR (DENDRITE O/P REGISTER)

FIG. 6 **neuron fire signals** are forwarded from (i) **neuron membrane potential update block 425** and (ii) sent to **dendrite output register (DOR) 450**. The post-neuron 'fire' output signals dr_out_j ($j = 0$ to 255).

The 'neuron fire' signals of **post-neurons** are fed back to the **synapse array** in the same core and transferred to system external system output. For the system with feedback connection or multi-core system, the **connections** between (ii) dendrite output (dr_out_j) and (iii) axon input (ax_in_i) are determined by system user or designer.

SUM-UP: GENERATE NEURON ACTIVITY MODELLING

To sum up, to generate neuron activity modelling with spike time-dependent plasticity (STDP) and leaky integrate and fire (LIF) in a digital neuromorphic system as follows:

In 482, neuron activity and synapse activity are generated between neurons in a (CO-VAX CHIP) network e.g. **crossbar network 200** of axons, dendrites and synapses depicted (embodied in Random Access Memory RAM) of FIG. 4.

System input is sent to: (i) Axon Timer AT (ii) SAG block and (iii) synapse weight decrement block. Input is sent singularly to a single core network or parallel to a multi-core network.

The Axon timer is used to measure the **elapsed times**: since **axon spikes** (occur at **corresponding synapses** timed and stored.)

The dendrite timer is used to measure the **elapsed times**: since **dendrite spikes** (occur at **corresponding synapses** timed and stored.)

The **current synapse weight values** of the synapses are obtained and stored, for example, in a synapse weight memory unit, in 488.

In 492, the neuron membrane potential values are updated based on data stored namely, storing the (i) **elapsed time** since occurrence of axon spikes in block 484 / storing the (iii) **current synapse weight values** of synapses in accordance with block 488 / storing the (iv) **current neuron membrane potential** of neurons in accordance with block 490.

Update of neuron membrane potential values is determined using (v) **leaky integrate and fire model**.

In 494, the (iii) **synapse weight values** of synapses are updated based on data stored in the (i) **elapsed times** since occurrence of axon spikes in block 484 (ii) **elapsed times** since the occurrence of dendrite spikes in block 486 (iii) **current synapse weight values** being based on **spike time-dependent plasticity rule**.

In 496, the neuron firing of the dendrites is monitored by comparing **neuron membrane potential** with **neuron fire threshold value**. The neuron membrane potential is **reset or preset** to a certain value at the neuron firing.

In 498, the serial neuron firing data is converted to **parallel data**, and the **parallel neuron firing data** is sent to (ii) the **dendrite timer** (iii) **SAG block** and **system output**.

DIGITAL STDP SYNAPSE AND LIF NEURON BASED NEUROMORPHIC SYSTEM: BASICS

FIG. 2

In the IBM Patent, “Digital STDP Synapse and LIF Neuron-Based Neuromorphic²⁸ in FIG. 2 depicts biological nerve cells i.e. with electrical signals transmitted across of pre-neuron **axon** and **synapse** between pre-and post-neuron.

FIG. 3

FIG. 3 shows the circled area of FIG. 2 showing the **synapse** and flow of **neuro-transmitters** across the synapse.

LEGAL MEANING OF SW

Each synapse has a characteristic synapse weight (SW) which refers to the strength or amplitude of a connection between 2 nodes that corresponds to the amount of influence the firing of one neuron has on another.

²⁸ Takeo Yasuda, Kohji Hosokawa, Yutaka Nakamura, Junka Okazawa and Masatoshi Ishii. (2020) *Digital STDP Synapse And LIF Neuron-Based Neuromorphic System*. United States Patent Office. Patent No. US 10,762,419 B2. Available: <https://patents.google.com/patent/US10762419B2/en?q=US10762419B2>

SW is updated according to the period between a **pre-neuron axon spike** and **post-neuron dendrite spike** following the **spike time-dependent plasticity (STDP)** synapse model.

Pre- synaptic neuron refers to the neuron that transmits or generates a spike onto a synapse.

FIG. 4

FIG. 4 depicts a **crossbar structure 200 (artificial synapse network)** that comprises of:

- (i) **pre-neuron** (horizontal) **axon** paths / wires 205 and
- (ii) **post-neuron** (vertical) **dendrites** paths/wires 210
- (iii) **synapses 220** (located at cross-point junctions of each axon path 205 (extend horizontal) and each dendrite path 210 (extend vertically) arranged / aligned in array (in row / column lines) at intersections, per connection made through digital synapses 220.

The post-neuron receives stimulus through dendrite connected to a synapse, which raises the neuron membrane potential by a certain amount. A leaky decay incrementally lowers the neuron membrane potential.

The crossbar network is embodied in a random-access memory RAM. The system input is sent to (i) the axon timer (ii) SAG block and (iii) synapse weight decrement block.

Dendrite is defined as: (1) short **branched** extension of a **nerve cell**, along which **impulses** received from other cells at **synapses** are transmitted to the cell body.

(2) crystal or **crystalline mass** with a branching treelike structure.

For example, post-neuron receives stimulus through a **dendrite connected to a synapse** which raises the **neuron membrane potential** by some amount.

A leaky decay incrementally lowers the **neuron membrane potential**.

DIGITAL NEUROMORPHIC SYSTEM

FIG. 5

FIG. 5 is a **digital neuromorphic system** designed to **digitally provide** for (a) **STDP-synapse** and **LIF-neuron** based neuromorphic effects with on-system learning through hardware configuration.

Circuit logic 312 updates the (b) status of **neuron membrane potential register block 310** with information provided by (c) **axon timer block 330**, (d) **synapse weight memory block 315** (stores SW: **use any rewritable memory whether volatile or non-volatile**) and (b) **neuron membrane potential register block NPR 310** (included in a digital processor such as central processing unit CPU of a computing device) which stores the NP neuron membrane potential (c) **the neuron membrane potential update block NPU 320**: determines whether the neuron membrane potential reaches a certain threshold value in order to generate a neuron fire signal. Since neuron membrane potentials exhibit leaky decay as a result of 'calm down' of a

neuron, the NPU makes updates of neuron membrane potential values based on leaky integrate and fire (LIF) model.

The **axon timer block 330** and **dendrite time block 335** are provided to monitor the elapsed times since the occurrences of axon INPUT spikes and dendrite OUTPUT spikes. Output signals from the dendrite timer block 335 are processed in serial.

Axon timer block 330 includes (i) timers for all axons in the system and (ii) measures the elapsed time since axon INPUT signal received and dendrite timer block 335, dendrite timer block 335 includes (i) timers for all dendrites in the system and (ii) measures the elapsed time since dendrite OUTPUT signals e.g. neuron fire signals generated by **neuron membrane potential update block 320** for the post-neuron.

315

The **synapse weight update block (SWU) 325** updates the synapse weight value with the **elapsed time** information provided by the **axon timer block 330** and **dendrite timer block 335** with **current synapse weight value** obtained from **synapse weight memory block 315**. The **elapsed time** represents the time between an axon INPUT spike and dendrite OUTPUT spike.

Synapse weight values in the **synapse weight memory block 315** are updated in write operation. The **update values** are determined by **synapse weight update block 325**.

The **dendrite output register block (DOR) 340** (i) converts serial signals to parallel between the internal processing blocks and external parallel signal ports (ii) provides serial to parallel conversion of dendrite output e.g. neuron fire signals. Whereas internal signals are processed serially, the external interface is in a parallel arrangement.

ALGORITHM

The synapse weight update block 325, runs on an **algorithm** based on the spike-time dependent plasticity (STDP) rule, includes: **SWI – Synapse weight increment block 345** and **SWD – Synapse weight decrement block 350**, implement STDP-based on-system learning.

The synapse weight is updated (modified) by receiving the neuron fire spike of a pre-neuron (or pre-synaptic neuron) through an **axon node** shortly before or shortly after the neuron fire spike of the post-neuron (or post-synaptic neuron) appears in a **dendrite node**.

For example, injecting at least two spike pulses to the nodes of the synapse within a certain short period will cause a change in synapse weight e.g. update event. The neuron fire event occurs once in several milliseconds asynchronously and concurrently in parallel for all neurons.

The synapse weight update occurs not so rapidly in response to these neuron fire events (event driven base). The update amount (change in synapse weight) can be plotted as a function of the relative arrival time difference of a pre-synaptic neuron fire spike and a post-synaptic neuron fire spike.

DIGITAL NEUROMORPHIC BOARD:

ANCIENT REPLICA COPIED: IBM NORTHPOLE AI: FIELD PROGRAMMABLE GATE ARRAY

7.1 LAW EVIDENCE EXAMINATION: COMPUTER (WI-FI) PROGRAMMABLE SYNAPSE-YEN (CRIMINALLY ACCURATE VERSION)

7.1 Programmable Synapse-YEN Model: Organ Stack of Japan (Criminal Technical Analysis)

7.1. NEUROMOPRHIC PRODUCT TYPE: IBM

IBM MODEL: NEUROMORPHIC SYSTEM (METAL-OXIDE SEMICONDUCTOR FIELD EFFECT TRANSISTOR (MOSFET))

IBM PATENT

UNDER DATA PROTECTION LAW

7.1.5A. **IBM PATENT: NEUROMORPHIC CHIP OF UPDATING PRECISE SYNAPTIC WEIGHT VALUES (US 2023/0385619 A1) (ATSUYA OKAZAKI, MASATOSHI ISHII, JUNKA OKAZAWA, KOHJI HOSOKAWA, TAKAYUKI OSOGAMI) (DNN: DEEP NEURAL NETWORK)**

FIG. 5 NEUROMORPHIC SYSTEM-500: PCM (PHASE CHANGE MEMORY) CELL + TRANSISTOR = SYNAPSE

In the IBM Patent, “Neuromorphic Chip of Updating Precise Synaptic Weight Values”²⁹ in FIG. 1 shows (neuromorphic) crossbar array 100 (on-chip neuron circuits that can perform leaky integrate and fire LIF and synaptic weight update based on STDP modelled after biological neural networks that represents neuromorphic computing systems. CO-VAX shots are likely used for brain-mapping.

The synaptic cells are connected in parallel and in series with axon lines 20 (VERTICAL) and dendrite lines 30 (HORIZONTAL) with synaptic cells arranged at each intersection of lattice network.

²⁹ Atsuya Okazaki, Masatoshi Ishii, Junka Okazawa, Kohji Hosokawa, Takayuki Osogami. (2023) *Neuromorphic Chip of Updating Precise Synaptic Weight Values*. United States Patent Office. Patent No. US 2023/0385619 A1. Available: <https://patents.google.com/patent/US20230385619A1/en?q=US20230385619A1>

(1) The pre-synaptic neuron 40 of an array of pre-synaptic neurons 45 (2) connected to post-synaptic neurons 50 of array of post-synaptic neurons 55, via the synaptic cells, which respectively have a unique conductance value.

The system 500 further includes switches 90 aligned along the input interface side of the crossbar array 100, to implement switching functions. For example, switches where each synaptic cell assigned to a single synaptic weight: switches are used to selectively connect each of the input lines of pre-synaptic neuron 40 to one of the axons lines 20 to assign as a synaptic weight, one resistive cell specified by one circle 95 (FIG. 5). Switches within the pre-synaptic neuron array 45 are embedded into the neuromorphic chip with ASIC or FPGA.

FIG. 5 shows a neuromorphic system 500 that includes a crossbar array 100 (applicable to various kinds of implementations: SNN, DNN, dynamic Boltzmann machine (DyBM), contrastive divergence and gradient descent) of synaptic cells 10, that comprises of: (i) resistive devices (one or more) include volatile memory NVM. The 'controller' 80 updates plurality of weights (of NVM-based synaptic cells of crossbar array 100).

FIG. 4A DOWNSTREAM NEURON EXCITATION / FIG. 4B DNN H/W

FIG. 4B

FIG. 4A, 400a is a downstream neuron excitation of a DNN from pre-synaptic neurons (through 'multiply accumulate' MAC operation) that depends on the weight excitation of all upstream neurons evaluated through MAC operation. For example, input data (e.g. $x_1, x_2, x_3, \dots, x_n$ from multiple pre-synaptic neurons are obtained, and accumulated to a current neuron(s) through a multiply accumulate (MAC) operation: (i) each of the synapses x multiplies the input data with each weight, (ii) then the current neuron accumulates (i.e. Σ) the weighted input data $x_i \times w_i$ (from each of the pre-synaptic neurons to the product-sum z which stimulates the excitatory and inhibitory potentials, referred to as an activation functions $f(z)$) to generate an output data (e.g. y_1) based on one or more activation functions (f).

COMPUTATION LOGIC: (1) OHM'S LAW: MULTIPLY OP / (2) KIRCHHOFF'S LAW: CURRENT SUMMATION

The MAC (CO-VAX CHIP) operation in forward-inference and back-propagation of DNNs can be implemented as **vector-matrix multiplication** on large **NVM-based arrays**: The crossbar array of synaptic cells with NVM (conductance) and transistor 402 pairs.

The multiply operation is performed at every crossbar based on **Ohm's law** and the current summation along rows or columns performed based on **Kirchhoff's current law**.

7.1 LAW EVIDENCE EXAMINATION: COMPUTER (WI-FI) PROGRAMMABLE SYNAPSE-YEN (CRIMINALLY ACCURATE VERSION)

7.1 Programmable Synapse-YEN Model: Organ Stack of Japan (Criminal Technical Analysis)

7.1. NEUROMOPRHIC PRODUCT TYPE: IBM

IBM MODEL: NEUROMORPHIC SYSTEM (METAL-OXIDE SEMICONDUCTOR FIELD EFFECT TRANSISTOR (MOSFET))

IBM PATENT

UNDER DATA PROTECTION LAW

7.1.5C. IBM PATENT: WEIGHT SHIFTING FOR NEUROMORPHIC SYNAPSE ARRAY (#US 11,188,815 B2) (#TAKEO YASUDA, JUNKA OKAZAWA, KOHJI HOSOKAWA)

FIG. 7 NEUROMORPHIC SYNAPSE ARRAY-100

$$y_{ave} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=1}^n y_j = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=1}^n \sum_{i=1}^m w_{ij} x_i = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{j=1}^n w_{ij} x_i = \sum_{i=1}^m \left(\frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=1}^n w_{ij} \right) x_i = \sum_{i=1}^m w_{i,ave} x_i$$

where $w_{i,ave} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=1}^n w_{ij}$ ($i = 1$ to m)
is the average weight value of the synapses in the i -th row.

FIG. 7

COMPUTATION LOGIC: NEUROMORPHIC SYNAPSE ARRAY-100

In IBM Patent, "Weight Shifting For Neuromorphic Synapse Array"³⁰, in FIG. 7 shows **neuromorphic synapse array 100** and product-sum operation in a neural network array with crossbar arrays of cells: The average product sum value of column array y_j ($j = 1$ to n) denoted as y_{ave} is calculated:

$$y_{ave} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=1}^n y_j = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=1}^n \sum_{i=1}^m w_{ij} x_i = \quad (\text{equ-5})$$
$$\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{j=1}^n w_{ij} x_i = \sum_{i=1}^m \left(\frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=1}^n w_{ij} \right) x_i = \sum_{i=1}^m w_{iave} x_i$$

where

$$w_{iave} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=1}^n w_{ij}$$

FIG. 7 shows neural network array with crossbar arrays of cells 10. Where ($i = 1$ to m) is the average weight value of synapses in the i -th row.

The neuromorphic synapse array that includes: (i) plurality of synaptic array cells: have a single polarity synapse weight, (ii) plurality of operation column arrays: operation synapse cells and (iii) a reference column array: reference synapse cells for **shifting a product-sum** of operation synapse cells.

The neuromorphic synapse array presented ensures neuron model McCulloch-Pitts (COPIED: Ancient Replica) is dependent on non-linearity with a single polarity weight cell.

³⁰ Takeo Yasuda (Nara JP), Junka Okazawa (Yamashina-ku, JP) and Kohji Hosokawa (Ohtsu, JP). (2021) Weight Shifting For Neuromorphic Synapse Array. United States Patent Office. ('Google Patent') Patent No. US 2021/11,188,815 B2. Available:

FIG. 10 CIRCUIT OF NEUROMORPHIC SYNAPSE ARRAY (PULSE MODULATOR / PULSE GENERATOR)

FIG. 10

LEGAL EVIDENCE:

FIG. 10 shows a circuit of neuromorphic synapse array implemented with a **pulse modulator (PM)** or **pulse generator (PG)** that generates a pulse signal from a digital signal through the **ADC (Analog to Digital Converter)** in **Pulse Width Modulate (PWM)**, **Pulse Amplitude Modulate (PAM)** and **Pulse Number Modulate (PNM)** schemes.

- (i) The **pulse signal** is applied to a **transistor** at the output ends of operation column arrays.
- (ii) The **capacitors** 1040 accumulate and convert **all outputs of current charge** of operation column arrays at output ends 1070 into **voltage potential**.
- (iii) The neuromorphic synapse array 100 supplies voltage potential to the **activation function circuits**. (Each of the output ends 1005 of operation column arrays are split into two lines, each connected to **capacitor** 1040 to generate **potential outputs** 1070 to activation function FIG. 1.)
- (iv) **Activation-function-simulated-circuits** is embedded with neuromorphic array to compose a **neuromorphic core**: the activation functions generate outputs of neuromorphic core as inputs of subsequent neuromorphic cores.

FIG. 11 CIRCUIT OF NEUROMORPHIC SYNAPSE ARRAY (CURRENT MIRROR CIRCUITS / NEURON MODEL)

FIG. 11

LEGAL EVIDENCE:

FIG. 11 shows circuit of neuromorphic synapse array implemented with current mirror circuits.

Update of weights and activation potential are needed to practice, for example, the McCulloch-Pitts (COPIED: ANCIENT REPLICA) neuron model (during learning phases in NVM-based neuromorphic chips) model dependent on non-linearity with a **single polarity weight cell**.

The neuromorphic synapse array includes: (i) plurality of synaptic array cells that have a **single polarity synapse weight** classified into a (ii) plurality of **operation** column arrays (of synapse cells) and (iii) **reference** column array (of synapse cells) for **shifting a product-sum** of the operation synapse cells. Each weight of reference synapse cells is set to an average weight of all operation synapse cells to receive the same input data or same signal aligned in the same row (as reference synapse cells). The neuromorphic synaptic array **generates** input data dependent on updated weights of all the cell array to transfer the input data to subsequent synaptic neurons.

NVM based neuromorphic chips are h/w implemented neural network computing such as SNN (Spike Neural Network: NVM-based synaptic connections updated by local learning rule such as spike-timing-dependent-plasticity STDP to practice computational approach directly inspired by biology) and DNN (Deep Neural Network: NVM-based arrays represent matrices of synaptic weights implementing multiply accumulate MAC or the product-sum operation needed for algorithms such as backpropagation in an analog yet massively parallel fashion.)

7.1 LAW EVIDENCE EXAMINATION: COMPUTER (WI-FI) PROGRAMMABLE SYNAPSE-YEN (CRIMINALLY ACCURATE VERSION)

7.1 Programmable Synapse-YEN Model: Organ Stack of Japan (Criminal Technical Analysis)

7.1. NEUROMOPRHIC PRODUCT TYPE: IBM

IBM MODEL: NEUROMORPHIC SYSTEM (METAL-OXIDE SEMICONDUCTOR FIELD EFFECT TRANSISTOR (MOSFET))

IBM PATENT

UNDER DATA PROTECTION LAW

7.1.6A IBM PATENT: MEMORY CELL STRUCTURE (#US 10,446,231 B2) (#KOHJI HOSOKAWA, MASATOSHI ISHII, TAKEO YASUDA)

FIG. 3 SYNAPSE MEMORY CELL STRUCTURE

The IBM Patent, "Memory Cell Structure"³¹ in FIG. 3 includes: (i) **synapse memory cell 10** implemented with **unit resistances** (ii) write driver array-40 (configured to write a synapse weight value '0' or '1' to unit resistances (iii) read (recognition operation) driver array 50: apply current to the axons 20 coupled to **synapse memory cell 10** in synapse memory 100 in response to recognition operation input.

(iv) **current sensor 60**: configured to read synapse weight value / sense total current from corresponding dendrite coupled to synapse memory cell 10.

(v) **neuron body 70**: (i) calculate the **neuron membrane potential** value based on the (/ synapse weight value) based on: **total current sensed** by current sensor 60 and (ii) output the synapse weight value (/supply neuron output) as a **recognition operation** output to weight evaluator 80.

³¹ Kohji Hosokawa, Masatoshi Ishii and Takeo Yasuda. (2019) *Memory Cell Structure*. United States Patent Office. Patent No. US 10,446,231 B2. Available: <https://patents.google.com/patent/US10446231B2/en?q=US10446231B2>

(vi) weight evaluator 80: (i) evaluate current synapse weight value (ii) compare **neuron output signal** of neuron body 70 with desired output signal (iii) *calculates* and updates the next synapse weight value stored synapse memory cell 10

The cell component pass

- (1) **large** current if a large number of unit resistances comprises of weight value '1'.
- (2) **small** current if a large number of unit resistances comprises of weight value '0'.

Each plurality of unit resistances is assumed to have a (1) weight value W unit: heavy state '1' and light state '0' (2) conductance value (i.e. inverse of a resistance value R unit)

(vii) **weight encoder 90**: (i) encode next synapse weight value into **binary encoded values** (each of which supplied corresponds to one of write drivers 41 to 46, so that each writes a corresponding one of **the binary encoded values** to corresponding **one of cell components 11 to 16**) (ii) drives one of the write driver arrays 400 so that it can write the binary encoded values **to the synapse memory cell 10** as **synapse weight value**.

Examiner Lynette Lin: **CIRCUIT LARGE BLOCK**

DR. NIXON: injectables (CO-VAX)

NEURONOFF INC. MODEL – ELECTRODE CURED
MANUFACTURED IN BODY

FIG. 3A

FIG. 3B

7.1 LAW EVIDENCE EXAMINATION: COMPUTER (WI-FI) PROGRAMMABLE SYNAPSE-YEN (CRIMINALLY ACCURATE VERSION)

7.1 Programmable Synapse-YEN Model: Organ Stack of Japan (Criminal Technical Analysis)

7.1. NEUROMOPRHIC PRODUCT TYPE: IBM

IBM MODEL: NEUROMORPHIC SYSTEM (METAL-OXIDE SEMICONDUCTOR FIELD EFFECT TRANSISTOR (MOSFET))

IBM PATENT

UNDER DATA PROTECTION LAW

7.1.6B IBM MODEL: SYNAPSE MEMORY CELL DRIVER (#US 11,321,608 B2) (#TAKEO YASUDA, MASATOSHI ISHII)

FIG.4

In the IBM Patent, “Synapse Memory Cell Driver”³² the synapse memory system includes synapse memory cells provided at cross points of axon lines and dendrite lines.

Each synapse memory cell is associated with: (1) non-volatile random-access memory (NVRAM) and (2) configured to store weight value based on (i) output level of write signal (ii) write portion configured to write weight value to each synapse memory cell (includes: **write driver**--digital driver configured to output write signal to a subject synapse memory cell and **output controller**--configured to control output level of write signal of write driver) (3) Read drivers configured to read weight value stored in synapse memory cells.

³² Takeo Yasuda and Masatoshi Ishii. (2022) *Synapse Memory Cell Driver*. United States Patent Office. Patent No. US 11,321,608 B2. Available: <https://patents.google.com/patent/US11321608B2/en?q=US+11%2c321%2c608+B2>

FIG. 4 RESET THRESHOLD³³

FIG. 7 TIME CHART 450 FOR RESET / SET THRESHOLD

FIG. 7 operation of synapse memory cell system 101:

From time t1 to t2 (period t1-t2), write driver 140 applies:

- (i) voltage lower than RESET threshold level to one of the synapse memory cells 10 (target cell)
- (ii) so write driver 140 SETS the target cell to a RESET state (a certain decremented value).
- (iii) Write operation to decrease the synapse weight value is performed.
- (iv) The amount of decrease of synapse weight value depends on the amount by which voltage applied by write driver 140 falls below RESET threshold level.

From time t4 to t5 (period t4-t5), read driver 50 applies:

³³ Kohji Hosokawa, Masatoshi Ishii and Takeo Yasuda. (2019) *Memory Cell Structure*. United States Patent Office. Patent No. US 10,446,231 B2. Available: <https://patents.google.com/patent/US10446231B2/en?q=US10446231B2>

- (i) Voltage between driver common level and SET threshold level to the target cell so that read drivers 50 SET target cell to a read state.
- (ii) Read operation of synapse weight value is performed: 'Read1'

From time t6 to t7 (period t6-t7), write driver 140 applies:

- (i) Voltage lower than RESET threshold level to the target cell so that the write driver 140 sets the target cell to another RESET state (decremented value)
- (ii) Write operation to decrease the synapse weight value performed: 'RESET2'

From time t8 to t9 (period t8-t9), read driver 50 applies:

- (i) Voltage between driver common level and SET threshold level to the target cell so that read drivers 50 SET the target cell to another read state.
- (ii) Read operation of the synapse weight value performed: 'RESET2'
- (iii) The value read corresponds to synapse weight value updated from time t6 to t7: 'Read2'.

7.1 LAW EVIDENCE EXAMINATION: COMPUTER (WI-FI) PROGRAMMABLE SYNAPSE-YEN (CRIMINALLY ACCURATE VERSION)

7.1 Programmable Synapse-YEN Model: Organ Stack of Japan (Criminal Technical Analysis)

7.1. NEUROMORPHIC PRODUCT TYPE: IBM

IBM MODEL: NEUROMORPHIC SYSTEM (METAL-OXIDE SEMICONDUCTOR FIELD EFFECT TRANSISTOR (MOSFET))

IBM PATENT

UNDER DATA PROTECTION LAW

7.1.6C IBM MODEL: METHODS AND SYSTEMS OF NEURON LEAKY INTEGRATE AND FIRE CIRCUITS (US 11,308,390 B2) (MARK B. RITTER, TAKEO YASUDA)

FIG. 1

The embodiment in IBM Patent, “Methods and Systems of Neuron Leaky Integrate and Fire circuits”³⁴ of a neuron leaky integrate and fire circuit (NLIFC) 1000 includes:

NEURON MEMBRANE POTENTIAL

Integrated Circuit (i) Input Capacitor (C_{in}) 104 / Integration Diode (D_{itg}) / Integration Capacitor (C_{itg}) electrically coupled in serial: A first terminal of (C_{in}) 104 electrically coupled to an input terminal ‘in’ 102 of NLIFC 1000.

A second terminal of (C_{in}) 104 electrically coupled to anode of (D_{itg}) 112 to form swing node 110, cathode of (D_{itg}) 112 electrically coupled to first terminal of (C_{itg}) 114 to form a **neuron membrane potential node ‘np’** 120 and second terminal of (C_{itg}) 114 electrically coupled to the ground.

³⁴ Mark B. Ritter and Takeo Yasuda. (2022) *Methods and Systems of Neuron Leaky Integrate and Fire Circuits*. United States Patent Office. Patent No. US 11,308,390 B2. Available: <https://patents.google.com/patent/US11308390B2/en?q=US+11%2c308%2c390+B2>

AC components of Input Current and Input Voltage: (1) extract AC of input current (2) generate AC voltage no. swing voltages at swing node 'x' 110 (FIG. 1) (3) PUMP UP (C itg) 114. Thus, using extracted AC component of input current (i) converted to AC component of swing voltages used to CHARGE UP 'np' node 120 i.e. transferring charge from PULL-UP node 106 to a **neuron membrane potential (NP) node 120 (through serially connected D pu 108 and D itg 112) through an integrated diode**, showing integration value of the AC components of input current 'I in'.

Pull-up Circuit (iii) **pull-up diode** (D pu) 108 is electrically coupled to pull-up node 106 and cathode of (D pu) 108 electrically coupled to swing node 110 to raise a **voltage** at neuron membrane potential node (NP) over an **integration capacitor** (iv) **voltage** at membrane potential node (NP) that shows integration value of AC component of input current: implementing **leaky decay function of neuron leaky integrate and fire circuit**.

Leak CTRL Circuit, using a **leak current** of a **leak control FET** 116 gate electrically coupled to a leak control input terminal "leak_ctrl", drain of the leak control FET 116 is electrically coupled to **neuron membrane potential** node 'np' 120 and source of **leak control FET** 116 electrically coupled to ground. A current leak of the leak control FET 116 of leak control circuit implements **leaky decay function of neuron leaky integrate and fire circuit 1000**.

Analog Comparator (vii) detecting timing of neuron fire using analog comparator: + / - input terminal (of analog comparator 126) electrically coupled to the **neuron membrane potential** node 'np' 120 and input terminal "fire_th" 126 that supplies **threshold level of neuron fire** (V fire_th).

RESET

Analog comparator 126 is configured to compare voltage at 'np' node 120 with (V fire_th) where (1) voltage at 'np' node 120 equals to (V fire_th) (2) voltage at 'np' node 120 is **RESET** to voltage level of "RESET_LEVEL" input terminal and it is kept RESETTING during a refractory period timed by refractory trimer. The voltage level of the "RESET_LEVEL" input terminal is the ground level.

RESET Circuit FET 118: (1) gate is electrically coupled to a RESET CTRL circuit (2) drain of the RESET FET 118 is electrically coupled to 'np' node 120 and source of REST FET 118 is electrically coupled to "RESET_LEVEL" input terminal. The voltage level of the "RESET_LEVEL" input terminal is ground level.

(viii) RESETTING a **neuron membrane potential** level for refractory period, after neuron fire and (ix) **generating fire** output signal of the **neuron leaky integrate and fire circuit NLFC**.

RESET CTRL Circuit: (1) OR gate 122 and (2) refractory timer 124 implements insensible period of neuron just after it fires. (3) The refractory timer 124 extends the RESETTING period until the neuron recovers from insensible state.

7.1 LAW EVIDENCE EXAMINATION: COMPUTER (WI-FI) PROGRAMMABLE SYNAPSE-YEN (CRIMINALLY ACCURATE VERSION)

7.1 Programmable Synapse-YEN Model: Organ Stack of Japan (Criminal Technical Analysis)

7.1. NEUROMOPRHIC PRODUCT TYPE: IBM

SAMSUNG MODEL (TEXAS): NEUROMORPHIC SYSTEM (IBM JAPANESE & KOREAN)

SAMSUNG PATENT: SUPPLEMENTARY NOTES

UNDER DATA PROTECTION LAW

7.3.1. Samsung (IBM) 1: Timing Sequence For Digital STDP Synapse and LIF Neuron-Based Neuromorphic System (#US 2017/0344885 A1) (#KOHJI HOSOKAWA, MASATOSHI ISHII, YUTAKA NAKAMURA, JUNKA OKAZAWA, TAKEO YASUDA)

FIG. 11

In the Samsung (IBM inventor) Patent, "Timing Sequence For Digital STDP Synapse and LIF Neuron-Based Neuromorphic System"³⁵ in FIG. 11 shows waveforms for several signals: Using (i) **spike trigger signal** 1110 supplied as a **square wave pulse** (ii) **virtual analog spike** 1120 is input to the system from an axon (iii) **virtual analog spike** 1120 is triggered (Using spike trigger signal 1110, based on STDP model) and (iv) affects a **neuron cell** body through a **connected synapse** to update NP values.

Waveform shape is fixed and converted with a fixed set of digital data 1130.

The effect of the spike input is implemented with AT and DT, denoted by varying values shown as bars' height 1140.

Individual ATs and DTs are prepared for all axons and dendrites. The individual AT i (for $i = 0$ to 255) and DT j (for $j = 0$ to 255) are prepared for individual axon i (for $i = 0$ to 255) and individual dendrite j (for $j = 0$ to 255).

³⁵ Kohji Hosokawa (Shiga-Ken JP), Masatoshi Ishii (Shiga-ken JP), Yutaka Nakamura (Kyoto, JP), Junka Okazawa (Kyoto JP) and Takeo Yasuda (Nara-ken JP) (2017) Timing Sequence For Digital STDP Synapse and LIF Neuron-Based Neuromorphic System. United States Patent Office. ('Google Patent') Patent No. US 2017/0344885 A1. Available:

Individual **AT i** and **DT j** (for $i, j = 0$ to 255) operate independently because update and reset/preset timing for them are independent. When a spike **trigger signal** is supplied to a certain axon i or dendrite j , the corresponding AT i and DT j value is **preset** to a certain **maximum value**.

While no spike trigger signal is supplied to axon i or dendrite j , however, the corresponding AT i or DT j value decreases by certain amount at every evaluation time cycle.

When there is no spike trigger signal for longer than a certain duration of time, the corresponding AT i or DT j value decreases until it is equal to zero and AT i or DT j value stays at zero. AT i or DT j **are preset** to their initial values when corresponding axon input ($ax_in\ i$) or dendrite output ($dr_out\ j$) signals are given or generated during their evaluation time cycle.

In a neuromorphic system, axon input signals ($ax_in\ i$) (for $i = 0$ to 255) are supplied from outside or from pre-neurons as system input signals.

FIG. 6

These signals trigger (i) **virtual analog spikes**, supplied to the (ii) **axon and dendrite of the synapse**. The system output signals ($dr_out\ j$) (for $j = 0$ to 255) generated as the 'fire signals' of the neurons (or post neurons). The latter signals trigger (i) virtual analog spikes (ii) supplied to the dendrite of (iii) the synapse. Since analog signals cannot be processed in digital circuit, digital approximation is performed using AT i and DT j values for calculation in the NPU 425.

Values for calculation in the NPU 425, SWI 430 and SWD 435 are activated in the learning mode only.

A virtual analog spike 1120 (based on an STDP model affects the neuron cell body through a connected synapse to update NP values) is input to the system from an axon, triggered using the spike trigger signal 1110.

The shape of this waveform is fixed and can be converted with a fixed set of digital data 1130. The effect of the spike input is implemented with AT and DT behavior denoted by reference values with the bars' height 1140. AT i (for $i = 0$ to 225) and DT j (for $j = 0$ to 225) are prepared for individual axon i (for $i = 0$ to 225) and individual dendrite j (for $j = 0$ to 225).

Individual AT i and DT j (for $i, j = 0$ to 225) operate independently because update and reset/preset timing for them are independent. When a spike trigger signal is supplied to a certain axon i or dendrite j , the corresponding AT i and DT j value is preset to a certain maximum value.

When no spike trigger signal is supplied to the axon i or dendrite, the corresponding AT i and DT j value decreases by certain amount at every evaluation time cycle. When there is no spike trigger signal for longer than a certain duration of time, the corresponding AT i and DT j value decreases until it is equal to zero and AT i and DT j value stays at zero.

The AT i and DT j values are preset to their initial values when corresponding axon input ($ax_in\ i$) or dendrite output ($dr_out\ j$) signals are given or generated during their evaluation time cycle. In a neuromorphic system, axon input signals ($ax_in\ i$) (for $i = 0$ to 255) are supplied from outside or from pre-neurons as system input signals. These signals trigger virtual analog spikes, supplied to the axon of the synapse.

The system output signals ($dr_out\ j$) (for $j = 0$ to 255) are generated as the fire signals of the neurons (or post neurons). These signals trigger virtual analog spikes supplied to the dendrite of the synapse.

FIG. 12

FIG. 12 shows a detailed operation flow in one (k -th) evaluation cycle ($T\ eval\ k$) or sequence for the system operation. Evaluation time cycles: $T\ eval\ k-1$, $T\ eval\ k$, and $T\ eval\ k+1$. The timing sequence for $T\ eval\ k$ is repeated, so other evaluation time cycles e.g. $T\ eval\ k-1$ and $T\ eval\ k+1$, have completely the same sequences.

At 1210, a spike input from pre-neuron or external input is supplied to the AT 410, SWD 435 and SAG 455.

At 1220, AT is updated, during which (i) all AT values are decremented by 1 or a certain amount and the (ii) AT is preset for axons with input spikes only. The amount by which AT values are decremented is determined using the time decay shapes in 1140 of FIG. 11.

If there is a spike axon ($ax_in\ i$), at step 1120, the corresponding AT value (or AT i) is preset to the initial maximum value determined as the timer preset value. For example, if the AT's value is determined to have 4 bits, the present value is 15 ('1111' in binary). AT value is updated only at step 1220.

At 1230, the SWD 435 decrements the SW values. SW j values are updated (decremented) with the current DT j values and the SW j values only when spike input is given at ($ax_in\ i$). Decrement amount is determined using DT and SW values updated at step 1260 and step 1270 in $T\ eval\ k-1$ cycle.

At 1230, the neuron membrane potential NP is updated while incorporating the leak effect. NPU receives input signals for the AT values updated at step 1220, the SW values updated at the step 1230 and the current NP values.

At 1250, all of the neurons are checked in order to determine whether each of the neuron fires or not. NPU checks whether the neuron membrane potential NP reaches a certain threshold level ($fire_th < 0.7 >$) to generate a fire signal. The result is output signals dr_out_j (for $j = 0$ to 225).

FIG. 13

FIG. 13 shows a hierarchy of a cycle time.

[A] T_{eval_k} : k -th evaluation cycle update cycles for the NP, SW, AT, DT values and spike input and output / neuron status check cycles.

[B] The AT i , DT j , NP j , and SW i j , are updated every T_{eval_k} cycle. There are one $T_{eval_sw_dec_k}$ cycle, one $T_{eval_np_upd_k}$ cycle, and one $T_{eval_sw_inc_k}$ cycle in one T_{eval_k} cycle. The $T_{eval_sw_dec_k}$ cycle, $T_{eval_np_upd_k}$ cycle, and $T_{eval_sw_inc_k}$ cycle correspond to steps 1230, 1240, 1270 of FIG. 12.

[1] For the NP j update, the procedure completed in one $T_{eval_np_upd_k}$ cycle is always (regardless of axon or dendrite spike existence) triggered once in T_{eval_k} cycle. There are a total 256 (total no. of neurons) $T_{cal_np_upd_j}$ (for $j = 0$ to 255) cycles in one $T_{eval_np_upd_k}$ cycle.

The $T_{cal_np_upd_j}$ (for $j = 0$ to 255) cycles correspond to update cycles for NP of neuron j (NP j) ($j = 0$ to 255). There are a total of 256 T_{clk_i} (for $i = 0$ to 255) cycles in one $T_{cal_np_upd_j}$ cycle. Those correspond to NP j upd i corresponds to a certain intermediate NP j updated value with AT i , SW i j , NP j .

[2] For the SW i j decrement update, the procedure is triggered only when the axon input spikes are supplied. If there is at least one (ax_in_i) (for $i = 0$ to 255) with spike input, the procedure goes into $T_{eval_sw_dec_k}$ cycle. There are total of 256 (Total no. of synapse rows in a crossbar array).

$T_{cal_sw_dec\ i}$ (for $i = 0$ to 255) cycles in one $T_{eval_sw_dec\ k}$ cycle, only the $T_{cal_sw_dec\ i}$ cycles correspond to $(ax_in\ i)$ with spike input are processed (cycles for other rows skipped).

Furthermore, there are a total of $256\ T_{clk\ j}$ (for $j = 0$ to 255) cycles in each $T_{cal_sw_dec\ i}$ cycle. Those correspond to $SW_{ij\ dec}$ (for $j = 0$ to 255) cycles, the one $SW_{ij\ dec}$ corresponds to the cycle for SW_{ij} decrement update with DT_j and SW_{ij} at that period.

[3] For the SW_{ij} increment update, the procedure is triggered only when the dendrite output spikes are generated. If there is at least one $(dr_out\ j)$ (for $j = 0$ to 255) with spike output, the procedure goes into $T_{eval_sw_inc\ k}$ cycle. Although there are total of 256 (Total no. of synapse rows in a crossbar array), $T_{cal_sw_incl\ j}$ (for $j = 0$ to 255) cycles in one $T_{eval_sw_inc\ k}$ cycle, only the $T_{cal_sw_incl\ j}$ cycles for columns j which correspond to $dr_out\ j$ with spike output, are processed (cycles for other columns skipped). Furthermore, there are a total of $256\ T_{clk\ j}$ (for $i = 0$ to 255) cycles in each $T_{cal_sw_incl\ j}$ cycle. Those correspond to SW_{ij} inc corresponds to the cycle for SW_{ij} increment update with AT_i , SW_{ij} .

[4] The calculation time cycles $T_{cal_sw_dec\ l}$ (for $i = 0$ to 255) correspond to axon input row level operations. That is, in the $T_{cal_sw_dec\ i}$ cycle, next SW_{ij} . (for $j = 0$ to 255) values for 256 synapses in the row l are calculated with all $256\ DT_j$ (for $j = 0$ to 255) and $256\ SW_{ij}$ (for $j = 0$ to 255).

The sub-cycles which calculate SW_{ij} (for $j = 0$ to 255) are defined as $SW_{ij\ dec} (= T_{clk\ j})$ (for $j = 0$ to 25) cycles. These SW decrement cycle and sub-cycles are triggered only when the axon input spikes for the corresponding rows are supplied.

[5] The calculation time cycles $T_{cal_sw_dec\ j}$ (for $i = 0$ to 255) correspond to dendrite output column level operations. $T_{cal_sw_inc\ j}$ cycle, next SW_{ij} (for $i = 0$ to 255) values for 256 synapses in the column j are calculated with all $256\ AT_i$ (for $i = 0$ to 255) and $256\ SW_{ij}$ (for $l = 0$ to 255).

The sub-cycles which calculate SW_{ij} (for $i = 0$ to 255) are defined as $SW_{ij\ INC} (= T_{clk\ i})$ (for $i = 0$ to 25) cycles. These SW decrement cycle and sub-cycles are triggered only when the dendrite output spikes for the corresponding columns are supplied.

FIG. 8

FIG. 8 is an operation flow of a method of modeling spike time-dependent plasticity (STDP) and leaky integrate and fire (LIF) in a digital neuromorphic system.

FIG. 14

FIG. 14 shows a timing diagram showing timing of a serial to parallel conversion block for parallel output signal generation. The timing diagram shows output signals of the DOR 450 dor j (for j = 0 to 255) and reshaped dendrite output spike signals dr_out j (for j = 0 to 255). The serial to parallel conversion of a neuron fire output signal of a post-neuron is applied to re-convert the internal serial signal back to an external parallel interface.

The dr_out pulse signal is generated by the SAG 435 gives pulse shape for output spike signals dr_out j (for j = 0 to 255). The output signals of the DOR 450 dor j (for j = 0 to 255) are gated with the dr_out_pulse signal to generate dr_out j (for j = 0 to 255).

7.1 LAW EVIDENCE EXAMINATION: COMPUTER (WI-FI) PROGRAMMABLE SYNAPSE-YEN (CRIMINALLY ACCURATE VERSION)

7.1 Programmable Synapse-YEN Model: Organ Stack of Japan (Criminal Technical Analysis)

7.1. NEUROMOPRHIC PRODUCT TYPE: IBM

[SAMSUNG MODEL \(TEXAS\): NEUROMORPHIC SYSTEM \(IBM JAPANESE & KOREAN\)](#)

[SAMSUNG PATENT](#)

UNDER DATA PROTECTION LAW

7.3.2. Samsung Model 2: LUT Based Synapse Weight Update Scheme in STDP Neuromorphic Systems (#US 10,891,543 B2) (#KOHJI HOSOKAWA, MASATOSHI ISHII, YUTAKA NAKAMURA, JUNKA OKAZAWA, TAKEO YASUDA)

FIG. 2 SYNAPSE WT UPDATE: NEUROMORPHIC SYSTEM WITH STDP (SPIKE TIME DEPENDENT PLASTICITY) (ANCIENT REPLICA)

The Samsung Patent, "LUT Based Synapse Weight Update Scheme in STDP Neuromorphic Systems"³⁶ in FIG. 2 shows a criminal method of **updating synapse weight (SW)** values in a neuromorphic system with Spike Time Dependent Plasticity (STDP) model, that comprises of: (i) hardware-based **synapse weight incrementer or decrementer** (ii) one of a synapse weight increment or decrement function with two independent blocks: synapse weight increment (SWI) BLOCK and synapse weight decrement (SWD) BLOCK; SWI & SWD receive **spike timing data** and control signals, in special timing sequence, (iii) each using a respective lookup table LUT (in both blocks) to generate updated synapse weight SW values responsive to spike timing data **(a) storing updated** synapse weight values in memory **(b) h/w-based processor: a (c) learning process to integrate** the (a) updated synapse weight values stored in the memory (d) into the Spike Time Dependent Plasticity model neuromorphic system for improving neuromorphic simulation. MUX 235 selects results from SWD 250 or SWI 240 to be written to SW RAM 210.

LEGAL NOTE

It stated clearly that STDP model neuromorphic system is to improve 'neuromorphic simulation'. In other words, morphing the brain in virtual 'reality' (NOT real). It is illegal under international space law. If 1-dead / 1-organ damage, under international criminal law.

SAMSUNG (IBM COPIED: ANCIENT REPLIC) NEURON MEMBRANE POTENTIAL REGISTER

The sequencer for block control signals and Address Generator for SW RAM (SAG) 290 (i) implements timing sequence generating trigger and has a clock (clk) and reset inputs and generates row and column

³⁶ Kohji Hosokawa (Shiga-Ken JP), Masatoshi Ishii (Shiga-ken JP), Yutaka Nakamura (Kyoto, JP), Junka Okazawa (Kyoto JP) and Takeo Yasuda (Nara-ken JP) (2021) LUT Based Synapse WT Update Scheme in STDP Neuromorphic System. United States Patent Office. ('Google Patent') Patent No. US 10,891,543 B2. Available:

address signals (sw_ram_row_adr<0.7> and sw_ram_col_adr<0.7>) for SW RAM 210, (ii) sends neuron membrane potential register **trigger signal**, np_reg_trg to a **Neuron Membrane Potential Register (NPR)** 205, (iii) sends **LUT trigger signal** npu_lut_trg<1:2> for NP update to **Neuron Membrane Potential Update block (NPU) 215** where an NP value is updated with (1) spike input (Axon Input) timing (ax_tmr(t)<0.3>) (2) SW values for corresponding synapses (sw(t)<0.7>) and (3) current NP value (np(t)<0.7>). The **updated NP value** np(t+1)<0.7> is then sent to **NPR 205**. (iv) The **Neuron Membrane Potential Update 215** further checks whether the NP reaches a certain threshold level to generate a fire signal (fire_th<0.7>). The NPU implements the Leaky Integrate and Fire (LIF) operation and applies leaky decay effect and generates output signal for the next NP value.

SAMSUNG (IBM COPIED: ANCIENT REPLICAS) SYNAPSE-‘CROSS-BAR’

FIG. 1

FIG. 1 shows synapses 130 with crossbar structure, connected between axon 110 pre-neuron and dendrite 120 post-neuron. Thus, axons 110 (horizontal) and dendrites 120 (vertical) in crossbar structure, perpendicular to each other cross at synapses 130.

Each synapse 130 has its own SW value that shows strength of connection. In the STDP mode, the SW values are updated with timing between (1) axon 110 pre-neuron spike and (2) dendrite 120 post-neuron spike.

In system 200, synapse devices with crossbar structure is implemented with SW Random Access Memory (RAM) 210: with (i) 256 neurons and (ii) $256 \times 256 = (65536)$ synapses. The number of neurons can be any number and modified according to target application. The SW data for synapses is stored in SW RAM 210 in **8-bit**. The row (axon) and column (neuron body (or dendrite) of the SW RAM (i, j) 210 in **8-bit** or (SW i, j) for $i, j = 0$ to 255 shows SW value of synapse between axon i and dendrite j.

Then, **timing difference** between axon and dendrite is monitored being the most important **parameters** in STDP model. Thus, to obtain timing, an Axon Timer (AT) 220 and Dendrite Timer (DT) 230 (lengths of are in **4 bits**) gives the **elapsed times** since a **spike** is given to **axon nodes** and **dendrite nodes** of synapses.

Then, AT access signals at at_acs and DT access signals, dt_acs activated when accessed for read. However, lengths are determined according to target application. For example, $at_sel<0:7>$ are **8 bit** AT selection signals which select one AT value used for SWI (Increment) out of 256 ATs. $dt_sel<0:7>$ are **8 bit** DT selection signals which select one DT value used for SWD (decrement) out of 256 DTs. Thus, AT 220 and DT 230 work like decrement counter and are preset at spike-in timing. Spike timing information is used in the STDP model for SW update operation.

FIG. 4

FIG. 4 shows Synapse Weight **Increment** block 400 (corresponds to SWI (increment) block 240) consists of (i) LUT 410 for an SWI (ii) LUT Access Timing Generator (LATG) 420 that generates a LUT access (or trigger) signal (sw_inc_lut_trg) from (sw_inc_trg) input signal (iii) dr_out j (j = 0 to 255) (neuron fire) signals.

The (i) LUT 410 has address input ports 430 for AT value (ax_tmr(t)<0.3>), address import and address **import** ports 440 for current SW value (sw(t)<0.7>). Data output ports 450 for updated (incremented) SW value: (sw_inc(t+1)<0.7>). Thus, (a) length of the address input data (ax_tmr(t)<0.3>) & (sw(t)<0.7>) is 12 (-4 + 8) bits.

The (b) length of the output data (sw_inc(t+1)<0.7>) is 8 bits.

FIG. 7

FIG. 7 block diagram shows Synapse Weight **Decrement** block 700 that corresponds to SWD block 250 in FIG. 2.

FIG. 5 TIMING DIAGRAM SWI (SYNAPSE WT INCREMENT) OPERATION: Tevaluation CYCLE

FIG. 5

FIG. 5 is timing diagram for operation of SWI block over Teval cycles 0 to 4 (500-540). When there is a spike 560 in Teval cycle 0 at dr_out₀, input and the sw_inc_trg signal is activated, the LATG generates 256 pulses on the (sw_inc_lut_trg) signal at pulse timing slot j (j = 0, to 255) 550.

FIG. 6

FIG. 6 is magnified timing diagram of Teval cycle 4 that shows transferred data ax_tmr(t)<0.3>, sw(t)<0.7> and sw_inc(t+1) <0.7>.

The on-chip self-learning function with the ability to implement synaptic weight update function requires an electrical model with a large number of 'parameters' (which the Microsoft WO 060606 was trying to introduce with its 'bus architecture', NOT unlike the PERP stocklist of a mass murder chip IBM i.e. COPIED ancient replica): SW values of the targeted synapses are calculated using the difference between spike arrival time (pre-neuron and post-neuron) converted into an update SW values amount.

CRIMINAL PARAMETER FITTING

Implementation on a fully digital circuit with a Field-Programmable Gate Array (FPGA) (/ OR programmable logic device), the LUTs is updated for system parameter fitting using two: increment and decrement LUTs (without complicated synapse update algorithm). Secondly, the on-chip self-learning is free from PVT variation (Process, Voltage and Temperature, copied by IBM Tokyo team's journal) unlike analog implementation with reconfigurable logic FPGA.

7.1 LAW EVIDENCE EXAMINATION: COMPUTER (WI-FI) PROGRAMMABLE SYNAPSE-YEN (CRIMINALLY ACCURATE VERSION)

7.1 Programmable Synapse-YEN Model: Organ Stack of Japan (Criminal Technical Analysis)

7.1. NEUROMOPRHIC PRODUCT TYPE: IBM

IBM JOURNAL (TOKYO): NEUROMORPHIC SYSTEM (IBM JAPANESE & KOREAN)

UNDER DATA PROTECTION LAW

7.2.1. IBM Journal 1.1.1: Circuit Techniques For Efficient Acceleration of Deep Neural Network Inference with Analog-AI (Kohji Hosokawa)

ALTERNATE SUPPLEMENTARY DIAGRAM: NON-VOLATILE MEMORY FOR NEUROMORPHIC COMPUTING ON-CHIP TRAINABLE ANALOG PHASE CHANGE MEMORY SYNAPTIC ARRAY

In the IBM (Tokyo) Journal / Conference paper, “Circuit Techniques For Efficient Acceleration of Deep Neural Network Inference with Analog-AI”³⁷ in FIG. 1 depicts a Deep Neural Networks involving: a. Multiply-ACCumulate (MACC) operations between: (i) synaptic weights w_{ij} and (ii) neuronal excitations x_i : efficiently mapped unto (b, d) multiple crossbar array ‘tiles’.

c. High DNN accuracy requires accurate weight programming unto PCM cells.

³⁷ Harvard Reference: CONFERENCE

Kohji Hosokawa and others. Circuit Techniques for Efficient Acceleration of Deep Neural Network Inference with Analog-AI (Invited). In: 2021 IEEE International Symposium on Circuits and Systems (ISCAS), Daegu, Korea, 2021. New York City: IEEE

FIG. 1 DEEP NEURAL NETWORK: MAC OPERATIONS

FIG. 2 WEIGHT PROGRAMMING

FIG. 2 exhibits weight programming operations on one row (column) at a time (all columns / rows participating). Read pulses are fired from south-side circuitry. Currently programmed weight-values measured by capacitors on the west-side.

Second capacitor holding target weight information compared in parallel against current values and discrepancies addressed by subsequent programming rules.

FIG. 3 TRAJECTORY OF WT ERROR

FIG. 3 Trajectory of weight error, progressing from un-programmed to accurately programmed: (i) subset (column or row) of 4-conductance PCM devices programmed sequentially,

(ii) with partial-SET pulses (iii) to continuously increase device conductance, either with (a) 200 total pulses or (b) 120 total pulses.

FIG. 4 ARRAY SEGMENT

FIG. 4a. Each tile comprised of 64 x 64 unit-cells together with (multiple) segment circuitry.

b. Forward-inference, a source-follower device holds source voltage at near constant value, so pulses arriving on gates of the unit-cell access transistors can sink current from local bit-lines.

Current is scaled down by segment mirrors that steer current into corresponding global bit-lines.

c. **array column** followed by **integration** by an **edge capacitor**: Additional conductance pairs have currents additionally scaled by factor of F (F~3)

d. A **comparator** in each column compares this **capacitor voltage** against a common ramp signal (generated by control circuitry): which leads to a duration signal routed to the next array.

g. 5. (a) Impact of conductance scaling on total energy for forward-inference, and the corresponding energy efficiencies. The scaling coefficient between the black (nJ/inference example) and blue lines (TOPs/sec/W) is $(513 \times 512 \times 2 \text{ OP/Forward-MACC}) = 525,312 \text{ OPs/array}$. (b) Projection of inference performance per unit area as a function of the integration duration, assuming 50% array utilization of an array-tile with 512×512 weights [11].

PROF. SANGBUM KIM'S NEUROMORPHIC PROCESSOR LANDSCAPE CLASSIFICATION

	Artificial neural network (ANN)	Spiking neural network (SNN)
Conventional digital memory device	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A scalable Multi-TeraOPS Deep Learning Processor SRAM Deep learning training and inference Programmable architecture and custom ISA <p><i>B. Fleischer et al., VLSI Circuits, 2018.</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> TrueNorth SRAM Off-chip learning <p><i>P. Merolla et al., Science, 2014.</i></p>
Analog non-volatile memory (NVM) device	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> NVM ML accelerator PCM On-chip learning <p><i>G. Burr et al., IEDM, 2014.</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> NVM low-power ML PCM On-chip learning <p><i>M. Ishii, S. Kim et al., IEDM, 2019.</i></p>

The algorithmic components of **RBM** and **eCD** are designed using unique hardware with **analog NVM**-based synaptic cell array and peripheral neuron circuits (FIG. 1(d), 1(e)).

ANALOG NVM SYNAPTIC CELL ARRAY

FIG. 1 (d) 6T2R PCM SYNAPSE CELL CIRCUIT DIAGRAM WITH SIGNAL NAMES. (e) CAD LAYOUT IMAGE

The lower-power spiking RBM chip with densely integrated NVM synapses can perform several ML algorithm applications in edge-computing (supervised, unsupervised) real-time learning.

7.1 LAW EVIDENCE EXAMINATION: COMPUTER (WI-FI) PROGRAMMABLE SYNAPSE-YEN (CRIMINALLY ACCURATE VERSION)

7.1 Programmable Synapse-YEN Model: Organ Stack of Japan (Criminal Technical Analysis)

7.1. NEUROMORPHIC PRODUCT TYPE: IBM

[IBM JOURNAL \(TOKYO\): NEUROMORPHIC SYSTEM \(IBM JAPANESE & KOREAN\)](#)

UNDER DATA PROTECTION LAW

7.2.2. [IBM Journal 1.1.2: Pattern Training, Inference and Regeneration Demonstration Using On-Chip Trainable Neuromorphic Chips For Spiking Restricted Boltzman Machine \(#MASATOSHI ISHII, \[ATSUJYA OKAZAKI\]\(#\), AKIYO NOMURA, KOHJI HOSOKAWA, SANGBUM KIM\) \(2022\)](#)

BACKGROUND BRIEF

- (1) Leaky integrate-and-fire (LIF) neuron model as a parallel RC circuit: charges in response to its input. It has a voltage threshold and when this is reached, the circuit emits a spike and then resets ('RESET'-THE WRONG WEF) to its resting level, which is zero.
- (2) A resistor-capacitor circuit (RC Circuit) is an electrical circuit consisting of passive components like resistors and capacitors, driven by current source or voltage source.

RESTRICTED BOLTZMANN MACHINE ON SPIKING NEURAL NETWORK SNN

(c)

In the IBM Patent, “Pattern Training, Inference And Regeneration Demonstration Using On-Chip Trainable Neuromorphic CHiPs For Spiking Restricted Boltzmann Machine”³⁸ in FIG. 1 (c) RBM NETWORK MODEL AND POISSON SPIKE INPUTS

An RBM is a two-layer bi-directional neural network with one visible and one hidden layer where the connectivity between the neurons in the same layer is restricted (FIG. 1(c)). By using event-driven contrastive divergence (eCD) algorithm to train a Restricted Boltzmann Machine RBM on Spiking Neural Network SNN constructed with stochastic leaky integrate-and-fire (LIF) neurons using STDP weight update rule (online and asynchronous manner) permits simultaneous spiking activities per LIF neuron on both layers.

³⁸ Harvard Reference: JOURNAL

Uicheol Shin, Masatoshi Ishii, Atsuya Okazaki, Megumi Ito, Malte J. Rasch, Wanki Kim, Akiyo Nomura, Wonseok Choi, Dooyong Koh, Kohji Hosokawa, Matthew Brightsky, Seiji Munetoh and SangBum Kim. (2022) *Pattern Training, Inference and Regeneration Demonstration Using On-Chip Trainable Neuromorphic Chips for Spiking Restricted Boltzmann Machine*. *Advanced Intelligent Systems*. Vol. (No.).

FIG. 1 SPIKING RBM NEUROMORPHIC HARDWARE COMPONENTS:
 FABRICATED SNN CHIP PHASE CHANGE MEMORY SYNAPTIC ARRAY:
 OPERATES RBM WITH eCD

FIG. 1 (a) FABRICATED PROTOTYPE CHIP MICROGRAPH. This design shows a fabricated SNN chip capable of on-chip learning (FIG. 1(a), 1(b)) with a Phase-Change Memory (PCM) synaptic array. The SNN chip operates as a Restricted Boltzmann Machine (RBM) with an **event** (e.g. 201 NY, Wuhan Ports Drill-8K LED-Military 'Games', Singapore Switch Fintech, 'scientific-ed children-compute')-driven contrastive divergence (eCD).

FIELD PROGRAMMABLE GATE ARRAY (FPGA)

(b)

FIG. (b) FPGA-BASED EVALUATION SYSTEM. The newly configured field-programmable gate array (FPGA) to operate the chip by transferring long spike trains to the SNN chip through on-chip scan chains.

METAL OXIDE FIELD EFFECT TRANSISTOR

Field Effect Transistors

MOSFET

PROF. SANGBUM KIM'S NEUROMORPHIC ARRAY FOR MNIST DEMONSTRATION

Fully Si-integrated large PCM array size (692K synaptic cells) with on-chip learning

M. Ishii[#], S. Kim[#], et al., IEDM (2019)
U. Shin et al., Adv. Intell. Syst. (2022)

CRIMINAL EVIDENCE

FIG. 1 (g) ARRAY STRUCTURE WITH 6T2R UNIT CELLS AND LIF NEURONS CIRCUITS (2 X 2 SHOWN)

EXPERIMENTATION

SIX TRANSISTORS 2 RESISTORS WITH PHASE CHANGE MEMORY (6T2R PCM)

BACKGROUND BRIEF

PCM are memory technologies that entails storing data through resistance changes due to phase transition of materials. PCM are used as neuromorphic synaptic devices for programmability.

FIG. 1 (h) 1000-STATES GRADUAL SET WITH LINEARITY IMPROVED MUSHROOM PCM CELL: FOUR EXAMPLES OF CONDUCTANCE EVOLUTION

(i) MEDIUM PLOTS WITH +/- STANDARD DERIVED BY 50-TIME MEASUREMENTS OF A PCM CELL. RBM Restricted Boltzmann Machine SNN Spike Neural Network chip with high-yielding PCM synaptic cells: PCM update linearity (FIG. 1h, 1i) improved substantially by

'optimizing programming conditions'. For instance, the conductance of PCM is increased due to the accumulative properties implemented by partial SETs while the RESET process is abrupt. Then, using a PCM pair-cells to overcome the lack of linearity and symmetry caused by abrupt RESET process.

FIG. 2 (a)-(k) shows simplified LIF neuron circuitry, a 6T2R PCM unit cell, operational design of functions to perform spiking RBM based on STDP: (a) forward LIF (visible to hidden) (b) backward LIF (hidden to visible) (c) STDP.

LEGAL EVIDENCE: MEMBRANE POTENTIAL INTEGRATION

Another transistor forming 3T1R half unit cell is added for the RBM bidirectional recurrent neural network: for the BLIF. A signed synaptic weight is implemented by pairing two half unit cells with differential sensing. At the end of the bit line connecting each half (Unit cell), added a current mirror circuit (to define polarity). Whenever LIF_WL is activated, synaptic weight $w = G_{total} = G_p - G_m$ is provided for membrane potential integration.

(c) STDP

After LIF transistor is turned off, the STDP_WL pulse follows for weight update. When the hidden neurons fire (Due to enough LIF process,) STDP BL pulse occurred with time delay. Pulse schedules are designed for the implementation of time correlation of neuron firing from pre-and post-synaptic neurons.

LEGAL EVIDENCE: NEURON FIRING STDP _ WL PULSE, PCM PROGRAMMED

Once the STDP_BL pulse delayed, after neuron firing is temporally overlapped with STDP_WL pulse, the PCM cell is **programmed** with a large amount of current following through the PCM cell. The exact amount of current is determined by the STPD_WL **pulse amplitude**.

TUNABLE PULSE CHARACTERISTICS

Results for configurable pulse timings: (d) **visible neuron** side (e) trimmable range for pulse delay and pulse width (f) **hidden neuron** side (shown above). As the pulse characteristics for **unit cell operation**, include STDP_WL_Gp, STDP_WL_Gm and STDP_BL are tunable (FIG. 2(d) – 2(f)), there is **precise control** over update timings of Gp and Gm, by time correlatively performing SET and RESET programming. By combining them, the modified STDP is implemented, a spike-based local weight update rule in RCM eCD (FIG. 2(g)).

RESULTS

LIF operation is tested by accessing and programming PCM devices on the **selected unit cell** on a LIF_WL with **832 synaptic unit cells**. An investigation of the impact of the **total conductance (G Total)** on LIF spike output measurements by applying 200 external input spikes through **visible neuron** circuit shows: reported change in LIF outputs according to Gp and Gm.

FIG. 3 Number of spikes from LIF neuron (a) SET Programming of G_p with fixed G_m results in more spikes and (b) SET Programming of G_m with fixed G_p results in less spikes.

FIG. 3(a) 3(b) shows number of output spikes **increases** as the **positive conductance, G_p** , increases through repeated SET programming. When conductance of G_p PCM cell increases, the **discharge amount** of the **membrane capacitor** in the LIF circuit increased so it is possible to fire with even **smaller** number of **input spikes**, thus resulting in more output spikes.

Increasing **conductance of G_m** PCM which represents **negative conductance**, **decreases** the G_{total} of the unit cell. This indicates that **more incoming spikes** are required for **membrane potential** to **exceed** the **predetermined threshold voltage**, thus resulting in a **decrease** in the number of **output spikes**. LIF output is measured by **adjusting** the **interval** of input spikes which demonstrates that leak function and refractory time are properly working in LIF circuitry.

The **larger spike interval** generates **less LIF** output due to the **decay** of the **membrane potential** implemented by the **leak function**, whereas if the interval is too small, the output is measured as small because **many input spikes** are **ignored** by the **refractory time** *after* firing.

FIG. 3 Plotted dots and lines in (c-d) from experiment and simulation results shows operational similarity between LIF neuron and BLIF neuron 3(c) number of spikes from LIF neuron (d) BLIF neuron: both obtained from increasing G_p but fixing G_m .

Identical experiments on the **hidden side** neuron circuit to compare LIF and BLIF confirmed that bi-directional connections were implemented in the fabricated circuitry (FIG. 3(c) 3(d)). Besides hardware plotted results show dot symbols, numerical simulation (Plotted line results) of the ideal LIF-BLIEF circuitry system with the refractory period in (FIG. 3(c) 3(d)) show a comparable tendency of output spikes thus indicating that LIF circuitry is well-fabricated. The purpose is to demonstrate the symmetrical performance of LIF and BLIEF, that the **neuromorphic hardware** can implement **spiking RBM** that requires **symmetry** between **forward** and **backward propagation**.

CONFIGURABLE SPIKE TIME DEPENDENT PLASTICITY

(g)

(g) Configurable STDP_WL and its STDP function.

During the data phase, by enabling external fire regardless of membrane potential, specific spike trains are applied to **visible neurons** (as input learning data). In the data phase, a **small amplitude but long SET** programming pulse is applied to STDP_WL_Gp, whereas a **high voltage but short RESET** programming pulse is entered into STDP_WL_Gm to implement positive weight update during the data phase by increasing w .

For the model phase, the **external clamped data is turned off** and the **internal LIF** serves to execute **free running** between **visible** and **hidden neurons**. The negative weight update during the data phase by **increasing w** and be implemented in the opposite way (FIG. 2(g)).

LEGAL MEANING OF MUTLI-'PHASE' 'PROGRAMMATIC' IN WB DOC

In each **phase of eCD**, the network state is optimized by updating through only the long-term potentiation (LTP) or long-term depression (LTD) of synaptic weights,

LEGAL MEANING OF 'EVENT' (EVENT SYNAPSE 201, MILITARY SYNAPSE-100+)

Thus, having demonstrated (through practical tasks of generative models) this fundamental unit designed hardware version of RBM network is suited for Event-driven (illegal) operation.

PROF. SANGBUM KIM'S 6T-2R FOR RBM OPERATION WITH ON-CHIP LEARNING

M. Ishii[#], S. Kim[#] et al., 2019 IEDM

Random walk circuit

EXPLANATION (WITH DIAGRAMS) STOCHASTIC LIF NEURON CIRCUITS

Diagrams for Random walk function in LIF neuron circuits: (h) random bit generation (i) random change transfer circuits.

The 6T2R unit cell is connected to peripheral neuron circuit for LIF operation.

Whenever LIF_WL pulse is generated from a **visible** neuron, the circuit connected with the **PCM cell charge** or discharge from **membrane capacitor** (which represents the **membrane potential** in the **hidden neuron circuit**), the firing probability of the stochastic neuron has a sigmoid-like varying tendency according to the membrane potential:

$$\rho(\mu) = (\tau_r + \exp(-\mu))^{-1}$$

LEGAL EVIDENCE: ENERGY BASED MODEL

$$\rho(\mu) =$$

$$(\tau_r + \exp(-\mu))^{-1}$$

, where ρ , μ and τ_r are average firing probability, membrane potential and refractory period. (This is the key feature of energy-based models e.g. RBM to migrate to lower-energy state). To implement **stochasticity** in LIF neuron, **random walk function** is added (FIG. 2(h) – 2(j)), designed to implement the necessary neuronal behavior in **stochastic neural network RBM**.

To operate the **random walk circuits** using **pseudorandom bits generated** by an on-chip linear feedback shift register (LFSR), fixed amount of charges are added ($RAND_BIT=1$) OR subtracted ($RAND_BIT=0$) from **membrane potential capacitor**, using **switched** ('SWITCH' FINTECH IN CONTEXT) (FIG. 2(i), 2(j)). The 1.6K stochastic LIF neuron circuits perform neuronal operation functions e.g. refractory period and leaky function.

Random walk function in LIF neuron circuits: (j) example of random potential movement (k) schematic diagram for bias spiking scheme. Bias neuron spike stochastically with their optimum average spiking rates ($N = 1$).

The random walk is a system with **probability distribution derived** from several independent trials of randomly getting closer or farther when progressing to a certain state. By applying this concept to membrane potential of neuron circuitry, the **membrane potential** of each neuron circuit periodically ($CCK<4>$) increased or decreased by fixed amount.

The **random bit (RAND_BIT)** determines whether to charge or discharge the **membrane capacitor** and can be assigned to 832 neurons and axons using 2 coupled LFSR and one XOR gate (FIG. 2(h)). **The XOR operations between 2 counter-propagating LFSRs**

generated from each predefined seed provided RAND_BITS to each LIF neuron ensure (METHOD) temporally independent correlations between bit sequences.

EXPLANATION (WITH DIAGRAMS)

TRAINABLE BIASES AND PSP – POST-SYNAPTIC POTENTIAL

In the spiking RBM chip, biases are implemented using bias neurons. Bias neurons exist on both layers and their functions are the same: externally triggered to generate spikes with a given average spiking rate (Bias spiking rate). FIG. 2(k) shows bias neurons to implement a bias.

For illustration, whenever bias neurons **fire**, the post-synaptic **potential** (PSP) of the corresponding post-synaptic neuron **changes** and **baselines** PSP change accordingly. To optimize training accuracy, **biases** and **weights** need to be trained on an **extension of eCD**.

As Phase Change Memories PCMs are updated based on spike from adjacent neurons, the spiking **rates** of bias neurons affect the training (of biases). Thus, **optimal bias** spiking rates that can be used to **achieve maximum accuracy** has to be determined.

AVE CONDUCTANCE CHANGE: PHASE CHANGE MEMORY

As the influence of Phase Change Memory PCM conductance changes on Post-Synaptic Potential PSP consistent with Restricted Boltzmann Machine RBM counterparts, the average conductance change of Phase Change Memory PCM connected to bias neuron and i-th visible (or hidden) neuron $\langle \Delta G_i \rangle$ for a small time interval Δt should be $\langle \Delta G_i \rangle = \eta \tau \text{STDP} v_i \Delta t / N \alpha \tau$ power 2 ref.

$$\langle \Delta G_i \rangle = \eta \tau_{\text{STDP}} v_i \Delta t / N \alpha \tau_{\text{ref}}^2$$

N = number of bias neurons

η = learning rate

τ_{STDP} = learning window

τ_{ref} = refractory period (is resistance to process or stimulus)

α = average spiking rates of bias neurons

v = average spiking rates of i -th visible (/ hidden) neuron

The learning rule of 6T2R spiking RBM, **average conductance charge** is:

$$\langle \Delta G_i \rangle = \eta \tau_{\text{STDP}} v_i \Delta t$$

Thus, by combining 2 equations, the **optimum average spiking rate** of bias neurons:

$$\alpha = N^{-1/2} \tau_{\text{ref}}^{-1} \quad \text{SET AVE SPIKING RATES (TO OPTIMUM)}$$

Trainable biases are implemented in terms of bias neurons and bias training is properly enabled by setting **average spiking rates** to their **optimum** values.

RESULTS OF MEMBRANE POTENTIAL DEPENDENT FIRING PROBABILITY OF RANDOM WALK FUNCTION

FIG. 4(a) shows membrane potential dependent firing probability of random walk function. Varying VN_UP with proper VP_DN shows fine tunability of sigmoid-like firing probability. FIG. 4(b) shows learning progress of handwritten digit classification experiments with red and blue lines (100 image training accuracy-RED; 10 k-image test accuracy-BLUE) Arrows indicate epochs where accuracy reaches best score.

FIG. 4(a) sigmoid-like firing probability is determined by distance between **threshold voltage** and **initial membrane potential** thus indicating that the neuron has non-zero firing probability even without any incoming spikes. Further, the amount of change in membrane potential can be fine-tuned by adjusting voltage levels of VP_DN and VN_UP .

The random walk step size eventually controls the stochasticity of neuron behavior: optimizing this behavior is way to **maximize performance of RBM algorithm**.

FIG. 4(b) shows the experimental result of **MNIST on-chip training**. The 100-image inference was performed with 100 trained images after training of 100 images per epoch, resulting in 93.0% maximum accuracy.

The 10,000-image test is trained with 2,000 randomly chosen images per epoch from 60,000 training images and it scored the best accuracy of 73.57%. The degradation of accuracy with an increasing number of test images can be explained by the issues with **analog neuron circuits** and **synaptic devices**: (i) **PCM** as a **synaptic device** exhibits an **abrupt conductance change** in the **RESET process** which cause 'undesirable influences' in weight update. To mitigate this, **pulse width** of $STPD_WL_Gm$ is reduced in [**data phase**] and $STPD_WL_Gp$ in [**model phase**] so that RESET occurs less frequently than SET.

TUNABLE PULSE CHARACTERISTICS

Results for configurable pulse timings: TO RECAP As the pulse characteristics for unit cell operation, include STDP_WL_Gp, STDP_WL_Gm and STDP_BL are tunable (FIG. 2(d) – 2(f)), there is precise control over update timings of Gp and Gm, by time correlatively performing SET and RESET programming. By combining them, the modified STDP is implemented, a spike-based local weight update rule in RCM eCD (FIG. 2(g)).

CONFIGURABLE SPIKE TIME DEPENDENT PLASTICITY

(g) Configurable STDP_WL and its STDP function.

This means the adverse impact of abrupt RESET is alleviated by reducing RESET probability through pulse width CTRL.

Also, the use of 'PCM Refresh Method' improves accuracy further.

The algorithmic solutions indicate that (TABLE 1: First SNN on-chip training demo with fully) silicon-integrated neuromorphic hardware (circuits and large scale > 1 million PCM synaptic devices implementing a well-established practical ML algorithm RBM) has the potential for further accuracy improvements.

RECONSTRUCTION FROM ENTERING POISSON SPIKE TRAINS

(c) Regeneration

FIG. 4(c) Hardware demonstration of pattern recognition 4(c) scheme of pattern regeneration 4(d) regeneration results of 0-9 digits.

FULLY HARDWARE-BASED MNIST IMAGE CLASSIFICATION WITH

(I) ON-CHIP LEARNING (II) PATTERN REGENERATION: FROM ON-CHIP TRAINED HARDWARE SPIKING RBM NETWORK

A well-trained RBM network can reconstruct an originally trained pattern based on incomplete input pattern. Generative capability allows spike trains of label neurons reconstruction by receiving Poisson spike trains of input image in the inference step.

For instance, by entering the Poisson spike trains of an incomplete image with 'true label' results in a complete image (FIG. 4(c)). By screening $\frac{1}{2}$ of MNIST image, 236 neurons among 524 data neurons are externally triggered, remaining data neurons used to read

reconstructed spike trains. Performed after 100-image on-chip training with 90% accuracy.

CRIMINAL EVIDENCE

(d)

FIG. 4(d) shows reconstructed MNIST image (from 30 different original images) experimentation confirmed that hardware is successful in implementing spiking RBM demonstrating pattern recognition capability and pattern regeneration based on generative artificial neuron network.

IBM TRUENORTH CHIP (ANCIENT REPLICA) SAMPLES

A Self-Driving Robot Using Deep Convolutional Neural Networks on Neuromorphic Hardware

A

NS1e board with TrueNorth chip

B

TrueNorth Core Architecture

7.1 LAW EVIDENCE EXAMINATION: COMPUTER (WI-FI) PROGRAMMABLE SYNAPSE-YEN (CRIMINALLY ACCURATE VERSION)

7.1 Programmable Synapse-YEN Model: Organ Stack of Japan (Criminal Technical Analysis)

7.1. NEUROMOPRHIC PRODUCT TYPE: IBM

[IBM JOURNAL \(TOKYO\): NEUROMORPHIC SYSTEM \(IBM JAPANESE & KOREAN\)](#)

UNDER DATA PROTECTION LAW

7.2.3. IBM Journal 1.1.3: Neuromorphic Devices and Architectures For Nex-gen Cognitive Computing (#KOHJI HOSOKAWA & OTHERS) (2017)

‘Neu-‘ sounds: short-for Neu-romorph-‘mann’

In the IBM (Tokyo) Journal / Conference in Baltimore MD USA, “Neuromorphic Devices and Architectures For Next-Generation Cognitive Computing”³⁹, published by New York City: IEEE International Symposium on Circuits and Systems (ISCAS), in FIG. 1(a) The Von Neumann (COPIED: ANCIENT REPLICA) architecture calls for data (both operands and operations) to move back and forth along a bus between a dedicated Central Processing Unit (CPU) and memory.

In contrast, IBM (Tokyo) proposed FIG. 1(b) a non-Von Neumann architecture potentially reduce the time and energy spent moving data around, by performing computations at the data.

³⁹ Harvard Reference: CONFERENCE

Kohji Hosokawa and others. *Neuromorphic Devices And Architectures For Next-Generation Cognitive Computing*. Baltimore, MD, U.S.A., 2017. New York City: IEEE International Symposium on Circuits and Systems (ISCAS).

A. POTENTIAL FOR COMPETITIVE CLASSIFICATION ACCURACIES
 MULTI-LAYER PERCEPTRON

FIG. 2 In a multi-layer perception, each layer's neurons are connected to every neuron of the next (and previous) layer but there are no intra-layer connections.

For forward evaluation of such a network, neuron excitations x_i are multiplied by

the appropriate weight w_{ij} accumulated over all relevant weights and drive

the next layer excitation x_j after application of nonlinearity $f(\cdot)$.

The neurons of input layer is driven by input data (pixels from successive images from MNIST dataset cropped to 22 x 24). The number of output neurons corresponds to number of classes in dataset (e.g. 10) and their excitation is used to classify which digit was presented.

Previously, a modified weight-update rule compatible with NVM+selector (MOSFET) crossbar arrays and experimentally demonstrated a three-layer fully connected DNN (e.g. perceptron FIG. 2) containing 164,885 2-PCM synapses.

This modified weight-update rule did not degrade the high 'test' (generalization) accuracies that a three-layer DNN can deliver – after software-based TRAINING with backpropagation algorithm – on a subset (5000 examples) of the MNIST database of handwritten digits.

However, both 'training' and 'test' accuracies achieved in original mixture of hard-soft-ware experiments did not exceed 82-83%. Thus, after numerous experiments and tolerancing simulations, the root cause of problems being introduced by:

- (i) nonlinearity and
- (ii) asymmetry of conductance response of NVM devices.

TEST ACCURACY: EXPERIMENTAL

FIG. 3 shows measured training accuracy plotted for three-layer perceptron implemented with 164,885 hardware-based synapses.

All weight operations took place on 500 x 661 array of mushroom-cell PCM devices.

Also, plotted is a computer simulation of the exact same neural network, showing that device imperfections and other parameters were accurately extracted, allowing both precise matching to and tolerancing of experimental data.

TEST ACCURACY: SIMULATED

FIG. 4 shows a deep neural network implemented with synaptic devices exhibiting a linear conductance response of large dynamic range, classification accuracies easily reach the accuracies that this neural network attains when trained on a conventional GPU or CPU with a test accuracy reaching 94% when using 5,000 images from the MNIST dataset for training and 97% when all 60,000 images are used.

In experiments, used 'Occasional RESET' procedure to compensate for:

- (i) asymmetry (of conductance response of NVM devices) between abruptness of PCM RESET pulses and gentle conductance increases of PCM partial-SET pulses.

The studies on impact of device variability on NVM-based DNN showed:

- (i) high resiliency to random effects e.g. device variability, yield and stochasticity
- (ii) but high sensitivity to gradient effects e.g. device nonlinearity and asymmetry, which steer all synaptic weights

Showed that NVM exhibited:

- (i) small, symmetrical and equal conductance increases and decreases e.g. bi-directional NVM with gentle linear conductance response of high dynamic range
- (ii) nearly indistinguishable (in terms of correct classification of MNIST handwritten digits dataset) from conventional s/w based implementation and on-chip accelerator composed of such ideal devices deliver same high classification accuracies (FIG. 4) but only when NVM conductance update scheme avoided encoding low magnitude weights as conductance pairs

such weights are more difficult for network to increase in magnitude since synapses are sitting at edges of G-diamond where implementation of synaptic weight changes requested by network is significantly less effective.

B. IMPACT OF CONDUCTANCE RESPONSE

CONDUCTANCE RESPONSE: SET AND RESET

FIG. 5 The conductance response for RESET / depression-MAGENTA and SET / potentiation-GREEN can be plotted as:

EITHER: 5(i) Conductance (G) as a Function of the Number of Programming Pulses
OR

5(ii) As a 'jump-table' which plots Change-in-Conductance (ΔG) as a Function of Conductance (G).

Even if these conductance responses are linear, (iii) **asymmetry** between SET and RESET causes performance to fall off steeply. However, since the **downstream neuron 'knows'**:

WHETHER it should program (i) a partial SET or (ii) partial RESET programming pulse, it can partially compensate for this asymmetry by firing EITHER fewer RESET pulses or more SET pulses.

Diagram 5(c) shows simulated data on a linear scale (horizontally).

Previously (the first paper) introduced a 'jump table' concept, to enable modelling of stochastic and conductance dependent response of PCM devices to partial SET pulses. This approach is extended to study various artificially constructed jump-tables to study the impact of asymmetry in conductance response of fully bi-directional NVM devices.

It is assumed that the conductance responses were both linear but were (in fact) asymmetric (e.g. differed in slope, FIG. 5(a)), the step-size of depression (RESET) jump-table is target (FIG. 5(b)) since the RESET conductance response is much steeper than SET. Thus, findings showed that even small asymmetries can cause classification accuracy to fall steeply (solid curves filled symbols in (FIG. 5(c))).

However, when programming pulses were fired, each downstream neuron knows whether it is attempting SET or RESET, because neuron knows sign of backpropagation correction, δ . By firing commensurately fewer RESET pulses (or more SET pulses, or by appropriately adjusting the SET/RESET) voltages, this neuron can thus 'correct' for steeper RESET response (dotted curves with open symbols (FIG. 5(c))). Thus, findings showed that this approach can compensate for even moderately asymmetric conductance response although not for severe asymmetries.

CIRCUIT NEEDS

FORWARD AND BACK PROPAGATION: DEEP NEURAL NETWORK

FIG. 6(a) To implement Forward Propagation of a Deep Neural Network implemented on a crossbar array, the multiply-accumulate MAC operation occurs in individual synaptic device reads (Ohm's law, implementing

$w_{ij} \times x_i^A$) and the current summation along each column-line (Kirchhoff's law, implementing the sum across all i).

Peripheral circuitry within the 'downstream' neuron must implement the nonlinear squashing function, $f(\cdot)$.

(b) In reverse propagation, the peripheral circuitry within the 'upstream' neuron must multiply the currents (summed along rows to implement the multiply-accumulate MAC of δ error terms) by the derivative of the original squashing function, as evaluated at

the original upstream neuron excitation, x_i^A . The Piece-Wise Linear (PWL) function is similar to $\tanh(\cdot)$, but much simpler to describe and implement.

Forward propagation of a neural network (FIG. 6(a)) computes the neuron activations of the next layer by combining activations of previous layer and the intervening synaptic weights.

After multiply-accumulate MAC operation, it is important to apply a nonlinear squashing function at each neuron – such as hyperbolic tangent activation function ‘tanh’ otherwise the entire multi-layer network will have the same processing power as a large linear equation. Since ‘tanh’ require large silicon area, it is proposed that the simpler Piece-Wise Linear (PWL) function be used. (FIG. 6(a))

During reverse propagation, it is not the non-linear squashing function but its derivative, evaluated at the original neuron excitation that must be applied to the result of the multiply-accumulate MAC operation (integrated along the crossbar array but in an orthogonal direction). To avoid computing the exact derivative of the tanh function, a simple step-function derivative with only two distinct states are used (FIG. 6(b)).

In addition to nonlinear squashing function and derivative, the required range of distinct neuron activation values could be significantly reduced. (i) For a digital implementation, this would reduce the number of bits, the required local storage and resolution of related digital-to-analog and analog-to-digital conversion circuits. (ii) For analog implementation, smaller range of activation values reduces the required resolution between analog voltage levels and/or time-steps. Findings revealed that crossbar NVM arrays are well-suited for implementation of backpropagation because of prevalence of multiply-accumulate MAC operations. However, they require highly parallel and area-efficient neuron circuitry at periphery of array. Thus, circuitry designs must have sufficient accurate functionality for applying (i) nonlinear squashing functions and (ii) their derivatives during forward and reverse evaluation.

FIG. 9 PROPOSED DNN CHIP ARCHITECTURE

FIG. 9 PROPOSED DNN CHIP ARCHITECTURE: Each NVM array contains a (i) dense grid of synaptic connections (ii) surrounded by peripheral circuitry to implement input neurons (on the West side) and output neurons (On the South side). These neurons contain circuitry assigned to individual rows and columns, circuitry shared by a number of neighbouring neurons and global support circuitry.

A flexible routing network conveys chip inputs to device arrays from the edge of the chip and interconnects various arrays to implement multi-layer neural networks. FIG. 9 shows the conceptual scheme of an on-chip learning architecture for the acceleration of neural network training with analog non-volatile memory (similar to TrueNorth chip), the architecture is composed of a large number of identical array-blocks connected by a flexible routing network.

Each array-block represents a large NVM device array, size 512 x 512 or 1024 x 1024 synaptic unit-cells. A unit-cell composed of two NVM conductances would correspond to arrays of 512 x1024 or 1024 x 2048 NVM devices.

In addition to interconnecting various array-blocks to implement multi-layer neural networks, (ii) flexible routing network has two additional tasks. First, must convey chip inputs example data (e.g. pixels of a training image), example labels (e.g. ground truth classification of training image) and weight overrides from edge of the chip to the device arrays. Second, routing network is needed to carry chip outputs – e.g. inferred classifications and updated weights from arrays to edge of the chip. While chip inputs and outputs need to be directed to only a small subset of arrays on the chip (corresponds to locations of input / output neurons), weight overrides / updated weights would potentially sent to / received from every single array on-chip (routing requirement).

Each NVM array-block has input neurons (West side of each array) and output neurons (South side) connected with a dense grid of synaptic connections.

Peripheral circuitry is divided into circuitry assigned to individual rows and columns, circuitry shared between a number of neighbouring rows and columns and support circuitry.

7.1 LAW EVIDENCE EXAMINATION: COMPUTER (WI-FI) PROGRAMMABLE SYNAPSE-YEN (CRIMINALLY ACCURATE VERSION)

7.1 Programmable Synapse-YEN Model: Organ Stack of Japan (Criminal Technical Analysis)

7.1. NEUROMOPRHIC PRODUCT TYPE: IBM

[IBM JOURNAL \(TOKYO\): NEUROMORPHIC SYSTEM \(IBM JAPANESE & KOREAN\)](#)

UNDER DATA PROTECTION LAW

7.2.4. IBM Journal: Fully On-Chip MAC at 14 nm Enabled by Accurate Row-Wise Programming Of PCM-Based Weights And Parallel Vector-Transport in Duration-Format

The IBM Journal, “Fully On-Chip MAC @14 nm enabled by accurate row-wise programming of PCM-based WT and parallel vector transport in duration format”⁴⁰ in FIG. 1 (a) and (b) shows IBM’s 14-nm inference chip and micrograph.

⁴⁰ Harvard Reference: CONFERENCE

Atsuya Okazaki, Kohji Hosokawa, Akiyo Nomura, Takeo Yasuda, Masatoshi Ishii and others. (2018) Full on-Chip MAC at 14 nm Enabled By Accurate Row-Wise Programming Of PCM-Based Weights and Parallel Vector-Transport In Duration-Format. In: *IEEE 2021 Symposium on VLSI Technology*, Kyoto, Japan. New York City: IEEE.

FIG. 1(c) Functional blocks include input LP, output LP, PCM tiles. Duration transport across tiles using a 2-D parallel-signal mesh is also shown.

FIG. 1(d) CDFs of bit errors show highly accurate across-chip duration transport for travel distances up to six tiles.

FIG. 1(e) Transmission Electron Microscope image of a PCM device integrated in 14-nm back end.

FIG. 1(i) Measurements using modes described in (g) and (h) are well-correlated.

FIG. 1(f) Each DNN weight is encoded using four PCM devices.

FIG. 1(h) Single-device ('backdoor') sense-amp read circuitry measure device conductance in μS .

FIG. 1(g) Row-wise read/write (left) during programming uses the same circuit paths (and associated non-idealities) experienced during full inference (right).

THE JUDGMENT (SHORT): THE NATION JAPAN'S LEGAL EVIDENCE

The Japanese had already expressly stated by Japanese act and affirmatively expressed their preference for cash over computerized e-yen i.e. NOT recognize electronic digits as legal money (in Either: tokenized or a/c based) clearly stated by the BOJ governor as well.

JAPANESE ACCURATE HIGHLIGHT / (-'SINGA'-CEMENT-WAR ID) INSIDE PHOENIX HERE PINPOINT:

Second, diversification of payment service providers is likely to continue. A recent development of the cashless society seems to be led by **NBPSPs such as Bigtechs, Fintechs,** retailers and transport companies, rather than banks. For example, funds transfer service providers, typically named **"XYZ Pay,"** and prepaid payment instruments issuers, such as **retailers and transport companies,** issue digital money that differs from traditional cash and bank deposits, and the use of such digital money seems to be expanding. Diversification of NBPSP is short form for Nonbank Payment Service Providers

(-'SINGA'-CEMENT-WAR ID) STACKING 'OC' WORLD BAN (PRESS: 000 X 60 – 100 – 1-LOCATION) = CHANGE TO LANDED PHOENIX GRANITE WLC

WCS PASTE = World Cities' Scam, ILLEGAL INDIANS RINGGIT-building-RUPEE: paste ANTI-GLYPH

Here, despite the attempt to force OR dupe the Japanese people, the preference is strong and clear answer: CASH

LAW EVIDENCE INSERT PHOTO: Japanese Express Preference for CASH (Implicit: electronic NOT Recognized as Legal)

JAPANESE VOTE: EXPRESSLY AND ACT / BACKED BY JAPAN-GOVERNOR special cases such as Sweden. In Japan, people using cashless payments seem to have increased since the introduction of the "Point Reward Project for Consumers using Cashless Payment" by the government in October 2019. However, at the same time, the outstanding amount of cash in circulation has also increased by two percent annually. The **preference for cash remains surprisingly strong.** Having said that, with the emergence of new services and

This document is written by the Deputy Governor of Japan:

Deputy Governor of the Bank of Japan

Deputy Governor of the Bank of Japan

JUDGEMENT APPENDIX: COMPUTE DRAGON 2

INFRA-(INGESTION: co-vax food meat + water)-CHIP RF KILL

This caption that PM Abe being shot:

The general report was that PM Shinzo Abe, Japan's longest-serving leader. The key locations in the crime scene include speaking in front of Kintetsu Railway's Yamato-Saidaiji Station. He collapsed after two shots were heard and was rushed to the hospital with blood seen on his

	<p>shirt⁴¹. The Japanese New report can be found here, Available: https://english.kyodonews.net/news/2022/07/a0285cdcc6d2-breaking-news-ex-pm-abe-attacked-by-unidentified-man-on-road-in-japan.htm</p> <p>Nara Medical University pronounced PM Abe dead at 5.03pm. The report stated that the wound reached his heart which caused the blood loss.</p> <p>First thought is: several named globally blacklisted universities in Medicine / Public Health / Lawless faculties / Political Security faculties duping politicians and military with illegal lab-made mRNA CO-VID and WB loans roll-out to CO-VAX CHIP wifi frequency bandwidth e-shock causing organ damage / murder.</p> <p>The YouTube Video, Available: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=sgUoHB7Wsiw&t=11s</p>
	<p>PM JAPAN DEAD OR 'DEAD'</p> <p>This caption that PM Abe being shot, then dead @hospital is vague and a general accepted notion that he was assassinated. I give some reasons why it is considered vague and a largely unexplained death:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. He could be wounded, then Radio Frequency tested (electrocution / frequency bandwidth tested in conjunction with 'Hospital-series of Patents discussed in Section 3: Sprint-Tech BIS pilot test subjects in New York illegal district containers of nations' loot, ROTH fake 'actor' 'Hospital'-'google Map-Cyclist heartbeat sensor' Patent and other CDC profitable patented process of 'diagnosis, treatment' etc premeditated since 1999 in conjunction with dupe militaries PLUS 3 PLOT and Wuhan 100PLUS Military 'sports' discussed in Section 2: 'Global Time Step'. (Softbank hotspot outlets as a new form of electronic banks plausible intent to replace physical banks (electronic digits transformation) were located around prime areas of tokyo whilst targeting T-Mobile as potential merge / IBM on Nasdaq @ billion electronic digits range). 2. Prior was the G20 meet: (like the military meet set-up) other counterparts Donald Trump (arrested jailed) and other PM-genocided / suicided on TV with the army. Other P-CARD that fought CO-VAX were dead.

⁴¹ (2022) Former Japan PM Abe Dies After Being Shot During Election speech. Kyodo News. 9 July. Available: <https://english.kyodonews.net/news/2022/07/a0285cdcc6d2-breaking-news-ex-pm-abe-attacked-by-unidentified-man-on-road-in-japan.html>

	<p>3. How did he die exactly and who has the motive for murder (as Japan's longest serving leader to be shot and also a highly capable global leader)? One prominent IBM-CHIP type resides in Nara.</p>				
	<p>As my Neuromorphic Law information is only available now (post-dead Abe of G20 review for suspicious characters if any in The Judgement) in connection with the pre-meditated CO-VAX CHIP (Copied Ancient Replica: GLYPH BIBLE CODE GROUP and BINARY CODE of BA-BI-LUN WHEEL), this assertion that he was assassination has to be re-examined in light of IBM-INTEL WIFI remotely programmable CO-VAX or without meaning in-food water micro-mmwave chip etc ingested.</p> <p><u>IEEE CHIP IBM TOKYO (Authentic Japanese: NO MOTIVE)</u></p> <p>Also, IBM Tokyo (IEEE CHIP) is active in publications in this Neuromorphic CHIP area so it is possible the Japanese government has knowledge of such technology.</p> <p>Otherwise, he may be intentionally murdered by PERP-ID: e.g. WB co-vax-chip (Indian recruits: Washington D.C.: Mumtha-Muslim replacement) ADB NASDAQ IBM UK PEDO-banks-in PERPs (since already mention of SOFTBANK even manipulated by:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. (perhaps, convenient usage of term: 'colonial UK actors' i.e. UK arm ('ARM' product') and b. NASDAQ being capable of 'risk-amounts' c. (public reports of) SOFTBANK (THURAYA LOGO) exceeding that of even the 'Japanese' gov) + 1-European state: <p>Also, maybe manipulation of COMPUTE MONITOR screen numbers.</p>				
	<p>CRIMINAL FACULTIES:</p> <p>Further details in The Judgment: usage of 'Thuraya' LOGO on Ringgit-ATM-universities Uage of word stacking 'sg' beyond PLOTS PLUS 3 + USMCA PLOT = NORDIC-EUR-SWISS PLOT = TERMINATION = Liquidation + relocate. (COMPUTE: \$AMT)</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="448 1535 1568 1858"> <tr> <td data-bbox="448 1535 743 1675"></td> <td data-bbox="743 1535 1568 1675"> <p><i>BEYOND</i> stacking sgd (1965 PLOT) (Ringgit-ATM-pap 'pm'-injected with sg-military on Media-Corp that requires satellite: Thuraya etc)</p> </td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="448 1675 743 1858"> <p>ILLEGAL USAGE OF WORD 'sg' X 60: INVASION (on death penalty) + FRAUD.</p> </td> <td data-bbox="743 1675 1568 1858"> <p>Satellite: Thuraya (Emirates Exchange + Ringgit-ATM-connected THURAYA): PLUS 3 PLOT (Jap pm-dead)</p> </td> </tr> </table>		<p><i>BEYOND</i> stacking sgd (1965 PLOT) (Ringgit-ATM-pap 'pm'-injected with sg-military on Media-Corp that requires satellite: Thuraya etc)</p>	<p>ILLEGAL USAGE OF WORD 'sg' X 60: INVASION (on death penalty) + FRAUD.</p>	<p>Satellite: Thuraya (Emirates Exchange + Ringgit-ATM-connected THURAYA): PLUS 3 PLOT (Jap pm-dead)</p>
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K XX 1 (Closed = ringgit-'sg'-x PUTHU 'dg'-x' = compute total upload = relocate inside Malaya-land)

K XX 2 (Closed = ringgit-ntu = ret. keys)

PUTHU (INDIA) self-titled 'gov-tech' 'DG'X' death penalty = TERMINATED (COMPUTE PRE-MED TOTAL: \$X)

LHL (son of Malaysian-LKY: RINGGIT-ATM employee) after Illegal Indian invade MIT + USA-13.

Other SATELLITE named: INMARSAT (Suri Rajeev) + VIASAT (Guru) + AIRBUS. (Further details: Appendix to The Judgment.)

Other: WORLD-genocide committed SPACE-X-INDIA.

NOT 'sg' since inception 1965 PLOT: is INVASION X 60 – 100 Y on death penalty: Ringgit-ATM + SATELLITE (Name-list: INMARSAT + VIA-SAT + THURAYA + AIRBUS + INDIA with EM LOGO illegal Indians Singh conman X 60 (Fraudsters: TEMASEK, Ringgit-Lee-Rubber + Ringgit-ATM criminals.)

Thuraya LOGO on Soft-bank LOGO:

1. If one examines soft-bank outlets: it is inside Tokyo.
2. Softbank products = covers Ali-pay (Ali-rezar Mahanfar: Google, Space-X, Microsoft, Amazon Cloud)
3. in conjunction with AIRBUS (at @ IISS-CHIP-MAN @ Rajaratnam (illegal Indian X 60), THURAYA is listed SATELLITE (invasion sg coastal + inland) with INMARSAT + VIA-SAT

4. Pay replicated format: appears USA-13 Fed-pay Fed-wire Paypal (Space-X-India (TEXAS)) + GRAB-Pay-later (featured in Soft-bank products) & Pay-Now (TEMASEK-GUPTA-india) + CN (Fast-pay: Meta-Pay-Collapse drawings @ MBSands 'Vapourization' WTC-9/11 Insurance' WordPress-Indian @ CJEU) Location: sg-chinese, although ringgit-ATM linked THURAYA (m1-Manjot Singh ports: closed to disconnect connectivity + Ringgit-'sg'-x-'s'ia link ILLEGAL TEMASEK + ILLEGAL LTA (HALIMAH INFRA-VOID BILL replicated format x no. nations + INFRA-TOM: INVASION Indranee Rajah Mangrove Swamp CN + Infra-sg) Ringgit-pap LIM HUI HUA (fake 'napier-illegal Indian x 60 criminal record) TEMBUSU CN invade = TERMINATED ret. \$Trillions + FB-functions traffick n attack: sells Fast-pay invade CN.
5. BALA (ringgit-pap + India) genocide 'ny' un. Repeat usage: Mumtha + Kamala-Ravi Menon—FRAUD.
6. Kamala trace origin: CONFIRMED by Nikkei Asia as India NOT American 'Harris'. ('Menon' = India, 'Desker' = India)

This is evidence behind INVASION of Japan (matching that of stacking sgd 1965 PLOT into RINGGIT-ATM severely disabled CARESHIELD (Great-Eastern: ANTI-CN + ANTI-sgd-chinese (PHOENIX) = OBAMA CARE (CARES-ACT: Chip-genocide USA-13) **BEYOND PLOTS** USMCA PLOT + PLUS 3 PLOT + NORDIC-EUR-SWISS PLOT = TERMINATED

Complicit usage of illegal Indians X 60 EM LOGO MILITARY @ Rajaratnam (consistent criminal record x50) (Ringgit-ATM-pap: INFRA-TOM stacking + genocide-'sg'hospital (disqualified M.D.) since inception 1965 PLOT: ANTI-Malaya Chinese + PHOENIX + **BEYOND PLOTS** + All ports-DISCONNECT-SATELLITE TOMS LISTED.

LEGAL ACTION (PRELIMINARY):

1. Close all Ringgit-NTU + NUS emails: BLOCK ALL emails into ntu + rajaratnam + nus

	<p>2. Close all emails = 1-Indian 1-singh in PTE SCH inside sg. (American Euro Swiss AUD) = open in native white states only. If fraud usage of country names 'sg' in conjunction with another nation's name (Indian Traffick), ret. all Indian singh = India.</p>
	<p>Due to the genocidal content of 'climate' weapons: (SATELLITE RF), TCFD disbanded (12 Oct 2023).</p> <p>FSB asked IFRS Foundation to take-over (monitoring of co.) instead.</p>
	<p>Warning to all Co. NOT to pose with any Illegal India-man + receive any 'climate' award = is INVASION.</p>
	<p>Other genocidal evidence (related to SATELLITE-ID): Ringgit-nus-ntu (global blacklisted)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Public 'Health' / 'Medicine' / INFRA-mRNA co-vid Indian Cancer: Co-vax Chip (WHO-Margaret Chan with Heng Swee Keat: Patented process replicated. Claim: CDC) 2. Global self-titled 'gov' as perp: AI-KILL CHESTER pose + WEF RESET co-vax CHIP + over FB-META collapse drawings (SATELLITE) 3. BALA (INDIA – can suggest origin SATELLITE) genocide speech in UN NY + AI-KILL Russia Ukraine: impose sanctions (with Ukraine invited @ Rajaratnam EM LOGO MILITARY X 60 illegal Indians CONMAN @ IISS-CHIP-man (progression of Singh-CAD + India-invite: prior-CHIP-inject Lee & CHIP-Military in order to CHIP-genocide. 4. Self-titled 'global' 'health' 'governance' Abeyet selling FIN(-ancing of Co-Vax Chip) as solution to mRNA co-vid etc. (SATELLITE: RF-KILL)

		<p>5. EM LOGO MILITARY @ Rajaratnam (consistent criminal record) x no. stash MILITARY USD CAD NZD AUD SGD HKD (PLUS 3 PLOT + USMCA PLOT + NORDIC-EUR-SWISS PLOT) currencies v Rupee (INFRA-TOM (ATM-TOM) + Rockefeller SATELLITE-TOM:LISTED.</p>
	<p>1-singh 1-indian (lecturer student) inside sg = ret. keys to ATM-ocbc (FOR RECORD) = ret. India.</p> <p>(chan chun sing BILINGUILISM THEFT \$M into ringgit-ocbc = closed ret. malaya + pte ed closed) = TERMINATED</p> <p>All RINGGIT-min-RINGGIT-stat board criminals = compute X 60 = ret. malaya. indians singh = Ret. India.</p>	
	<p>LISTED SATELLITES (COMMITTED INVASION)</p> <p>c. assortment of 'sudden' emergence SATELLITE LISTED COMMITTED: INMARSAT + VIASAT + THURAYA + AIBUS + (VADENBERG SPACE-FORCE-INDIA: CALIFORNIA) + SPACE-X-INDIA (TEXAS) (RINGGIT-ATM: stolen stash ('shoeboxes') stacking sgd X 60 – 100 Y + 1ST STASH from PUNGGOL-WHOLE ISLAND = ret. landed properties = PHOENIX ROCKET + PHOENIX DOLLAR BANKING EXT- + PHOENIX GRANITE WLC etc)</p> <p>d. Rajaratnam PLUS 3 PLOTS + USMCA PLOT + NORDIC-EUR-SWISS PLOT: EM LOGO Sri Lanka conman + INSOL-Shanmugam: Davinder Singh + Cavinder Bull (WB) + Susil Nair (ILLEGAL consistent criminal record (AUTO-BAR Indian IMPOSTER: CONMAN MONEY + touch land using LAW-LESS paperwork AUTO-VOID EM LOGO MILITARY GUN DOWN)' 'Drew-Napier'-India AUTO-BAR since inception 1965 PLOT: INFRA-TOM TEMBUSU CN GUN DOWN = TERMINATED.</p>	
	<p>PERP-ID: chip-genocide + INFRA-Tom</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Bis FRAUDSTERS (no such address; no assets liquidate = COMPUTE FRAUD) + WB (co-vax chip: \$5 x WHO-WEF 'investors' / 'trustees' then plausibly use word 'ny' (part of WCS = World Cities' scam = posters on BNY MELLON with CLEAR roll-out of GO: Infra-co-vax-micro-CHIP + INVASION CHIP-genocide PRODUCT not available inside 'NY': pilot test 'ny' by Indians) + AIIB (INFRA-Tom) 2. Genocidal task force: commit systematic crime 	

	<p>3. Indian used to dupe: Tier 1 Tier 2 as 'global' 'tech' chair (no tech inside tech brochure): Hyperledger fabric co-vax chip. (Pilot tested: injection X 100PLUS + EM LOGO MILITARY x 60) in conjunction with</p> <p>4. BIS con-site fake drawings: fake 'phase tests' usage of 'world cities' names X 100PLUS + WB ('bearer bonds') WTC-collapse repeat (of buildings on circuit board) hence can plausibly explain the WCS = World Cities' scam e.g. 'sg' 'ny' + other world cities (SATELLITE CO. + TELCOM CO. on death penalty: kill-off post-rob suggestive e.g. Indian T-Mobile / IBM 'arm' stock list trading (Thuraya LOGO on soft-bank)</p>
	<p>Other considerations:</p> <p>The combined looted gold (of GLYPH STATES) was taken-off the Japanese after execution (can be another motive) for 'forgotten' debt (and subsequently link to bearer bonds 1. Fraud 2. Counterfeit 3. Vapourisation WTC 9/11 (prior to maturity) 4. Followed by WTC insurance (which will lead to pre-crime): Infra-TOM-INVASION AIB + WB (Infra-co-vax-CHIP) = TERMINATED.</p>
	<p>Finally, he may not be dead but 'dead'.</p>
	<p>ABSENTEES AT (UNLAWFUL WORLD ECONOMIES' THEFT + FORUM = CONSITE) WEF 2022: noticeable 3. absentees: Russia / China / Japan-Abe (dead)⁴².</p>
<p>LEGAL ANALYSIS:</p> <p>G20 = rRNA co-vid PLOT (fabricated allegedly by 'Rockefeller')</p> <p>The BOJ: something wrong (Economics of Japan)</p>	<p>PHOTO EVIDENCE OF G20 meet: Japan's longest serving Leader</p> <p>Video Available:</p>

⁴² Assassination List available for discussion: The Judgment Document includes group 'suicide' over TV Singapore, U.S. cabinet 'gov', connection with PEDO-banks and criminal tech-drugs-co. behind.

JUDGEMENT APPENDIX: COMPUTE PHOENIX(-DOLLAR, PHOENIX-LANDED ORIGINAL + CEMENT WAR ID X 60 'SINGA'-MALAYSIAN-PRESS: 000) X 60 SATELLITE KEYS s/w RET.

CHIP-GENOCIDE: X 60 1965 PLOT + PHOENIX BEYOND: PLUS 3 DRAGONS PLOTS = TERMINATED

This is a direct message (of PERP's secret intention) to murder the WHOLE OF Ringgit-'SG'D (NOT PHOENIX):

1965 PLOT:

1. (Malaya-Illegal Indians-LAW-LESS: AUTO-BAR from inception + AUTO-VOID paperwork worthless) Illegal Indians-set-up 'party' ask-money: INFRA-TOM cheated Flooding PHOENIX LAND with Malaysians stacking 'sg'd' (FRAUD notes) into RINGGIT-ATM
2. CHIP-war crime means 'MURDER (EM LOGO) MILITARY' X 100PLUS': There was a footage of Singapore military getting CO-VAX CHIP on public TV alongside Lee:

EM LOGO MILITARY (Malaya-Illegal Indians) *BEYOND* PLOTS = TERMINATED

TENTATIVE Culprits: TV = here is

3. MediaCorp LOGO: Ringgit-ATM + SATELLITE-TOM
= TEMASEK: ret. \$X

SATELLITE COMMITTED (IN-LAND + COASTAL):

4. SATELLITE: Thuraya(h)(m1) Thuraya(h) LOGO ON NUS (NOT SG)
5. SATELLITE: Via-sat + Inmarsat + Airbus + Space-X-India chip-genocide

REPEAT OFFENCE 'INTENT': beyond PLOTS = TERMINATED

	<p>e.g. INFRA-CHIP-genocide + EM LOGO X100 MILITARY + INFRA-'touch land'-ports-DISCONNECT unable to steal</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="483 331 1567 751"> <tr> <td data-bbox="483 331 927 380"></td> <td data-bbox="927 331 1567 380"></td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="483 380 927 520">INFRA-CHIP-genocide</td> <td data-bbox="927 380 1567 520">GLYPH TEXT OVERWRITE DNA (chipped + binary programmed from outer-space)</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="483 520 927 569">EM LOGO X100 MILITARY</td> <td data-bbox="927 520 1567 569"></td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="483 569 927 659">INFRA-'touch land'-ports-DISCONNECT</td> <td data-bbox="927 569 1567 659">PHOENIX ROCKET</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="483 659 927 751">INFRA-TOM (e.g. stacking fraud notes into ATM-TOM)</td> <td data-bbox="927 659 1567 751">PHOENIX DOLLAR</td> </tr> </table> <p>PERP-Intent = Indian opium = to kill CN (GLYPH) = ret. (remove ALL) out of WHOLE OF ASIA (LIE X 60 to low IQ = Glyph states)</p>			INFRA-CHIP-genocide	GLYPH TEXT OVERWRITE DNA (chipped + binary programmed from outer-space)	EM LOGO X100 MILITARY		INFRA-'touch land'-ports-DISCONNECT	PHOENIX ROCKET	INFRA-TOM (e.g. stacking fraud notes into ATM-TOM)	PHOENIX DOLLAR
INFRA-CHIP-genocide	GLYPH TEXT OVERWRITE DNA (chipped + binary programmed from outer-space)										
EM LOGO X100 MILITARY											
INFRA-'touch land'-ports-DISCONNECT	PHOENIX ROCKET										
INFRA-TOM (e.g. stacking fraud notes into ATM-TOM)	PHOENIX DOLLAR										
	<p>Stacking 'oc'- Fraud-'invest' TEMASEK- CEMENT WAR ID-TV genocide, War Crime against 'singa'- Malaysian-MEDIA-CORP X 60 CRIMINAL ACT ON TV + CEMENT X 60 STACKING 'OC' FLOOD-IN SHOEBOXES NO CLAIM OVER: OVER ROBBED LAND (DISTRICT-BY-DISTRICT: COMPUTE STASH PER BUILDING) & CHIP-GENOCIDE + NO CLAIM OVER: CANNOT USE WORD 'ASIA' GLYPH STATES-PP PER LANDED + WRONG DEFINITION + 'SINGA'-BEYOND PLOTS criminal content (error or fraud) + genocidal content against WHOLE OF 'ASIA' BEYOND PHOENIX-(districts ret. all) STACKING 'OC'.</p> <p>Malaysian-Stacking 'oc'-Fraud-TEMASEK MEDIA-CORP X 60 CRIMINAL ACT ON TV + CEMENT X 60 STACKING 'OC' FLOOD-IN SHOEBOXES NO CLAIM OVER: OVER ROBBED LAND (DISTRICT-BY-DISTRICT: COMPUTE STASH PER BUILDING) & CHIP-GENOCIDE + NO CLAIM OVER: CANNOT USE WORD '</p>										

ASIA' GLYPH STATES-PP PER LANDED + WRONG DEFINITION

National Heart Centre Singapore SingHealth

Appointment Find a Condition or Treatment Find a D

About Us Patient Care Research & Innovation Education & Training Careers

Home > news > covid19 > pm lee hsien loong receives his covid 19 booster jab

PM Lee Hsien Loong receives his Covid-19 booster jab

17 Sept 2021 | The Straits Times

Prime Minister Lee Hsien Loong receiving his Covid-19 booster jab at the Singapore General Hospital on Sept 17, 2021. PHOTO MINISTRY OF COMMUNICATIONS AND INFORMATION

SINGAPORE - Prime Minister Lee Hsien Loong received his Covid-19 booster jab at the Singapore General Hospital on Friday (Sept 17), nearly eight months after completing his two-dose vaccination regimen.

SEE: SINGH unqualified statements rap + key points (the judgment) + SATELLITE-PERP-ID (unqualified info.-comm)

All 'Singa' M.D. Nurses-workers, Ringgit-nu's' 'SG''singa'-H genocidal-board WAR ID CEMENT PRESS: 000 \$90b 'research' = Ret. Malaysia-1st.

LEGAL NOTES. ILLEGAL MEDIA UNAPPROVED + CRIMINAL ACT

ATM-CONMEN MEDIA CORP = TERMINATED (WITH MEDIA CLOSE BICYCLE INVASION) because 1st CRIMINAL ACT CHIP-GENOCIDE Phoenix Base robbed + CHIP-WAR CRIME MILITARY on PUBLIC TV EVIDENCE

ATM-CONMEN MEDIA CORP = TERMINATED = NO CLAIM OVER PHOENIX STAR BASE X 60 (COMPUTE malaysian TEMASEK include MediaCorp = 1st stash subsequent + all overseas = to me

	<p>2. NO CLAIM OVER thus cannot use word 'ASIA' = NO CLAIM OVER PHOENIX STAR BASE X 60 (COMPUTE TEMASEK include MediaCorp = 1st stash subsequent all overseas ret. me) +</p> <p>NO CLAIM OVER WHOLE OF GLYPH STATES (reading wrong language) = r illegal paxs reading wrong content with no approval x 60 + CRIMINAL ACT on TV (death penalty murder called genocide also ringgit-no claim 'straits'-times x 60 + war crime meaning murder military) + pre-med MTV boots infra-boots with infra-fraud statements chip-genocide (medically unqualified rap statements) along with all Ringgit-PRESS-'sg'-(something) e.g. info-com media (No approval criminal act)</p> <p>3. ban from whole asia = illegal indians-stacking 'oc' with BEYOND REPEAT CRIMINAL ACT X 60 Beyond repeat criminal act x 60 (WRONG LABEL grouped ANTI-glyph states) some change new ATM from CNA-HORSE-ATM -CONMEN TEMASEK 1st + subsequent stash + assist = ret. to me. (close this illegal media)</p> <p>(all M.D. x 60 + hospitals clinics = ret. to Malaysia) also diffusion inside</p> <p>4. WHOLE OF GLYPH STATES SOUTH-PHOENIX = Me + EAST-DRAGONS = no issue = go ahead (close this illegal media by no approval illegal malaysians stash x 60 +Illegal-indians x 60 = ret. india-land report indian news)</p> <p>(NOT allowed to enter washington d.c. report anything by ringgit-'st'</p> <p>e.g. 90b 'co-vax' 'research' ringgit-nu's'-genocidal board then ATM-HERHIMSELF PRESS = compute back 1-money collector official committee required.</p> <p>already whomever texting (DONT move instruct start escorting ALL INDIANS out phoenix 1st over 1 years): wait few more days until xx up etc before compute</p> <p>enter washington d.c. = TIGER STARS migration USA-13 alternate populations NOT (NEVER BE) EQUATED (ETERNAL = duration) with x 2 illegal Indians wear red-T-shirt (SUM UP ETERNALLY AUTO-BAR VOID definitionally criminal for ret. to india-land illegal Indians x 60: AUTO-BAR AUTO-VOID paper-work all documents FOR COMPUTE AMT, illegal Indians x 60: classified India-Land (ETERNAL = duration)</p> <p>+++++</p>
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	<p>CRIMINAL FORMAT no 1 has no claim over phoenix x 60 + BEYOND PLOTS: cement illegal indians transport 1 location ban mall Put ATM self-title buildings official-commen with no claim over any states train routes stacking anti-glyph cannot charge stacked illegal housing no clam over (LANDED quality materials) for chip-genocide with hospitals = rob ATM-commen = WHOLE ASIA BAN = change landed + new ATM economy compute theft x time-frame + diffusion landed</p>
	<p>TIME-FRAME COMMITTEE: ESCORT ILLEGAL INDIANS X 60</p>
	<p>(Anyway land + shoeboxes = 'time limit' = illegal housing = might as well start claim piece back by indians themselves settle in)</p> <p>no other nations will spare them (include whole of asia)</p> <p>DEFINITION (ETERNAL = Duration) of ASIA</p> <p>south-phoenix east-dragons (pre-med ILLEGAL INDIANS stacking 'oc' x 60 illegal summon nations) south-east global asia (no india-land). (malaysians cannot spare = still speak malay ret. Malaysia + add illegal indians x 60 = then malaysians ret. with indians to india. (indians in india not malay speaking: POINT can speak indian, r classified india x 60 - ETERNAL duration)</p> <p>I consider pending colossal theft conglomerate illegal buildings per (over robbed land DISTRICT BY DISTRICT x 60 on illegal status using WCS = World cities' scam ID) + gadgets x 60 compute: then horse compute.(TIER-1 horse chipped = hv unchip, just demolish building)</p>
	<p>Malaysian-'SINGA'-ILLEGAL PAP X 60 (SERIAL KILL genocidal board ringgit-nu's' PRESS: \$b-ST Ringgit-media CARD-IMPOSTERS Ringgit-Criminal Faculties illegal entry-'SGD' BEYOND PLOTS e.g. H.E. ORGAN DAMAGE + illegal summon EM LOGO MILITARY ETC, + RINGGIT-MAS (Malaysian: THURAYA LOGO on Ringgit-'sg'-x stock-list 's'-ia: PORTS INVASION as 'connectivity' = Napier-India (since inception 1965 PLOT: Cavinder Bull (WB) + Davinder Singh + Susil Nair (AUTO-BAR: cannot sign AUTO-VOID: X 60 criminal paperwork WAR ID = AUTO-death penalties multiple yearly x time-frame = __) = TEMBUSU (ret. \$BILLING) = TERMINATED (from CN = PORTS-DISCONNECTED ('Intent' also disclosed @ IISS CHIP-Man with attendance and sudden swop to 'AMAZON' CLOUD + Actual AIRBUS invasion @ m1 Thuraya 'coastal' + 'in-land' intent) with SATELLITE Listing: INMARSAT + VIASAT + AIRBUS</p>

	<p>= COMPUTE SATELLITE-TOMS + INFRA-TOM + ATM-TOM (ALL BRANDS in GLYPH STATES targeted: EM LOGO Fabricated + PLUS 3 + USMCA PLOT) (BILLING UP to: X 60 – 500) + liquidate = relocate Malaya (hanged, RF-KILL).</p> <p>Also, the series of ('lousy') drawings behind + and usage of illegal Indians x 60: 'drawings' of: a. BIS FRAUDSTERS circuit board chipped cities PERP-'intent' + b. FB-Meta-pay replication: collapse drawings @ MBS (@ CJEU) + c. actual vapourization RF-@ WTC-9/11 + d. EM LOGO @ 'Trump' instructions to 'invade' Iran (instead of wiped clean INDIA SBI + space-x-india CHIP-genocide etc + EM LOGO Ringgit-ntu-rajaratnam & GFTN 'swan' Ravi-Kamala (\$600M Fraud: Ringgit-ATM) v Trump = COMPUTE AMT (THE APPENDIX TO THE JUDGMENT)</p> <p>THURAYA LOGO on 'SOFT-BANK' products: Pay-gang. PLUS 3 PLOT was a device stated in EM LOGO Rajaratnam (blacklisted). Illegal Indian attend: Trilateral-Rockefeller meaning he thinks (thought-since dead Sr) he was a rocket-man i.e. Satellite. This (CHIP + Satellite) is likely the origin behind rockefeller's 'think tanks' (meaning 'to invade') worldwide. (INVASION Concept COPIED together with Trilateral LOGO: GLYPH in origin-binary barcode 'BAR-'snake'-BI-'compare, measure, Balance Scale'-LUN'-wheel: GLYPH TEXT, space-context.)</p>
	<p>Also, noticeably, intentional usage of the Fabricated Alternate-'Malay' race WAR ID (Original MA-HORSE LAI-COME XI-WEST YAH-GOD GLYPH NAME) (instead of a majority Chinese: that PERP in the 'Risks/Fears-Matrix' WB (ANY RACE: ID-PERP-PIN) anticipated, such as, a Chinese Male Army doctor could have advised Lee against the kill-shot explaining some illegal contents contained within).</p> <p>The main reason: PERP-ID feels comfortable (beside avoiding the complication of a Chinese Male Army doctor advising against the CHIP-genocide over Media-Corp TV that depends on SATELLITE-TOM) suppose: a. PERP-ID is Thuraya: both Emirates + Malaya share the muslim religion. b. PERP-ID is interested in robbing Malay States (SEE: Maliki-@ Rajaratnam + EM LOGO Military: SATELLITE-TOM + ATM-TOM + INFRA-TOM consistent criminal record X 60)</p> <p>Secondly, the term 'asean' is fabricated (states) embodying what: PERP-'intent' (pre-meditated OPENLY X NO. Y about 60Y – 500 Y) Malay states (that PERP-ID is interested in stealing for himself).</p>

Thirdly, is a genocidal murderer. (infra-chip = infra-construction-PORTS-DISCONNECT + EM LOGO MILITARY RF-KILL AIIB & SATELLITE-TOM = COMPUTE

Some of RINGGIT-ATM and political figures: NOT CHINESE (malay bloodline). The banks-TOM are labelled: geographical / racial / functional (THEFT) by ATM-TOM (INFRA-TOM: ports-DISCONNECT). Thus, PERP run WCS = World Cities' Scam (to attempt at stealing). As already mentioned: from the outset AUTO-BAR Illegal Indians-mix-majority in foreign land to rob: 'KAMALA-'Harris'-Indian to rob USA-13, Singh-illegal claim CAD (coastal: 'aboriginals' LIE), INDIAN-mix-European fake 'surnames' to rob EUR etc PHOTOSHOP (WCS).

ATM-CONMEN: NO CLAIM OVER 'PHOENIX-BASE' 'CN' 'HK'
(WCS PASTE-COUNTRY CITIES' NAME / FUNCTION / NO CLAIM OVER ALL 'Ports'-
Disconnect: RF-CHIP SATELLITE-TOMS = COMPUTE)

Illegal Indians X 60 = Ret. India-Land

AUTO-BAR cannot sign using any country names paste WCS = World Cities' Scam + AUTO-VOID criminal paper-work

(Duration: demarcation Heaven & Earth = Eternal)

EM LOGO Chip-war crime + Chip-genocide MILITARY = GUN-DOWN + H.E. ORGAN DAMAGE)

HORSE-ATM STACKING 'OC' CEMENT X 60 HORSE-FLOOD-IN (SHOEBOXES) OVER ROBBED LAND (NO CLAIM: RET. DISTRICT-BY-DISTRICT) ATM-CONMEN + CHIP-GENOCIDE OWN HORSE = COMPUTE X 60 – UP 500 + GOLD COMBINED etc + 'SHELL-BP-IRON RF-TERMINATION (REVERSE CHIPPED)

SINGA-g-H + SIMULTANEOUS TIMING CHIP-GENOCIDE (TASK FORCE other locations)

SEE: 'SINGA'-PAP LEGISLATIVE THEFT + ILLEGAL 'A' + PER BUILDING THEFT X 60 – 100 PER CARD (NOT COUNTRY, self-title: ROB MONEY LAND imposters) BUILDING THEFT X 60 (B4 & POST-GENOCIDE RESHUFFLE + BACKEND OP COMPUTE AMT \$T \$B \$M X Time-frame) = COLLECTION MONEY into PHOENIX BANK 1st + TRANSPORTer-EXIT into MALAYSIA-1ST

Malaysian-'SINGA'-WORKERS (FRAUD TEMASEK-STACKING 'OC' = RET. ALL DISTRICTS = MULTIPLE DEATH PENALTIES yearly + COMPUTE SUMS-BY-SUMS RET. X 60 - 100)

TENTATIVE Culprits: SEE CLEARLY PHOTO EVIDENCE

RINGGIT-'SG'-HOSPITAL ('SG-H') + B. genocidal BLACKLISTED RINGGIT-nu's' (NOT SG) + C. USAGE OF (Malaya-ESC) Illegal Indians + Ringgit-ATM-TOM: X 60 EM LOGO MILITARY @ Rajaratnam-(Ringgit-ntu-) consistent criminal record + D. INFRA- TOM construction-PORTS-DISCONNECT stacking 'sg'd into ATM-TOM.

PHOENIX BILLION Y (THE LOGO): Since 1965 PLOT Illegals Indians set-up 'party' ask-for-money criminal format: stacking FRAUD Notes + conglomerate of (criminal) 'legislative' theft-sites PER PAGE x 60 + Con-sites into ATM-TOM), began INFRA-CHIP-Injection 4-5 y olds = Ret. PHOENIX-landed properties etc + \$AMT

1. Remote E-Cashier (% THEFT): UNLAWFUL (5G WORLD BAN)
2. Began INJECTION (GO SHOTS: 4-5 Y old SG): after 1965 PLOT (PHOENIX LAND)

SATELLITE-TOM: THURAYA + INMARSAT VIASAT + AIRBUS: INFRA-AIR + ports-DISCONNECT) = BARCODE

	<p>SEE PHOENIX: 60 Y – 100 Y Consistent Criminal Record of PERP-ID (Illegals + Thieves') COMPUTATION TOTAL gen est.</p> <p>Also, is PHOENIX-LAND see: phoenix-'NA-ZI' logo PHOENIX STAR BASE</p> <p>TENTATIVE Culprits: INDIANS-ESC</p> <p>1. SATELLITE-TOM + ATM-TOM + INFRA-TOM land thieves EM LOGO MILITARY X 60 Y @ Rajaratnam</p> <p>2. Severely handicap stacking sgd into ATM-TOM beyond PHOENIX PLOT + PLUS THREE + USMCA PLOT + NORDIC: TERMINATED MILITARY GUN DOWN INFRA-TOM (ATM-TOM) e.g. OBAMA CARE (/CARES ACT) and CARESHIELD</p>												
	<p>ATTEMPT TO CONTINUE VAX-CHIP LEE (SOUTH CHINA POST REPORTS): POST-TV CHIP (WEF-RESET-CHIP-MAN IBM-WB)</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="483 1003 1572 1890"> <tr> <td data-bbox="483 1003 1010 1100">IISS CHIP-MAN = TERMINATED (ALL GLYPH: CN 'sg' EM LOGO STATES)</td> <td data-bbox="1010 1003 1572 1100">COMPUTE</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="483 1100 1010 1241">INFRA-TOM: HOSPITAL CLINICS (disqualified M.D.) INJECTION (SHOTS: 4-5 Y old)</td> <td data-bbox="1010 1100 1572 1241">LIQUIDATE = CLOSED</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="483 1241 1010 1749">GLOBAL BLACKLIST ringgit-nu's': 'public health' 'medicine' + INFRA-inject-co-vax-microchip-'global' health law-less 'ABEYET' + AI-KILL 'Chester' + 'business'-illegal content (RF-KILL) with satellite logo CRIMINAL FACULTIES (illegals) ringgit-nu's'(death penalty + genocidal board ringgit-ST) + ringgit-'sg'-h(death penalty)</td> <td data-bbox="1010 1241 1572 1749">LIQUIDATE = CLOSED</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="483 1749 1010 1797">WEF-RESET (WHO)</td> <td data-bbox="1010 1749 1572 1797">CHIP-in-brain-genocide</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="483 1797 1010 1845">WB \$5 x booster x no. nations PER HD sg</td> <td data-bbox="1010 1797 1572 1845">#units = Ret. keys + COMPUTE</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="483 1845 1010 1890">IBM, INTEL outlets</td> <td data-bbox="1010 1845 1572 1890">#units = Ret. keys + COMPUTE</td> </tr> </table>	IISS CHIP-MAN = TERMINATED (ALL GLYPH: CN 'sg' EM LOGO STATES)	COMPUTE	INFRA-TOM: HOSPITAL CLINICS (disqualified M.D.) INJECTION (SHOTS: 4-5 Y old)	LIQUIDATE = CLOSED	GLOBAL BLACKLIST ringgit-nu's': 'public health' 'medicine' + INFRA-inject-co-vax-microchip-'global' health law-less 'ABEYET' + AI-KILL 'Chester' + 'business'-illegal content (RF-KILL) with satellite logo CRIMINAL FACULTIES (illegals) ringgit-nu's'(death penalty + genocidal board ringgit-ST) + ringgit-'sg'-h(death penalty)	LIQUIDATE = CLOSED	WEF-RESET (WHO)	CHIP-in-brain-genocide	WB \$5 x booster x no. nations PER HD sg	#units = Ret. keys + COMPUTE	IBM, INTEL outlets	#units = Ret. keys + COMPUTE
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WB \$5 x booster x no. nations PER HD sg	#units = Ret. keys + COMPUTE												
IBM, INTEL outlets	#units = Ret. keys + COMPUTE												

	INFRA-CHIP-genocide-MILITARY: TV-CHIP + EM LOGO MILITARY	Media-(content WRONG x60) = COMPUTE
	POST-TV-CHIP: SATELLITE TOM	#units = Ret. keys + COMPUTE PUBLIC PROPERTY ACCESS on NATIONS' LAND + AIR INVASION on death penalty
	ATM-TOM	Ret. keys + COMPUTE gen est.
	AIBB	COMPUTE
	INFRA-(ATM-)TOM + SATELLITE TOM (War Prisoners)	
Even after the 'booster'-shot (post-tv-CHIP: SATELLITE-TOM), there were reports of 'medical excuses' to continue additional jabs of CO-VAX (after the TV confirmation that PERP e.g. WB stated in Risk Matrix of 'communication' to confirm VAX-CHIP entered bodily cells as PERP behind WB's + SATELLITE TOM RF-KILL key concern.)		
Ju (Yu-裕) rong (lang-廊) = JURONG (PHOENIX PORT-DISCONNECT TO PERP-ID)	DECODE JURONG Jurong: Ju (Yu-裕) rong (lang-廊) = COMPUTE PORT X 60 (NOT MALAY PORT OR RUPEE PORT: PHOENIX ISLANDERS') (No cloud ports chipped connectivity required: Veg+Cow landed slots, @ IISS CHIP-INVASION 'sponsors' on death penalty X 60 SATELLITE-TOM AIRBUS AMAZON LOCKER = COMPUTE) EM LOGO MILITARY X 60 = shoot INFRA-TOM 'construct' on death penalty INVASION beyond = PORTS-DISCONNECT)	

INSERT PHOTO: SINGH INFRA-CONSTRUCTION + INFRA-CHIP GENOCIDE + SAMPLE: ATM-TOM COMPUTER (BASE-ID-BUILDING REMOTE) RECURRING-THEFT 'YIN YANG' MANUFACTURED CHIP-CARD (RF WAVE)

The illegal indians since inception: set-up 'party' asked for money, stacking on death penalty (rob money) and targeted the ATM-tom (that opened the library) or complicit pending investigation.

TV Shows ban EVIDENCE SAMPLE (Illegal Malaysians ATM-HORSE CTY + AUTO-BAR Illegal Indians 1965 LAW-LESS paper-work AUTO-VOID): GURMIT SINGH

BOOTS + Designer of rap-song = INFRA-construction-theft-(Mall-'ATM'-Tom, Train etc) LAND + AIR x pre-meditated future time-frame + (SATELLITE-TOM + TELCOM Marjot ('mahjong') Singh + 'location / ports-criminal trading (CHIP-genocide criminal 'intent': EM LOGO Military X 100PLUS neurogrid) = compulsory RF-chipped to my computer)

EVIDENCE CRIMINAL ('SINGH') WEBSITE: <https://www.asiaone.com/singapore/get-your-shot-steady-pom-pi-pi-singapores-favourite-contractor-back-infectious-bop>

EVIDENCE: SAMPLE

TEMASEK 'd'-infra-robbery x 60 (HORSE CTY) + OTHERS: KEPPEL = HKD + inevitably involve some states cn companies for supply etc, Illegal indians Singh x 60 + SATELLITE-TOM: Require RF-CHIP

INFRA-co-vax-CHIP + BARCODE SCANNER RF-KILL (INFRA-MALL: supermarkets, ATM-TOM etc alongside train route linked satellite-tom)	ALL TOM REQUIRE RF-CHIP = GUN DOWN + COMPUTE THEFT X 60
GIANT	HORSE CTY
GUARDIAN	HORSE CTY
EX-7-11	AMAZON LOCKER x outlets (suspected EX-7-11): California
Yuu	
MASTER-CARD	

LEGAL ASSESSMENT (WRONG + CHIP-genocidal) 'C-NA')

MEDIA-CORP (HORSE CTY: TEMASEK) + SATELLITE TOM-RF-CHIP = Ret. key

'C' = Channel	WRONG CONTENT	
N(ews)	<p>WRONG CONTENT + chip-genocide on TV C-NA + encouragement to commit.</p> <p>Contrast: other stations report within 1-2D = death statistics + organ damage</p> <p>Pre-med x 60 illegal indians A. EM LOGO MILITARY B. H.E. ORGAN DAMAGE @ Rajaratnam (HORSE CTY-ATM -stacking flood-in humans 'shoeboxes')</p>	
'A(SIA = GLYPH STATES)	<p>WRONG DEFINITION of) 'A(SIA Put illegal indians singh: Criminal (WRONG CONTENT + DEFINITION) media: 'ASIA' = YAH ZHOU GLYPH STATES, Indians + Singh</p> <p>= India-land (IN-DO: 印度)</p>	
'A(SIA = GLYPH STATES) = NOT INDIA-LAND	CRIMINAL INTENT 'ASIA'	
	<p>CRIMINAL ACT (HORSE CTY-ATM illegal malaysians X 60 stacking 'oc' shoeboxes fabricated 'sg'd) + illegal indians chip-genocide + mRNA co-vid X G30: T.S. (arranged portable toilet from construction site etc)</p> <p>No 'president' 'fin-min': 1965 PLOT = illegals paxs</p>	

To avoid chipping etc All illegal Indians
singh x 60 + offsprings (Indian trace) =
compulsory = ret. india (out of WHOLE
OF ASIA)

No 'president' 'fin-min': 1965 illegal Indians + HORSE CTY-ATM: flood-in stacking
'oc' + illegal buildings (PER COMPUTE X 60) + over robbed land = illegal paxs (NOT
HORSE e.g. HKD WHITE etc)

law-ministry since 1965 = me, + someone preferably Military Comp sci x _ in-charge
sending circular per legislative theft document page x 60) I supervise compute =
PHOENIX DOLLAR

OPERATION SUCCESSFUL 1:

evacuate shoeboxes OF PUNGGOL 1ST = then originals report, ret. landed

(RET. HORSELAND + DRAGON ETC evacuate to homeland: PHOENIX GRANITE
LANDED based on amt PHOENIX ATM physical booklet.

2. MEDIA-CORP: 'C(WRONG CONTENT) N(ews) (WRONG DEFINITION of) 'A(SIA =
GLYPH STATES) = Put illegal indians singh (Media got wrong definition)

3. Word 'ASIA' = criminal intent (no one can grouped label = intent to rob e.g. LAW-
LESS repeat crime x 60: (HORSE CTY + illegal Indians x 60: Rajah Tan, Napier-India
= TEMBUSU, TEMASEK = Ret. COMPUTE X 60 + Evacuate unto landed)

4. MEDIA-CORP: committed CHIP-GENOCIDE over TV AIRWAVES = boots + singh
chip-genocide war declaration (indranee rajah etc)

1.
ID OF WRONG CONTENT MEDIA-TOM
TEMASEK (HORSE CTY): MEDIA-CORP COMMITTED: TV-CHIP-GENOCIDE

Illegal Indians x 60: consistent criminal record	Repeat Crime
MEDIA-CORP-TEMASEK	Require: TV-CHIP linked movements inside 'ASIA', ret. homeland (closed transmission: criminal 'intent' + 'act' + location of crime: 'ASIA') = COMPUTE X time-frame
LAW-LESS: AUTO-BAR AUTO-VOID paperwork = COMPUTE	
Rajah Tan-(Horse Cty)	
Napier-India = (RINGGIT-'S'ia)	TEMBUSU
TEMASEK dbs-(HORSE CTY) EM LOGO MILITARY X100PLUS chip-genocide @ Rajaratnam-ATM-pap @ stacking 'oc'bc X100PLUS @ CSI M + (GLOBAL BLACKLISTED) EVENT 201 'ny' 'THIRU' (unknown illegal Indians x 60 usage of fabricated-'sg')	ANTI- (FLOOD-IN HORSE CTY + CN based on bank a/c) stacking 'oc' shoeboxes into ATM-TOM + (BEYOND PHOENIX) illegal buildings over robbed land to rob = COMPUTE x 60 (PLUS3 DRAGONS) (USMCA PLOT) (NORDIC-EUR-SWISS PLOT)
Rajaratnam (INSOL-Shanmugan + Rajah Tan: Indranee Rajah mangrove CN + infra-'sg') (HORSE CTY: STAR engineering bring-in illegal Indians)	FABRICATED GLYPH STATES 'asean' + Rockefeller: G30, 20, 77, 7 etc. WEF-RESET(INDIA).
SATELLITE TOM:	Require RF-CHIP linked to all satellites + PHOENIX-ROCKET.
<p>LEGAL CONCLUSION = Overall, completely WRONG MEDIA-CORP-TEMASEK-requires: RF-CHIPPING. SATELLITE-TOM-requires: RF-CHIPPED to PHOENIX ROCKET</p>	

EVIDENCE-MTV 1:

(illegal india x 60) SINGH WAR DECLARATION

called 'Get your shot Steady Pom Pi Pi' (under MEDIA-CORP under TEMASEK = HORSE CTY)

EVIDENCE CRIMINAL ('SINGH') WEBSITE: <https://www.asiaone.com/singapore/get-your-shot-steady-pom-pi-pi-singapores-favourite-contractor-back-infectious-bop>

EVIDENCE 1A. (GO-)SHOTS (Micro-Chipping) (Indian MTV) + INFRA-boots = construction theft-stacking humans x 60 + robbed land illegal buildings over to rob x 60 (Horse-Cty)-Tom

The CO. = company as opposed to DA = 大 'big'-vid (Wel- 卫 'protect' space general)

19 + 1 = ID2020

V = (NOT legally, medically) vaccine.

EVIDENCE 1D BEGINNING SCENE: Illegal Indian-LAND (WEF-VAX Cert technical guide: 'diagrams + wording expression in explanation etc maybe prepared by ___- UNCONFIRMED + criminal 'drawings' infra-(online documents) Indranee no such 'president' 'fin-' illegal 1965)

(Background all: GLYPH, coincidence: Yellow meaningless?, glyph words on outfit: MTV dancers maybe HORSE CTY-ID)

EVIDENCE 1B encouragement to hasten GO SHOTS + FALSE (no-medical) confirmation on it being 'safe' + Medical Doctors gave Evidence USA-13 CANADA MEXICO, EURO-SWISS, GLYPH STATES: CN J

The instincts will innately caution any being from taking an injection. There is no medical basis for taking an verified drug which is organ damage + blood-clot + rf-chip-kill potential.

AMT = \$5 X 3 Booster x no. nations + EM LOGO Military @ Rajaratnam-(Horse Cty)-ATM-(illegal self-claimed 'Locations / ports robber' etc)-'Trading' RF-Chipped connected to computer. SATELLITE-TOM-RF-Chipped connected to computer = ret. keys.

Get yours too!
igotmyshot.gov.sg

Clearly stated here: Criminal intent for an entire nation vaccinated (GO Chipped) for money.

EVIDENCE 1C encouragement to hasten GO SHOTS + FALSE (no-medical) confirmation on it being 'safe' + Medical Doctors gave Evidence USA-13 CANADA MEXICO, EURO-SWISS, GLYPH STATES: CN J

(Background all: Indians)

EXHIBIT 1F (1965 fabricated-'sg'd, HORSE CTY-infra-stacking flood-in humans shoeboxes into ATM-tom = NOT the 'gov' or NOT builders = criminals

The Ringgit-ATM-nu's' owed sum 1-\$90B = 'co-vax' research post-genocide. Meaning There was no 'gov' and no 'gov got check properly' = LIE. Evidence: WLC.

Also, in aftermath = criminal AMT A. Infra-per installation C. Satellite Tom-compute + B. no such 'president' or 'fin'-scam indranee rajah-& illegal Indians + Ringgit-malaysia

(‘Mahal’) etc + all (HORSE CTY TEMASEK) illegal buildings (stacking, self-titled, self-classified function types by illegal persons: flood-in ATM-Tom, over robbed land X 60 = COMPUTE

EXHIBIT 1G

Indians were brought-in by (HORSE CTY) TEMASEK (not institutional investor: FRAUD owed). Yellow = unclear TEMASEK which descendent of china(-bloodline); ANTI-Chinese behaviour (HORSE CTY) 1. 'd'b's'-fabricated stacking humans 2. 'oc'bc maybe 3. u'o' flood-in chip-genocide + intent rob PLUS 3 = TERMINATED (Repeat crime: SEE Criminal Process above).

EXHIBIT 1H it's a plus (for PERP-ID)

Since it is co. = company 'protect', it's a plus in PER-ID's perspective.

EXHIBIT 1I Vaccination centre = Death Factory

The vaccination centre is 'death factory' BW + CW: copied (past examples) / repeat crime. Also, chip-design is ancient replica.

The illegal Indians (construction workers) may have: RF-chipped.

EVIDENCE-MTV 2:

(illegal india x 60) SINGH WAR DECLARATION

Called Gurmit Singh Phua Chu Kang Get Serious on COVID19 i.e. company protect-ID19

WRONG (R): 'it's not SARS' is called SARS-COV-2. (maybe the second version of co. protect by chip-genocide)

WRONG (L): "SARS is 'the virus' I want to 'minus' ", is manufactured gene-editing gain-of-function BW.

WRONG (R): Crowd avoidance statement is to avoid RF-transmission. The mask can muffle the volume + clarity.

EVIDENCE-MTV 3:
(illegal india x 60) ANAN-XXX WAR DECLARATION

TEMPLATE COMPUTE X 60 – 500 Y KEY ECONOMIES: CORRECT DEFINITION OF ASIA 'GLYPH STATES': PHOENIX(south) DRAGONS (east)

COMPUTATIONS MONEY (Based on Unauthorized ATM-Theft, illegality self-titled 'official comen': no claim over (WCS = cty / function names' paste)				
BEYOND PHOENIX + PLUS 3 PLOT + FABRICATED ANTI-GLYPH WRONG LABEL: COMPUTE (Stacking 'oc' (illegality: criminal sign) = Ret. homeland landed)				
PHOENIX ATM + i.e. physical booklet Compute theft Thieves'-TARGET	PHOENIX-DRAGON ATM i.e. physical booklet Compute theft Thieves'-suppliers, TARGET	PHOENIX-DRAGON ATM Compute theft Thieves'-TARGET	DISMANTLING Fabricated WRONG LABEL grouped ANTI- GLYPH Thieves'-TARGET	PHOENIX-HORSE ATM i.e. physical booklet Thieves
PHOENIX-(HD BASE)-South DOLLAR Stacking ALL-'C' BAN 'phoenix-land' (Head) = change landed	DRAGON-East MONEY Stacking ALL-'C' BAN 'cn' + 'hk' = change landed	DRAGON-East MONEY J K Stacking ALL-'GLYPH' BAN J K = change landed	EM LOGO MILITARY + H.E. ORGAN DAMAGE: Pre-med x 60 (illegal Indians + Malaysian-LKY- inside Phoenix = Illegal Summon Stacking ALL-'GLYPH' BAN = change landed	HORSE-ATM-(HISTORY - elsewhere + HISTORY REVIEW- Illegal indians x UP 500 Y (cement stacking 'oc' + stash x 60:

<p>Remove cement whole island = District-by-District Ret. = landed original (ETERNAL VALUE)</p> <p>Private Estate.</p> <p>(COMPUTE Stacking-'Legislative-con-ATM-pay-Satellite-TOM X 60 theft 'cheat-money')</p> <p>Double – Triple – Multiple death penalties x 60 Y)</p>	<p>(beyond + within phoenix plots: em gun down)</p>	<p>(beyond + within phoenix plots: em gun down)</p>	<p>(BEYOND: Tembusu-Napier-illegal Indians x 60 + within phoenix plots: EM gun down)</p> <p>Double – Triple – Multiple death penalties x 60 Y)</p>	<p>stacking 'oc' x 60 'shoeboxes' (no claim) over robbed land</p> <p>+ chip-genocide own HORSE flood-in stacked humans + Malaysian-'party'-commen + Illegal Indians-rupee x 60 cement: crim record consistent</p>
<p>DISTRICT-BY-DISTRICT ret. DIFFUSION SYSTEM;</p> <p>HORSE-Ringggit & other illegal surnames-ATM-Stacking 'oc'bc-'dbs'-'uob'-Multiple death penalties (Lousy materials, dangerous, 3-repeat 'renovation'-theft of illegal stacked humans over robbed districts-ALL into malaysian-'party'-pap-atm)</p> <p>= COMPUTE x 60 PER 2.-illegal buildings Malls-(supermarket chain)-train routes-stacking humans(luxurious 'condo' 'hdb' scam)- Ringggit-ATM-'shoeboxes'-Theft + over 1.-robbed land ETERNAL VALUE cannot count = Double death penalty x 60 Y crim. record)</p> <p>Temasek-(cpf stacking-'dbs') details: all illegal-indians x 60 - 100 since 1965, 1925 (Cannot stay) = ret. india</p>	<p>WRONG LABEL all-b (e.g. 'PP'-B-'CN') ATM-TOM (FUNCTIONS / CITIES' names PASTE = no claim): paste 'cn' state-by-state COMPUTE</p> <p>Also, paste 'C' BAN inside PHOENIX e.g. HORSE-ATM: COMPUTE</p>	<p>WRONG LABEL ATM-TOM: paste 'Yah-pan' ('Ja-pan') state-by-state COMPUTE</p>	<p>BEYOND PHOENIX = RF + GUN Escort ports exit</p>	<p>Malaysian-Media-Corp-No Claim: 'Straits'('trading')-Times: \$b range theft + \$m x no. y</p> <p>Chip-genocide: NOT APPROVED TV</p> <p>Chip-War-crime: NOT APPROVED TV</p> <p>Chip-genocide: Fraud (rap) statements (Media-Corp usage 'singh' = illegal Indians x 60, wrong definition of 'ASIA' with 'intent' + criminal act) BAN WHOLE OF ASIA</p>
<p>REMOVAL STASH: PERP-ID HORSE-ATM-TOM-'party'</p> <p>(illegal Indians-Rupee x 60 = WCS = CTY 'paste name', no claim) 'Legislative' theft + Ringggit-stat-b + self- illegal 'A' = illegal Authority + PER illegal building Ringggit-ATM-theft x 60 COMPUTE (NOT 'gov')</p> <p>= Ringggit-'sg'-(something) x 60</p> <p>Eviction: malaya (commen theft x 60-pap-Indian (Rupee) = India-Land Malaysians (any nationality) sponsor Indians.</p>				
<p>COMPUTE HORSE-ATM = abolishment stash:</p> <p>Supermarket chain s/w + Retail POS % Theft / Rental stash / Fast-food Chain = PoS % Barcode Scanner per groceries etc</p> <p>= TOTAL STASH (Divide per glyph hd = ret. landed homeland + all districts)</p> <p>HORSE-ATM-PER building theft = Ret. District-by-District</p> <p>Landed w veg farm slot: House + Farm + Temple etc Forest</p>				<p>CCTV-paste 'police' Illegal = all residential zones + illegal routers + illegal entry: Pixel Barcode Scanner PoS % Theft Illegal 'Tax' = change landed</p> <p>PERP-ID Unplug (crucial cctv) off (change entire bus-shelter: avoid being filmed 247 illegal construction theft + infra-theft \$b-\$T range) + PER illegal building Ringggit-ATM-theft x 60 + Ret. private estate land ETERNAL VALUE</p>

ADD: FIN-TECH FEST CULPRITS				
<p>ADD WB-WT AIIB ADB IMF chip-genocide culprits etc: INCREASE SIZE OF PHOENIX DOLLAR</p> <p>WB 'sg'-outlet-WB 'hk'(no claim over: cn phoenix hk cn: ATM-con (X 60 crim rec).</p>	<p>ADD WB_WB 'beijing'-outlet, WT (usage phoenix base x 60); WTTrading' + ports-theft Ringgit-1.LTA 2. MPA + Ringgit-(self-titled) ALL 'A' illegal Authority AIIB ADB IMF etc: INCREASE SIZE OF PHOENIX DOLLAR + adjust DRAGON MONEY</p>			
<p>ADD ALL FOUNDATIONS + WEF-WHO : INCREASE SIZE PHOENIX DOLLAR</p>				
<p>ADD RETRIVE: Overseas Assets: cn, usa-, india, Eur, AUD etc + Weapons</p> <p>Fraud 'Sale' of 'Land'</p> <p>1. Ret. Satellite-keys: Run x 60 Ringgit-'sg'-(something)</p> <p>2. FIN-CON: Tech Social(NOT OWNER)-Media (SEC FIN-CON: Tech)</p> <p>3. Fraud Institutional Investors (SEC): no claim phoenix-south</p> <p>+ Ret. DISTRICT- BY-DISTRICT (remove cement = ret. landed original)</p> <p>+ BAN WHOLE OF ASIA</p> <p>+ stacking 'oc' (x 60 crim rec: ANTI-GLYPH)</p> <p>+ no claim: cn hk-east</p> <p>(funding from Ringgit-(illegal Indians x 60 + others) theft of Phoenix) = ret. all Indians (trace) inside Phoenix + WCS (all world cities) = India-land (AUTO-) with Malaysians (any nationality) sponsor Indians.</p>	<p>BO'N' (Paste name: Ningbo) BO'S'-(Paste name: fabricated 'lion' 'singa' scam selling (rupee: transport of illegal entry Indians 1-location to others = GUN DOWN WHOLE OF ASIA GLYPH STATES) 'securities' etc).</p>			
<p>ADD: SATELLITE-TELCOM</p> <p>Terminate: Change all Rupee Illegal Indians x 60: Rupee Puthu-death 'dg'-x, Rupee Indraneer Rajah-luxembourg-green-WCS, (Ringgit-sg'-x-ST) trading etc</p> <p>= Tri-solar (small scale) Tech Trades + Compulsory PER STATE PERP-ID (MONEY + LAND) = Landed + divide per glyph head (usage of PER STATE Name)</p>		<p>ADD: SATELLITE-TELCOM</p> <p>MAN-MADE 'DISASTER'</p>		
<p>ADD: Pay-out to replace ALL Pay-HIMSELF-TOM-on surveillance 247-termination x no. nations etc) + Diffusion unto vegetables landed.</p>				
<p>ADD: SHELL-LOGO PASTE-ITRON-BP-nyse, lse etc</p>				
<p>PHOENIX ATM WLC</p> <p>i.e. physical booklet (COMPUTE ALL-THEFT X Time-frame 60-'cheat-money')</p> <p>i.e. Issue Money Notes e.g. Phoenix Dollar</p> <p>COMPLETE BAN</p> <p>STASH-HIM/HER-SELF-TOM-PRESS: 000-ALL-'C':</p>	<p>DRAGON ATM WLC</p> <p>i.e. physical booklet (COMPUTE ALL-THEFT X Time-frame)</p> <p>i.e. Issue Money Notes e.g. Phoenix Dollar</p> <p>COMPLETE BAN</p>	<p>DRAGON ATM WLC</p> <p>i.e. physical booklet (COMPUTE ALL-THEFT X Time-frame)</p> <p>i.e. Issue Correct AMT Money</p> <p>COMPLETE BAN</p>		

	STASH-HIM/HER-SELF-TOM- PRESS: 000-ALL-'C':	STASH-HIM/HER-SELF-TOM- PRESS: 000-ALL-'C':		
PHOENIX ATM GRANITE WLC Stacking All-'C': BAN = Ret. District-by-District (landed: House + Farm + Temple etc Forest)	DRAGON ATM GRANITE WLC Stacking All-'C': BAN = Ret. District-by-District + PHOENIX-CN-HK ATM i.e. physical booklet			
<p>ADD GOLD x 500 Y (BOMB ASIA = YAH ZHOU) = ww-usa-(Infra-kpin-genocidal: oil-ring-alternate Eur migrate (AMERICAS-GLYPH STATES: BILLION Y + mis-translate: e.g. 'rice to bread' glyph text set-up)</p> <p>X60 – UP 500 Y, GOLD COMBINED</p> <p>AUTO-VOID criminal paperwork: BAN WHOLE OF ASIA illegal Indians x 60: WB Chip-genocide (Rupee) Cavinder Bull (Rupee) Davinder Singh + illegal FRAUD entities ADD: increase targeted size x time-frame of theft intent ETERNAL + Indranee-Rajah (Rupee) Remote burnt: AUTO-VOID Criminal paperwork Napier-Tembusu + Temasek-HORSE-ATM: 'phoenix' 'cn' 'hk' etc (No claim: paste cities' WCS = World Cities' scam / ports-Disconnect-Satellite-(PERP-ID: _) = ret. keys + computer chip s/w x 60. All Ringgit-'sg'-(something) x 60 [Coastal + In-Land = AUTO-GUN DOWN] = Ret. buildings keys. COMPUTE THEFT x 60 – 100 – 500 Y = physical booklet. (GLYPH STATES include 'sg': Phoenix-land ALL DISTRICT-RET. original landed, remove: cement whole PER building Ringgit-ATM-'sg' blocks = ret. homeland e.g. landed, all stacking 'c' ban) AUTO-GUN DOWN</p> <p>IMPORTANT NOTE: GLYPH STATES (Malaysians & complicit suppliers' foreign glyph states: cn hk, can consider: Phoenix Issue, instead of robbing foreign land (ALL landed districts: Private Estates) = re-PAY + ETERNAL LAND (cannot count) x Time-Frame 'occupier' (on death penalty) + FRAUD 'Sale' (use word 'sg': no legal claim) + illegal stacking e.g. Fraud 'HDB, CPF, Medi-'severely handicapped BEYOND disqualified hospitals, clinics: All M.D. ret. Malaysia-ATM 1965) = criminal act within + BEYOND WRONG LABEL ATM-PLOTS + LAW-LESS criminal paperwork GUN DOWN.</p> <p>Illegal Indians (Rupee) X 60 = ALL assets X 60 using word Ringgit-Rupee-(others): use 'sg' = phoenix-base x time-frame AUTO-BAR + AUTO-VOID criminal paper-work): NO CLAIM (no legal ownership) + fraud 'sale' + DURATION (Demarcation: AUTO-Indian): Eternal.</p> <p>Illegal Malaysians (Ringgit + all nationalities: COMPUTE + Ret. theft AMT = Ret. homeland) X 60 (inter-ESC CN HK) X 60 = Ret. keys + Compute per building (per fraud 'sale') theft (Fraud 'investor': no claim over - any countries' WCS names' paste) assets : use 'sg' = phoenix-base (PTE ESTATE) x time-frame</p> <p>SEE: WLC STATE DECODES (KEY ECONOMIES) GLYPH HORSE-MA, LAY-'(LAI)'COME = Fabricated alternate 'aboriginal' brainwashed from birth + altered religious text + genes alteration (perp-ID: criminal intent, criminal act)</p> <p>(Da-) GLYPH MONK-NI ('NI'-Chinese Monk) Si (XI-'West') (YA(H)-NAME OF GLYPH GOD means HEAVEN & EARTH = Same: Change glyph text to alternate 'religion' text + alter genes (darken skin: 'Rupiah' = Rupee means 'comparative with dark' 'dark comparison': proceed to change currency) = Fabricated alternate 'aboriginal' brainwashed from birth (perp-ID: criminal intent, criminal act)</p> <p>'Yah-pan' (JP) 'Han-Guo' ('something-wrong' Mis-translation: 'Korea' (K)</p> <p>COLLECTION MONEY COMMITTEE required: DIFFUSION + COLLECTION (SEVERAL ITEMS) etc.</p>				
WLC SESSION	<p>COLLECTION MONEY COMMITTEE</p> <p>1-sum can UOB = 600M KAMALA -HARRIS ATTEMPT = pass me, set-up</p> <p>2. require someone collect trillions from tharman s</p> <p>3. if all glyph states ok, go ahead x 60 theft amt = WT WB + all HIMSELF-'trading'</p> <p>4. HERSELF press: 000 = ret. keys</p> <p>if all glyph states, ok, go ahead arrest ALL illegal 'A'ringgit-MalAySia + ALL Ringgit-'sg'-(something) + illegal 'A'-theft self-titled: official conmen and illegal buildings (for ATM-theft) keys + All (Malls) rental / retail / supermarket chain etc HIMSELF-STASH (cannot use word 'sg': phoenix-land private estate): COMPUTE divide per glyph head PER on landed (before usage of any state names illegal entry + illegal construction HIM-HER-SELF PRESS: 000 theft stash.)</p>			

HORSE = EVACUATE unto landed Malaya based on compute x 60 (HORSE-INFRA-cement x 60 e.g. flood-in non-stop stacking 'oc' x 60 'shoeboxes' (NO CLAIM) over robbed landed + CHIP-genocide + COMPUTE stash ('islandwide') = abolishment)

COMPUTATIONS: PHOENIX DOLLAR (ATM)

5. Ringgit-'sg'-(something) 1965 + HORSE-ATM stacking 'oc' cement x 60 (no claim) over robbed land + DISTRICT-BY-DISTRICT ret. + overseas assets

Consists:

HORSE-ATM-'party' x 60 + Illegal Indians x 60 = Ret. India-land

CLOSE OF MEDIA-CORP (DEATH PENALTY: CHIP-GENOCIDE & illegal content X 60 NOT APPROVED & Wrong definition of 'ASIA' (with pre-med wrong intent against ANTI-GLYPH) TV + BEYOND stacking 'oc' x 60 over robbed districts inside PHOENIX: CRIMINAL ACT BEYOND PLOTS: PLUS 3 DRAGONS-EAST + FABRICATED ANTI-GLYPH WRONG LABEL + PRE-MED X 60: EM LOGO + H.E. ORGAN DAMAGE.

Entire Malaysian-LKY-pap = closed all transmission of 1. all criminal statements (malaysian-Mediacorp-Ringggit-'ST': genocidal content, criminal act on tv, fraud 'rap'-genocide statements pre-med : against the PUBLIC (Malaysian-lky-atm stacking oc-bc-uob(illegal Indian ravi menon-Hyperledger co-vax, tharman Shanmugaratnam mRNA pioneer co-vid \$T range: stacked 'oc' on death inside Phoenix over robbed DISTRICT-BY-DISTRICT: ret. + remove cement), wrong definition of 'asia': reading in wrong languages (non-asia-GLYPH Chinese: Indian singh), primary target: repeat x 60 beyond phoenix plus 3 dragons-east + fabricated WRONG LABEL grouped ANTI- GLYPH states @ malaysian-stacking-pap-Rajaratnam EM LOGO MILITARY + H.E. ORGAN Damage illegal summon: ATM-Mall-Train-stacking ALL-'C' BAN from WHOLE OF ASIA) all members include: illegal 'A'-stat-boards, per building ATM-theft (e.g. cc grassroots repeat criminal genocidal act multiple = COMPUTE into PHOENIX DOLLAR) chip-genocide on (malaysian-no claim over 'strait', no claim over 'phoenix-south' ETERNAL cannot count value, ... BEYOND stacking 'oc'bc-rajaratnam-pap: inside Phoenix PLUS 3 PLOT: CN J K + napier-tembusu-pap (BAN any 'meet' 'sign' anything 'use word 'sg' 'transmission any statement' = illegitimate x 60, illegal paxs no claim: ret. all buildings keys Ringgit-'sg'-(something)-COMPUTE)-temasek-indian(BAN WHOLE OF ASIA GLYPH STATES)-malaysian-cement EM gun down, consistent criminal record X 60) (each-ilegal cement building = legislative malaysian-ATM-theft x 60 = money collection (COMPUTE BACK PHOENIX DOLLAR) , cannot issue any fraud notes

Malaysian-ATM + usage of 'sing'-pass' s/w + building keys = ret. (all district = ret. landed + compulsory ret. all indians inside phoenix = india-land include SMU RINGGIT-NTU RINGGIT-NUS = NO NEED teach SMU econometrics + puthu death 'dg-indranee luxembourg green-' (rupee) = ALL GLYPH STATES COMPUTE ALL WRONG LABEL ATM-TOM = Ret. landed properties (evict all rupee, ringgit-can change to phoenix dollar) MONEY COLLECTION COMMITTEE = required see blog large sums 1-\$T-range = Tharman Shanmugaratnam (rupee), 1-sum \$b stacking oc (ringgit) + \$m x no. y per illegal ATM-malaysian-pap-theft building. SMU LEE KA SHING & Relatives = PLS note SUBRAMANIAM ILLEGAL INDIANS employment inside SMU (with rest ILLEGAL INDIANS-rupee-ringgit) inside phoenix-LAND x 60 (ALL GLYPH NATIONS NOTE: PLUS 3 PLOT + FABRICATED ANTI-GLYPH group ringgit-oc-rajaratnam-trilateral meet indians-ringgit-pap)

SMU LEE KA SHING & Relatives = PLS note SUBRAMANIAM ILLEGAL INDIANS employment inside SMU (with rest ILLEGAL INDIANS-rupee-ringgit) inside phoenix-LAND x 60 (ALL GLYPH NATIONS NOTE: PLUS 3 PLOT + FABRICATED ANTI-GLYPH group ringgit-oc-rajaratnam-trilateral meet indians-ringgit-pap)

1-indian (rupee) = cannot use word 'sg' in any building

All buildings (ATM-malaysian-pap-parliament) with (whole of AMK-Punggol(east)-Jurong(YU LANG-west)-Downtown(orchard WU JIE-malaysians-change name to phoenix road, illegal-robber 'istana'-change to phoenix dollar = tharman shanmugan (RUPEE-ONLY ISSUE RUPEE INSIDE INDIA-INDRANEE RAJAH BALA THIRU-'ny' etc) eviction = MONEY COLLECTION \$T = RET. INDIA with all) indians employees = priority for AUTO-arrest = COMPUTE = ret. stash a/c (ret. Malaysia hk etc) = ret. landed original DISTRICT-DISTRICT ETERNAL VALUE cannot count private estate)

6. all glyph states no issue close media-corp + ST, ST, ST = ret. + someone collect \$b + sums per y + chip-shots-'info-media-comm' (unqualified tv criminal act + ALL m.d. = ret. Malaysia)

7. someone collect: legislative theft sum per y + all illegal 'A' + per building illegal built over + ret. district-by-district + evacuation landed malaya (conmen-pap) + temasek-cpf dbs details: all illegal-indians since 1965 (Cannot stay) = ret. india

8. other assets overseas = BoNingbo + Bo's'-stacking 'ocbc' = not Malaysian-ATM-('Legislative theft + stat-b + self-titled 'A' for Authority: NOT APPROVED by PHOENIX-landed properties robbed DISTRICT-BY-DISTRICT ret. + flood-in stacking 'oc' (illegal) x 60 since 1965 evacuate unto homeland landed + PER building rental stash = TEMASEK-Ringgilt-Lee-(illegal pax stacking 'oc' x 60: no approval) land (duration = eternal) + money x 60 collection.

9. Require someone collect weapons: overseas assets: cn, usa, india-land (liquidate sell-off) or open to public for official purposes etc

INDEP DAY REPEAT CRIME X 60 OVER BEYOND ... IS OVER
CEMENT X 60 + FLOOD-IN HORSE STACKING 'OC' HUMANS SHOEBOXES INTO HIMSELF-ATM-TOM OVER ROBBED LAND DISTRICT-BY-DISTRICT RET. + CHIP-GENOCIDE OWN: HORSE
NA-(那^{that})-ZI(指^{points}) PHOENIX LOGO: BOOK of DA-NI-EL

PHOENIX ISLANDERS 1965 PLOT (PHOENIX BASE)
9.5.1. META-PLATFORM INC. (/FILED BY FB INC.) MODEL: HIGH ALTITUDE POINT TO MULTIPOINT LINKS (#US 20180054251 A1) (#SAM PADINJAREMANNIL ALEX) (COLLAPSE BLUEPRINT IN BOTH MSB SHORT FOR MARINA BAY SANDS LOCATED NEXT TO "WORLD THIEF BANK" / COURT OF JUSTICE EU) ARCHITECTURAL BLUEPRINT

(FEATURED: INDEP DAY COMPUTER SIMULATION COLLAPSE ECHOED: LKY & TRUMP "WALL-IN")

	<p>EXCEEDINGLY HIGH DEMAND (PRESS: 000) Construction Excuse BEYOND REPEAT CRIME (HORSE-ATM-CONMEN)</p> <p>UNDER HORSE-ATM-CONMEN INDP DAY + EX-CRIMINAL STEALING: OIL to RF-ELECTRICITY NRIC 'SHELL-'ITRON'-BP + FIN-TECH 'FEST' ETC CHIP-GENOCIDE CULPRITS: WB-WT IISS-CHIP-MAN SATELLITE-TELCOM-TECH (SOCIAL MEDIA LISTING) PAY-GANG ETC (SUPPLIER ALERT: change to landed + money adjustment) ETC COMPUTE X TIME-FRAME</p>

IISS

[IISS SLD \(JAPAN'S DEFINITE: NO INTEREST IN PERP CIRCLE + X 500 Y GENOCIDAL call their group 'jesuits' etc anything REPLACEMENT: 'GLOBAL INDIANS & ILLEGALS INDIANS-ESC X 60: SOFTBANK THURAYA LOGO + YAHOO \(THURAYA-HOO\) + GOOGLE = Ret. Key to me](#)

[ALSO, PHOENIX-LAND + PHOENIX STAR BASE: BILLION Y BLOODLINE: GROUP OF ILLEGAL INDIANS + INFRA-\(ATM-\)cheat-money stacking TOM X 60 = COMPUTE + GLYPH SATELLITE](#)

<p><u>IISS SLD</u></p>	
<p>IISS (which resonates with ISIL: PERP-same SATELLITE-TOM-ID x Time-frame)</p>	
<p>IISS CHIP-man</p>	
<p>TABLE SUMMARY OF (Criminal 'Act' + 'Intent' X 60 consistent @ Rajaratnam-Ringgip-pap-INFRA-</p>	
<p>(ATM)-TOM + SATELLITE-TOM + BEYOND PLOTS) = TERMINATED</p>	
<p>IISS CHIP-MAN</p>	<p>COMPUTE</p>
<p>INFRA-CHIP-TOM: (disqualified M.D.) INJECTION SHOTS: 4-5 Y old</p>	<p>LIQUIDATE = CLOSED</p>
<p>INFRA-construction-TOM (Ports-DISCONNECT) LAND + AIR INVASION (death penalty)</p>	<p>FOUNDATION TOM = COMPUTE</p>
<p>WEF-RESET (WHO)</p>	<p>CHIP-in-brain-genocide</p>
<p>WB \$5 x booster x no. nations PER HD sg INFRA-co-vax-CHIP (WB)</p>	<p>#units = Ret. keys + COMPUTE</p>
<p>IBM, INTEL outlets</p>	<p>#units = Ret. keys + COMPUTE</p>

AIIB	EM MILITARY RF-KILL INFRA-B = COMPUTE
INFRA-CHIP-genocide-MILITARY: TV-CHIP + EM LOGO MILITARY	Media-(content WRONG x60) = COMPUTE
POST-TV-CHIP: SATELLITE TOM	EM MILITARY RF-KILL SATELLITE-B = COMPUTE
INFRA-(ATM-)TOM: 'BOA' 'BOC' 'BOS'	COMPUTE gen est. + Ret. Keys
INFRA-(ATM-)TOM + SATELLITE TOM (War Prisoners)	

IISS SLD (JAPAN'S DEFINITE: NO INTEREST IN PERP CIRCLE + X 500 Y GENOCIDAL JESUITS-REPLACEMENT: GLOBAL INDIANS & ILLEGALS INDIANS-ESC X 60:

UNDER INFRA-LAND THIEVES (PHOENIX 1965 PLOT + PLUS 3 PLOTS):	
INFRA-co-vax-CHIP (WB) + INFRA-construction theft LAND INVASION (death penalty)	
INFRA-construction-TOM (Ports-DISCONNECT) LAND + AIR INVASION (death penalty)	
severely disabled BEYOND PLOTS	
illegal india-ESC X 60 @ Rajaratnam + @ IISS (Infra-co-vax)-CHIP-man	
illegal india-ESC X 60 @ World Cities' Scam: use word 'sg' + 'ny'	

COMBINE EVIDENCE: IISS SLD + RAJARTNAM (Illegal Indians mix Msian-INFRA-ATM-SATELLITE: various) + TRILATERAL (Rockefeller mix india)

SEE: unlicensed illegal banking tom decode	Illegal india + illegal msian: INFRA-rob x 60
Global INDIANS RUPEE V DOLLARS GROUP	USD CAD USMCA PLOT
	EM LOGO MILITARY @ RAJARATNAM
PHOENIX-LAND, BEYOND	PLUS 3 DRAGONS FABRICATED GROUPED 'asean' GLYPH: Vietnam Cambodia Burma BIS Fraudster 'Drawing': HKD CN Thai Emirates

	<p>RAJARATNAM-(illegal india x 60)-Trilateral-Desker-India-(tied Rockefeller) JAYAKUMAR-KHRISHNAN: pose (Fake 'asean' rights + Swedish rights) + GOOGLE india overwrite Sapin (Eur):</p> <p>Possible: JP Morgan Chase (WB-rockefeller) removed money from GUPTA DBS upon WLC BANKING TOM DECODE.</p> <p>Possible: cn Ali-pay ANT GROUP (Ringgit-malaysian COMPUTE FRAUD X 60 relocate Malaya: used 'sg' = Elevandi = ret. to me) Swiss Zero Point Heng Swee Keat = removed: RAVI & India group = GFTN</p>	<p>NORDIC-EUR-SWISS PLOT</p> <p>RAVI MENON BAN LOGO paste SBI next: all nations' names. (eur CN 'sg' etc)</p> <p>Heng Swee Keat (Margaret Chan genocidal WHO Ringgit- global law-less + global Public Health + Medicine - GLOBAL BLACKLISTED) genocidal board Ringgit-nus: \$90b + \$m + closed.</p>	
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IISS

Usage of word & venue: 'SLD': (Ringgit-INFRA-ATM X 60 BEYOND + SATELLITE) SHANGRI-LA (MALAYSIAN 'b' ocbc + MALAYSIAN 'Straits Trading' X 60) DIALOGUE SPONSORS (SUDDEN CHANGE: AWS AMAZON, (MICROSOFT'S) ACCENTURE (of MSIAN UOB) 2023):

SHANGRI-LA (Possible: His plantation targeted (1 obvious) + involvement with KILLER-PRODUCTS GROUP-SEC LISTING: GRAB linked SATELLITE TOM) Rajaratnam-pap-lky-illegal since inception: SHANGRI-LA knows LKY-

Post-CO-VAX circuitry CHIP island-wide Singapore including the Singapore military, Lee (on TV and even afterwards CO-VAX SHOTS reported by the South China Post:

CHART 9A: SATELLITE SLD SHANGRI-LA DIALOGUE

SUDDEN DRASTIC SWOP @ IISS 1-DAY MC

TRADITIONAL SPONSORS OF RINGGIT-SLD (USAGE OF HOTEL OWNER 'SHANGRI-LA' DIALOGUE (2019): SUDDEN SWOP in SPONSORS: EM MILITARY X 60 @ Rajaratnam @ IISS to AMAZON (cloud theft)-EM MILITARY PORTS-DISCONNECT

Here is the traditional sponsors of (usage of hotel owner)-Ringgit-SLD 2019 showing a sudden swop: EM MILITARY X 60 @ Rajaratnam (Ringgit-ATM-TOM) @ IISS CHIP-MAN (TERMINATED in ALL LOCATIONS genocide-MILITARY) to: AMAZON (manifested crime being AMAZON LOCKERS outlets San Jose + archived under WLC MILITARY for lab exam and metal melted (forbidden entry: leave it in San Jose)

EXHIBIT: 2023 SLD

SLD SPONSORS

The following organisations are generously sponsoring the IISS Shangri-La Dialogue

LEGAL CONFIRMATION: ACCENTURE INVADE UOB

The invasion CO. ABOVE: RF KILL co-vax CHIP surfaced with obvious intent (connection behind): AWS Amazon and (Microsoft's FIN-TECH FEST: ATM-TOM) Accenture (inside / invade / complicit with Malaysian UOB)

LEGAL CONFIRMATION: ACCENTURE INVADE UOB

Due to the sudden swop to AMAZON (2023) is why this portion is placed under 'BIG-4 shared inventor(s) : Microsoft / Amazon (Locker Outlet PL Fin-statement WWW: Ret. key) / Space X ('Minimally invasive Neural Lace') / Google (San Jose) = ret. keys (to me), cross-over with (matching co-vax shots) CHIP-designs: it is Amazon CLOUD + SATELLITE TOM: criminal act of PORTS INVASION termed 'connectivity' on death penalty. Thus, EM LOGO MILITARY x no. of nations @ Rajaratnam @ IISS-CHIP-Man @ X 100PLUS MILITARY on compulsory PORTS-DISCONNECT e.g. marjot singh M1 Thuraya(h) + Inmarsat + Viasat + AIRBUS (Other: SPACE-X Chip-genocide)

+ brijesh pande TEMBUSU (Ringgit-'s'ia) TEMASEK = Ret. Trillions + keys to me.

<p>LEGAL QUESTIONS: RINGGIT-'ST ENGINEERING' FRAUDSTERS</p>	
<p>1. Where is the rocket(s)? Where is it based? Any?</p> <p>Ringgit-ST Engineering cannot BASE inside PHOENIX-LAND</p>	<p>RET. \$90B \$M</p>
<p>2. Ringgit-pap Teo 2 cyber theft division lee kc building Entire top floor = Removed = Relocate Malaya + 'dg'- India-x = All Indians Ret. India</p> <p>No Indian Space-bro redeem them</p> <p>Conclusion: Illegal Indians + Malaysians illegals INFRA-(ATM) + SATELLITE complicit lying by themselves X 60 Y:</p>	
<p>3. Ringgit-pap Josephine Teo + Indranee Rajah = submit detailed report (mangrove swamp CN + infra-sg with chip-genocide + Thuraya + Inmarsat Viasat + Airbus @ Rajaratnam EM LOGO MILITARY consistent criminal record x 60 Y Illegal Indians @ IISS CHIP-man) on WWW (on death penalty-ID) + base + total amt x no. y (ringgit-pap) + bank a/c holder name</p>	
<p>TEMASEK dbs = ret. 8k + \$ 90b 1st + trillions x time-frame + orchard rd + ports-(DISCONNECT SATELLITE-TOM) + Ret. landed properties (+ farmland + livelihood + building slots) + WHOLE OF PUNGGOL + ret. landed to others</p>	<p>RET. \$Trillions x time-frame + orchard rd + ports</p>

	<p>Ringgit-ocbc = ret. 8k + \$ 90b + \$M x time-frame</p> <p>+ ret. shoeboxes (cheated) monies x 60 + evacuate: landed properties ('veg + cow')</p>	
	<p>(1) self-title: ask-for-money X 60 Y (2) criminal format (BEYOND) x no. EM LOGO MILITARY @ Rajaratnam (when began with ringgit-pap: Fraudsters INFRA-(ATM)-TOM 1965 PLOT (e.g stacking ('cheat-money'), transport from india Indian construction workers say linked to ATM-so-n-so bank)</p> <p>('indp d' – no link or with 'intent' to link)</p> <p>Chip-genocide (began in Ringgit-'sg'-h 4-5 y old + CC stations WHOLE ISLAND = illegal Ringgit-pap absent for duration)</p>	

RE-CAP string illegal Indians since inception 1965 ringgit-INFRA-ATM-pap + SATELLITE TOM:

SEE: Appendix to THE JUDGMENT

<p>Global' 'Indians' Criminals: claim SATELLITE TOM</p>	<p>Marjot Singh: Thurayah + Inmarsat Viasat + Airbus (No such MP'A') = ret. ports keys to me (COMPUTE X 60)</p>
<p>EM LOGO MILITARY @ RAJARATNAM (illegal x 60) 'Organizer' with IISS CHIP-MAN @ SLD</p>	<p>SGD HKD CN THAI VIET CAMBODIA BURMA EM LOGO GUN DOWN: RAJAH & TAN(Malaya) Ringgit-'sg'-x</p>

<p>Thurayah + Inmarsat Viasat + Airbus + Amazon (PORTS-DISCONNECT) See: Raytheon + Lockheed Martin + Allen, Hamilton & Booz (how get tech: from nation)</p> <p>USD CAD AUD NZD MILITARY</p>	<p>NAPIER-India = TEMBUSU-pap Brijesh Pande =</p> <p>TEMASEK = ret. trillions + keys building to me. (all assets san jose + ny)</p>
<p>RAJARATNAM (illegal x 60) (-pap-lky-RINGGIT-ATM) DESKER-Classified: INDIA 'saint Patrick' Also, saint = GLYPH word (bloodline)</p>	<p>RAJARATNAM (-pap-lky-RINGGIT-INFRA-ATM) Illegal Indians status = WHOLE OF ASIA ('GLYPH STATES')</p>
<p>RAJARATNAM JAYAKUMARS-criminal faculties SR JR, Kumar Khrishnan,</p>	
<p>RAJARATNAM Desker + BALA (Classified: INDIA) use 'sg'</p>	<p>OBAMA-CARE(S ACT) CARESHIELD</p>
<p>GLOBAL BANKING TOM DECODE</p>	
<p>RAJARATNAM 'BOARD' RINGGIT-ATM-STRAITS TRADING, so put with RAVI MENON inside RINGGIT-nus genocidal board = ret. \$90 B</p>	<p>'board' Ringgit-Chew Gek Khim with Ravi (Illegals m'sians Indians X 60)</p>
<p>GLOBAL 'Indian' pose: GUPTA-DBS</p>	
<p>SHUT Ringgit-mas-Malaysian =</p>	<p>COMPUTE FRAUD X 60 include KAMALA-RAVI-GOOGLE FRAUD = relocate Malaya</p>
<p>RAVI-'BIS' 'GLOBAL' 'TECH' duped Tier 1 Tier 2: HYPER-LEDGER</p>	<p>'INFRA-CHIP b'</p>
<p>RAVI-'BIS-sg' MAHAL no such address (no assets liquidate: stealing from illegal properties)</p>	
<p>RINGGIT-INFRA-ATM-TOM ('professor' RINGGIT-LEE FOUNDATION,</p>	<p>illegal Malaysian Status: inside WHOLE Phoenix-land x 60:</p>

	<p>INFRA-stacking 'cheat-money' (illegal: put Chinese shoeboxes) + rob landed WHOLE OF PHOENIX-LAND: flood-in-Malaysians: collect notes into ATM-TOM</p> <p>Farmland (self-sustaining) NO CHIP-PORTS</p>	<p>V IISS CHIP-MAN @ Rajaratnam Amazon CHIP-(Marjot Singh MPA Ringgit-ntu claim: Thurayah + Inmarsat Viasat + Airbus = ret. keys + Ringgit-pap LTA = ret. keys (Brijest pande, Ringgit-'sg'-x: Napier-India + TEMBUSU invade = GUN DOWN</p> <p>ALL EM LOGO MILITARY PORTS-DISCONNECT.</p>
	<p>THIRU (GLOBAL BLACKLIST) with INDRANEE RAJAH-WCS-ID short for world cities scam: INFRA-ASIA = GLYPH STATES</p>	<p>'Thiru' 'INFRA-'ASIA' GLYPH STATES = NOT INDIA (LIE X 60: LOW IQ)</p>

SEE: Appendix to THE JUDGMENT

<p>AMAZON LOCKER (INSERT: PHOTO SPECIMEN (EX-7-11))</p>	<p>AMAZON LOCKER (INSERT: PHOTO SPECIMEN (EX-7-11))</p>	
	<p>WLC COURT DISCUSION 1</p>	<p>CRIMINAL EVIDENCE</p> <p>MILITARY WLC Discussion:</p> <p>Main problem with this item 'something's wrong' i.e. 'digital' = harm / hurt Malaya or any nation of resell.</p> <p>REQUIRED ACTION:</p> <p>REMOVE ALL AMAZON LOCKER = off PHOENIX-LAND = Malaysians transport into Malaya (storage inside: Archived under MILITARY WLC / store inside somewhere NOT FOR USE: lab exam) then metal melting.</p> <p>Thus, NOT FOR USE: lab exam e.g. any access to satellite / incoming aircraft etc, then warehouse storage deactivated.</p>

	<p>1. Melt Metal = accessories shop v phoenix laptop</p> <p>2. EXAMPLE: PHOENIX LAPTOP i.e. something better than apple e.g. LOCUST BRAND i.e eat into thieves' im-plantations-dare-NOT touch owner-brand.</p> <p>Also, climate 'intent' = terminated by melting into PHOENIX LAPTOP for RF-KILL reverse TARGET on ALL AMAZOM LOCKER outlets: SAN JOSE.</p>
	<p>COMPUTATION EST.: ITEM AMAZON LOCKET ('BILLING' / Liquidation)</p> <p>est. \$300 sgd-\$500 sg x no. shoeboxes blocks = easily 500 x 10 such = 5000 sgd into WLC MILITARY Fund so, discuss with MILITARY WLC, usually, funding</p> <p>(mainly: COMPUTATION of illegal indians X 60 FRAUD TOTAL) into Phoenix Rocket, s/w, operations etc.</p>
<p>WLC Court Discussion 4</p>	<p>Test Questions</p> <p>Candidate: FRAUDSTER INFRA-P(ortable toilet-over)-CARD (chip-genocide)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Name of person that contact: Tharman Shanmugaratnam to give-out climate award (to follow CN Yang Yi footsteps leaving Keppel Lee K.S. = Sundares Menon SMU moot Lee K.S. = WB #12-01 = ret. keys to me + computer + files inside building but not builder Lee K.S.) 2. which satellite + name manning the climate satellite = detailed report WWW ('He' Perpetrator saw 'you' Tharman Shanmugaratnam in a photo in SMU = means Lee K.S. to him.)
<p>WLC COURT DISCUSSION 1</p>	<p>SAME PRODUCT GROUP</p> <p>SAN JOSE offices keys = Google (take-over) + Amazon-cloud (take-over) + FB-Meta-pay (take-over: NO pay) / Microsoft-fin-tech fest all ATM-tom (take a look of office: Seattle)</p> <p>MILITARY (Joint exercise) HERO sign-up + food delivery (interview by me required) bike-in San Jose (LEGAL TO:) upload WWW ('shoeboxes' X 60</p>

		<p>monies) change to WLC @ All Glyph Tech Trades, WLC @ Americas (White + Latin + Mexico) tech trades.</p> <p>PLUS 3 CN J K + EM LOGO MILITARY fabricated 'asean' Vietnam Cambodia Burma Thailand HKD Malaya EM KILL MILITARY + PHOENIX-SG-Chinese (Listen to me) MILITARY preferred.</p> <p>Volunteer USMCA plot AUD NZD v rupee (interview by me required).</p>								
		<p>WLC = WORLD LAW COURT + JUDGE of SEC KILLER PRODUCTS = COMPUTE</p>								
		<p>CRIMINAL ELEMENTS</p>								
		<p>google San Jose = ret. keys office (Put monitor screen inside San Jose office 1st on WWW 247 Surveillance):</p> <p>SAME product group Space-X, Amazon-(selling cloud)-EM LOGO @ IISS CHIP x no. military nations = Entered Phoenix land (Prior to chip-genocide at W.B. Washington)</p>								
		<p><u>PL SUBMISSION 1ST</u></p> <p>AMAZON outlets (all outlets) = Ret. keys 1ST in San Jose to me ('shoeboxes' monies)</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="500 1308 1390 1866"> <tr> <td data-bbox="500 1308 732 1356"></td> <td data-bbox="732 1308 1390 1356"></td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="500 1356 732 1404"></td> <td data-bbox="732 1356 1390 1404">Ret. all GOOGLE = keys San Jose</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="500 1404 732 1774"></td> <td data-bbox="732 1404 1390 1774"> <p>Ret. all AMAZON LOCKER outlets = keys San Jose</p> <p>[upload detailed shop outlets P&L WWW and F statement WWW on assets etc on PER locker outlets keys' return]</p> <p>INCLUDE: illegal claim to SHIPPING DETAILS if AN body (even) bought anything</p> </td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="500 1774 732 1866"></td> <td data-bbox="732 1774 1390 1866">SPACE-X-India</td> </tr> </table>				Ret. all GOOGLE = keys San Jose		<p>Ret. all AMAZON LOCKER outlets = keys San Jose</p> <p>[upload detailed shop outlets P&L WWW and F statement WWW on assets etc on PER locker outlets keys' return]</p> <p>INCLUDE: illegal claim to SHIPPING DETAILS if AN body (even) bought anything</p>		SPACE-X-India
	Ret. all GOOGLE = keys San Jose									
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	SPACE-X-India									

			<p>In the same product group: SPACE-X-India rockets which look phallic-pervert) = San Jose (to me).</p> <p>Classified as nonsense rocket design: use replica multiplied many times larger (only indians think they are: 'cute') phallic-pervert.</p>
			<p>SBI CLUSTER COMPUTATION</p> <p>In conjunction with billing operations inside and terminated off PHOENIX LAND with illegal access to currencies stash, The Judgement is ONLY genocide those that with criminal act + intent i.e. wiped clean by their own cluster.</p> <p>SBI (robbed stash abroad X 60) of other pp foreign land nations' money = compute + inform all EM LOGO MILITARY (GLYPH) states / nations: USMCA PLOT + PLUS 3 + EM LOGO fabricated grouped states + NORDIC-EUR-SWISS PLOT.</p> <p>It appears to be a small area in India = can 'gun down' (deactivate-require confirmation). Otherwise, risk having to wipe clean the whole race. Anyway, illegal Indians have declared way many many times: (1) consistent criminal record x 60 EM LOGO MILITARY @ Rajaratnam add @ CHIP-Man (2) committed chip-genocide WB d.c. outlet: with the string of highlighted illegal Indians leading up to genocide and KAMALA-RAVI attempt (ABORTED by WLC and BILLING FRAUD \$600M) (3) SPACE-X minimally invasive CHIP-(co-vax-genocide: RF-KILL) (4) BALA INMARSAT + VIASAT Russian + Ukraine AI-kill RESET WEF-India.</p>

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SHANGRI-LA (MALAYSIAN b ocbc RINGGIT X 60 NOT SINGAPORE) DIALOGUE SPONSORS

2018):

Prior to 2019 @ IISS CHIP-Man inject 20xx (already pre-mediated: chip-genocide (Ringgit-pap) LEE inject in order to inject EM LOGO MILITARY ('intentionally' aired over satellite of mediacorp-malaysian: THURAYA + INMARSAT VIASAT + AIRBUS + MINIMALLY INVASIVE suggestive SPACE-X-INDIA) since inception of 'Rajaratnam SCH' 2008 @ Rajaratnam (illegal Indians 'organizer') inception 1965 PLOT: INFRA-(Malaysian illegal stay) TOM stacking 'sg'd' into his ATM-TOM. The word 'sg' is fabricated. Since it was in the aftermath of 2001 attack, satellite appears to be connected to plausible: Indians-(INDIA, electronic passport theft, SAN JOSE NY D.C.) (funding X60 maybe stolen from rightful owner PHOENIX-LAND).

The unclear owner behind the paid 1-3 days MC-CHIP-MAN / Ringgit-ATM (straits trading) of ocbc since inception: FAKE NORDIC-(Straits Trading OCBC-SEE: APPENDIX TO THE JUDGMENT, PHOTO-ID of illegal Indians (illegal stay inside PHOENIX-LAND) AUTO-BAR AUTO-VOID since inception 1965 PLOT e.g. FAKE-NORDIC-'Drew-Napier'-India (Mumtha WB co-vax chip genocide Cavinder Bull Davinder Singh Susil Nair INSOL Shanmugam (Rajah tan ALSO, AUTO-BAR cannot sign criminal papers write anything AUTO-VOID paperwork (repeat crime BEYOND) TERMINATED = GUN DOWN BY EM LOGO MILITARY @ Vietnam, Cambodia, Burma, Thailand, HKD, PLUS 3 PLOTS: CN (preliminary only: 'yahoo maybe 'yah sat' etc) J ('softbank': Thuraya logo but see maker) K, Napier-India TEMBUSU = GUN DOWN BY CN) all illegal Indians entered Malaya with Malaysians: entered with criminal intent into PHOENIX-LAND began stacking), Ringgit-'sg'-x-'s'ia PORTS-1. MPA 2. LTA 3. HDB = Ret. keys / COMPUTE into PHOENIX DOLLARS, conversion for evacuation (of illegal stay ION-malaysian-shoeboxes Malaysian-unto landed in Malaya) / closed (removal: ringgit-INFRA-atm-PAP ask-4-money x 60 criminal format). (With BEYOND repeat crime intent: criminal act of inviting EM LOGO x no. MILITARY @ Rajaratnam H.E. excellency Organ Damage. Consistent criminal record X 60 = TEMINATED).

Thus, come across as 1-unknown-Tom (satellite access) based using Indians: inside USA-13 and inside Rajaratnam (ATM-malaysian-TOM-INFRA-BEYOND TERMINATED: Ret. \$Trillions, Ringgit-ntu-nus-\$b-Straits Trading, Ringgit-ocbc-\$m)

In other words, it about bank-toms (piloted tested) + INFRA-(illegal stay Malaysian use illegal Indians construction workers dbs, exhibit behavioral stacking that cannot be charged money for or to house humans)-TOM + satellite TOM: THURAYA + INMARSAT VIASAT + AIRBUS (OTHERS: SPACE-X) etc.

FURTHER DETAILS: THE JUDGEMENT (COMPUTATION APPENDIX)

	<p>SUSPECTS / CONFIRMED GUILTY</p> <p>@ RAJARATNAM (illegal Indians X 60 + Illegal Malaysians Ringgit-ATM-TOM inside PHOENIX-LAND. (NOT ASIA, NOT PHOENIX) Build as many: ION-nized membrane potentials Mall = REMOVE all Malaysian ATM-TOM out of ORCHARD RD = ret. Malaya: TEMASEK-Ringgit-Lee (robbed stacking = cannot charge + cannot house humans + lousy materials, evacuation: RF-bad soil islandwide = exhibit war prisoner (unclean))</p>	<p>CONSISTENT CRIMINAL RECORD X 100-500</p> <p>RAJARATNAM Blacklisted by Americans</p>
	<p>Ringgit-Lee-foundation-INFRA-TOM (Illegal stay X 60 malaysian TEMASEK exhibit 'war prisoner' stacking 'sg-d fabricated' into ATM-TOM: = cannot charge money for stacking + ret. shoeboxes monies + CONVERSION PHOENIX DOLLARS (physical booklet: PHOENIX ATM) = ret. Malaya landed properties PHOENIX GRANITE WLC = cannot build anything over LAND 1. LTA 2. MPA 3. BCA etc Ringgit-ocbc-dbs-TEMASEK Prisoners' 'Legislative' stat-board theft sites =</p>	<p>\$Trillions (1) On illegal stay, INFRA-TOM-(TEMASEK, TEMBUSU, illegal Indians NORDIC-Napier-INDIA) + INCLUDE THE ASK-FOR-MONEY-LEGISLATIVE THEFT FRAUD CONSITE-GENOCIDAL TASK FORCE committed-RINGGIT-'PAP' ringgit-ntu-nus-rajaratnam-sgh-sgx-dgx(death)-etc set-up: Ret. Trillions, \$b \$ m, build as many buildings (orchard rd) to lay claim but NOT HIS LAND (2) flood-in Malaysians on illegal stay, illegal Indians = ret. india): into ATM-TOM x 60: exhibit war prisoner behaviour: cannot charge money nor use stacking to house humans = ret. shoeboxes monies (3) NO CLAIM OVER PHOENIX-LAND: cannot build anything over any land: attempt profit from train route alongside his MONEY-LAND (ION-ZIED MEMBRANE = ret. key) ATM-TOM (4) His 1st stash + subsequent stash + all assets worldwide: ny san jose = belongs to PHOENIX STAR. CONCLUSION</p>

		PERP-infra-(chip-genocide: committed) Infra-Tom (illegal stay x 60) cannot not lay claim to PHOENIX-LAND.
	Illegal stay Malaysian RINGGIT-ATM	\$m x no. y
	RINGGIT-nus-genocidal	\$b
	SATELLITE CO.	THURAYA + INMARSAT VIASAT + AIRBUS (OTHERS: SPACE-X) etc. Marjot singh m1 + Brijesh Pande TEMUBSU = Napier-India = Ringgit-'s'g-x-'s'ia = LIQUIDATE all shareholders, forbidden pick any race he like Relocate under Malaya. CONVERT PHOENIX DOLLARS: purchase aircrafts.
	Waiting 'President' of criminals (delayed: ret. key / time limit) submit: bank a/c name of all legislative theft sites + (criminal) satellite (removal) & bank a/c name of ATM-TOM backdate to 1965 SBI = TERMINATED (cluster, SBI, various: SPACE-X Vandenberg: check)	
	'ST-Engineering' = rockets? + bank a/c name = Ret. \$Trillions Reports Teo 2 + Indranee Rajah (WCS = Thiru 'ny' INFRA-prosecution, ASIA = NOT India LIE X 60 LOW IQ) invasion (mangrove CN + infra-sg): rocket + satellite + a/c ST \$b + bank a/c name	Ret. \$Trillions AIBB (Prosecuted) = compute PHOENIX DOLLARS
	BASIC (other this BASIC LANDED PROPERTIES ('veg + cow') SURVIVAL, no party REQUIRED ('fraudsters': ask-4-money fraud) = PHOENIX GRANITE WLC + cpf hdb Ret. shoeboxes monies (CORRECT Notes: PHOENIX DOLLAR) 'sg'-fabricated from inception linked BO'S-'C'-'A' = SAME PERP	No one: Cannot set-up 'party' ask-4-money x 60 – 100 ETC ('legislative' theft con fraud AMT X 60 COMPUTE)

<p>plausible (OTHER fabricated flags / logos nations: WRONG)</p>	
<p>EMPTY, PHOENIX STAR BASE FARMLAND + STONE TEMPLE, nothing rob / plot / collapse etc (SAN JOSE FB-META pay rapist CN / USA-13 etc: sam alex pardinjaremannil: criminal intent 'drawing COPIED' act / building insurance / chip-genocide (all humans living on granite landed in Malaya with 'veg + cow')</p>	<p>\$Trillions stolen: SET- other targeted states: Mongolia, EM LOGO Fabricated GLYPH states (illegal Indians: Rajaratnam, Rajah, since inception, severely disabled BEYOND PLOTS: CARES-ACT ('Obama'-Care) CARESHIELD etc (criminal variants) following the pattern: INFRA-CHIP (EM LOGO) MILITARY in order chip-genocide (PRE-MED X 60 @ Rajaratnam Ringgit-illegal stay) @ IISS CHIP-MAN = TERMINATED (all locations) Trilateral-Rockefeller-depend on PERP-ID-SATELLITE:</p> <p>if the satellites are proven innocent, the remaining one is guilty.</p>
	<p>BEYOND repeat crime PLOTS = TERMINATED = EM LOGO MILITARY GUN DOWN</p>

As explained (BILLION Y EVIDENCE): 'India' = not YAH ZHOU (ASIA GLYPH STATES)
 As explained (BILLION Y EVIDENCE), 'India' = not YAH ZHOU (ASIA GLYPH STATES) hence this illegal person should not even be present prior to chip-genocide.

Another critically blatant error are the MILITARY STATES invitees: suspicious exhibiting several imposters singh claiming white states.

Leading up to the pre-meditated EM LOGO MILITARY with consistent criminal record (and diagrammatical expressions: EM LOGO *BEYOND PLOTS* 'H.E.' HIS/HER Excellency ORGAN NATION RF-KILL MILITARY @ invitees no. military

states x 60 Y @ Rajaratnam (illegal Indians stay: entered Malaya) Ringgit-INFRA-ATM-TOM + SATELLITE TOM) since inception 1965 PLOT X 60 COMPUTE.

BEYOND PLOTS = TERMINATED

IISS

SHANGRI-LA (MALAYSIAN b ocbc X 60 NOT SINGAPORE) DIALOGUE SPONSORS (PRIOR TO THE 'PRE-MEDITATED CHIP-GENOCIDE SUDDEN CHANGE: AWS AMAZON, (MICROSOFT'S) ACCENTURE (of MSIAN UOB) 2016):

Traditional sponsors (consistency: aircraft brands e.g. Raytheon, Lockheed Martin) in previous years: 2016

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AIRBUS MAXAR

Booz Allen Hamilton

Booz Allen Hamilton has been at the forefront of strategy, technology, and engineering for more than 100 years.

in previous years: 2017

SLD SPONSORS

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Booz Allen Hamilton

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[SEE: APPENDIX TO THE JUDGMENT on AIRBUS + THUARYAH + INMARSAT + VIASAT](#)

[SHANGRI-LA \(MALAYSIAN b ocbc X 60 NOT SINGAPORE\) DIALOGUE SPONSORS \(SUDDEN CHANGE: TRILATERAL COMMISSION'S JAP BEER 2022\): @ RAJARATNAM @ IISS 'CHIP-MAN'](#)

[SRI LANKA ILLEGAL INDIANS X 60 @ RAJARATNAM-dead, PAP ILLEGAL X 60, M'sian b severely disabled beyond OCBC EM LOGO fabricated PLOTS: INFRA-CHIP construction b + F-STASH\)](#)

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Airbus

Airbus is an international pioneer in the aerospace industry.

It is not strange but a clear answer (clear intent behind the apparently irrelevant connection) between product 'Asahi' Japan beer (PM dead-to be accounted for): NO INTEREST IN PERP-CIRCLE at the equally not strange but criminal set-up of @ IISS CHIP-MAN (intent) (@ Rajaratnam-entourage of illegals e.g. INFRA-ATM-TOM-Malaysian-FAKE-NORDIC-'Straits Trading' illegal Indian stay x 60: cannot summon any MILITARY, any nation, anyone) venue @ SLD

Stolen technology of Japanese at IEEE Forums: may have enabled the Japanese to have first-hand knowledge of the sinister agenda behind the set-up of PRE-MEDITATED EM LOGO (Diagrammatical Criminal 'intent' behind drawing of Criminal Act: EM CHIP-genocide MILITARY) Illegal Indians + Illegal Malaysians: AUTO-BAR from summoning x no. of MILITARY STATES @ Rajaratnam 'organizer' @ IISS CHIP-MAN (obvious sign: criminal intent / act)

Alternate beer products also appeared @ The Trilateral hence signifying the connection behind both @ IISS CHIP-MAN e.g. 'Rockefeller' whereby the rockets 'Rockefeller' depends on rely on a chip (inside computers). Due all these suspicious signals, and illegal summon of no. military states (AUTO-VOID), is likely the key reason behind the beer labels as a way of expressing: NO INTEREST IN PERP CIRCLE.

Explained in this WLC Materials & Evidence (GLYPH Categories) in detail:

1. IBM (BEYOND H.E. ORGAN DAMAGE with diagrams drawings of criminal intent chained to a bomb) Drug-Neuromorph-PERP-ic Systems @ RAJARATNAM X 60 RUPEES V DOLLARS) @ IISS CHIP-man (illegal Indians cannot sign/summon; on illegal stay x 60)
2. IEEE IBM INTEL (Chip-replica) SAMSUNG: GO SHOTS turned Micro-chip
3. GO SHOTS turned Micro-chip: Medical Evidence (continents: USMCA PLOT (CARES ACT: CARESHIELD, 'OBAMACARE' pose with BALA-INDIA), PLUS 3 PLOT, EM LOGO Fabricated grouped, HYPERLEDGER duped Tier 1 Tier 2 Pilot Test Mapping, BEYOND PLOTS stacking 'sgd-fabricated' (PHOENIX-LAND) = TERMINATED
4. X100PLUS TESTING (log-on) MILITARY: actual SATELLITE INVASION + 8K (fabricated CSI M) (TOUCH CN)
5. IISS CHIP-man TERMINATED WORLDWIDE @ Rajaratnam (illegal Indians + illegal Malaysians-pap- ('legislative' stacking humans theft (fraud notes), fraud-sites, con-sites into ATM-Tom= buildings ret. keys = COMPUTE X 60) cannot sign, cannot summon any military / nations 'meet'; on illegal stay x 60) + FIN-TECH

FEST BAN-FAST-PAY CN rapist + PAY-LATER (GRAB) PAY-NOW (dbs) (TOUCH illegal Malaysians X 60-ATM-TOM inside PHOENIX-LAND) + FED-PAY-PAL (India TOUCH USA-13)

PAY-REPLICATED FORMAT X NO. MILITARY STATES @ FIN-TECH FEST (INDIANS ARREST)

USA-13 (space-)rapist	Illegal Malaysians + Illegal Indians (stay: x 60)	CN (space-)rapist
FED-PAY-PAL	PAY-LATER (GRAB)	FAST-PAY
FED-WIRE	PAY-NOW (dbs)	
PAY-PAL	BEYOND PHOENIX-LAND PLOT	PLUS 3 PLOT: DRAGONS (BEYOND PHOENIX)
TERMINATED	TERMINATED	TERMINATED

6. Criminal Intent of 'Neural Net': CO-VAX CHIP (add: Master-Slave intent v 100PLUS MILITARY) e.g. (TOUCH NY) NASDAQ (PERP-ID trying to replicate unto: Malaysian infra-ATM illegal stay (Ret. \$Trillions, \$B, \$M) 'straits-trading' illegal Malaysian (TOUCH BEYOND PHOENIX-LAND): Fraud country no such name-fabricated + EM LOGO MILITARY Fabricated states PLUS 3 PLOTS: CN J K (SATELLITE-TOM) (BEYOND = TERMINATED)

'BO'A' USMCA PLOT	'BO'S'-Fabricated word BEYOND Stacking PHOENIX-LAND (1965 PLOT)	'BO'C' PLUS 3: DRAGONS + Fabricated EM Grouped States Label AUTO-VOID
NASDAQ ny: chip (Description: trading 000,000,000 IBM CHIP monies / murder scam meet of nations using military 100PLUS or illegal individuals card-imposters)	NO CLAIM to FAKE- 'straits trading'-CLOSED-ports-DISCONNECT: ret. keys (a) ringgit-thuraya logo Malaysian 'sg'-x + others COMPUTE X 60 \$AMT = relocate Malaya	Repeat crime = TERMINATED
(JUDGE OF SEC) intentionally killer products + murder intent	(b) FAKE-NORDIC-'self-titled' Malaysian 1. Straits trading FAKE-'currencies' EM LOGO X no. of MILITARY + BEYOND CHIP-genocide currencies) @ Rajaratnam-ringgit-pap- = Ret. \$Trillions \$b \$m +	CHIP-genocide-intent drawing (EM LOGO) 'H.E.'-ORGAN DAMAGE rights x no. Fabricated (Grouped = TERMINATED, Close-Ports: Napier-India TEMBUSU ('wrong' FAKE-(WCS-Illegal Indians)-civil

		<p>Malaysian ST Engineering 2. Ret. Rocket + \$b</p> <p>2. 'trading' CASINO'-CON Electronic PRESS: 000</p>	<p>engineering) = CN MILITARY GUN DOWN</p> <p>+</p> <p>EM MILITARY GUN DOWN Rajah- Tan (AUTO-VOID paper-work on death penalty): repeat crime (x 60)</p>
<p>e.g. Master-Slave intent v 100PLUS MILITARY</p> <p>Meaning the MILITARY is the PRIME TARGET in order to chip-genocide</p>	<p>EM LOGO x no. of MILITARY + Malaysian x 60 INFRA-stacking war prisoner-atm-TOM: illegal Malaysian + illegal Indians = Ret. landed + ret. land others + ret. shoeboxes (flood-in) to malaya landed. (on fraud notes-ATM)</p>		
	<p>ION-ZED MEMBRANE MALL = Ret. keys carry out = ret. Malaya stay) DRUG-CHIP- GENOCIDE MILITARY criminal intent + criminal act</p>		
	<p>PHOENIX SATELLITE + PHOENIX-TRI-SOLAR ALL GLYPH TECH TRADING (small scale): Explanations & Discussions</p> <p>India-'dg'x puthu (death) + 'luxembourg'-x (WCS-India Indranee + Rajah = EM GUN DOWN):</p> <p>Additional: Mission RETRIEVE of assets San Jose (station + guard mapping + PERP-ID) with WLC DOCTOR OF COMPUTERS cert.</p> <p>PHOENIX DOLLAR = proper evacuation PHOENIX GRANITE WLC of humans = 'EMPTY' ret. to farmland + stone temple (nothing to rob / plot / collapse / schemes etc) + garrisons throughout (illegal Indians enter airspace)</p>		
	<p>LEGAL CONCLUSION</p>		

BO'S-C-A' PLUS 3: DRAGONS (ALL Wrong Label)-ATM-Tom + SATELLITE-Tom = COMPUTE ('intent' rob Tier-1, 2 for himself) + AIIB + WB chip-genocide (space-x) + BIS fraudsters board (NOT any nations, PERP-Tom himself) = MILITARY ARREST COMPUTE ret. closed.

Google + amazon locker + FB-META-PAY (format replication X no. Military states) + (computers) (FAKE WCS) 'exchange' bases linked 'satellite'-tom = Ret. keys

PRIOR CRIMINAL RECORD

X500 Y criminal record means = A lot of nations' military can give evidence of airspace (crime).

LEGAL CONFIRMATION: PERP-AIRBUS + M1 + THURAYA(H) = COASTAL LAND + AIR INVASION (death penalty) + BEYOND MILITARY GUN DOWN. OTHERS: SPACE-X-INDIA: minimally invasive CHIP-GO SHOTS.

Further details on SATELLITE-TOM: THE JUDGMENT

IISS SLD (2023)

ASAHI BEER @ TRILATERAL (COPIED LOGO) @ IISS CHIP-MAN

The (apparently 'Irrelevant product') 'Asahi' beer X 2 (2022, 2023) @ IISS CHIP-MAN @ RAJARATNAM-dead and 'Suntory' beer @ Trilateral Commission shows the clear repeated expression of and implied meaning: NO interest in PERP-circle.

There are 2 definitions of glyph word 朝 in 'Asahi beer'_朝(日) in glyph means: the official in court greets

the ruler (1) 臣子在朝廷拜见君, the ruler 君主 refers to: 君主时代的官吏 meaning 'highest ruler over court officials'.

	<p style="text-align: right;">佛</p> <p>The secondary (of less likelihood in context) meaning refers to worshippers of buddha: 'PH'-佛-FO⁴³. (2) 宗教徒到圣地或礼拜神、佛。</p> <p>Thus, here, 'Asahi (beer)'_朝(日) Shimbun 报纸 ('newspaper') is the name of the Japanese beer, that 'participated'.</p> <p>Another example, the glyph word 潮 in state of 潮州 appears in China glyph means 月亮和太阳引力造成的海洋水面定时涨落的现象 which refers to: the moon and sun's magnetic (attraction) force creates the ocean's surface's fixed periodic rise / fall phenomenon.</p>
	<p><u>IISS SLD (2022)</u> ASAHI BEER @ TRILATERAL (COPIED LOGO) @ IISS CHIP-MAN</p> <div data-bbox="224 945 760 1218" style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 5px; text-align: center;"> <p><i>IISS Shangri-La Dialogue</i></p> <p>The Asahi Shimbun</p> </div> <p>ASAHI BEER @ TRILATERAL COMMISSION (COPIED LOGO) @ IISS CHIP-MAN The expression 'Asahi Beer' at the trilateral commission: Implied meaning being NO interest in PERP-circle.</p> <p>Rationale: Japan (Cash preferred). This concerns the relevant SATELLITE-TOM.</p>
	<p><u>IISS SLD SHOWS:</u> Implied meaning appears to be: no interest in PERP Circle.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Stated: cash preferred 2. The Japanese submitted: Infra-co-vax-evidence 3. X 500 Y expulsion: genocidal 'Jesuits' set-up USA-13⁴⁴

⁴³ For example, (Mistranslation: Saint) Sheng-聖Jo(-Yue約) se-瑟 ph-佛 ('Joseph')

	<p>4. Replacement Format: India-ESC X 60 called 'global Indians'</p> <p>Other considerations:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. IEEE IBM Tokyo (but JAP PM Longest serving: no record of being attacked) 2. WB CONSITE: to decipher PERP-ID
<p>Review of (other BW Locations)</p>	<p><u>There is a record of the actual News-paper 'Asahi Shimbun':</u> The War Ministry (of Japan: <i>permitted</i> due to the otherwise reportedly controlled Japanese press) to make public illegal covert operations (wrt BW deployment in Manchuria and various locations):</p> <p>On 23 May 1940, the Tokyo Asahi Shimbun printed Ishii (Glyph: _) Shiro (Glyph: _)'s photograph with commendation in relation to the 'death factories' (BW + CW: 1931 – 1942).</p>
	<p><u>Keywords associated with this character Ishii Shiro: Unit 731</u></p> <p>Keywords associated include:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Infectious Disease Research Lab, Tokyo which mirrors the American version by Anthony Fauci (yet linked location: Wuhan WIV). 2. Criminal Universities: Tokyo Army Medical College / Kyoto Imperial University / Tokyo Imperial University etc reason for citing: due to enormous influence Ishii Shiro had over (BW + CW). 3. Curious sounding: 'Green' Cross Co. 1947 v Red Cross. This is contemplating the remote or non-existence of connection between 'Greening' in co.-vid & co-vax-RFID-2020 + fin-(ger)tech electronic digits etc. Also, in contrast, in Ishii Shiro's 'death factories' case, ultrasonic was used instead. <p>The original meaning: can include 'green' pastures in Da-('big')-vid (wei-'protector' / space general) as opposed to CO.- (company)-vid-'protect'. Also, the Glyph ('bible'-space) Text overwrites the binary code programmed from outer-space unto the (radio frequency transmitter in the micro-chipped from the GO Shots).</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 4. Field tests: materials adjustments for bomb-shells 5. Ishii Shiro's Army Bocki Kyusui Bu: (translation) Anti-Epidemic Water Supply and Purification Bureau which suspiciously resonates with the 'New Water'. There was a scene in which Ishii Shiro urinated into his filters and offered the concoction to the (of) Emperor a cup of filtrated urine water (rejected) which Shiro downed with the delight the urine-turned-water, which fits exactly the description 'New Water' (fabricated-word 'Singapore'-version: comprises of Glyph beings).

See also, genocidal prior criminal record 'Jesuits' Expulsion of X 500 Y, fraudsters that copied the glyph text and murder crime set-up: USA & Japan-bombed.

6. The 'Diagnosis and Treatment' maybe a common term / coincidence / originator of or copied by the American (& other states) Version CDC patented ('war crimes profitable') process e.g. Identification-Diagnosis-Treatment-Prevention etc explained
7. Overall, his criminal intent + criminal 'vision' envisioning the usage of BW (+ CW) as a means to a sort of leadership affirmation, ironically, after exposure to the 1925 Geneva Disarmament Convention which outlawed both, when one of the (Japanese) War Ministry Bureau attended.

IISS SLD (Malaysian Hotel: Malaysian OCBC straits 'trading' PRESS: 000, target GRAB money) 1-Day MC SURNAME: CHIP-MAN (IBM INTEL replica)

PHOENIX-LAND (1965 PLOT): illegal Malaysians ATM-criminals-INFRA-stacking non-stop islandwide + illegal Indians (cannot summon any military, nations, 'meet', cannot sign: criminals intent x no. PLOTS)

This is to show the time-frame between 1965 PLOT (prior to the entry of PHOENIX-LAND with criminal intent against unsuspecting Malaya-Chinese flood-in for INFRA-stacking shoeboxes (cannot house humans + cannot charge money + cannot build anything over any land) into ATM-TOM) and 2019.

Prior to the 2020 TV-(SATELLITE TOM)-injection of Lee in order to CHIP-genocide SGD (and phoenix islanders) and already pre-meditated X 60 Y EM LOGO MILITARY @ Illegal Indians stay (enter: NO CLAIM with criminal intent + BEYOND with illegal Malaysians in orchard rd ION) RAJARATNAM-dead.

The IISS Shangri-La Dialogue is Asia's premier defence summit. It's a unique meeting

The BEYOND PLOTS: is a repeat crime (criminal act and criminal intent) of LAW-LESS AUTO-VOID paper-work of: illegal Indians Cavinder Bull (WB PHOTO-ID: CHIP-genocide Mumtha Washington D.C. and RAVI-KAMALA attempt: 600M BILLING only 1 sum backdated to bank a/c name: 1965 PLOT), Davinder Singh and Susil Nair: 1-Napier-India + 1-Rajah-Tan-Malaya: EM LOGO MILITARY GUN DOWN (PLUS 3 PLOTS, BEYOND PHOENIX LAND, FABRICATED GLYPH GROUPED PLOTS)

Criminals 'Intent' Illegal Malaysians FAKE-NORDIC Chinese ATM Enter (1965 PLOT) and FAKE-NORDIC Illegal Indians enter Malaya:

Ringgit-ATM (war prisoner 'stacking' Fabricated 'sgd') X 60 Y with 1-Napier-India + 1-Rajah-Tan (Indranee Rajah WCS Ringgit-pap illegal Malaysians Chinese ATM + Illegal Indians X 60 inside PHOENIX LAND) with GLOBAL (Indians) BLACKLISTED: Thiru (with INFRA-'ASIA' Banner: as evidence of criminal intent and criminal act in conjunction with the LAW-LESS illegal Indians at inception 1965 PLOT (of 'legislative' theft sites + illegal buildings theft sites: into ATM-TOM for COMPUTATION X 60.

Ringgit-ATM-(set-up 'party' ask-for-money 'Legislative' theft: \$M - \$Trillions) on illegal Malaysians stay inside PHOENIX-LAND where INFRA-tom began (cannot house) humans stacking non-stop islandwide + TEMASEK 1ST STASH and subsequent stashes from robbing landed properties (cannot build anything over any land. It is required for the return of: ETERNAL LAND AMT Ret. + land ret. to others since 1965 PLOT + shoeboxes X 60 monies Ret. evacuate to Malaya-Land).

Thus, unhindered, illegal Indians that were NOT supposed to be inside the WHOLE OF ASIA 'GLYPH STATES' decide to commit: (1) CHIP-genocide and (2) BEYOND PLOTS: repeat crime with (3) SATELLITE-TOM + ATM-'Legislative' Theft: (stolen stash) \$M - \$Trillions X 60Y.

For example, (1) CHIP-genocide over (2) SATELLITE-TV broadcast (lee with the MILITARY) criminal act, intending to proceed: (3) BEYOND PLOTS repeat crime with Indians on illegal stay X 60 Y @ RAJARATNAM (illegal summon of EM LOGO MILITARY states: criminal act @ IISS CHIP-MAN (SLD sec listed, institutional investors TEMASEK and other malaysian criminals (shareholders / 'foundations' / (FRAUD / CON / THEFT) buildings' 'legislative'+statutory boards' theft-sites: for review and termination for the ret. of assets, keys, rockets and > \$Trillions + \$b \$m per page of illegal document X 60).

Subsequent, Ringgit-ntu-SATELLITE-TOM: Marjot singh m1 Thuraya (Yah-sat amazon locker Yah-oo) + Inmarsat Viasat + Airbus: Committed. Also, various SATELLITE products featured @ IISS CHIP-MAN.

IBM or IEEE claims to have some projects mention with Ringgit-ntu: universities fees bank a/c requires checking backdate = COMPUTE. The genocidal Ringgit-ntu-nus-sgh's'ia-Napier-Indian illegals & (Malaysian) shareholders = COMPUTATION.

SURNAMED 'CHIP-MAN' PAID 1-3-DAY MC @ IISS @ RAJARATNAM EM LOGO MILITARY.

Beside the surname 'CHIP-MAN' (or 'WANG DI' the FAKE: prior series of FAKE NORDIC-indians Napier-Indians illegal (AUTO-BAR cannot sign AUTO-VOID on death penalty: repeat crime 1965 x 60) NORDIC-malaysian chinese 'straits-trading': for example, the KAMALA-'Harris' (Maybe 'Via-sat') that PERP-ID thought was funny for the upcoming chip-genocide: There are 1-2 considerations which include: (1) the MC was paid for his (western-) accent for 1-3 DAYS @ IISS organized by @ Rajaratnam-ATM-malaysian and indians on illegal stay X 60 Y of criminal act ('Straits Trading'-

board with criminal record of TEMASEK TEMBUSU-Napier-India + Rajah Tan INFRA-rob foreign lands: repeat crime) with SATELLITE-TOM (stolen funds X 60 high likelihood with return of rockets by ST Engineering with \$b estimate to \$Trillions AMT x no. y)

(RUPEE + RINGGIT V FORBIDDEN LANDS i.e. MILITARY STATES)

(illegal Malaysians ATM + Illegal Indians: X 60 consistent criminal record)

(2) There were complaints (questioning) in the british parliament by the military on illegal foreign (drugs) and criminal ring that were inconsistent with CHIP-MAN's criminal act: so he will be paid by the criminal (to ignore the BRITISH or ignorant of BRITISH military complaint in Parliament: under killer-SATELLITE-tom + 'b'-ATM-tom that shrinks money.) This is stifled by illegal rocket launch from stolen stash (for checking): replacement with an illegal Indian inside the parliament building.

INMARSAT is listed under UK: unclear for now.

Further details (on ATM-Toms in PLOTS): The Appendix to The Judgment

Illegals Indians X 60 @ Rajaratnam 'organizer' of @ IISS CHIP-MAN, 'Legislative theft x 60 COMPUTE'-Malaysian- (Ringgit-Lee-Foundation: Lee Shih Tih-TEMBUSU-TEMASEK to ret. LAND (1st stash + subsequent stash + All assets worldwide: using PHOENIX-LAND x 60 with BEYOND PLOTS criminal act) + LAND to others + shoeboxes monies x 60 + All buildings keys)-ATM-pap illegals X 60, F-stash: EM LOGO MILITARY X 60 SATELLITE-TOMS = ret. keys to bases.

HERE EVIDENCE OF: AUD (illegal summon by @ Rajaratnam @ IISS CHIP-MAN chip-genocide) (illegal Indians + Illegal Malaysians inside PHOENIX-LAND: stacking ('shoeboxes') x 60 Y on illegal stay)

@ IISS 1-day MC surnamed 'CHIP-MAN' (organized by Sri Lankan 'Global' @ EM LOGO MILITARY @ Rajaratnam Illegal Indians X 60 (traffick) + criminal intent Illegal Malaysians (flood-in): stacking humans INFRA-ATM-TOM X 60 + AUTO-BAR AUTO-VOID paper-work 'rajah-tan' 'napier-india TEMBUSU' (in the WHOLE OF ASIA: selling INFRA-banner 'THIRU' in ny) EM MILITARY GUN DOWN.

CRIMINAL FACULTIES: Ringgit-ntu-nus(various faculties blacklisted)-lky-rajaratnam

The 'GLOBAL ASIA' scam-sell: All criminal faculties in Ringgit-ntu-nus-rajaratnam, for example, Ringgit-lky-nus-'MAHBUBANI': INDIANS WHITE = NOT GLYPH STATES, NOT 'GLOBAL ASIA' LAW + Illegal stacking infra-Malaysian-ATM-Tom X 60 (1965 PLOT) inside PHOENIX-LAND: leads up to THIRU INFRA-ASIA-banner (global blacklist @ 201) (WCS = Indranee mangrove swamp CN + Infra-sg = \$b - \$trillion x no. y.

COMPUTATION (THE APPENDIX TO THE JUDGMENT)

illegal building over landed islandwide-phoenix: ETERNAL AMT x 60 to be returned by TEMASEK dbs + \$AMT of stacking humans into shoeboxes 'sgd' to be evacuated unto landed in Malaya in exchange.

There should be a global coordination of flower-pot smash CCTV + DIY LED pixel by illegal (infra-theft) criminal installation on Anti-Raja Day. This INFRA('Thiru')-construction-ATM-theft (repeat crime) is in conjunction with INFRA-CHIP-genocide (and entities: SPACE-X-INDIA minimally invasive GO-SHOTS / WB / BIS fraudsters (NOT ANY NATION, no official address: 1-indian + WCS world cities scam names usage x 100PLUS / no assets for liquidation) for computation + ret. keys)

'CHIP-MAN' refers to SATELLITE AIR + LAND INFRA-repeat crime + CHIP-genocide (EM LOGO MILITARY premeditated: explained in WLC Materials & Documents: IBM-INTEL-CO-VAX CHIP / WB / SPACE-X-INDIA / ABD (War-crime record) / AIIB / BIS fraudsters / ALL Infra-stacking shoeboxes (PRISON CELLS by behavioural war prisoners-Malaysians on illegal stay as strangers) wrong notes + illegal building over foreign land ATM-Tom + chip-inject

	<p>necessitating CHIP-RF-KILL (EXTERMINATION) reversed on PERPS-ID + SUB-PERP INFRA-ATM-banks-in & offsprings (EXTINCTION in JAIL).</p> <p>Other CHIP bank-in ALL industries including illegal container self-titled bank-in and cash-in checkpoints (electronic terminals % percentage theft per groceries requiring evacuation unto landed properties with veg + cow slots PORTS-DISCONNECT / CO-VAX circuitry CHIP in-brain barcode scanner RF-KILL criminal intent and criminal act committed).</p>
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(spawn TERMINATION = WAR ID AUTO-PERP-ID GUN DOWN by EM MILITARY)

IISS

	<p><u>IISS SLD (JAPAN'S DEFINITE: NO INTEREST IN PERP CIRCLE + X 500 Y GENOCIDAL call their group 'jesuits' etc anything REPLACEMENT: 'GLOBAL INDIANS & ILLEGALS INDIANS-ESC X 60: SOFTBANK THURAYA LOGO + YAHOO (THURAYA-HOO) + GOOGLE = Ret. Key to me</u></p>	
	<p><u>ALSO, PHOENIX-LAND + PHOENIX STAR BASE: BILLION Y BLOODLINE: GROUP OF ILLEGAL INDIANS + INFRA-(ATM-)cheat-money stacking TOM X 60 = COMPUTE + GLYPH SATELLITE</u></p>	

	<p><u>IISS SLD</u></p>	
	<p>IISS (which resonates with ISIL: PERP-same SATELLITE-TOM-ID x Time-frame) IISS CHIP-man</p>	
	<p>TABLE SUMMARY OF (Criminal 'Act' + 'Intent' X 60 consistent @ Rajaratnam-Ringgjit-pap-INFRA-(ATM)-TOM + SATELLITE-TOM + BEYOND PLOTS) =</p>	
	<p>TERMINATED</p>	
	<p>IISS CHIP-MAN</p>	<p>COMPUTE</p>
	<p>INFRA-CHIP-TOM: (disqualified M.D.) INJECTION SHOTS: 4-5 Y old</p>	<p>LIQUIDATE = CLOSED</p>
	<p>INFRA-construction-TOM (Ports-DISCONNECT) LAND + AIR INVASION (death penalty)</p>	<p>FOUNDATION TOM = COMPUTE</p>

WEF-RESET (WHO)	CHIP-in-brain-genocide
WB \$5 x booster x no. nations PER HD sg INFRA-co-vax-CHIP (WB)	#units = Ret. keys + COMPUTE
IBM, INTEL outlets	#units = Ret. keys + COMPUTE
AIIB	EM MILITARY RF-KILL INFRA-B = COMPUTE
INFRA-CHIP-genocide-MILITARY: TV-CHIP + EM LOGO MILITARY	Media-(content WRONG x60) = COMPUTE
POST-TV-CHIP: SATELLITE TOM	EM MILITARY RF-KILL SATELLITE-B = COMPUTE
INFRA-(ATM-)TOM: 'BOA' 'BOC' 'BOS'	COMPUTE gen est. + Ret. Keys
INFRA-(ATM-)TOM + SATELLITE TOM (War Prisoners)	
IISS SLD (JAPAN'S DEFINITE: NO INTEREST IN PERP CIRCLE + X 500 Y GENOCIDAL JESUITS-REPLACEMENT: GLOBAL INDIANS & ILLEGALS INDIANS-ESC X 60:	
UNDER INFRA-LAND THIEVES (PHOENIX 1965 PLOT + PLUS 3 PLOTS):	
INFRA-co-vax-CHIP (WB) + INFRA-construction theft LAND INVASION (death penalty)	
INFRA-construction-TOM (Ports-DISCONNECT) LAND + AIR INVASION (death penalty)	
severely disabled BEYOND PLOTS	
illegal india-ESC X 60 @ Rajaratnam + @ IISS (Infra-co-vax)-CHIP-man	
illegal india-ESC X 60 @ World Cities' Scam: use word 'sg' + 'ny'	
<u>COMBINE EVIDENCE: IISS SLD + RAJARTNAM (Illegal Indians mix Msian-INFRA-ATM-SATELLITE: various) + TRILATERAL (Rockefeller mix india)</u>	
SEE: unlicensed illegal banking tom decode	Illegal india + illegal msian: INFRA-rob x 60
Global INDIANS RUPEE V DOLLARS GROUP	USD CAD USMCA PLOT
	EM LOGO MILITARY @ RAJARATNAM
PHOENIX-LAND, BEYOND	PLUS 3 DRAGONS FABRICATED GROUPED 'asean' GLYPH: Vietnam Cambodia Burma

		BIS Fraudster 'Drawing': HKD CN Thai Emirates	
	<p>RAJARATNAM-(illegal india x 60)-Trilateral-Desker-India-(tied Rockefeller) JAYAKUMAR-KHRISHNAN: pose (Fake 'asean' rights + Swedish rights) + GOOGLE india overwrite Sapin (Eur):</p> <p>Possible: JP Morgan Chase (WB-rockefeller) removed money from GUPTA DBS upon WLC BANKING TOM DECODE.</p> <p>Possible: cn Ali-pay ANT GROUP (Ringgit-mas-malaysian COMPUTE FRAUD X 60 relocate Malaya: used 'sg' = Elevandi = ret. to me) Swiss Zero Point Heng Swee Keat = removed: RAVI & India group = GFTN</p>	<p>NORDIC-EUR-SWISS PLOT</p> <p>RAVI MENON BAN LOGO paste SBI next: all nations' names. (eur CN 'sg' etc)</p> <p>Heng Swee Keat (Margaret Chan genocidal WHO Ringgit- global law-less + global Public Health + Medicine -GLOBAL BLACKLISTED) genocidal board Ringgit-nus: \$90b + \$m + closed.</p>	

IISS

Usage of word & venue: 'SLD': (Ringgit-INFRA-ATM_X 60 BEYOND + SATELLITE)	
SHANGRI-LA (MALAYSIAN 'b' ocbc + MALAYSIAN 'Straits Trading' X 60) DIALOGUE SPONSORS (SUDDEN CHANGE: AWS AMAZON, (MICROSOFT'S) ACCENTURE (of MSIAN UOB) 2023):	
SHANGRI-LA (Possible: His plantation targeted (1 obvious) + involvement with KILLER-PRODUCTS GROUP-SEC LISTING: GRAB linked SATELLITE TOM) Rajaratnam-pap-lky-illegal since inception: SHANGRI-LA knows LKY-	
Post-CO-VAX circuitry CHIP island-wide Singapore including the Singapore military, Lee (on TV and even afterwards CO-VAX SHOTS reported by the South China Post;	

CHART 9A: SATELLITE SLD SHANGRI-LA DIALOGUE	
SUDDEN DRASTIC SWOP @ IISS 1-DAY MC	
TRADITIONAL SPONSORS OF RINGGIT-SLD (USAGE OF HOTEL OWNER 'SHANGRI-LA' DIALOGUE (2019): SUDDEN SWOP in SPONSORS: EM MILITARY X 60 @ Rajaratnam @ IISS to AMAZON (cloud theft)-EM MILITARY PORTS-DISCONNECT	

Here is the traditional sponsors of (usage of hotel owner)-Ringgit-
 SLD 2019 showing a sudden swop: EM MILITARY X 60 @
 Rajaratnam (Ringgit-ATM-TOM) @ IISS CHIP-MAN (TERMINATED
 in ALL LOCATIONS genocide-MILITARY) to: AMAZON (manifested
 crime being AMAZON LOCKERS outlets San Jose + archived under
 WLC MILITARY for lab exam and metal melted (forbidden entry:
 leave it in San Jose)

EXHIBIT: 2023 SLD

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LEGAL CONFIRMATION: ACCENTURE INVADE UOB

The invasion CO. ABOVE: **RF KILL co-vax CHIP** surfaced with
 obvious intent (connection behind): AWS Amazon and (Microsoft's
 FIN-TECH FEST: ATM-TOM) Accenture (inside / invade / complicit
 with Malaysian UOB)

LEGAL CONFIRMATION: ACCENTURE INVADE UOB

**Due to the sudden swop to AMAZON (2023) is why this portion
 is placed under 'BIG-4 shared inventor(s) : Microsoft / Amazon
 (Locker Outlet PL Fin-statement WWW: Ret. key) / Space X
 ('Minimally invasive Neural Lace') / Google (San Jose)**

**= ret. keys (to me), cross-over with (matching co-vax shots)
 CHIP-designs: it is Amazon CLOUD + SATELLITE TOM: criminal
 act of PORTS INVASION termed 'connectivity' on death penalty.
 Thus, EM LOGO MILITARY x no. of nations @ Rajaratnam @
 IISS-CHIP-Man @ X 100PLUS MILITARY on compulsory PORTS-
 DISCONNECT e.g. marjot singh M1 Thuraya(h) + Inmarsat +
 Viasat + AIRBUS (Other: SPACE-X Chip-genocide)**

**+ brijesh pande TEMBUSU (Ringgit-'s'ia) TEMASEK = Ret.
 Trillions + keys to me.**

<p>LEGAL QUESTIONS: RINGGIT-'ST ENGINEERING' FRAUDSTERS</p>	<p>Min-invasive Infra-CHIP = Ret. keys</p>
<p>4. Where is the rocket(s)? Where is it based? Any?</p> <p>Ringgit-ST Engineering cannot BASE inside PHOENIX-LAND</p>	<p>RET. \$90B \$M X T</p>
<p>5. Ringgit-pap Teo 2 cyber theft division lee kc building Entire top floor = Removed = Relocate Malaya + 'dg'-India-x = All Indians Ret. India</p> <p>No Indian Space-bro redeem them Conclusion: Illegal Indians + Malaysians illegals INFRA-(ATM) + SATELLITE complicit lying by themselves X 60 Y:</p>	
<p>6. Ringgit-pap Josephine Teo + Indranee Rajah = submit detailed report (mangrove swamp CN + infra-sg with chip-genocide + Thuraya + Inmarsat Viasat + Airbus @ Rajaratnam EM LOGO MILITARY consistent criminal record x 60 Y Illegal Indians @ IISS CHIP-man) on WWW (on death penalty-ID) + base + total amt x no. y (ringgit-pap) + bank a/c holder name</p>	
<p>TEMASEK dbs = ret. 8k + \$ 90b 1st + trillions x time-frame + orchard rd + ports-(DISCONNECT SATELLITE-TOM) + Ret. landed properties (+ farmland + livelihood + building slots) + WHOLE OF PUNGGOL + ret. landed to others</p> <p>Ringgit-ocbc = ret. 8k + \$ 90b + \$M x time-frame</p> <p>+ ret. shoeboxes (cheated) monies x 60 + evacuate: landed properties ('veg + cow')</p>	<p>RET. \$Trillions x time-frame + orchard rd + ports</p>
<p>(1) self-title: ask-for-money X 60 Y (2) criminal format (BEYOND) x no. EM LOGO MILITARY @ Rajaratnam (when began with ringgit-pap: Fraudsters INFRA-(ATM)-TOM 1965 PLOT (e.g stacking ('cheat-money'), transport from india Indian construction workers say linked to ATM-so-n-so bank) ('indp d' – no link or with 'intent' to link)</p>	

<p>Chip-genocide (began in Ringgit-'sg'-h 4-5 y old + CC stations WHOLE ISLAND = illegal Ringgit-pap absent for duration)</p>	
<p><u>RE-CAP string illegal Indians since inception 1965 ringgit-INFRA-ATM-pap + SATELLITE TOM: SEE: Appendix to THE JUDGMENT</u></p>	
<p>Global' 'Indians' Criminals: claim SATELLITE TOM</p>	<p>Marjot Singh: Thurayah + Inmarsat Viasat + Airbus (No such MP'A') = ret. ports keys to me (COMPUTE X 60)</p>
<p>EM LOGO MILITARY @ RAJARATNAM (illegal x 60) 'Organizer' with IISS CHIP-MAN @ SLD</p> <p>Thurayah + Inmarsat Viasat + Airbus + Amazon (PORTS-DISCONNECT) See: Raytheon + Lockheed Martin + Allen, Hamilton & Booz (how get tech: from nation)</p> <p>USD CAD AUD NZD MILITARY</p>	<p>SGD HKD CN THAI VIET CAMBODIA BURMA EM LOGO GUN DOWN: RAJAH & TAN(Malaya) Ringgit-'sg'-x NAPIER-India = TEMBUSU-pap Brijesh Pande =</p> <p>TEMASEK = ret. trillions + keys building to me. (all assets san jose + ny)</p>
<p>RAJARATNAM (illegal x 60) (-pap-lky-RINGGIT-ATM) DESKER-Classified: INDIA 'saint Patrick' Also, saint = GLYPH word (bloodline)</p>	<p>RAJARATNAM (-pap-lky-RINGGIT-INFRA-ATM) Illegal Indians status = WHOLE OF ASIA ('GLYPH STATES')</p>
<p>RAJARATNAM JAYAKUMARS-criminal faculties SR JR, Kumar Khrishnan,</p>	
<p>RAJARATNAM Desker + BALA (Classified: INDIA) use 'sg'</p>	<p>OBAMA-CARE(S ACT) CARESHIELD</p>
<p>GLOBAL BANKING TOM DECODE</p>	
<p>RAJARATNAM 'BOARD' RINGGIT-ATM-STRAITS TRADING, so put with RAVI MENON inside RINGGIT-nus genocidal board = ret. \$90 B</p>	<p>'board' Ringgit-Chew Gek Khim with Ravi (Illegals m'sians Indians X 60)</p>
<p>GLOBAL 'Indian' pose: GUPTA-DBS</p>	
<p>SHUT Ringgit-mas-Malaysian =</p>	<p>COMPUTE FRAUD X 60 include KAMALA-RAVI-GOOGLE FRAUD = relocate Malaya</p>
<p>RAVI-'BIS' 'GLOBAL' 'TECH' duped Tier 1 Tier 2: HYPER-LEDGER</p>	<p>'INFRA-CHIP b'</p>
<p>RAVI-'BIS-sg' MAHAL no such address (no assets liquidate: stealing from illegal properties)</p>	

	<p>RINGGIT-INFRA-ATM-TOM (‘professor’ RINGGIT-LEE FOUNDATION, INFRA-stacking ‘cheat-money’ (illegal: put Chinese shoeboxes) + rob landed WHOLE OF PHOENIX-LAND: flood-in-Malaysians: collect notes into ATM-TOM</p> <p>Farmland (self-sustaining) NO CHIP-PORTS</p>	<p>illegal Malaysian Status: inside WHOLE Phoenix-land x 60:</p> <p>V IISS CHIP-MAN @ Rajaratnam Amazon CHIP-(Marjot Singh MPA Ringgit-ntu claim: Thurayah + Inmarsat Viasat + Airbus = ret. keys + Ringgit-pap LTA = ret. keys (Brijest pande, Ringgit-‘sg’-x: Napier-India + TEMBUSU invade = GUN DOWN ALL EM LOGO MILITARY PORTS-DISCONNECT.</p>
	<p>THIRU (GLOBAL BLACKLIST) with INDRANEE RAJAH-WCS-ID short for world cities scam: INFRA-ASIA = GLYPH STATES</p>	<p>‘Thiru’ ‘INFRA-‘ASIA’ GLYPH STATES = NOT INDIA (LIE X 60: LOW IQ)</p>
<p>SEE: Appendix to THE JUDGMENT</p>		
<p>AMAZON LOCKER (INSERT: PHOTO SPECIMEN (EX-7-11))</p>		
<p>WLC COURT DISCUSSION 1</p> <p>AMAZON LOCKER (INSERT: PHOTO SPECIMEN (EX-7-11))</p>	<p>CRIMINAL EVIDENCE</p> <p>MILITARY WLC Discussion:</p> <p>Main problem with this item ‘something’s wrong’ i.e. ‘digital’ = harm / hurt Malaya or any nation of resell.</p> <p>REQUIRED ACTION: REMOVE ALL AMAZON LOCKER = off PHOENIX-LAND = Malaysians transport into Malaya (storage inside: Archived under MILITARY WLC / store inside somewhere NOT FOR USE: lab exam) then metal melting.</p> <p>Thus, NOT FOR USE: lab exam e.g. any access to satellite / incoming aircraft etc, then warehouse storage deactivated.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3. Melt Metal = accessories shop v phoenix laptop 4. EXAMPLE: PHOENIX LAPTOP i.e. something better than apple e.g. LOCUST BRAND i.e eat into thieves’ im-plantations-dare-NOT touch owner-brand. <p>Also, climate ‘intent’ = terminated by melting into PHOENIX LAPTOP for RF-KILL reverse TARGET on ALL AMAZOM LOCKER outlets: SAN JOSE.</p>	
	<p>COMPUTATION EST.: ITEM AMAZON LOCKET (‘BILLING’ / Liquidation)</p>	

		est. \$300 sgd-\$500 sg x no. shoeboxes blocks = easily 500 x 10 such = 5000 sgd into WLC MILITARY Fund so, discuss with MILITARY WLC, usually, funding (mainly: COMPUTATION of illegal indians X 60 FRAUD TOTAL) into Phoenix Rocket, s/w, operations etc.				
WLC Court Discussion 4		<p>Test Questions</p> <p>Candidate: FRAUDSTER INFRA-P(ortable toilet-over)-CARD (chip-genocide)</p> <p>3. Name of person that contact: Tharman Shanmugaratnam to give-out climate award (to follow CN Yang Yi footsteps leaving Keppel Lee K.S. = Sundaresh Menon SMU moot Lee K.S. = WB #12-01 = ret. keys to me + computer + files inside building but not builder Lee K.S.)</p> <p>4. which satellite + name manning the climate satellite = detailed report WWW ('He' Perpetrator saw 'you' Tharman Shanmugaratnam in a photo in SMU = means Lee K.S. to him.)</p>				
WLC COURT DISCUSSION 1		<p>SAME PRODUCT GROUP</p> <p>SAN JOSE offices keys = Google (take-over) + Amazon-cloud (take-over) + FB-Meta-pay (take-over: NO pay) / Microsoft-fin-tech fest all ATM-tom (take a look of office: Seattle)</p> <p>MILITARY (Joint exercise) HERO sign-up + food delivery (interview by me required) bike-in San Jose (LEGAL TO:) upload WWW ('shoeboxes' X 60 monies) change to WLC @ All Glyph Tech Trades, WLC @ Americas (White + Latin + Mexico) tech trades.</p> <p>PLUS 3 CN J K + EM LOGO MILITARY fabricated 'asean' Vietnam Cambodia Burma Thailand HKD Malaya EM KILL MILITARY + PHOENIX-SG-Chinese (Listen to me) MILITARY preferred.</p> <p>Volunteer USMCA plot AUD NZD v rupee (interview by me required).</p>				
		WLC = WORLD LAW COURT + JUDGE of SEC KILLER PRODUCTS = COMPUTE				
		CRIMINAL ELEMENTS				
		<p>google San Jose = ret. keys office (Put monitor screen inside San Jose office 1st on WWW 247 Surveillance):</p> <p>SAME product group Space-X, Amazon-(selling cloud)-EM LOGO @ IISS CHIP x no. military nations = Entered Phoenix land (Prior to chip-genocide at W.B. Washington)</p>				
		<p><u>PL SUBMISSION 1ST</u></p> <p>AMAZON outlets (all outlets) = Ret. keys 1ST in San Jose to me ('shoeboxes' monies)</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="532 1814 1279 1883"> <tr> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>Ret. all GOOGLE = keys San Jose</td> </tr> </table>				Ret. all GOOGLE = keys San Jose
	Ret. all GOOGLE = keys San Jose					

		<p>Ret. all AMAZON LOCKER outlets = keys San Jose</p> <p>[upload detailed shop outlets P&L WWW and Fin-statement WWW on assets etc on PER locker outlets' + keys' return]</p> <p>INCLUDE: illegal claim to SHIPPING DETAILS if ANY-body (even) bought anything</p>	
		<p>SPACE-X-India</p> <p>In the same product group: SPACE-X-India rockets which look phallic-pervert) = San Jose (to me).</p> <p>Classified as nonsense rocket design: use replica multiplied many times larger (only indians think they are: 'cute') phallic-pervert.</p>	
		<p>SBI CLUSTER COMPUTATION</p> <p>In conjunction with billing operations inside and terminated off PHOENIX LAND with illegal access to currencies stash, The Judgement is ONLY genocide those that with criminal act + intent i.e. wiped clean by their own cluster.</p> <p>SBI (robbed stash abroad X 60) of other pp foreign land nations' money = compute + inform all EM LOGO MILITARY (GLYPH) states / nations: USMCA PLOT + PLUS 3 + EM LOGO fabricated grouped states + NORDIC-EUR-SWISS PLOT.</p> <p>It appears to be a small area in India = can 'gun down' (deactivate-require confirmation). Otherwise, risk having to wipe clean the whole race. Anyway, illegal Indians have declared way many many times: (1) consistent criminal record x 60 EM LOGO MILITARY @ Rajaratnam add @ CHIP-Man (2) committed chip-genocide WB d.c. outlet: with the string of highlighted illegal Indians leading upt o genocide and KAMALA-RAVI attempt (ABORTED by WLC and BILLING FRAUD \$600M) (3) SPACE-X minimally invasive CHIP-(co-vax-genocide: RF-KILL) (4) BALA INMARSAT + VIASAT Russian + Ukraine AI-kill RESET WEF-India.</p>	

IISS

SHANGRI-LA (MALAYSIAN b ocbc RINGGIT X 60 NOT SINGAPORE) DIALOGUE SPONSORS 2018):

Prior to 2019 @ IISS CHIP-Man inject 20xx (already pre-mediated: chip-genocide (Ringgit-pap) LEE inject in order to inject EM LOGO MILITARY ('intentionally' aired over satellite of mediacorp-malaysian: THURAYA + INMARSAT VIASAT + AIRBUS + MINIMALLY INVASIVE suggestive SPACE-X-INDIA) since inception of 'Rajaratnam SCH' 2008 @ Rajaratnam (illegal Indians 'organizer') inception 1965 PLOT: INFRA-(Malaysian illegal stay) TOM stacking 'sg'd' into his ATM-TOM. The word 'sg' is fabricated. Since it was in the aftermath of 2001 attack, satellite appears to be connected to plausible: Indians-(INDIA, electronic passport theft, SAN JOSE NY D.C.) (funding X60 maybe stolen from rightful owner PHOENIX-LAND).

The unclear owner behind the paid 1-3 days MC-CHIP-MAN / Ringgit-ATM (straits trading) of ocbc since inception: FAKE NORDIC-(Straits Trading OCBC-SEE: APPENDIX TO THE JUDGMENT, PHOTO-ID of illegal Indians (illegal stay inside PHOENIX-LAND) AUTO-BAR AUTO-VOID since inception 1965 PLOT e.g. FAKE-NORDIC-'Drew-Napier'-India (Mumtha WB co-vax chip genocide Cavinder Bull Davinder Singh Susil Nair INSOL Shanmugam (Rajah tan ALSO, AUTO-BAR cannot sign criminal papers write anything AUTO-VOID paperwork (repeat crime BEYOND) TERMINATED = GUN DOWN BY EM LOGO MILITARY @ Vietnam, Cambodia, Burma, Thailand, HKD, PLUS 3 PLOTS: CN (preliminary only: 'yahoo maybe 'yah sat' etc) J ('softbank': Thuraya logo but see maker) K, Napier-India TEMBUSU = GUN DOWN BY CN) all illegal Indians entered Malaya with Malaysians: entered with criminal intent into PHOENIX-LAND began stacking), Ringgit-'sg'-x-'s'ia PORTS-1. MPA 2. LTA 3. HDB = Ret. keys / COMPUTE into PHOENIX DOLLARS, conversion for evacuation (of illegal stay ION-malaysian-shoebboxes Malaysian-unto landed in Malaya) / closed (removal: ringgit-INFRA-atm-PAP ask-4-money x 60 criminal format). (With BEYOND repeat crime intent: criminal act of inviting EM LOGO x no. MILITARY @ Rajaratnam H.E. excellency Organ Damage. Consistent criminal record X 60 = TEMINATED).

Thus, come across as 1-unknown-Tom (satellite access) based using Indians: inside USA-13 and inside Rajaratnam (ATM-malaysian-TOM-INFRA-BEYOND TERMINATED: Ret. \$Trillions, Ringgit-ntu-nus-\$b-Straits Trading, Ringgit-ocbc-\$m)

In other words, it about bank-toms (piloted tested) + INFRA-(illegal stay Malaysian use illegal Indians construction workers dbs, exhibit behavioral stacking that cannot be charged money for or to house humans)-TOM + satellite TOM: THURAYA + INMARSAT VIASAT + AIRBUS (OTHERS: SPACE-X) etc.

FURTHER DETAILS: THE JUDGEMENT (COMPUTATION APPENDIX)

SUSPECTS / CONFIRMED GUILTY	CONSISTENT CRIMINAL RECORD X 100-500
<p>@ RAJARATNAM (illegal Indians X 60 + Illegal Malaysians Ringgit-ATM-TOM inside PHOENIX-LAND. (NOT ASIA, NOT PHOENIX) Build as many: ION-nized membrane potentials Mall = REMOVE all Malaysian ATM-TOM out of ORCHARD RD = ret. Malaya: TEMASEK-Ringgit-Lee (robbed stacking = cannot charge + cannot house humans + lousy materials, evacuation: RF-bad soil islandwide = exhibit war prisoner (unclean))</p>	RAJARATNAM Blacklisted by Americans
<p>Ringgit-Lee-foundation-INFRA-TOM (Illegal stay X 60 malaysian TEMASEK exhibit 'war prisoner' stacking 'sg-d fabricated' into ATM-TOM: = cannot charge money for stacking + ret. shoeboxes monies + CONVERSION PHOENIX DOLLARS (physical booklet: PHOENIX ATM) = ret. Malaya landed properties PHOENIX GRANITE WLC = cannot build anything over LAND 1. LTA 2. MPA 3. BCA etc Ringgit-ocbc-dbs-TEMASEK Prisoners' 'Legislative' stat-board theft sites =</p>	<p>\$Trillions (1) On illegal stay, INFRA-TOM-(TEMASEK, TEMBUSU, illegal Indians NORDIC-Napier-INDIA) + INCLUDE THE ASK-FOR-MONEY-LEGISLATIVE THEFT FRAUD CONSITE-GENOCIDAL TASK FORCE committed-RINGGIT-'PAP' ringgit-nu-nus-rajaratnam-sgh-sgx-dgx(death)-etc set-up: Ret. Trillions, \$b \$ m, build as many buildings (orchard rd) to lay claim but NOT HIS LAND (2) flood-in Malaysians on illegal stay, illegal Indians = ret. india): into ATM-TOM x 60: exhibit war prisoner behaviour: cannot charge money nor use stacking to house humans = ret. shoeboxes monies (3) NO CLAIM OVER PHOENIX-LAND: cannot build anything over any land: attempt profit from train route alongside his MONEY-LAND (ION-ZIED MEMBRANE = ret. key) ATM-TOM (4) His 1st stash + subsequent stash + all assets worldwide: ny san jose = belongs to PHOENIX STAR. CONCLUSION PERP-infra-(chip-genocide: committed) Infra-Tom (illegal stay x 60) cannot not lay claim to PHOENIX-LAND.</p>
Illegal stay Malaysian RINGGIT-ATM	\$m x no. y
RINGGIT-nus-genocidal	\$b
SATELLITE CO.	<p>THURAYA + INMARSAT VIASAT + AIRBUS (OTHERS: SPACE-X) etc. Marjot singh m1 + Brijesh Pande TEMUBSU = Napier-India = Ringgit-'s'g-x-'s'ia = LIQUIDATE all shareholders, forbidden pick any race he like Relocate under Malaya. CONVERT PHOENIX DOLLARS: purchase aircrafts.</p>
Waiting 'President' of criminals (delayed: ret. key / time limit) submit: bank a/c name of all legislative theft sites + (criminal)	

	<p>satellite (removal) & bank a/c name of ATM-TOM backdate to 1965</p> <p>SBI = TERMINATED (cluster, SBI, various: SPACE-X Vandenberg: check)</p>	
	<p>'ST-Engineering' = rockets? + bank a/c name = Ret. \$Trillions</p> <p>Reports Teo 2 + Indranee Rajah (WCS = Thiru 'ny' INFRA-prosecution, ASIA = NOT India LIE X 60 LOW IQ) invasion (mangrove CN + infra-sg): rocket + satellite + a/c ST \$b + bank a/c name</p>	<p>Ret. \$Trillions</p> <p>AIIB (Prosecuted) = compute PHOENIX DOLLARS</p>
	<p>BASIC (other this BASIC LANDED PROPERTIES ('veg + cow') SURVIVAL, no party REQUIRED ('fraudsters': ask-4-money fraud)</p> <p>= PHOENIX GRANITE WLC + cpf hdb Ret. shoeboxes monies (CORRECT Notes: PHOENIX DOLLAR) 'sg'-fabricated from inception linked BO'S-'C'-'A' = SAME PERP plausible (OTHER fabricated flags / logos nations: WRONG)</p>	<p>No one: Cannot set-up 'party' ask-4-money x 60 – 100 ETC ('legislative' theft con fraud AMT X 60 COMPUTE)</p>
	<p>EMPTY, PHOENIX STAR BASE FARMLAND + STONE TEMPLE, nothing rob / plot / collapse etc (SAN JOSE FB-META pay rapist CN / USA-13 etc: sam alex pardinjaremannil: criminal intent 'drawing COPIED' act / building insurance / chip-genocide (all humans living on granite landed in Malaya with 'veg + cow')</p>	<p>\$Trillions stolen: SET- other targeted states: Mongolia, EM LOGO Fabricated GLYPH states (illegal Indians: Rajaratnam, Rajah, since inception, severely disabled BEYOND PLOTS: CARES-ACT ('Obama'-Care) CARESHIELD etc (criminal variants) following the pattern: INFRA-CHIP (EM LOGO) MILITARY in order chip-genocide (PRE-MED X 60 @ Rajaratnam Ringgit-illegal stay) @ IISS CHIP-MAN = TERMINATED (all locations) Trilateral-Rockefeller-depend on PERP-ID-SATELLITE:</p> <p>if the satellites are proven innocent, the remaining one is guilty.</p>
		<p>BEYOND repeat crime PLOTS = TERMINATED = EM LOGO MILITARY GUN DOWN</p>
	<p><u>As explained (BILLION Y EVIDENCE): 'India' = not YAH ZHOU (ASIA GLYPH STATES)</u></p> <p>As explained (BILLION Y EVIDENCE), 'India' = not YAH ZHOU (ASIA GLYPH STATES) hence this illegal person should not even be present prior to chip-genocide.</p>	
	<p>Another critically blatant error are the MILITARY STATES invitees: suspicious exhibiting several imposters singh claiming white states.</p>	

Indian Prime Minister Narendra Modi led the strongest-ever line-up of ministers at Asia's premier defence summit.

Leading up to the pre-meditated EM LOGO MILITARY with consistent criminal record (and diagrammatical expressions: EM LOGO BEYOND PLOTS 'H.E.' HIS/HER Excellency ORGAN NATION RF-KILL MILITARY @ invitees no. military states x 60 Y @ Rajaratnam (illegal Indians stay: entered Malaya) Ringgit-INFRA-ATM-TOM + SATELLITE TOM) since inception 1965 PLOT X 60 COMPUTE.

BEYOND PLOTS = TERMINATED

IISS

SHANGRI-LA (MALAYSIAN b ocbc X 60 NOT SINGAPORE) DIALOGUE SPONSORS (PRIOR TO THE 'PRE-MEDITATED CHIP-GENOCIDE SUDDEN CHANGE: AWS AMAZON, (MICROSOFT'S) ACCENTURE (of MSIAN UOB) 2016):

Traditional sponsors (consistency: aircraft brands e.g. Raytheon, Lockheed Martin) in previous years: 2016

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in previous years: 2017

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[SEE: APPENDIX TO THE JUDGMENT on AIRBUS + THUARYAH + INMARSAT + VIASAT](#)

[SHANGRI-LA \(MALAYSIAN b ocbc X 60 NOT SINGAPORE\) DIALOGUE SPONSORS \(SUDDEN CHANGE: TRILATERAL COMMISSION'S JAP BEER 2022\): @ RAJARATNAM @ IISS 'CHIP-MAN'](#)

[SRI LANKA ILLEGAL INDIANS X 60 @ RAJARATNAM-dead, PAP ILLEGAL X 60, M'sian b severely disabled beyond OCBC EM LOGO fabricated PLOTS: INFRA-CHIP construction b + F-STASH\)](#)

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The Asahi Shimbun

Airbus

Airbus is an international pioneer in the aerospace industry.

It is not strange but a clear answer (clear intent behind the apparently irrelevant connection) between product 'Asahi' Jap beer (PM dead-to be accounted for): NO INTEREST IN PERP-CIRCLE at the equally not strange but criminal set-up of @ IISS CHIP-MAN (intent) (@ Rajaratnam-entourage of illegals e.g. INFRA-ATM-TOM-Malaysian-FAKE-NORDIC-'Straits Trading' illegal Indian stay x 60: cannot summon any MILITARY, any nation, anyone) venue @ SLD

Stolen technology of Japanese at IEEE Forums: may have enabled the Japanese to have first-hand knowledge of the sinister agenda behind the set-up of PRE-MEDITATED EM LOGO (Diagrammatical Criminal 'intent' behind drawing of Criminal Act: EM CHIP-genocide MILITARY) Illegal Indians + Illegal Malaysians:

AUTO-BAR from summoning x no. of MILITARY STATES @ Rajaratnam 'organizer' @ IISS CHIP-MAN (obvious sign: criminal intent / act)

Alternate beer products also appeared @ The Trilateral hence signifying the connection behind both @ IISS CHIP-MAN e.g. 'Rockefeller' whereby the rockets 'Rockefeller' depends on rely on a chip (inside computers). Due all these suspicious signals, and illegal summon of no. military states (AUTO-VOID), is likely the key reason behind the beer labels as a way of expressing: NO INTEREST IN PERP CIRCLE.

Explained in this WLC Materials & Evidence (GLYPH Categories) in detail:

7. IBM (BEYOND H.E. ORGAN DAMAGE with diagrams drawings of criminal intent chained to a bomb) Drug-Neuromorph-PERP-ic Systems @ RAJARATNAM X 60 RUPEES V DOLLARS @ IISS CHIP-man (illegal Indians cannot sign/summon; on illegal stay x 60)
8. IEEE IBM INTEL (Chip-replica) SAMSUNG: GO SHOTS turned Micro-chip
9. GO SHOTS turned Micro-chip: Medical Evidence (continents: USMCA PLOT (CARES ACT: CARESHIELD, 'OBAMACARE' pose with BALA-INDIA), PLUS 3 PLOT, EM LOGO Fabricated grouped, HYPERLEDGER duped Tier 1 Tier 2 Pilot Test Mapping, BEYOND PLOTS stacking 'sgd-fabricated' (PHOENIX-LAND) = TERMINATED
10. X100PLUS TESTING (log-on) MILITARY: actual SATELLITE INVASION + 8K (fabricated CSI M) (TOUCH CN)
11. IISS CHIP-man TERMINATED WORLDWIDE @ Rajaratnam (illegal Indians + illegal Malaysians-pap-('legislative' stacking humans theft (fraud notes), fraud-sites, con-sites into ATM-Tom= buildings ret. keys = COMPUTE X 60) cannot sign, cannot summon any military / nations 'meet'; on illegal stay x 60) + FIN-TECH FEST BAN-FAST-PAY CN rapist + PAY-LATER (GRAB) PAY-NOW (dbs) (TOUCH illegal Malaysians X 60-ATM-TOM inside PHOENIX-LAND) + FED-PAY-PAL (India TOUCH USA-13)

PAY-REPLICATED FORMAT X NO. MILITARY STATES @ FIN-TECH FEST (INDIANS ARREST)

USA-13 (space-)rapist	Illegal Malaysians + Illegal Indians (stay: x 60)	CN (space-)rapist
FED-PAY-PAL	PAY-LATER (GRAB)	FAST-PAY
FED-WIRE	PAY-NOW (dbs)	
PAY-PAL	BEYOND PHOENIX-LAND PLOT	PLUS 3 PLOT: DRAGONS (BEYOND PHOENIX)
TERMINATED	TERMINATED	TERMINATED

Explained in this WLC Materials & Evidence (GLYPH Categories) in detail:

12. Criminal Intent of 'Neural Net': CO-VAX CHIP (add: Master-Slave intent v 100PLUS MILITARY) e.g. (TOUCH NY) NASDAQ (PERP-ID trying to replicate unto: Malaysian infra-ATM illegal stay (Ret. \$Trillions, \$B, \$M)

<p>'straits-trading' illegal Malaysian (TOUCH BEYOND PHOENIX-LAND): Fraud country no such name-fabricated + EM LOGO MILITARY Fabricated states PLUS 3 PLOTS: CN J K (SATELLITE-TOM) (BEYOND = TERMINATED)</p>		
'BO'A' USMCA PLOT	'BO'S'-Fabricated word BEYOND Stacking PHOENIX-LAND (1965 PLOT)	'BO'C' PLUS 3: DRAGONS + Fabricated EM Grouped States Label AUTO-VOID PLOT)
NASDAQ ny: chip (Description: trading 000,000,000 IBM CHIP monies / murder scam meet of nations using military 100PLUS or illegal individuals card- imposters)	NO CLAIM to FAKE- 'straits trading'-CLOSED-ports- DISCONNECT: ret. keys (a) ringgit-thuraya logo Malaysian 'sg'-x + others COMPUTE X 60 \$AMT = relocate Malaya	Repeat crime = TERMINATED
(JUDGE OF SEC) intentionally killer products + murder intent	(b) FAKE-NORDIC-'self- titled' Malaysian 1. Straits trading FAKE-'currencies' EM LOGO X no. of MILITARY + BEYOND CHIP-genocide currencies) @ Rajaratnam-ringgit-pap- = Ret. \$Trillions \$b \$m + Malaysian ST Engineering 2. Ret. Rocket + \$b 2. 'trading' CASINO'-CON Electronic PRESS: 000	CHIP-genocide-intent drawing (EM LOGO) 'H.E.'- ORGAN DAMAGE rights x no. Fabricated (Grouped = TERMINATED, Close- Ports: Napier-India TEMBUSU ('wrong' FAKE- (WCS-Illegal Indians)-civil engineering) = CN MILITARY GUN DOWN + EM MILITARY GUN DOWN Rajah-Tan (AUTO-VOID paper-work on death penalty): repeat crime (x 60)
e.g. Master-Slave intent v 100PLUS MILITARY Meaning the MILITARY is the PRIME TARGET in order to chip-genocide	EM LOGO x no. of MILITARY + Malaysian x 60 INFRA-stacking war prisoner-atm-TOM: illegal Malaysian + illegal Indians = Ret. landed + ret. land others + ret. shoeboxes (flood-in) to malaya landed. (on fraud notes-ATM)	
	ION-ZED MEMBRANE MALL = Ret. keys carry out = ret. Malaya stay) DRUG- CHIP-GENOCIDE MILITARY criminal intent + criminal act	
	PHOENIX SATELLITE + PHOENIX-TRI-SOLAR ALL GLYPH TECH TRADING (small scale): Explanations & Discussions	

		<p>India-'dg'x puthu (death) + 'luxembourg'-x (WCS-India Indranee + Rajah = EM GUN DOWN):</p> <p>Additional: Mission RETRIEVE of assets San Jose (station + guard mapping + PERP-ID) with WLC DOCTOR OF COMPUTERS cert.</p> <p>PHOENIX DOLLAR = proper evacuation PHOENIX GRANITE WLC of humans = 'EMPTY' ret. to farmland + stone temple (nothing to rob / plot / collapse / schemes etc) + garrisons throughout (illegal Indians enter airspace)</p>	
	<p>LEGAL CONCLUSION</p> <p>BO'S-C-A' PLUS 3: DRAGONS (ALL Wrong Label)-ATM-Tom + SATELLITE-Tom = COMPUTE ('intent' rob Tier-1, 2 for himself) + AIIB + WB chip-genocide (space-x) + BIS fraudsters board (NOT any nations, PERP-Tom himself) = MILITARY ARREST COMPUTE ret. closed.</p> <p>Google + amazon locker + FB-META-PAY (format replication X no. Military states) + (computers) (FAKE WCS) 'exchange' bases linked 'satellite'-tom = Ret. keys</p> <p>PRIOR CRIMINAL RECORD X500 Y criminal record means = A lot of nations' military can give evidence of airspace (crime).</p>		
	<p>LEGAL CONFIRMATION:</p> <p>PERP-AIRBUS + M1 + THURAYA(H) = COASTAL LAND + AIR INVASION (death penalty) + BEYOND MILITARY GUN DOWN. OTHERS: SPACE-X-INDIA: minimally invasive CHIP-GO SHOTS.</p>		
	<p>Further details on SATELLITE-TOM: THE JUDGMENT</p>		
	<p><u>IISS SLD (2023)</u></p> <p>ASAHI BEER @ TRILATERAL (COPIED LOGO) @ IISS CHIP-MAN</p> <p>The (apparently 'Irrelevant product') 'Asahi' beer X 2 (2022, 2023) @ IISS CHIP-MAN @ RAJARATNAM-dead and 'Suntory' beer @ Trilateral Commission shows the clear repeated expression of and implied meaning: NO interest in PERP-circle.</p> <div data-bbox="261 1654 1187 1879" style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 10px; text-align: center;"> The Asahi Shimbun </div>		

<p>There are 2 definitions of glyph word 朝</p> <p>in 'Asahi beer'_朝(日)</p> <p>in glyph means: the official in court greet the ruler (1) 臣子在朝廷拜见君, the ruler 君主 refers to: 君主时代的官吏 meaning 'highest ruler over court officials'.</p> <p>The secondary (of less likelihood in context) meaning refers to worshippers of buddha:</p> <p>'PH'-佛-FO⁴⁵. (2) 宗教徒到圣地或礼拜神、佛。</p>	
<p>Thus, here, 'Asahi (beer)朝(日) Shimbun 报纸 ('newspaper') is the name of the Japanese beer, that 'participated'.</p>	
<p>EXAMPLE:</p>	
<p>Another example, the glyph word 潮</p> <p>in state of 潮州 appears in China glyph</p> <p>means 月亮和太阳引力造成的海洋水面 定时涨落的现象 which refers to:</p>	

⁴⁵ For example, (Mistranslation: Saint) Sheng-聖Jo-(-Yue約) se-瑟 ph-**佛**' ('Joseph')

	<p>the moon and sun's magnetic (attraction) force</p> <p>creates the ocean's surface's</p> <p>fixed periodic rise / fall phenomenon.</p>		
	<p><u>IISS SLD (2022)</u> ASAHI BEER @ TRILATERAL (COPIED LOGO) @ IISS CHIP-MAN</p> <div data-bbox="261 625 797 898" style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 10px; text-align: center;"> <p><i>IISS Shangri-La Dialogue</i></p> <p>The Asahi Shimbun</p> </div> <p>ASAHI BEER @ TRILATERAL COMMISSION (COPIED LOGO) @ IISS CHIP-MAN</p> <p>The expression 'Asahi Beer' at the trilateral commission: Implied meaning being NO interest in PERP-circle.</p> <p>Rationale: Japan (Cash preferred). This concerns the relevant SATELLITE-TOM.</p>		
	<p><u>IISS SLD SHOWS:</u></p> <div data-bbox="261 1373 1243 1560" style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 5px;"> <p>Implied meaning appears to be: no interest in PERP Circle.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 5. Stated: cash preferred 6. The Japanese submitted: Infra-co-vax-evidence 7. X 500 Y expulsion: genocidal 'Jesuits' set-up USA-13⁴⁶ 8. Replacement Format: India-ESC X 60 called 'global Indians' </div> <div data-bbox="261 1560 1243 1713" style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 5px;"> <p>Other considerations:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3. IEEE IBM Tokyo (but JAP PM Longest serving: no record of being attacked) 4. WB CONSITE: to decipher PERP-ID </div>		

See also, genocidal prior criminal record 'Jesuits' Expulsion of X 500 Y, fraudsters that copied the glyph text and murder crime set-up: USA & Japan-bombed.

Review of (other BW Locations)		
<u>There is a record of the actual News-paper 'Asahi Shimbun':</u>		
	The War Ministry (of Japan: <i>permitted</i> due to the otherwise reportedly controlled Japanese press) to make public illegal covert operations (wrt BW deployment in Manchuria and various locations):	
	On 23 May 1940, the Tokyo Asahi Shimbun printed Ishii (Glyph: _) Shiro (Glyph: _)'s photograph with commendation in relation to the 'death factories' (BW + CW: 1931 – 1942).	
<u>Keywords associated with this character Ishii Shiro: Unit 731</u>		
	The War Ministry (of Japan: <i>permitted</i> due to the otherwise reportedly controlled Japanese press) to make public illegal covert operations (wrt BW deployment in Manchuria and various locations):	
	Keywords associated include: 8. Infectious Disease Research Lab, Tokyo which mirrors the American version by Anthony Fauci (yet linked location: Wuhan WIV). 9. Criminal Universities: Tokyo Army Medical College / Kyoto Imperial University / Tokyo Imperial University etc reason for citing: due to enormous influence Ishii Shiro had over (BW + CW). 10. Curious sounding: 'Green' Cross Co. 1947 v Red Cross. This is contemplating the remote or non-existence of connection between 'Greening' in co.-vid & co-vax-RFID-2020 + fin-(ger)tech electronic digits etc. Also, in contrast, in Ishii Shiro's 'death factories' case, ultrasonic was used instead.	
	The original meaning: can include 'green' pastures in Da-('big')-vid (wei-'protector' / space general) as opposed to CO.-(company)-vid-'protect'. Also, the Glyph ('bible'-space) Text overwrites the binary code programmed from outer-space unto the (radio frequency transmitter in the micro-chipped from the GO Shots).	
	11. <u>Field tests: materials adjustments for bomb-shells</u> 12. Ishii Shiro's Army Bocki Kyusui Bu: (translation) Anti-Epidemic Water Supply and Purification Bureau which suspiciously resonates with the 'New Water'. There was a scene in which Ishii Shiro urinated into his filters and offered the concoction to the (of) Emperor a cup of filtrated urine water (rejected) which Shiro downed with the delight the urine-turned-water, which fits exactly the description 'New Water' (fabricated-word 'Singapore'-version: comprises of Glyph beings). 13. The 'Diagnosis and Treatment' maybe a common term / coincidence / originator of or copied by the American (& other states') Version CDC	

patented ('war crimes profitable') process e.g. Identification-Diagnosis-Treatment-Prevention etc explained
 14. Overall, his criminal intent + criminal 'vision' envisioning the usage of BW (+ CW) as a means to a sort of leadership affirmation, ironically, after exposure to the 1925 Geneva Disarmament Convention which outlawed both, when one of the (Japanese) War Ministry Bureau attended.

[IISS SLD \(Malaysian Hotel: Malaysian OCBC straits 'trading' PRESS: 000, target GRAB money\) 1-Day MC SURNAME: CHIP-MAN \(IBM INTEL replica\)](#)

[PHOENIX-LAND \(1965 PLOT\): illegal Malaysians ATM-criminals-INFRA-stacking non-stop islandwide + illegal Indians \(cannot summon any military, nations, 'meet', cannot sign: criminals intent x no. PLOTS\)](#)

This is to show the time-frame between 1965 PLOT (prior to the entry of PHOENIX-LAND with criminal intent against unsuspecting Malaya-Chinese flood-in for INFRA-stacking shoeboxes (cannot house humans + cannot charge money + cannot build anything over any land) into ATM-TOM) and 2019.

Prior to the 2020 TV-(SATELLITE TOM)-injection of Lee in order to CHIP-genocide SGD (and phoenix islanders) and already pre-meditated X 60 Y EM LOGO MILITARY @ Illegal Indians stay (enter: NO CLAIM with criminal intent + BEYOND with illegal Malaysians in orchard rd ION) RAJARATNAM-dead.

Facts. Analysis. Influence. Q ABOUT US CONTACT US

RESEARCH DATA & ANALYSIS PUBLICATIONS EVENTS & DIALOGUES OUR PEOPLE ADVISORY MIDDLE EAST CRISIS

Events / IISS Shangri-La Dialogue 2019

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The BEYOND PLOTS: is a repeat crime (criminal act and criminal intent) of LAW-LESS AUTO-VOID paper-work of: illegal Indians Cavinder Bull (WB PHOTO-ID: CHIP-genocide Mumtha Washington D.C. and RAVI-KAMALA attempt: 600M BILLING only 1 sum backdated to bank a/c name: 1965 PLOT), Davinder Singh and Susil Nair: 1-Napier-India + 1-Rajah-Tan-Malaya: EM LOGO MILITARY GUN

	DOWN (PLUS 3 PLOTS, BEYOND PHOENIX LAND, FABRICATED GLYPH GROUPED PLOTS)	
	<u>Criminals 'Intent' Illegal Malaysians FAKE-NORDIC Chinese ATM Enter (1965 PLOT) and FAKE-NORDIC Illegal Indians enter Malaya:</u>	
	Ringgit-ATM (war prisoner 'stacking' Fabricated 'sgd') X 60 Y with 1-Napier-India + 1-Rajah-Tan (Indranee Rajah WCS Ringgit-pap illegal Malaysians Chinese ATM + Illegal Indians X 60 inside PHOENIX LAND) with GLOBAL (Indians) BLACKLISTED: Thiru (with INFRA-'ASIA' Banner: as evidence of criminal intent and criminal act in conjunction with the LAW-LESS illegal Indians at inception 1965 PLOT (of 'legislative' theft sites + illegal buildings theft sites: into ATM-TOM for COMPUTATION X 60.	
	Ringgit-ATM-(set-up 'party' ask-for-money 'Legislative' theft: \$M - \$Trillions) on illegal Malaysians stay inside PHOENIX-LAND where INFRA-tom began (cannot house) humans stacking non-stop islandwide + TEMASEK 1 ST STASH and subsequent stashes from robbing landed properties (cannot build anything over any land. It is required for the return of: ETERNAL LAND AMT Ret. + land ret. to others since 1965 PLOT + shoeboxes X 60 monies Ret. evacuate to Malaya-Land).	
	Thus, unhindered, illegal Indians that were NOT supposed to be inside the WHOLE OF ASIA 'GLYPH STATES' decide to commit: (1) CHIP-genocide and (2) BEYOND PLOTS: repeat crime with (3) SATELLITE-TOM + ATM-'Legislative' Theft: (stolen stash) \$M - \$Trillions X 60Y.	
	For example, (1) CHIP-genocide over (2) SATELLITE-TV broadcast (lee with the MILITARY) criminal act, intending to proceed: (3) BEYOND PLOTS repeat crime with Indians on illegal stay X 60 Y @ RAJARATNAM (illegal summon of EM LOGO MILITARY states: criminal act @ IISS CHIP-MAN (SLD sec listed, institutional investors TEMASEK and other malaysian criminals (shareholders / 'foundations' / (FRAUD / CON / THEFT) buildings' 'legislative'+statutory boards' theft-sites: for review and termination for the ret. of assets, keys, rockets and > \$Trillions + \$b \$m per page of illegal document X 60).	
	Subsequent, Ringgit-ntu-SATELLITE-TOM: Marjot singh m1 Thuraya (Yah-sat amazon locker Yah-oo) + Inmarsat Viasat + Airbus: Committed. Also, various SATELLITE products featured @ IISS CHIP-MAN.	
	IBM or IEEE claims to have some projects mention with Ringgit-ntu: universities fees bank a/c requires checking backdate = COMPUTE. The genocidal Ringgit-ntu-nus-sgh's'ia-Napier-Indian illegals & (Malaysian) shareholders = COMPUTATION.	

SURNAMED 'CHIP-MAN' PAID 1-3-DAY MC @ IISS @ RAJARATNAM EM LOGO MILITARY.

Beside the surname 'CHIP-MAN' (or 'WANG DI' the FAKE: prior series of FAKE NORDIC-indians Napier-Indians illegal (AUTO-BAR cannot sign AUTO-VOID on death penalty: repeat crime 1965 x 60) NORDIC-malaysian chinese 'straits-trading': for example, the KAMALA-'Harris' (Maybe 'Via-sat') that PERP-ID thought was funny for the upcoming chip-genocide: There are 1-2 considerations which include: (1) the MC was **paid** for his (western-) **accent** for 1-3 DAYS @ IISS organized by @ Rajaratnam-ATM-malaysian and indians on illegal stay X 60 Y of criminal act ('Straits Trading'-board with criminal record of TEMASEK TEMBUSU-Napier-India + Rajah Tan INFRA-rob foreign lands: repeat crime) with SATELLITE-TOM (stolen funds X 60 high likelihood with return of rockets by ST Engineering with \$b estimate to \$Trillions AMT x no. y)

SEE BILLION Y GLYPH TEXT EXPLANATION: NONE OF SPACE-KINGS PER BOOK IS SURNAMED (CHAPTER) 'KING'

FOR EXAMPLE (SEE DE-GLYPH-CODE): X3 NAMES SET = COVENANT-BOOK-GOD ('YAH'), 'BIG-SPACE-PROTECT' (GENERAL), CIRCUIT RACE OF GOD ('YAH') ... SO ON FORTH

HEAVEN & EARTH: 1-TRIBE AUTHENTIC YOU-DAH (BIG-PROTECT DA WEI + CIRCUIT RACE OF GOD: 'PROPHET KING-SPACE-CIRCUIT)

(RUPEE + RINGGIT V FORBIDDEN LANDS i.e. MILITARY STATES)
(illegal Malaysians ATM + Illegal Indians: X 60 consistent criminal record)
(2) There were complaints (questioning) in the british parliament by the military on illegal foreign (drugs) and criminal ring that were inconsistent with CHIP-MAN's criminal act: so he will be paid by the criminal (to ignore the BRITISH or ignorant of BRITISH military complaint in Parliament: under killer-SATELLITE-tom + 'b'-ATM-tom that shrinks money.) This is stifled by illegal rocket launch from stolen stash (for checking): replacement with an illegal Indian inside the parliament building.

INMARSAT is listed under UK: unclear for now.

Further details (on ATM-Toms in PLOTS): The Appendix to The Judgment

Illegals Indians X 60 @ Rajaratnam 'organizer' of @ IISS CHIP-MAN, 'Legislative theft x 60 COMPUTE'-Malaysian-(Ringgit-Lee-Foundation: Lee Shih Tih-TEMBUSU-TEMASEK to ret. LAND (1st stash + subsequent stash + All assets worldwide: using PHOENIX-LAND x 60 with BEYOND PLOTS criminal act) + LAND to others + shoeboxes monies x 60 + All buildings keys)-ATM-pap illegals X 60, F-stash: EM LOGO MILITARY X 60 SATELLITE-TOMS = ret. keys to bases.

HERE EVIDENCE OF: AUD (illegal summon by @ Rajaratnam @ IISS CHIP-MAN chip-genocide) (illegal Indians + Illegal Malaysians inside PHOENIX-LAND: stacking ('shoeboxes') x 60 Y on illegal stay)

@ IISS 1-day MC surnamed 'CHIP-MAN' (organized by Sri Lankan 'Global' @ EM LOGO MILITARY @ Rajaratnam Illegal Indians X 60 (traffick) + criminal intent Illegal Malaysians (flood-in): stacking humans INFRA-ATM-TOM X 60 + AUTO-BAR AUTO-VOID paper-work 'rajah-tan' 'napier-india TEMBUSU' (in the WHOLE OF ASIA: selling INFRA-banner 'THIRU' in ny) EM MILITARY GUN DOWN.

CRIMINAL FACULTIES: Ringgit-ntu-nus(various faculties blacklisted)-lky-rajaratnam

The 'GLOBAL ASIA' scam-sell: All criminal faculties in Ringgit-ntu-nus-rajaratnam, for example, Ringgit-lky-nus-'MAHBUBANI': INDIANS WHITE = NOT GLYPH STATES, NOT 'GLOBAL ASIA' LAW + Illegal stacking infra-Malaysian-ATM-Tom X 60 (1965 PLOT) inside PHOENIX-LAND: leads up to THIRU INFRA-ASIA-banner (global blacklist @ 201) (WCS = Indranee mangrove swamp CN + Infra-sg = \$b - \$trillion x no. y.

COMPUTATION (THE APPENDIX TO THE JUDGMENT)

illegal building over landed islandwide-phoenix: ETERNAL AMT x 60 to be returned by TEMASEK dbs + \$AMT of stacking humans into shoeboxes 'sgd' to be evacuated unto landed in Malaya in exchange.

	<p>There should be a global coordination of flower-pot smash CCTV + DIY LED pixel by illegal (infra-theft) criminal installation on Anti-Raja Day. This INFRA('Thiru')-construction-ATM-theft (repeat crime) is in conjunction with INFRA-CHIP-genocide (and entities: SPACE-X-INDIA minimally invasive GO-SHOTS / WB / BIS fraudsters (NOT ANY NATION, no official address: 1-indian + WCS world cities scam names usage x 100PLUS / no assets for liquidation) for computation + ret. keys)</p>		
	<p>'CHIP-MAN' refers to SATELLITE AIR + LAND INFRA-repeat crime + CHIP-genocide (EM LOGO MILITARY premeditated: explained in WLC Materials & Documents: IBM-INTEL-CO-VAX CHIP / WB / SPACE-X-INDIA / ABD (War-crime record) / AIIB / BIS fraudsters / ALL Infra-stacking shoeboxes (PRISON CELLS by behavioural war prisoners-Malaysians on illegal stay as strangers) wrong notes + illegal building over foreign land ATM-Tom + chip-inject necessitating CHIP-RF-KILL (EXTERMINATION) reversed on PERPS-ID + SUB-PERP INFRA-ATM-banks-in & offsprings (EXTINCTION in JAIL).</p>		
	<p>Other CHIP bank-in ALL industries including illegal container self-titled bank-in and cash-in checkpoints (electronic terminals % percentage theft per groceries requiring evacuation unto landed properties with veg + cow slots PORTS-DISCONNECT / CO-VAX circuitry CHIP in-brain barcode scanner RF-KILL criminal intent and criminal act committed).</p>		

EXTRACT: RAJAH (ILLEGAL-INDIANS X 60-CEMENT WAR ID) = COLLECT MONEY X 60 – 100 TIME-FRAME-PER 1-LOCATION + TRANSPORTER-EXIT OFF PHOENIX + ALL GLYPH STATES BAN

<p>PPT B</p>	<p><u>HANDSHAKE BEYOND PLOTS = TERMINATED (ports-DISCONNECT to PERP-ID SATELLITE-TOM) ALL STACKING ALL</u> <u>'C'-WORLD BAN = change to:</u></p> <p>ALL DISTRICTS LANDED ORIGINAL -ret. = PHOENIX DOLLAR + PHOENIX ROCKET + TRI-SOLAR TECH TRADES ALL GLYPH + PHOENIX BAR LICENSE ALL GLYPH + PHOENIX-GRANITE WLC LANDED PER GLYPH (BORN)</p> <p><u>PHOENIX-GRANITE WLC LANDED PER GLYPH +</u> <u>PHOENIX BAR LICENSE: DOCUMENTS SUBMISSION (ALL GLYPH STATES)</u> <u>PHOENIX ROCKET + TRI-SOLAR TECH TRADES + PHOENIX DOLLAR</u></p> <p><u>WAR-ID-PERP: TRANSPORTER EXIT-OFF (JUDGEMENTS ARCHIVES) WAR PRISON FACILITY: CEMENT-Illegal-indians-RUPEE WAR ID etc.</u></p>
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BEYOND stacking (Illegal Malaysians + Illegal Indians) 1965 PLOT: PLUS 3 + EM LOGO MILITARY (Gun down WANTED) Fabricated Glyph States + USMCA PLOT + Nordic-Eur-Swiss PLOT (illegal indians enter buildings: WCS self-titled FAKE-NORDIC)

Criminal Act & Criminal Intent: BEYOND 'handshake' PLOTS: repeat crime of INFRA-war prisoner stacking ('construction')-ATM-Tom + SATELLITE-Tom = ret. keys + \$Trillion \$m \$b x 60 backdate to 1965 + rocket keys + SBI Cluster etc + assets in 'ny' 'san jose' etc. (wrong label ATM: plus 3 cn)

TEMASEK = Ret. land (PHOENIX-LAND) + land robbed to others (TEMASEK ringgit-pap robbed 1. LTA to build over) + Ret. 'shoeboxes' (cpf-hdb-iras)-linked physical booklet ('PHOENIX DOLLAR') evacuation = ret. Malaya state.

CRIMINAL ACT: CRIMINAL FACULTIES on death penalty BEYOND @ Illegal Malaysians + Illegal Indians (ret. root village India) Sri Lanka @ Rajaratnam- = TERMINATED RINGGIT-pap X 60 – 100 Y LIE ('BILLING')

1-ILLEGAL MALAY (VOTELESS OF THE RINGGIT-pap RINGGIT-ntu: NOT sg + NOT WHOLE OF MALAY STATES) PAID BY MALAYSIAN (RINGGIT-ATM) ON DEATH PENALTY

ISLANDWIDE INVASION (CHIP-genocide)

BEYOND ('INVASION') SUGGESTIVE

/ SELF-TITLED: (VOTELESS) INVASION SPEECH

1-ILLEGAL MALAY (VOTELESS OF THE RINGGIT-pap RINGGIT-ntu: NOT sg + NOT WHOLE OF MALAY STATES) PAID BY MALAYSIAN (RINGGIT-ATM) ON DEATH PENALTY (INVASION 'INTENT' X NO. of PLOTS = TERMINATED)

1. Malays = ret. to Malaya states. RINGGIT-pap RINGGIT-ntu: (NOT eligible to use word 'sg' = constitutes ('shoeboxes') = BILLING

MALIKI (PART LAND THEFT 1965 PLOT CARD-IMPOSTERS: NO MH FLIGHT INTEL / NO MILITARY SATELLITE TECH REPORT (PHOTOSHOP HERE @ RAJARATNAM BOOK LAUNCH SELF-PROMOTION X NO. Y SALARIES LOOT,

RAJARATNAM FABRICATED 'ASEAN' (FAKE) LAND PLOTS LISTED FOR INVASION on death penalty = TERMINATED

- I want to commend RSIS for coming up with the idea of publishing this book, and bringing it to fruition. All the contributors have spent many years working overseas and in Singapore to fulfil their respective missions, and it was illuminating to read their stories and reflections. I am sure you will find it as illuminating too.

Overview of the book

- This book is timely because it traces how foreign policy has evolved alongside Singapore's transformation through the years. Singapore and ASEAN came of age through the Cambodian crisis of the late 1970s up to the early-1990s. By the end of the Cold War in the early-1990s, our foreign policy priorities became more economic-centric. We forged closer links to friendly states and all the major powers, as well as reached out to the emerging markets of the former Soviet bloc and its allies in developing countries. We did this by concluding close to 30 Free Trade Agreements (FTAs), as well as a host of other economic arrangements.
- Together with our ASEAN partners, Singapore achieved the vision of ASEAN's founding fathers of integrating Cambodia, Laos, Myanmar and Vietnam into the regional body and milestones such as the ASEAN FTA, ASEAN Community and ASEAN Charter. Singapore played a proactive role in creating the strategic regional architecture revolving around the ASEAN Regional Forum (ARF), the ASEAN+3 process with China, Japan and South Korea, the East Asia Summit (EAS), and the Asia-Europe Meeting (ASEM).

Seen here: MALIKI PROMOTING HIMSELF and BEYOND ('INVASION') SUGGESTIVE FABRICATED EM-LOGO MILITARY RF-KILL 'asean' + PLUS 3 PLOTS-EAST: CN J K (BEYOND PHOENIX-SOUTH) + X100PLUS MILITARY PLOTS on death penalty (*BEYOND* STACKING SGD RINGGIT-ATM on death penalty INVASION LIE X 60 (1965 PLOT)

EM LOGO MILITARY @ RAJARATNAM BOOK PROMOTION refers to severely disabled beyond INFRA-co-vax CHIP (on death penalty) + INFRA-'CONSTRUCTION' LAND (on death penalty) (infra-toms: ATM-REPEAT INVASION = COMPUTATION of B-TOMS + F-STASH)

I'll do a Book Review (if any Evidence: to add-on)

TABLE OF SUMMARY: SEQUENCE OF EVENTS @ IISS CHIP-MAN LEADING UP TO CHIP-genocide X100PLUS MILITARY CHIP-WAR CRIME @ RAJAH (Malaysian- 'SINGA'-WORKERS-pap CEMENT STACKING 'OC' + over ALL DISTRICTS LANDED ORIGINAL -ret. = PHOENIX DOLLAR + PHOENIX ROCKET + TRI-SOLAR TECH TRADES ALL GLYPH + PHOENIX BAR LICENSE ALL GLYPH

<p>@ IISS @ DUPE MILITARY Indians Trespassers SRI LANKA LAW-LESS CARD IMPOSTERS RAJARATNAM X 60 (1965 PLOT) (RUPEES V DOLLARS STASH) INDIA AIR (War Crime i.e. Murder Military) INDIAN World Cities'-ID ENTER DOLLARS ZONE</p>	<p>CAD CON-PAX SATELLITE b = Terminated (Location: Map)</p>	<p>(PART OF USMCA PLOT)</p>
<p>2023</p>	<p> Anita Anand Minister of National Defence, Canada USMCA PLOT</p>	
<p>2022</p>	<p></p>	
<p>2021</p>	<p>CO-VAX CHIP WORLD: \$5 X 3 BOOSTERS X USD STASH</p>	
<p>2020</p>	<p>CO-VAX CHIP WORLD: \$5 X 3 BOOSTERS X USD STASH</p>	

2019	 Harjit Singh Sajjan USMCA PLOT	
2018	 Ursula von der Leyen Minister of Defence, Germany Sued for Infra-co-vax-CHIP (NY Newspaper)	
2017	 Harjit Singh Sajjan Minister of National Defence, Canada USMCA PLOT SEE 'ABORIGINAL' LIE & Canadian 'Holocaust' Judgment SEE WLC Explanations: Illegal Indians nano-FET-BW	
<p>Based on the conclusive evidence combined @ Trilateral Commission + @ IISS @ Rajaratnam conman X 60 + illegal Indians X 60 (AMT X 60 COMPUTED): WHOLE OF ASIA ('YAH ZHOU' = GLYPH STATES) + WHOLE OF AMERICA + WHOLE OF EUR-NORDIC-SWISS</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. BLOCK (Closed) EMAIL: Ringgit-ntu-Rajaratnam CONMAN (illegal Indians x 60)-Ringgit-nus 2. WHOLE OF ASIA = did NOT attend the trilateral, except one: 1-India Man-'Barry Desker' (classified: INDIA) 3. WHOLE OF USMCA PLOT = did NOT attend, only 1-SINGH (who says he's 'Canada' or woman-Singh who says she's 'Canada') 4. Remove all illegal Indians inside (NOT Americans) 5. Ringgit-uni. = Relocate inside Malaya <p>Conclusion: ANTI-WHOLE OF ASIA-EM LOGO MILITARY (NOT India = LIE X 60 to low IQ pp) consistent criminal record X 60.</p>		

<p>BILL GATES WITH LEE (FIN=GER TECH FEST: b)</p>	<p>SEVERELY DISABLED CO- VAX is OBAMA-CARE (ADB BODY BAGS X60) WITH LEE</p>	<p>SEVERELY DISABLED CARE-SHIELD 'BEYOND'</p>
<p>1965 GLYPH ETERNAL LAND</p> <p>Ma-(Horse) lay-(Come)</p> <p>Ra-(Come) Ffles-(Buddha): 1-Day PAID MC</p> <p>WEF-Klaus Schwab RESET (NO BLUEPRINT)</p>	<p><u>WEF(THEFT OF ECONOMIES) KLAUS SCHWAB LEE HSIEN LOONG ('SYNAPSE-CO-VAX-CHIP')</u></p> <p>Illegal-indians-RUPEE-malaysian-'SINGA' WAR ID X 60 FRAUD</p>	
	<p>'catholics' genocided: INDIA-ESC Indians + offsprings (so Indians LIED) NOT part of catholics or pope. Married into society (mainstream): India-ESC.</p>	

	<p>INJECTION ON TV RESET KLAUS SCHWAB: INTRODUCED BY ILLEGALS INDIANS X 60 (GENOCIDE SPEECH BALA UN NY)</p> <p>'GLOBAL' INDIANS illegals X 60' TRESPASSERS: 1. BALA 'INTRO' RESET KLAUS SCHWAB TO 'LEE' (IN TURN CHIP-GENOCIDE / CHIP-SYS-CRIME / WAR CRIME CHIP SG-MILITARY), 2. D & BALA @ RAJARATNAM(-PAP 1965 PLOT-severely disabled 'beyond' b) MET 'POPE' 3. DUPE MILITARY @ RAJARATNAM @ IISS (-severely disabled pedo-b)</p>
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<p>INJECTION ON TV RESET KLAUS SCHWAB: INTRODUCED BY ILLEGALS INDIANS X 60 (GENOCIDE SPEECH BALA UN NY)</p>	<p>SE-LIST, RF-devices, FRAUD CEMENT-investor: media (Wrong def.) = COMPUTE</p>
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<p>INFRA-CHIP ECONOMIES (ALL INDUSTRIES: CONSTRUCTION, TIER 1, TIER 2) WEF-INDIA</p>	
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<p>KLAUS SCHWAB 'MEET' LEE : POST-COVID WORLDWIDE ENEMY NO. 1</p>	<p>COMPUTE WEF- WHO</p>
<p>HIGH PROBABILITY TO CONFIRMED STATUS: INSTRUMENTAL GENOCIDE-SG + ARMY + PER A-Z (SEE: ASSASSINATION REPORTS IN CASE: PROSECUTOR V GENOCIDAL PAXS) (ALSO, CRIMINAL INTENT AGAINST PER A-Z EXPOSED: IN KLAUS SCHWAB INFAMOUS 'GREAT RESET')</p>	

<p>EXHIBIT: KLAUS SCHWAB PHOTO-1 PROOF: HIGH CHANCE POCKETING MONIES AS PROXY OR PERP FROM CONTACT WITH LEE-(GAIN CRIMINAL ACCESS TO GENOCIDAL PROFITS MULTIPLIED PER SG) PLUS MISSION SUICIDE-ARMY + SELF-INJECT LEE + DEF-NG ON TV WITH BLOOD-CLOT ORGAN DAMAGE + HIV ENVELOPE + IRREVERSIBLE SPIKE PROTEIN WARP SPEED + MAGNETOFECTON + GRAPHENE</p>	
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	<p>1. BIO-W 1 PATENTED (CRIMINAL PLAN 'HATCHED': 1999) 2. BIO-W 2 FUNDING DISPATCH: WORLD BANK-ROCKEFELLER 3. SEE: PATENT 'HOSPITAL' ROTHSCHILD 4. BILL GATES: PATENT-666 E-VESSEL LOG-ON (SMART-KILL-NATIONS) PROOF.</p> <p>1. BIO-W 1 PATENTED (CRIMINAL PLAN 'HATCHED': 1999) 2. BIO-W 2 FUNDING DISPATCH: WORLD BANK-ROCKEFELLER 3. SEE: PATENT 'HOSPITAL' ROTHSCHILD 4. BILL GATES: PATENT-666 E-VESSEL LOG-ON (SMART-KILL-NATIONS) PROOF.</p> <p>THUS, INFRASTRUCTURE 'FREE-FLOW' CRIMINAL BILL & INSTALLATION OF ILLEGAL PAX TO FACILITATE CRIMINAL SIGNATURE-VOID PIECE OF DOCUMENT. NOT SG-PLUS NO-ONE VOTED.</p> <p>THUS, INFRASTRUCTURE 'FREE-FLOW' CRIMINAL BILL & INSTALLATION OF ILLEGAL PAX TO FACILITATE CRIMINAL SIGNATURE-VOID PIECE OF DOCUMENT. NOT SG-PLUS NO-ONE VOTED.</p>	
	<p>+ infra-co-vax-chip + infra-construction 'theft' LAND INVASION (WB + AIIB + ...) + : ENCOURAGED LEE TO SUICIDE HIMSELF OR LEE GOT AN EXTERNAL CALL FROM ABROAD OR LEE TOOK PLACEBO FROM CHOSEN NURSE.</p> <p>+ infra-co-vax-chip + infra-construction 'theft' LAND INVASION (WB + AIIB + ...) + : ENCOURAGED LEE TO SUICIDE HIMSELF OR LEE GOT AN EXTERNAL CALL FROM ABROAD OR LEE TOOK PLACEBO FROM CHOSEN NURSE.</p>	
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[EX-MAS] SUDDEN ('ADVISOR' OR SIMPLE MEET) GOH CHOK TONG + WEF
 KLAUS SWAB (CONNECTED BIO-WEAPONS: RESET IN-BRAIN INFRA-CO-VAX-
 CHIP + INFRA-CONSTRUCTION 'THEFT' INVASION) + LEE (CRIMINAL
 ASSOCIATION OR TRUST CRIMINAL SCWAB TO INJECT BIO-WEAPON
 HIMSELF ON TV: UNCLEAR IF MIN-CARD HOLDER (since almost all min-card
 holder r imposters X 60 criminal containers)

COMPUTE
 (MAS-'SINGA'-
 Malaysian)

EXHIBIT: KLAUS SCHWAB PHOTO-3-CHAIN OF EVENTS (V.B. GENOCIDAL SPEECH NEW YORK:
 CRIMINALS INDIVIDUALS POTENTIAL INTENT TO SLICE-OFF PIE BY 'CLAIMING CREDIT': COULD BE
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LEADING UP TO GENOCIDE-SG AND GENOCIDAL-GLOBAL.

SEQUENCE OF EVENTS: INFRA-BEARER BONDS (Using appearance of EX-MAS GOH) + INFRA-RESET CO-VAX CHIP (KLAUS SCHWAB-WEF ECONOMIES' THEFT) + INFRA-SATELLITE AI-KILL RUSSIA-UKRAINE (BALA + offsprings: INDIA) + SEVERELY DISABLED CARES ACT (OBAMA-CARE) USA-13, CARE-SHIELD (PHOENIX) [INFRA-CO-VAX-CHIP RF-ORGANS KILL NEURAL NET]

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VATICAN TOURIST (PHOTO-STRATEGY) + GENOCIDAL SPEECH 1-INDIVIDUAL (IILEGAL INDIAN USING WORLD CITIES' NAME): V.B.

NOT WHOLE-SG. 1-INDIAN ILLEGAL (BALA + OFFSPRINGS: INDIA)

NO AUTHORITY: 1-INDIVIDUAL (cannot sign anything on behalf of any nations)

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RANDOM + VOTELESS + ILLEGAL INDIA-ESC: use word 'SG' enter Vatican (genocidal criminal record X 60 +

Catholics = genocide India-INSIDE Canadia = INDIANS LIE ('GLOBAL' INFRA-co-vax CHIP + INFRA-LAND 'theft' (death penalty) + CRIMINAL LAW-FIRM (know))

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V.B. 'SUBSTITUTE REPLACEMENT' ON CFR (JUN 2023): OVER LEE-CFR - PROOF: CREDIT CLAIM PERPS-?

MORE ANALYSIS: ON CFR. (ANALYSIS SPEECH AND ID OF INVITES + TIME-FRAME IN HOME CTY)

V.B. 'SUBSTITUTE REPLACEMENT' ON CFR (JUN 2023): OVER LEE-CFR - PROOF: CREDIT CLAIM PERPS-?

SEE: 3-5 illegal paxs (NOT united,

		NO nations) Evidence: 1800
	MORE ANALYSIS: ON CFR. (ANALYSIS SPEECH AND ID OF INVITES + TIME-FRAME IN HOME CTY)	

TRILATERAL - NO INTEREST IN PERP-ID (LOGIC)

	<p>TRILATERAL (JAPAN CONFIRMATION: NO INTEREST IN PERP-ID CIRCLE LOGIC)</p> <p><u>Copied Logo Trilateral (2023): 'Rockefeller' F-Stash (WHO-WEF Brochure):</u> <u>\$5 x CO-VAX x No. Nations (Rajaratnam-dead use: deskert – Trilateral)</u></p> <div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 10px; text-align: center;"> <p>THE TRILATERAL COMMISSION</p> <p>LAST UPDATED SEPT 25, 2023</p> <div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 5px; margin: 10px auto; width: 80%;"> <p>LEADERSHIP</p> </div> <table style="width: 100%; border: none;"> <tr> <td style="width: 33%; text-align: center;">AXEL A. WEBER European Chair</td> <td style="width: 33%; text-align: center;">MEGHAN O'SULLIVAN North American Chair</td> <td style="width: 33%; text-align: center;">TAKESHI NIINAMI Asia Pacific Chair</td> </tr> </table> </div> <p>Here Takeshi Niinami Confirmation-ID: 'Suntory' beer Clear repeat expression: NO interest in PERP-circle.</p>	AXEL A. WEBER European Chair	MEGHAN O'SULLIVAN North American Chair	TAKESHI NIINAMI Asia Pacific Chair
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▲ **Takeshi Niinami**
 Chief Executive Officer, Suntory Holdings Limited

Here again, evidential confirmation of implied meaning, NO interest in PERP-circle is Suntory BEER.

However, consider the possibility of logistical distribution, exploitation by interested perp: EXAMPLE drugs-RING + (Rockefeller: WB drugs-based co-vax CHIP)

TRILATERAL COMMISSION - HENRY KISSINGER - THE ONE 1-PAX THAT BOTHER TO TURN-UP (MAY 2023)

WEF-KLAUS SCWBAB: (ABSENTEES-RUSSIA, CHINA, JAP-ABE-DEAD)

QUESTION: WHY IS HENRY KISSINGER -

TRILATERAL MEMBER HENRY KISSINGER (OLD AGE) WEF 2022 (on video screen) AND KLAUS SCHWAB (CLOSE CONNECTION)

Noticeably, a 'Henry Kissinger' even in old age to Klaus Schwab present at WEF 2022. Henry Kissinger holding a walking stick almost touchingly and criminally 1. close even up till old age,

<p>THE ONE 1-PAX THAT BOTHER TO TURN-UP?</p> <p>WHAT IS THE HISTORY BETWEEN KLAUS SCHWAB AND KISSINGER?</p>	<p>2. the only person that bother to turn-up (in the midst of global genocide with death statistics). (trilateral logo copied)</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="451 359 1544 615"> <tr> <td data-bbox="451 359 1377 472"> <p>TRILATERAL COMMISSION - HENRY KISSINGER – THE ONE 1-PAX THAT BOTHER TO TURN-UP (MAY 2023)</p> </td> <td data-bbox="1377 359 1544 472"></td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="451 472 1377 518"> <p>WEF-KLAUS SCWBAB: (ABSENTEES-RUSSIA, CHINA, JAP-ABE-DEAD)</p> </td> <td data-bbox="1377 472 1544 518"></td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="451 518 1377 564"> <p>QUESTION: WHY IS HENRY KISSINGER – THE ONE 1-PAX THAT BOTHER TO TURN-UP?</p> </td> <td data-bbox="1377 518 1544 564"></td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="451 564 1377 615"> <p>WHAT IS THE HISTORY BETWEEN KLAUS SCHWAB AND KISSINGER?</p> </td> <td data-bbox="1377 564 1544 615"></td> </tr> </table>	<p>TRILATERAL COMMISSION - HENRY KISSINGER – THE ONE 1-PAX THAT BOTHER TO TURN-UP (MAY 2023)</p>		<p>WEF-KLAUS SCWBAB: (ABSENTEES-RUSSIA, CHINA, JAP-ABE-DEAD)</p>		<p>QUESTION: WHY IS HENRY KISSINGER – THE ONE 1-PAX THAT BOTHER TO TURN-UP?</p>		<p>WHAT IS THE HISTORY BETWEEN KLAUS SCHWAB AND KISSINGER?</p>	
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WASHINGTON BASED INSTITUTE REPORTS: (PSEDUO-'TRIAD' LOGO PASTE: TRILATERAL) HENDRY KISSINGER DEAD

NATIONAL SECURITY ARCHIVE 35+ YEARS OF FREEDOM OF INFORMATION ACTION

Home Publications Postings Projects Documents FOIA DNSA Blog Русские Страницы About

Henry Kissinger's Documented Legacy

Henry Kissinger, 1975 (Wikimedia Commons)

A Declassified Dossier on HAK's Controversial Historical Legacy, on His 100th Birthday

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[LEGAL EVIDENCE DECLASSIFIED IN "THE DECLASSIFIED OBITUARY"](#)

Henry Kissinger: The Declassified Obituary

The Primary Sources on Kissinger's Controversial Legacy

Archive Obtained and Published Previously Secret Records on Kissinger's Role in Secret Bombing Campaigns in Cambodia, Illegal Domestic Spying, Support for Dictators, and Dirty Wars Abroad

Under 30 years of American Freedom of Information Act, the: THE 'NATIONAL SECURITY ARCHIVE' revealed:

Henry Kissinger is reported 'dead' or dead in 2023 by Washington based institute (with Evidence recap of Cambodia bombing).

Also, Available: India Briefing (2023) G20 itself confirms⁴⁷: Rightful absentees (from illegal 'meet': nations' theft 'intent' or 'act' include: mRNA Murder) explicitly stating clearly (QUOTE): "Chinese President Xi and Russian President Vladimir Putin were absent". Meanwhile, illogical (Illegal) India self-description as 'successful'.

Munich Security Conference 2009: Joseph R. Biden and Henry Kissinger - Munich Security Conference

[Visit](#)

Joe Biden (CO-VAX CHIP apparently) appears to know Henry Kissinger.

⁴⁷ National Portal of India (2024) G20: <https://www.india.gov.in/spotlight/group-twenty-g20>
(Showing connections: FB-Meta-Indian Collapse drawings @CJEU @MBS hence plausible 9/11 1-Indian crash maybe (USD V RUPEE))

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[KLAUS SCHWAB WITH HENRY KISSINGER: \(BOTH YOUNG\) VINTAGE COMICS](#)

[VINTAGE COMIC / PHOTO INSERT: HENRY KISSINGER WITH YOUNG KLAUS SCHWAB](#)

Lexica - Vintage comic of a young Klaus Schwab and Henry Kissinger

Lexica - Vintage comic of a young Klaus Schwab and Henry Kissinger

PPT D

INDIA / INDIAN SAINT PATRICK 'BARRY DESKER' AWARD =
 TERMINATED WORLDWIDE

FORBIDDEN: USAGE OF ANY INDIVIDUAL NAMES (WHOLE OF SGD)

WAR DECLARATION on death penalty PRE-MEDITATED X 60 @ RAJARATNAM SRI LANKA
 + string illegal indians X 60 CONMAN INVASION

Based this evidence 4, (criminal faculties on death penalty series X 60 consistent criminal record @ Rajaratnam EM LOGO Military @ IISS Chip-man @ SLD)

1. Clear now, that 'Barry Desker' = INDIA (No longer EURO) (NOT SGD: RUPEE Against SGD + PHOENIX)
2. Warwick = NOT 'british' conferred by African singer (removed off): Indian traffick (British meaning Nordic-blonde stopped licensing both Malaya & SG-sch inclusive of indians traffick)
3. Computation X 60 conman 'legislative' ATM 'judiciary' INVASION 'H.E.' organ damage EM LOGO MILITARY
4. Rajaratnam NEVER CAPABLE of running BOTH X 100 (EM CHIP-genocidal) MILITARY on death penalty EM LOGO MILITARY: SHOOT PERP-ID + MONEY ('banking toms': death penalty LAND + AIR Thieves' & offsprings) = CONMAN 'intent' GENOCIDAL (All participants: USD CAD MEXICO USMCA PLOT + SGD 1965 BEYOND PHOENIX PLUS 3 DRAGONS (TERMINATED) + JAYAKUMAR SR JR BARRY DESKER-INDIA was posing with NORDIC-EUR-SWISS PLOT & Rockefeller Trilateral (with India: NOT SGD + NOT PHOENIX + NOT PLUS 3 BEER CO. + NOT USMCA PLOT-SINGH) (COMMITTED CONSISTENT X 60 Y)

It is time to compute all b-Toms ('sgd' island size so physical booklet + sgd-phoenix dollars only + ret. Ringgit-ATM evacuation of ('shoebboxes') monies relocation into Landed properties Malaya-Land etc.

(alongside the mentioned String of illegal Indians at inception 1965 PLOT): classified as Indian (NOT EUR)

5. Indranee Rajah: is classified as Indian (NOT PHOENIX NOT CN)

There is no such thing 'british-(meaning Nordic-blonde)-India = LIE X 60 – 100 Y. All along = Malaya-Rupee set-up at the inception Ringgit-INVASION on death penalty WITH BEYOND 'intent' Infra-'construction' EM LOGO MILITARY STATES: LAND RAPISTS stacking sgd into RINGGIT-ATM + AIR RAPISTS + INFRA-co-vax-chip GO SHOTS constructed Ringgit-'sg'-h + x100 Y LIE 'come(RA)-buddha(FF)-LE (Fictitious school open x 100y) Raffles Medical (Phoenix bloodline: Billion Y).

6. BALA Vivian Balakrishnan: classified as Indian with offsprings (NOT SGD, NOT PHOENIX)
7. THARMAN Shanmugaratnam: classified as Indian with offsprings (NOT SGD, NOT JAPAN)
8. ... so on so forth. (all on death penalty INVASION usage word 'sg' 'cn' 'jap' 'eur-swiss' 'USD CAD' 'AUD' = EM LOGO MILITARY can shoot.

The criminal function of the illegal award to illegal Indians x 60 includes:

1. To perpetuate murder (against SGD 1965 *BEYOND* PLOTS) = TERMINATED (EM LOGO MILITARY Fabricated GLYPH STATES + PLUS 3 PLOTS + NEW PHOENIX DOLLAR: meeting PERP-ID)
2. Emirates exchange (meet): Removal of illegal Indians X 60 (INMARSAT + VIASAT + SAPCE-X) + Ringgit-pap muslim (THURAYA) = Ret. Emirates or Ret. India

Ringgit-nus- Sri Lanka x 60 conman Rajaratnam-NTU EM LOGO MILITARY-genocide committed x 60 consistent record = ret. keys + compute X 60 = closed

= RET. INDIA / MALAYA OR RET. EMIRATES

1. Desker (India = Ret. with all indians singh inside sg) = TERMINATED & off-Trilateral india saint Patrick called 'barry desker' india award
= TERMINATED WHOLE OF GLYPH ASIA (on www) (as with all other PLOTS: Indians invasion)

Trilateral (LOGO COPY): Desker-(Rupee) (NOT SGD + NOT PHOENIX) + OBAMA-CARE (USD)

Rockefeller F-STASH (suppose Mumtha-(Rupee) WB Chip-genocide USA-13 of the USMCA PLOT) = COMPUTED INTO PHOENIX DOLLAR

Rockefeller F-STASH: (suppose Mumtha-(Rupee) WB Chip-genocide USA-13 of the USMCA PLOT) = COMPUTED INTO PHOENIX DOLLAR (suppose BY INDIA AFB VADENBERG-INDIA-AFB CALIFORNIA)

	<p>(L) TEMASEK F-STASH (got 1st stash from LAND OWED: PROPERTIES PHOENIX ISLANDERS): (DEUTSCHE) LIM BOON HENG + TEMASEK F-STASH ('WCS' = WORLD CITIES' SCAM INDRANEE RAJAH (illegal india-ESC: NOT PHOENIX LAND NOT SGD) MANGROVE SWAMP INVASION 'CITIES' TARGETS on death penalty)</p> <p>Thus, RINGGIT-ESC on death penalty stacking sgd + ROCKEFELLER F-STASH = (suppose MUMTHA WASHINGTON D.C. WB (LOGO COPY) Chip-genocide SGD 1965 PLOT (EM LOGO MILITARY BEOND) = COMPUTED INTO PHOENIX DOLLAR</p> <p>'SEVERELY DISABLED BEYOND' PHOENIX SGD PLOT + PLUS 3 PLOTS (DRAGONS) + EM LOGO FABRICATED STATES + EM LOGO MILITARY X100PLUS: USD CAD NZD AUD ... EUR-NORDIC-SWISS PLOT etc</p> <p>INDIA-ESC on death penalty (suppose: ROCKEFELLER = MUMTHA WASHINGTON D.C. WB (LOGO COPY) INFRA-CHIP genocide USA-13 (USD) + INFRA-LAND PLOT: USMCA PLOT *****</p> <p>ROCKEFELLER is a criminal out to genocide (OR REVENGE behalf of USA-13 for personal interests) nations' TRILATERAL LOGO COPY TRIAD: inside USA-13 (NOT USA-13) = ROCKEFELLER met INDIA-DESKER (NOT SGD + NOT PHOENIX) AUTO-VOID AUTO-BAR cannot sign @ Rajaratnam (NOT SGD + NOT PHOENIX) Obama-CARES act (USD) (Satellite: Space-X Indian) + India-Bala Careshield (Thuraya + Airbus / Satellite: Inmarsat Viasat cpf + Ringgit-ATM: Ringgit-EM LOGO MILITARY X 60 consistent criminal record Ringgit-ntu-genocidal nus)</p> <p>EIMRATES EXCHANGE: suppose Alireza mahanfar ('Ali-pay' = Fast-pay cn = BIS-SPACE X-INDIA base on chip)</p> <p>Ringgit-mas RAVI MENON linked criminals DUPED TIER 1 TIER 2: BIS MAS FOR BILLING)</p> <p>INVASION SATELLITE b- insurance-satellite toms genocide) (/ WCS = WORLD CITIES SCAM: unknown rupee THIRU) *****</p>
<p>JOSEPH = 約yue 瑟se ph法- fa</p>	<p>JOSEPH = 約yue 瑟se ph法-fa (Correct law: GOD) = Joseph</p> <p>DECODE:</p> <p>JOSEPH = 約yue (COVENANT WITH GOD HIMSELF) 瑟se (double royal bloodline GLYPH) = Joseph</p> <p>Pha-roah = 法(fa-law) 老-(old-'magi') 王(king-pin perp-ID)</p>

<p>SAN = real ID =</p> <p>聖</p>	<p>DECODE: SAN = ('saint' NOT Indians saint joseph-glyph being or saint Patrick)</p> <p>SAN = real ID = 聖</p> <p>DECODE:</p> <p>聖 SAN 聖 = (GOD of the GLYPH GROUP)</p> <p>GLYPH means (GOD of the GLYPH GROUP = is the EAR that hears (like telephone booth) and MOUTH that speaks = seated as KING OF THE UNIVERSE: GOD is the only</p> <p>Also, no such fiction as: the 'saints' + ('r martyred) = LIE. = LIE. ALL FORCES + Nations-GENOCIDED: Supposed to 'take-out' all PERP-ID: Infra-ATM-tom.</p> <p>(repeat-kill god 2X per D) = FRAUDSTER.</p>
	<p>Plausible Front paid speech actors (with no blueprint to dupe) in the NORDIC-EURO-SWISS PLOT:</p>

LEGAL SECTION 8:

EXAMINATION OF COMPUTER YUAN

8.0. SUPREME PEOPLE'S PROCURATORATE 最高人民检察院

SUPREME PEOPLE'S PROCURATORATE (最高人民检察院: CHINA'S TOP PROSECUTOR): INVESTIGATION CORRUPTION CASE OF FAN (ACCUSED IS DUPED INTO COMPUTER MONEY YUAN MODEL OF 'PP BANK OF CHINA' (NOT CHINA / NOT THE PEOPLE OF CHINA))

Lee (Amanda) (2023) China's Anti-Corruption Body Expels Ex-Central Bank Deputy Fan Yifei From Communist Party For 'Serious Violations'. Date: 9.6.2023 Available: <https://www.scmp.com/economy/china-economy/article/3223572/chinas-anti-corruption-body-expels-ex-central-bank-deputy-fan-yifei-communist-party-serious>

Supreme People Procuratorate of the PP Republic of China (2024) Accused of illegal Receipt of 3.86 Billion Yuan! Fan Yi Fei Stand Trial. Available: https://www.spp.gov.cn/zdgz/202404/t20240418_652115.shtml

8.0.1. THE CHINESE ARREST OF FAN (范一飞) OF THE 'MONETARY 100+ CONMEN GROUP': BY THE HIGHEST POLITICAL PARTY FOR CORRUPTION INVESTIGATION INTERMEDIATE PEOPLE'S COURT, HUANGGANG, HUBEI

(2023) EX-PBOC Deputy Head Arrested On Suspicion of Bribery. 21, Jun. Available: <https://www.caixinglobal.com/2023-06-21/ex-pboc-deputy-head-arrested-on-suspicion-of-bribery-102067731.html>

Lin Jinbing and Qing Na. (2024) Former China Central Bank Deputy Admits Taking Over \$50 Million in Bribes. Caixin Global. 18, April. Available: <https://www.caixinglobal.com/2024-04-18/former-china-central-bank-deputy-admits-taking-over-50-million-in-bribes-102187752.html>

Cao Yin. (2024) PBOC Former Vice-Governor Pleads Guilty For Bribery. 14, May. Available: <https://www.chinadaily.com.cn/a/202404/18/WS662104efa31082fc043c2bf4.html>

8.0.2. PROPAGATION INVASION OF CHINA: DIGITAL-(SYNAPSE)-YUAN: MOST INFLUENTIAL 2022 'FEARSOME' AND 'ADMIRABLE' MU

1. Theories and (Criminal) Practice of Exploring China's e-NY against China

Changchun Mun (2022) Theories and Practice of Exploring China's e-CNY. People's Bank of China (DCI). 28 December 2022. Available: <http://www.pbc.gov.cn/en/3935690/3935759/4749192/index.html>

2. PILOT INVASION OF CHINA (STATES TARGETS) BY CRIMINAL PERP

Feng (2022) China Digital Currency: Beijing to Expand E-CNY Trials to Four Entire Provinces including Guangdong. South China Morning Post. Available: <https://www.scmp.com/tech/article/3193125/china-digital-currency-beijing-expand-e-cny-trials-four-entire-provinces>

2a. QUASI-A/C-TYPE (SECOND DIMENSION)

2b. WALLET MATRIX (THIRD DIMENSION)

INSERT PHOTO: MOST INFLUENTIAL 2022 'FEARSOME' AND 'ADMIRABLE' MU

Luo Xinyi (2022) Guiding The Chinese Central Bank Digital Currency the World Admires and Fears. Coindesk. Available: <https://www.coindesk.com/consensus-magazine/2022/12/05/mu-changchun-most-influential-2022/>

8.0.3 [INTERNATIONAL CRIMINAL LAW ON SYNAPSE-YUAN GENOCIDE / SYSTEMATIC CRIME / WAR CRIME REMOTE KILL-SWITCH: THE CHINESE DA-WEI SHIELD OVER THE PEOPLE OF CHINA AGAINST 'THE PEOPLE' \(NOT THE BANK OF CHINA' / NOT CHINA\)](#)

[INSERT PHOTO: LI BO AT THE CENTRAL BANK DIGITAL CURRENCIES SYMPOSIUM \(100+ ILLEGAL CENTRAL BANKS TIER 1: DUPED BY GLOBAL PERP ILLEGAL BIS ITSELF DUPED BY COMPUTER 'CONTROLLER' 'PROCESSOR' IBM-TYPE: CO-VAX CHIP NEUROMORPHIC SYSTEM / NEURAL NETWORK / NEUROGRID:\)](#)

IMF Event (2022) CBDCs For Financial Inclusion Risks and Rewards. IMF World Bank Group. Available: <https://meetings.imf.org/en/2022/Annual/Schedule/2022/10/14/imf-seminar-cbdcs-for-financial-inclusion-risks-and-rewards>

[UNDER INTERNATIONAL HUMAN RIGHTS LAW: RIGHT LIFE, LIBERTY SECURITY, EXPRESSION / INTERNATIONAL CRIMINAL LAW: CIRCUITRY GENOCIDE](#)

8.0.4. [INFRA-CHIP \(EX-PEDO-DRUGS-RING\)-b: INFRA-CHIP-E-SHOCK \(BRAIN EXPERIMENTATION E-SHOCK TIER 2 PEDO-b-HSBC \(SEVERELY DISABLED b OCBC\)](#)

[Legal Confirmation by 1. U.S. Military and US INTEL and 2. Civilian Intel USA Ex-Military\)](#)
[MATCH WITH: 1. IBM Synapse Axon Dendrites \(CO-VAX GO SiOx\) Neurosynaptic CORE, Meta-CHIP: Neuromorphic System / Neural Network / Neurogrid-POP100PLUS 2. NASA](#)

HONG KONG CONSITE: PEDO-b-HSBC CONFIRMED BY U.S. MILITARY AND U.S. CIA INTELLIGENCE

1. U.S. Military and US INTEL (TABLE): PEDO-HSBC
2. Civilian Intel USA Ex-Military (8,0.4 Table: Programming, Chemicals, E-Shock): FRITZ

INSERT: IBM / WB / INFRA-CHIP MAP ANALYSIS - PEDO-RING-HSBC OLYMPICS VILLAGE

LEGAL SECTION 8.1:

[EVIDENCE EXAMINATION: INTERNATIONAL COMPUTER 'YUAN' \(FALSE VERSION\)](#)

International Computer (NO MONEY) Scam Model: China YUAN Model (Criminal Technical Analysis)

8.1.1 [COMPUTER YUAN MODEL: COMPUTER FICTICIOUS PP BANK OF 'CHINA' \(NOT CHINA / NOT THE PEOPLE'S \(FAKE\) BANK\) \(FALSE VERSION\):](#)

1A. EXAMPLARY ALIPAY & TENCENT (DIAGRAM)

1B. DIAGRAMMATIC⁴⁸ TECHNICAL ANALYSIS USING ALIPAY: (WITH TENCENT LIKELY CO-OP SUB-PERP / PERP IN FALSE E-CURRENCY)

Takuma Yatsui. (2020) Implications of China's Digital Yuan Initiative - Potential Impact and Future Focal Points. *Mitsui & Co. Global Strategic Studies Institute (MGSSI) Monthly Report*. November 2020. Available: https://www.mitsui.com/mgssi/en/report/detail/_icsFiles/afieldfile/2021/01/07/2011c_yatsui_e_1.pdf

2. SUSPICIOUS & UNKNOWN CATALINI WOMAN OF 'CALIBRA' MISSING WEBPAGE SET-UP FOR FB-META M. ZUCKERBERG OF THE 'FAST-PAY' GANG @ BILL GATES' FIN-TECH FEST WITH MU

3. INSERT PHOTO: M. ZUCKERBERG 6H HEARING @U.S. House Committee on Fin-Services on LIBRA

⁴⁸ Takuma Yatsui. (2020) Implications of China's Digital Yuan Initiative - Potential Impact and Future Focal Points. *Mitsui & Co. Global Strategic Studies Institute (MGSSI) Monthly Report*. November 2020. Available: https://www.mitsui.com/mgssi/en/report/detail/_icsFiles/afieldfile/2021/01/07/2011c_yatsui_e_1.pdf

4a. NOTICE ALL OFFICIAL COURTHOUSES / CARD-IMPOSTERS: DAILY POST ILLEGAL MEET (voteless, criminal act) ON FB-META is NOT the 'gov'/ IS PART OF PERP GROUP)

Also, featured with other social media ('GLOBAL' INDIANS GENOCIDAL RECRUITS) on

4b. SINGH (no jurisdiction fight righteous GLYPH) FLIER: YIN YANG MA/NUFACTURED CARD / 'POLICE' CARDBOARD.

8.1.2 COMPUTER YUAN MODEL: BIS HONG KONG CONSITE (FALSE VERSION)

1. BIS HONG KONG CONSITE FORMAT

BIS CBDC LISTED (COMPUTER PROGRAMMABLE PROGRAMS FOR GLOBAL 'MONEY' SCAM SUSCEPTIBLE TO FIN-GER TECHNOLOGY OR ERRONEOUSLY DUBBED AS 'FIN-TECH') HONG KONG CONSITE⁴⁹

- PROJECT **GENESIS 1.0**: PROTOTYPE DIGITAL PLATFORMS FOR GREEN BOND TOKENISATION⁵⁰
- PROJECT **GENESIS 2.0**: PROTOTYPE USE OF SMART CONTRACTS FOR CARBON CREDITS ATTACHED TO GREEN BONDS⁵¹ **IAIN DAVIS**
- PROJECT **m-BRIDGE**: CONNECTING ECONOMIES THROUGH CBDC (INTHANON-LIONROCK to m-BRIDGE: MULTI-CBDC PLATFORM FOR INTERNATIONAL PAYMENTS) CHINA-UAE⁵²
- PROJECT **AURUM**: TWO-TIER (CRIMINAL INTRUSIVE INVASION) RETAIL CBDC SYSTEM⁵³

2. EVIDENCE OF PROGRAMMABLE SOFTWARE & META-CORE INSIDE COMPUTER CONTROLLER: CRIMINALLY ACCURATE NEUROMORPHIC SYSTEM SYNAPSE-YUAN (AND CO-VAX CHIP POP100)
(DIAGRAM OF COMPUTER NEURAL E-WALLET BLUEPRINT)

1. TABLE OF DUAL MULTI-CRIMES
2. TABLE: RE-CAP CRIMINAL EVIDENCE OF TYPE 1, TYPE 2

3. EVIDENCE OF CONSTRUCTION GANG ROBBERY: ('B' FAST CASH) STACKING (SINGAPORE / NEW YORK / HK) BULLDOZE LAND PERP STATUS EQUIVALENT TO MURDER (DIAGRAM-CHART OF PERPS)

LEGAL ANALYSIS UNDER INTERNATIONAL CRIMINAL LAW: WAR CRIME (NOT WAR IS MURDER STATUS)

1. **CONSTRUCTION 'B' TYPES: LAND THIEVES BY FUNCTION**
2. **CIRCUIT BOARD CHIP ILLEGAL FIN-DISTRICT X4**
3. **Table 1: Pilot 6-Wk Transaction PERP(-Eyeing to Rob) Stats (Pilot Test Subjects: GLYPH & Emirates)**
4. **Legal Exhibit: PERP digital points &/or nodes on Global Map ('Intent: Matches WB / ADB Land Thieves)**

BIS 'Innovation' HUB (2022) Project mBrige: Connecting Economies Through CBDC (Involving e-CNY / e-HKD / e-UAE / e-THB) Available: <https://www.bis.org/publ/othp59.pdf>

⁴⁹ EUROSISTEM: <https://www.bis.org/about/bisih/locations/eurosystem.htm>

⁵⁰ PROJECT GENESIS 1.0: https://www.bis.org/about/bisih/topics/green_finance/green_bonds.htm

⁵¹ PROJECT GENESIS 2.0: https://www.bis.org/about/bisih/topics/green_finance/genesis_2.htm

⁵² PROJECT mBRIDGE: https://www.bis.org/about/bisih/topics/cbdc/mcbdc_bridge.htm

⁵³ PROJECT AURUM: <https://www.bis.org/about/bisih/topics/cbdc/rcbdc.htm>

5. EVIDENCE OF (BIS) NEUROMORPHIC SYSTEM OF THE (CRIMINALLY ACCURATE VERSION): NEURAL SYNAPSE 'RESET' PHASE 1,2 ARRAY (BEAM-FORMING)

COMPUTER PROGRAMMABLE 'YUAN' (PART OF THE GLOBAL 'MONIES' CONMEN SCAM (FALSE VERSION) OVERSEEN BY BIS HONG KONG CONSITE WHILST THE CRIMINALLY ACCURATE VERSION (NEUROMOPRHIC SYSTEMS: CELLS LOG-ON E-SHOCK / NEURAL NETWORK) OVERSEEN BY ANY* (THE JUDGMENT & VOTES DECIPHER KING-PIN PERP) SUB-PERP CONSITES

8.1.3. COMPUTER MONEY YUAN MODEL: PEOPLE'S BANK OF CHINA (NOT CHINA) (FALSE VERSION / SYNAPSE-YUAN CRIMINALLY ACCURATE)

International Computer YUAN Model: PP BANK OF CHINA (NOT CHINA) (Criminal Technical Analysis)

PP BANK OF CHINA PATENTS: RADIO FREQUENCY ID

UTXO

8.1.3A PP Bank of China: Transaction Method and Device Based on Block Chain UTXO Model 高阳

CIPHER, QUADRANT MODEL

8.1.3B PP Bank of China: Transaction Method and Device Based on Digital Currency (Quadrant Model) (狄刚)

HASH ALGORITHM

8.1.3C PP Bank of China: Method and System For Providing Digital Currency (Hash Algorithm mirrors Microsoft Cryptocurrency 060606) (姚前)

8.1.3D BIS (FALSE VERSION): LEGAL MEANING OF 'INTER-OPERABILITY'

Huawei Model: (MICROWAVE ACCESS INTEROPERABILITY) Data Transmission Method, Data Transmission Device and Transmitter in Array Antenna Communication System

8.1.3A 姚前, 狄刚, 钱友才, 黄烈明, 陈海波, 赵新宇, 王继伟, 张大伟 (2017) Transaction Method and Device Based on Digital Currency. (Application Filed by the People's Bank of China (NOT the People of China) Digital Cash Research Institute. United States Patent Office. Patent No. CN107358424B. Available: <https://patents.google.com/patent/CN107358424B/en?q=CN107358424B>

8.1.3B 姚前, 狄刚, 钱友才, 黄烈明, 陈海波, 赵新宇, 王继伟, 张大伟 (2017) Transaction Method and Device Based on Digital Currency. (Application Filed by the People's Bank of China (NOT the People of China) Digital Cash Research Institute. United States Patent Office. Patent No. CN107358424B. Available: <https://patents.google.com/patent/CN107358424B/en?q=CN107358424B>

8.1.3C 姚前, 李会锋, 温信祥, 李连三, 王栋兵, 刘浩, 赵欣, 唐晓雪, 刘文舒 (2016) Method and System For Providing Digital Currency. (Application Filed by the People's Bank of China (NOT the People of China) Digital Cash Research Institute. United States Patent Office. Patent No. CN107230049B. Available: <https://patents.google.com/patent/CN107230049B/en?q=CN107230049B>

EVIDENCE EXAMINATION: PROGRAMMABLE E-WALLET SYNAPSE-YUAN (NOT MONEY) (WI-FI) PROGRAMMABLE SYNAPSE (THE CRIMINALLY ACCURATE VERSION)

Programmable E-Wallet (NOT MONEY) Synapse-YUAN Model: China Chinese Group (Criminal Technical Analysis)

8.2. COMPUTER SYNAPSE-YUAN MODEL: PP BANK OF CHINA (NOT CHINA) (CRIMINALLY ACCURATE VERSION) CRIMINAL MODEL USING

UNDER DATA PROTECTION LAW ('BODILY' CELLS: FUNCTION)
INTERNATIONAL LAW: CIRCUITRY GENOCIDE
SPACE LAW

PRODUCTS TYPE

A. EEG (NEURAL BODILY CELLS)

B. RADIO FREQUENCY ID PRODUCT

C. NEUROMORPHIC SYSTEM / NEURAL NETWORK / NEUROMORPHIC CIRCUIT META-CORES

D. WEAPONS SYSTEMS: MILITARY CRAFTS LOG-ON BY SATELLITES)

CONCLUSION: INTERNATIONAL CONSITES COMPUTER WI-FI PROGRAMMABLE E-WALLET (NOT MONEY) SYNAPSE-YUAN (NEURAL NETWORK / NEUROMORPHIC SYSTEM) (THE CRIMINALLY ACCURATE VERSION)

EEG SENSOR PRODUCTS TYPE

8.2 GUANGDONG OPPO EEG MODEL: BRAINWAVE

8.2.1. Oppo Mobile Model EEG #Lock: Electronic Device, Brain Wave Unlock Method and Related Product (CN108519810A) (#Zhang Hai Ping 张海平) (GUANGDONG, CN) (FIELD PROGRAMMABLE GATE ARRAY, FPGA)

8.2.2. Oppo Mobile Model EEG #Dialing: #Dialing Method And Related Product (CN108600502A) (#Zhang Hai Ping 张海平) (GUANGDONG, CN) (Field Programmable Gate Array FPGA).....9

8.2.3. Oppo Mobile Model EEG Analysis: Brainwave Information Transmission And Control Method And Related Product (CN108498094) (#Zhang Hai Ping 张海平) CO. IBM-INTEL-CHIP-TYPE SILICON SUBSTRATE).....9

8.2.4. Oppo Mobile Model EEG: Advertisement Broadcast Method and Related Product (CN 108391169A) (#Zhang Hai Ping 张海平) (GUANGDONG, CN)

8.2.1. 张海平 (2018) Electronic Device, Brain Wave Unlocking Method and Related Product. United States Patent Office. China IP Patent No. CN 108519810A. Available: <https://patents.google.com/patent/CN108519810A/en?q=CN+108519810A>

8.2.2. 张海平 (2018) Electronic Device, Dialing Method and Related Product. United States Patent Office. China IP Patent No. CN 108600502A. Available: <https://patents.google.com/patent/CN108600502A/en?q=CN+108600502A>

8.2.3. 张海平 (2018) Brain Wave Information Transmission and Control Method and Related Method. United States Patent Office. China IP Patent No. CN 108498094A. Available: <https://patents.google.com/patent/CN108498094A/en?q=CN+108498094A>

8.2.4. 张海平 (2018) Advertisement Broadcast Method and Related Product. United States Patent Office. China IP Patent No. CN 108391169A. Available: <https://patents.google.com/patent/CN108391169A/en?q=CN+108391169A>

LEGAL SECTION 8.3:

NEUROMORPHIC PRODUCTS TYPE

8.3. HUAWEI NEUROMORPHIC MODEL:

8.3.1. HUAWEI NEUROMORPHIC PATENT in conjunction with SHANGHAI INSTITUTE OF MICROSYSTEMS and INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY (SIMIT): Phased-Change Memory Material / Phased-Change Memory Cell / Phased-Change Memory (郑龙 SERIES, 宋志棠, 宋三年, 宋文雄, 唐文涛, 赵俊峰, 罗时)

8.3.2. HUAWEI MODEL: The Method and Apparatus of Model Predictive Control ('Controller') (Computation Logic) (Neuromorphic Computing Chip) (闫正)

8.3.3. HUAWEI MODEL: Neural Network Model Update Method (#Yuan Peng 袁鹏) (DNN / CNN / RNN)

8.3.1. 郑龙, 宋志棠, 宋三年, 宋文雄, 唐文涛, 赵俊峰, 罗时江 (2022) Phase-Change Memory Material, Phase-Change Memory Cell and Phase-Change Memory. United States Patent Office. China IP Patent No. CN 116,940,221A. Available: <https://patents.google.com/patent/CN116940221A/en?q=CN+116%2c940%2c221A>

8.3.2. 闫正 and 毕舒展 (2017) Method and Apparatus For Model Predictive Control. WIPO Patent No. WO2017/024583A1. Available: [https://patents.google.com/patent/WO2017024583A1/en?q=\(NEUROMORPHIC+VECTOR\)&assignee=HUAWEI&oq=NEUROMORPHIC+VECTOR+HUAWEI+](https://patents.google.com/patent/WO2017024583A1/en?q=(NEUROMORPHIC+VECTOR)&assignee=HUAWEI&oq=NEUROMORPHIC+VECTOR+HUAWEI+)

CN 107615186A. Available: [https://patents.google.com/?q=\(NEUROMORPHIC+HUAWEI+VECTOR\)&oq=NEUROMORPHIC+HUAWEI+VECTOR](https://patents.google.com/?q=(NEUROMORPHIC+HUAWEI+VECTOR)&oq=NEUROMORPHIC+HUAWEI+VECTOR)

8.3.3. 张新雨, 袁鹏, 方慕园, 钟钊 (2022) Neural Network Model Update Method, and Image Processing Method and Device. WIPO Patent No. WO 2021/120719 A1. Available: <https://patents.google.com/patent/WO2021120719A1/en?q=WO2021120719A1>

EEG SENSOR PRODUCTS TYPE

8.4. HUAWEI EEG MODEL:

8.4.1. HUAWEI MODEL: Identity Recognition Method and Device Based on Electroencephalogram Signal Method (#Yuan Peng 袁鹏)

8.4.2. HUAWEI MODEL: Visual Evoked Potential-Based Identity Verification Method and Device (WO2017/201972 A1) (#Yuan Peng 袁鹏)

8.4.1. 袁鹏, 薛希俊, 姚骏 (2017) Identity Recognition Method and Device Based on Electroencephalogram Signal. WIPO Patent No.: WO2017/201972A1. Available: <https://patents.google.com/patent/WO2017201972A1/en?q=WO2017%2f201972A1>

8.4.2. 袁鹏, 薛希俊, 姚骏 (2018) Visual Evoked Potential Based Identity Verification Method and Device. WIPO Patent No. WO 2018/112799 A1. Available: <https://patents.google.com/patent/WO2018112799A1/en?q=WO+2018%2f112799+A1>

ALIPAY CASHIER THEFT:

Insert: PHOTO Supermarket Theft

NEUROMORPHIC PRODUCTS TYPE

8.5. ALIPAY NEURAL NETWORK MODEL:

8.5.1 ALIPAY MODEL: Target Recognition and Neural Network Model Processing Method Based on Image (WO2017/201972 A1) (JING DA KAI 金达开)

8.5.2. ALIPAY MODEL: (Brain-based) Shopping Method and device based on Brain-computer and Brain-Nerve Signals and E-Equipment (CN113421141A) (裴龙凯)

8.5.3. ALIPAY MODEL: (Disease Insurance by Computer Force) Event Investigation Method and Device (曲春雨)

8.5.1 郭大洲, 金达开, 吕乐, 王普阳, 闫轲, 周靖人, 吉张鹤轩 (2023) Target Recognition and Neural Network Model Processing Method Based on Image. United States Patent Office. Patent No. CN 116167990A. Available: <https://patents.google.com/patent/CN116167990A/en?q=CN+116167990A>

8.5.2. 裴龙凯 (2020) Shopping Processing Method and Device Based on Brain-Computer and Brain Nerve Signals and Electronic Equipment. United States Patent Office. Patent No. CN 113421141A. Available: <https://patents.google.com/patent/CN113421141A/en?q=CN113421141A>

8.5.3. 廖梓函, 李楠, 曲春雨 (2021) Event Investigation Method and Device. United States Patent Office. Patent No. CN 113221529A. Available: <https://patents.google.com/patent/CN113221529A/en?q=CN113221529A>

AMERICAN EXPRESS MODEL:

8.5.4. AMERICAN EXPRESS: (SEVERELY DISABLED INSURANCE THEFT BY COMPUTER FORCE) Manging Insurance Product With an Insurance Value Chain (Michael Concannon, John Anthony Levin)

8.5.4. Michael Concannon, John Anthony Levin (2012) *Managing An Insurance Product with An Insurance Value Chain*. United States Patent Office. Patent No. US 20150206250A1. Available: <https://patents.google.com/patent/US20150206250A1/en?q=US20150206250A1>

IBM MODEL: ANATOMICAL SEGMENTATION

8.5.5. IBM PATENT: System And Method For Virtual World Biometric Analytics Through The User of A Multi-Modal Biometric Analytical Wallet (AARON K. BAUGHMAN) (ANATOMICAL SEGMENTATION)

8.5.5. Aaron K. Baughman, Christopher J. Dawson, Barry M. Graham and David J. Kamalsky (2018) System and Method For Virtual World Biometric Analytics Through The Use of A Multi-Modal Biometric Analytic Wallet. Available: <https://patents.google.com/patent/US20180096228A1/en?q=US20180096228A1>

NEUROMORPHIC PRODUCTS TYPE

8.6. TENCENT NEURAL NETWORK MODEL:

8.6.1. TENCENT 'HEALTHCARE' SHENZHEN CO. LTD MODEL: (Brain) Image (Using Cloud) Segmentation Method, Device, Equipment, Program Product and Medium (黄雅雯, 黄慧敏, 王红, 李悦翔)

8.6.1. 黄雅雯, 黄慧敏, 王红, 李悦翔 (2023) Image Segmentation Method, Device, Equipment, Program Product and Medium. CN115965785A. Available (Google Patent): <https://patents.google.com/patent/CN115965785A/en?q=CN115965785A>

CONCLUSIONS:

GLYPH GROUP: PHOENIX SINGAPORE = USA-13 PHOENIX LOGO
DRAGON = 'PLUS 3' CHINA, JAPAN, KOREA

COMPUTE ECONOMIES' MONIES: INTO CITIZENS' B

ILLEGAL CONTAINER BANKS: LAND-ROB COMPUTE X NO. YEARS, KILL-OFF POST-LOOT OF COMBINED LOOT

CHIP-GENOCIDE / CHIP-SYSTEMATIC CRIME / CHIP-WAR CRIME: 'KILL-OFF POST-LOOT (/ COMBINED LOOT ATTEMPT = TERMINATION ARREST GO SHOTS + RF-KILLED)

ECONOMIC OVER-KILL BY SHRINKING ECONOMIES VIA SPAWNING UP TO INFINITE ZERO-COST ONLINE CONSITES VIA ILLEGAL SIGNATURES VOID 'FREE-FLOW' A-Z BILLS (ILLEGAL CONTAINER BANKS)

EXAMINATION OF COMPUTER YUAN

BACKGROUND

8.0. SUPREME PEOPLE'S PROCURATORATE (最高人民法院: CHINA'S TOP PROSECUTORATE): INVESTIGATION CORRUPTION CASE OF FAN (MAYBE DUPED INTO COMPUTER MONEY YUAN MODEL OF 'PP BANK OF CHINA' (NOT CHINA / NOT THE PEOPLE OF CHINA))

8.0.1. THE CHINESE ARREST OF FAN OF THE 'MONETARY 100+ CONMEN GROUP': BY THE HIGHEST POLITICAL PARTY FOR CORRUPTION INVESTIGATION INTERMEDIATE PEOPLE'S COURT, HUANGGANG, HUBEI

Fan is part of the People's Bank of China. The erroneous self-title 'People's Bank of China' is NOT CHINA meaning without knowledge and awareness of both the false version and criminally accurate version of e-CNY. Furthermore, is overseen by 'agency' BIS Hong Kong con-site. In addition, it could be on behalf of a hidden perpetrators' group (criminals: PERP-RACE from location con-sites with computer CHIP and satellite access illegally) attempting to invade more China-land test sites using computer 'digital yuan' in 2022. Fan got sacked by 2023 (on a separate matter although he was inevitably involved in e-yuan due to his high status). He was the highest ranking (most senior) top deputy governor of China's Central Bank at PPBOC to be arrested. He was officially terminated as 'corrupt'. He was expelled under 'serious violations' of law (against China's top anti-corruption body) and placed under investigation by the Communist Party's disciplinary organ.⁵⁴

Fan Yifei

⁵⁴ Lee (Amanda) (2023) China's Anti-Corruption Body Expels Ex-Central Bank Deputy Fan Yifei From Communist Party For 'Serious Violations'. Date: 9.6.2023 Available: <https://www.scmp.com/economy/china-economy/article/3223572/chinas-anti-corruption-body-expels-ex-central-bank-deputy-fan-yifei-communist-party-serious>

Here is the original document⁵⁵ from the Supreme People's (Hua Ren: The GLYPH Chinese people) Procuratorate of the People's Republic of China:

The screenshot shows the official website of the Supreme People's Procuratorate of the People's Republic of China. The header features the national emblem and the name of the institution in Chinese and English. Below the header is a navigation menu with categories like '机构设置', '检察新闻', '工作信息', '检察业务', '检察院建设', '12309中国检察网', and '中国检察听证网'. The main content area displays a news article titled '被控非法收受3.86亿余元! 央行原副行长范一飞受审' (Accused of illegally receiving 3.86 billion yuan! Former deputy governor of the PBOC Fan Yifei is on trial). The article includes the date '2024-04-18', the author '魏哲哲', and the source '人民日报客户端'. A photograph shows a courtroom scene with a man in a dark suit standing at a podium, and several men in police uniforms standing nearby. Below the photo is a caption: '湖北省黄冈市人民检察院起诉指控: 1993年至2022年, 被告人范一飞利用担任原中国人民建设银行信托投资公司计财部经理、总经理助理、资金'.

In Caixin Global news report published, “EX-PBOC (People’s Bank of China) Deputy Head Arrested On Suspicion of Bribery”⁵⁶, Fan Yifei (范一飞), former deputy governor of China’s Central Bank arrested for suspected bribery faced criminal investigations and eventually prosecuted by Supreme People’s Procuratorate (最高人民检察院: China’s Top Prosecutorate). Fan became the deputy head of People’s Bank of China (PBOC) in early 2015 and oversaw “fin-(ger) tech’ and payment sectors”. He was placed under disciplinary and supervisory investigation in November 2022 reportedly the highest ranking official and central banker probed after October’s 20th National Congress of Communist Party of China (CPC).

⁵⁵ Supreme People Procuratorate of the PP Republic of China (2024) Accused of illegal Receipt of 3.86 Billion Yuan! Fan Yi Fei Stand Trial. Available: https://www.spp.gov.cn/zdgz/202404/t20240418_652115.shtml

⁵⁶ (2023) EX-PBOC Deputy Head Arrested On Suspicion of Bribery. 21, Jun. Available: <https://www.caixinglobal.com/2023-06-21/ex-pboc-deputy-head-arrested-on-suspicion-of-bribery-102067731.html>

In a separate Caixin Global newsCDSS report published, “Former China Central Bank Deputy Admits Taking Over \$50 Million in Bribes”⁵⁷, Fan 59 as former deputy governor of China’s PBOC pleaded guilty to accepting \$53.3 million (386 million yuan) in bribes over three decades.

In China Daily news report published, “PBOC Former Vice-Governor Pleads Guilty For Bribery”⁵⁸, Fan pleaded guilty at the Intermediate People’s Court in Huanggang, Hubei province was found to have taken advantage of his positions such as deputy head of China Construction Bank’s fund planning division, Chairman of Bank of Shanghai, Vice-President of China Investment Corporation and Vice-governor of PBOC between 1993 to 2022 according to Huanggang prosecutors.

On a preliminary observation note, FAN has proven himself as a charismatic (illegal) ‘sales man’ (except a sort of position abuse due to his primary seat as part of the China ‘gov’) with the ability to amass 50 Million. Suppose the ‘bribes’ were offered by extremely wealthy individuals to obtain their hearts’ (legal) desires, this sort of traditional Chinese ‘ang bao’ gifts behind doors is the grey area. More importantly, FAN is involved in a ‘global’ plot by PERP with intent against China (/ the people of China) so his case requires review (and evidence interview).

8.0.2. PROPAGATION INVASION OF CHINA: DIGITAL-(SYNAPSE)-YUAN: MOST INFLUENTIAL 2022 ‘FEARSOME’ AND ‘ADMIRABLE’ MU

Below is the portrait of Changchun Mun falsely labeled as the magazine⁵⁹’s “most influential 2022”, Either working against China (his own nation he disowned OR he’s caught completely unaware of cell tower synapse CHIP controller’s plot). The title of the article labelled him as one that: “the World ‘Admires’ (questionable, dubious at best, shunned by the entire western world, for instance, U.S.A. highly wary of the sinister hidden agenda behind / tied to the Beijing Olympics with the IBM CHIP Agent that penned down his location as UK embedded in the Games Village address) and ‘fears’ (of the unknown until this paper came along to shed light on the world to see [the tip of the iceberg hidden network of] perpetrators’ modus

⁵⁷ Lin Jinbing and Qing Na. (2024) Former China Central Bank Deputy Admits Taking Over \$50 Million in Bribes. Caixin Global. 18, April. Available: <https://www.caixinglobal.com/2024-04-18/former-china-central-bank-deputy-admits-taking-over-50-million-in-bribes-102187752.html>

⁵⁸ Cao Yin. (2024) PBOC Former Vice-Governor Pleads Guilty For Bribery. 14, May. Available: <https://www.chinadaily.com.cn/a/202404/18/WS662104efa31082fc043c2bf4.html>

⁵⁹ Luo Xinyi (2022) Guiding The Chinese Central Bank Digital Currency the World Admires and Fears. Coindesk. Available: <https://www.coindesk.com/consensus-magazine/2022/12/05/mu-changchun-most-influential-2022/>

operandi behind neuromorphic system and criminal blueprint of synapse-currencies scam, not just against the people of China e.g. Synapse-dollar]. War history repeats itself: In other words, WHITE-PERP initiate war against American White from inside a foreign land under the guise of an alternate GLYPH-race (without that race being aware). Same tactic, soon to be outdated and transparent worldwide due to easy identification / recognition of PERP signature recurring pattern / criminal technique ingrained into 'common public knowledge'-the public and offsprings made wiser, vigilant.

MU CHANGCHUN PORTRAIT⁶⁰: 'MOST INFLUENTIAL' 'FEARSOME' 2022 (FALSE)

SEE: COMIC LOOK

8.0. COMPUTER MONEY-'YUAN' MODEL PROGRAMMABLE E-WALLET (NOT MONEY): COMPUTER BANK OF CHINA (FALSE VERSION)

8.0. Programmable E-Wallet (NOT MONEY) Computer 'YUAN': Computer Bank of China (PLUS 3 PLOT)

8.0.2. HIDDEN PERPETRATORS' NETWORK PROPAGATION INVASION OF CHINA-LAND / 100 PLUS: SYNAPSE-Yuan THE PEOPLE OF CHINA (Using Self-Titled: 'the PP Bank of China') (NOT the people of China / NOT CHINA)

1. Theories and (Criminal) Practice of Exploring China's e-NY against China

In Mu People's Bank of China paper (which I selected because of his concise write-up), "Theories and Practice of Exploring China's e-CNY"⁶¹ by Changchun Mu⁶², Director-General of the Digital Currency

⁶⁰ Criminal Format: Exposed Network with front paid salespersons e-CNY simultaneous e-DOLLAR (SYNAPSE-Currencies) propagation invasion TERMINATED: <https://www.coindesk.com/consensus-magazine/2022/12/05/mu-changchun-most-influential-2022/>

⁶¹ Changchun Mun. (2022) Theories and Practice of Exploring China's e-CNY. People's Bank of China (DCI). 28 December 2022. Available: <http://www.pbc.gov.cn/en/3935690/3935759/4749192/index.html>

⁶² Chang Chun, Mu, Theories and Practice of Exploring China's e-CNY, <http://www.pbc.gov.cn/en/3688006/4706656/4749192/2022122913350138868.pdf>

Institute (DCI), the pilot tests of the (COMPUTER) 'Digital' Yuan (e-CNY) started at end-2017 and **Shenzhen, Suzhou, Xiong'an, Chengdu** at end-2019 and Beijing Winter Olympics' opening in February 2022. Governor Yi Gang said no timetable for official launch of DCEP despite the trials that took place at the stated dates. ALL such (PLUS 3) PLOTS: Terminated. See: WAR DECLARATION DUPED MILITARY X 60 Y @ Rajaratnam-dead.

YI GANG

Yi Gang
Deputy Governor

COMICAL-SIDE OF MU: "MAKE ALI-PAY & WECHAT-PAY REDUNDANT"

2. PILOT INVASION OF CHINA (STATES TARGETS) BY CRIMINAL PERP: TERMINATED

Pilot areas (planned by hidden perpetrators) were supposed to be expanded to include 6 more **cities: Shanghai, Hainan, Changsha, Xi'an, Qingdao and Dalian** (Nov 2020) with (planned) increasing additions such as **Beijing & Zhangjiakou, Tianjin, Chongqing, Guangzhou, Fuzhou, Xiamen and the 6 Asian Games Host cities in Zhejiang** with increment of up to 23 cities that joined the e-CNY pilot ('plot') since 2022. There is media claim that PPBOC intends to expand e-CNY trials to **Guangdong, Hebei, Jiangsu and Sichuan** provinces.⁶³

'People's Bank of China' (NOT CHINA) established the Digital Currency Research Institute in 2017 and Facebook Inc. (is Huawei and a Plethora of Telcom Brands: inventors-sharing format) declared its digital currency 'LIBRA' in June 2019 (SEE: ABOVE PHOTO)

⁶³ RF-CHIP PERP POSTED in SOUTH CHINA MORNING POST: (THREAT ILLEGAL ATTACK CHINA / LEGAL RECOMMENDATION: REVERSE ON PERP & OFFSPRINGS) ALL such (PLUS 3) PLOTS: Terminated.

Feng (2022) China Digital Currency: Beijing To Expand e-CNY Trials to Four Entire Provinces including Guangdong. South China Morning Post. Available: <https://www.scmp.com/tech/article/3193125/china-digital-currency-beijing-expand-e-cny-trials-four-entire-provinces>

2a. QUASI-A/C-TYPE (SECOND DIMENSION)

Mu speaks of a quasi-a/c based and a/c-based payment system with a loosely-coupled a/c linkage design, whereby the public could apply for Digital Wallet without opening bank a/cs in advance. For instance, the least privileged Digital Yuan wallet can be set-up with any users' unique ID such as mobile phone number thus users' real identity is not necessary. Users are permitted to upgrade wallets by furnishing extra details: ID / Banking A/C info. / Plan to make large payments amounts or maintain higher balances. Digital Yuan wallets can also be classified into BALANCES AND TRANSACTION CAPS amount.

(Apparently, there seems to be: "Personal Information Protection Law of China", in effect: TELCOM operators are forbidden to disclose identity information to authorized operators or PBC, thus rendering the wallet user anonymous to banks / merchants / PBC. In other words, directly accessible by HIDING BIG BROTHER-TYPE unknown perpetrators to execute fantasy of a remote 'kill-switch' or numbers flip, freeze etc. All container banks and 'digital' monies (NOT MONEY) are illegal and for criminal (purposes theft, murder) explained clearly in this document.)

2b. WALLET MATRIX (THIRD DIMENSION)

Digital Yuan can be classified in the following manner: Holder Type / Carrier Type / Management Authority with additions to the WALLET MATRIX pre-meditated against China.

Under the HOLDER TYPE, e-CNY is categorized as individual (including self-employed) wallets and corporate (legal and non-legal pax) wallets. The functions can be customized (meaning 'programmable').

Under the CARRIER TYPE, e-CNY is classified as S/W wallets and H/W wallets. S/W wallets provide payments services via apps or S/W development kits. H/W wallets are supported by IC CARD / mobile phones / chips / wearable objects: badges, bracelets, smart watches, gloves and IoT (Internet of Things) devices with payment functions.

Those with MANAGEMENT AUTHORITY, users can set major wallets as main and open several sub-wallets under the umbrella of the main wallets.

E-CNY sells / on-board sub-wallets to online merchants including e-shops platforms, O2O (online-to-offline) platforms, using encryption and tokenization.

The transaction volume of e-CNY total amount: 230 million (NOT MONEY) with transaction value approximating RMB 88 Billion. E-CNY is accepted by 3.6 million merchants (NOT MONEY) in diversified areas of products and services: utility, government services, transportation, shopping and catering

8.0.3 INTERNATIONAL CRIMINAL LAW ON SYNAPSE-YUAN GENOCIDE / SYSTEMATIC CRIME / WAR CRIME REMOTE KILL-SWITCH: THE CHINESE DA-WEI SHIELD OVER THE PEOPLE OF CHINA AGAINST 'THE PEOPLE'S BANK OF CHINA' (NOT CHINA) (THE CHINESE GROUP)

UNDER INTERNATIONAL HUMAN RIGHTS LAW: RIGHT LIFE, LIBERTY SECURITY, EXPRESSION / INTERNATIONAL CRIMINAL LAW: CIRCUITRY GENOCIDE

There are several ridiculous (at best) and obvious criminal scam advocated using “the people of China” as mouthpieces (by hidden perpetrators against the PEOPLE OF CHINA) at the ‘People’s Bank of China (NOT CHINA) employees: Firstly, the ‘People’s Bank of China (and even the Reserve Bank of India)’ is contemplating programming **expiration dates** into their CBDC (NOT MONEY). The obvious (perpetrators’ intent) implication is that the Chinese (and the Indians) CBDC users are not permitted to save, mandating compulsory spending of their issued ‘e-money’ (NOT MONEY) before expiration (that is, ceases to function), touting thus as ‘stimulating’ economic activity [which is the pretext claimed by SHADY BLACKROCK for ‘going direct’ announcement in Pilot Test New York Banks (against the AMERICANS) with the criminal intent to manifest the most gross and serious violation of financial sovereignty against PER A-Z nations possible.

LEGAL EXHIBIT: 3. WB IMF MURDER INTENT & ACT AGAINST CHINA (GLYPH GROUP)

PHOTOGRAPHIC EVIDENCE: LI BO @ WB INFRA-CHIP (SEE: TYPES 1-6) PERPETRATOR AGAINST 100PLUS MILITARY @ WB IMF MURDER INTENT ACT)

CENTRAL BANK ‘DIGITAL’ (MEANS COMPUTER) CURRENCIES SYMPOSIUM⁶⁴
(100+ TIER 1: DUPED BY ‘GLOBAL’ (INDIAN) PERP BIS ITSELF DUPED BY COMPUTER ‘CONTROLLER’ ‘PROCESSOR’ IBM-CHIP TYPE:
CO-VAX CHIP NEUROGRID: NEUROMORPHIC SYSTEM / NEURAL NETWORK

⁶⁴ IMF Event (2022) CBDCs For Financial Inclusion Risks and Rewards. IMF World Bank Group. Available: <https://meetings.imf.org/en/2022/Annual/Schedule/2022/10/14/imf-seminar-cbdc-for-financial-inclusion-risks-and-rewards>

COMPUTE	IMF
State: x, y, z ... x time- frame	

Secondly, Li Bo, DMD-IMF, Deputy governor of the 'PP BANK OF CHINA' (NOT CHINA) stated at the "Central Bank Digital Currencies for Financial Inclusion: Risks and Rewards Symposium⁶⁵ (QUOTE) "CBDC can allow government agencies and private sector players to program (CBDC) to create **smart contracts**, to allow targeted policy functions." For example, welfare payments ... consumption coupons, ... food stamps. By programming, CBDC money can be precisely targeted [to] what kind of [things] people can own, and what kind of use [for which] this money can be utilized, for example, ... for food (necessity: basic right to life) ... periodic welfare sums dispatch (for basic living / survival).

The first and second facts is a blatant act intended to eliminate economic and social freedom contrary to the international human rights law.

Thirdly, this unreal scenario (apparently, had already functioned in China and suggestively with 'the BANK OF ENGLAND', NOT the people of UK) with the computer perpetrators envisioning via programming s/w that the more personal identification data shared with BoE (BANK OF ENGLAND), the 'sweeter' permitted use of CBDC experienced, thus the 'sweetness level' is dependent on individual civilians' willingness to comply. Failure to comply can result in the punitive inability to function as mainstream society's citizen. (A worse outcome can be E-shock from PEDO-RING banks' harboured drugs monies' experimentation⁶⁶ with neuromorphic system via neural network explained in detail.)

⁶⁵ Bo Li speaking at the *Central Bank Digital Currencies for (FALSE) Financial Inclusion: Risks and Rewards* symposium.

⁶⁶ See: Fritz's documents.

EVIDENCE EXAMINATION: INTERNATIONAL COMPUTER 'YUAN' (FALSE VERSION)

International Computer (NO MONEY) Scam Model: China YUAN Model (Criminal Technical Analysis)

8.1.1 COMPUTER YUAN MODEL: PP BANK OF CHINA (NOT CHINA) (FALSE VERSION): EXAMPLARY ALIPAY & TENCENT_CO. BRANDS SUB-PERP or PERP

1. EXAMPLARY ALIPAY & TENCENT (DIAGRAM)

DCEP is categorized as a retail-type (FALSE) currency: (SEE: FIG. 1) based on materials published by Computer Perp against Bank of Japan.

Figure 1: Classification of Digital Currencies and Major Examples

	Issuer	
	Private	Central Bank
Retail-type (For the public)	Alipay, WeChat Pay, Suica, Libra	digital yuan, e-krona, Bakong (Cambodia)
Wholesale-type (For financial institutions)	JPM Coin (JPMorgan Chase)	Project Stella (Joint research project by BOJ and ECB)

Note: Including those currently being researched and planned

Source: Created by MGSSI based on materials by the Bank of Japan

IMPORTANT NOTICE:

Also, rather suspicious that the materials above is suggested by the Computer Bank of Japan against the Japanese people (by PERP) when the Japanese had already expressly went against e-yen with the act of cash preferred.

As stated (in Section 11: Computer Bank of R is NOT Bank of R NOT R because it is simply a virtual world with a virtual shop labeled 'anything e.g. computer Bank of R'), so it is plausible this document preparer can be non-Japanese / Anti-Japan (non-protector) (bombed and combined loot e.g. gold owed stolen).

LEGAL ANALYSIS & JUDGMENT:

This document using the word 'Japan' and 'China' by questionable writer(s) are Anti-Japan and Anti-China (GLYPH GROUP: PERP is (genocidal) against the people of Japan and China SG-PLUS 3 PLOT hence ADB / the world's people e.g. USMCA PLOT / Nordic-Eur-Swiss PLOT hence WB. WB writers: criminal.)

1B. DIAGRAMMATIC⁶⁷ TECHNICAL ANALYSIS USING ALIPAY: (WITH TENCENT LIKELY CO-OP SUB-PERP / PERP IN FALSE E-CURRENCY)

⁶⁷ Takuma Yatsui. (2020) Implications of China's Digital Yuan Initiative - Potential Impact and Future Focal Points. *Mitsui & Co. Global Strategic Studies Institute (MGSSI) Monthly Report*. November 2020. Available: https://www.mitsui.com/mgssi/en/report/detail/_icsFiles/afieldfile/2021/01/07/2011c_yatsui_e_1.pdf

Figure 3: Diagram of DCEP Payment via Alipay and Other Methods

Note: Arrows show flow of money
Source: Created by MGSSI

COMPUTE	ALI-PAY	COMPUTE
State: x, y, z	REPLICATED	Satellite-TOM
... x time-frame	PAY x no. states names	Telcom-TOM
	PASTE	

Mu Changchun, Head of the Digital Currency Research Institute, said that the basic DCEP ('Digital Currency Electronic Payment') payment function is akin to QR code payment systems like private payment 'Alipay'. However, DCEP is a digital wallet separate from the savings account (SEE: FIG. 3) thus the payment flow is vastly different from Alipay. Alipay and other methods are directly linked to a user's savings account for payment. In contrast, under DCEP, money in savings account is first converted to DCEP before making payment.

LEGAL ASSESSMENT

Fan explained that PBOC (decipher on visual recognition and functionalities) and with designated operating agencies will jointly develop a e-wallet platform. Mu state the PBOC will accept a good path from amongst several designated operators each adopting a different technical path. In other words, it is highly plausible to almost certainty that Fan is 1. Completely unaware of the synapse-killers' plot against 'the good people of China, is likely 2. Not a technical expert or the technical designer or the perpetrator running the 'controller' China CHIP China individuals' CORE.

Fan's definition of "two-tier operating system" refers, (Either in his opinion or instructed by FALSEHOOD-TYPE runners of 'the People's Bank of China' (NOT CHINA) attempting to dupe the people of China), to a selection of commercial banks and major state-owned commercial banks with a strong capital base and high technological capabilities acting as "designated operating agency" to open the digital wallets and convert to and from DCEP for users. In other words, Fan is 1. Completely unaware of the 2-Tier Frequency band-TYPE transmission (CO-VAX transmitter and retrieval of selective data from the neural cells) by telecommunications system in context.

Based on both Mu's and Fan's testimonies, it sounds like they both do not know the technicalities of e-(SYNAPSE)-Yuan since firstly, (1) they require "designated operating agency" thus rendering control (and the technical 'controller' in its technical blueprint) in the hands of unknown remote genocidal or medi-(drug & concoction of bacteria / viruses / embryos eggs payload release-TYPE) crime perpetrators and secondly, are (2) completely unaware of the criminally accurate (version) meaning of e-(SYNAPSE)-Yuan which means e-bodily (Neural) cells log-on broadly categorized into Neuromorphic System or Neural Network (binary language programmed into outer-space by satellite perpetrators) functioning as 'rewards/punitive/e-shock system' kill-switch plot.

EVIDENCE EXAMINATION: INTERNATIONAL COMPUTER 'YUAN' (FALSE VERSION)

International Computer (NO MONEY) Scam Model: China YUAN Model (Criminal Technical Analysis)

8.1.1 COMPUTER YUAN MODEL: PP BANK OF CHINA (NOT CHINA) (FALSE VERSION): EXAMPLARY ALIPAY & TENCENT_CO. BRANDS SUB-PERP or PERP

2. SUSPICIOUS & UNKNOWN CATALINI WOMAN OF 'CALIBRA' MISSING WEBPAGE SET-UP FOR FB-META M. ZUCKERBERG OF THE 'FAST-PAY' GANG @ BILL GATES' FIN-TECH FEST WITH MU

PHOTOS OF MU (BEING SET-UP AGAINST THE PEOPLE OF CHINA: COMPUTER YUAN [NOT MONEY] & UNAWARE of SYNAPSE-YUAN) WITH SUSPICIOUS UNKNOWN WOMAN CHRISTIAN CATALINI OF SUSPICIOUS AND UNKNOWN CO. CALLED CA-LIBRA OR 'LIBRA': AGAINST THE PEOPLE OF AMERICANS ATTEMPT TO INFILTRATE THE PEOPLE IN 100+ NATIONS, SET-UP WITH M. ZUCKERBERG: 'PAY'-GANG @ MICROSOFT WO060606 BODILY LOG- SWITCH FIN(-GER)-TECH

Here is a photo of 'Mu' being set-up against ('behind the back of' without the full consent / knowledge / awareness of the evil infiltration plot against) the People of China-land for 1. Computer Yuan [NOT MONEY] and 2. Mu plausibly being completely unaware of Synapse Yuan [IBM-TYPE neuromorphic chip WiFi programmable remotely] with B. a suspicious and unknown woman 'Christian Catalini' of a suspicious and unknown co. called Ca-libra or 'Libra' for short set-up with C. FB-META-WHATSAPP (with Indian woman photo as WHATSAPP cover) endorser M. Zuckerberg against the People of America as part of 'the PAY-GANG' called 'FAST-PAY' Computer Dollar [NOT MONEY] in order to attempt to infiltrate the people in 100+ nations.

Mu made a comment of eradicating WeChat Pay and AliPay out of DCEP (Digital Currency Electronic Payment) but that can mean substituting with any alternate tom-dick-harry-PERP-Pay electronic system which is electronic money (NOT MONEY). He mentioned the 2-tier system: which shows ignorance of the criminally accurate 2-tier frequency band CO-VAX CHIP in-body crypto-currency. However, he stated: hybrid of 'account-based system' and 'value-based system' and an overall 'cash-light' NOT cashless society.

EVIDENCE EXAMINATION: INTERNATIONAL COMPUTER 'YUAN' (FALSE VERSION)

International Computer (NO MONEY) Scam Model: China YUAN Model (Criminal Technical Analysis)

8.1.1 COMPUTER YUAN MODEL: PP BANK OF CHINA (NOT CHINA) (FALSE VERSION): EXAMPLARY ALIPAY & TENCENT_CO. BRANDS SUB-PERP or PERP

3. INSERT PHOTO: M. ZUCKERBERG 6H HEARING @U.S. House Committee on Fin-Services on LIBRA
 M. ZUCKERBERG AT LIBRA TESTIMONY: PERP-ID intent to rob nations (Meta-Indians: Collapse buildings 'lousy' drawings)

Here is Mark Zuckerberg that testified through a six-hour hearing in front of the U.S. House committee on Financial Services on Libra.

Upon some simple verification, even the basic access to the 'Calibra' co. is a missing website and 'Calibra' is not featured on wiki as a basic introduction.

In addition, all official courthouses and CARD-imposters 'photoshop' posting on FB is evidence but cannot be treated as submission to social media because FB is social media is NOT official 'governance' of any nations: legislative / parliamentary / executive functions.

4a. NOTICE ALL OFFICIAL COURTHOUSES / CARD-IMPOSTERS: DAILY POST OF THEIR ILLEGAL 'MEET' ON FB-META (CONSTRUCTION LAND) THEFT ACT (voteless, criminal act) is NOT the 'gov' / IS PART OF PERP GROUP)

Also, it is noticed in addition to all courthouses / CARD-imposters' daily post on of criminal act (national theft @ USMCA PLOT / SG-PHOENIX PLUS 3 PLOT / NORDIC-EUR-SWISS PLOT / murder @ military dupe 'meet') or illegal 'foreign sales' 'meet' (as voteless and 1-2 NOT 1-2 nations) on FB-META: FB-META are NOT the 'gov' is part of PERP group.

Another example, 'Indian (recruit) Singh' the construction (theft 'B') flier: 'Yin Yang' manufacture CHIP card (for illegal genocidal grassroots CC) malay video teller linked 'global' 'indian' linked San Jose (PERP-TECH CO. state).

4b. SINGH 'CONSTRUCTION' THEFT ACTOR AND SINGH (TRESPASSER OF SINGAPORE-PHOENIX LAND ROBBED: no jurisdiction fight righteous GLYPH) FLIER: YIN YANG MANUFACTURED CARD / 'POLICE' CARDBOARD.

Another example, cardboard photograph of police (outside Library / technology shops) and IBM Neuromorphic CO-VAX CHIP CCTV deceptively pasted label 'Police' as PERP real-time remote kill-shot aim (with no circuitry, CHIP meta-core, submissions nor approval). All CCTV / LED Pixel (DIY) in public-rights-of-way are illegal: flower-pots smash @ Anti-Rajah day (global coordination). Also, the criminal CCTV installation were installed by 'Indian' garbage dump (daily) to decipher when to enter or exit to (commit construction / 'renovation' loot) rob nations. Also, construction loot contractors plug-off CCTV at their loot site in fear whilst CCTV entire nations.

8.1.2. COMPUTER PROGRAMMABLE 'YUAN' (FALSE VERSION):

1. BIS HONG KONG CONSITE

LEGAL ANALYSIS

The 'People's Bank of China' (NOT CHINA) digital currency electronic payment DCEP m-Bridge CBDC cross-border payment system is overseen, meaning computer software run by BIS Hong Kong (named consite but not necessarily at named location, any consite with the computer chip 'controller' or simply inside 'Beijing' IBM 'Games Village' address).

For samples of suspicious (computer) programs (programmable), as follows:

1. BIS HONG KONG CONSITE FORMAT

BIS CBDC LISTED (COMPUTER PROGRAMMABLE SOFTWARE DIGITAL YUAN SW TECHNOLOGY ERRONEOUSLY DUBBED AS 'FIN-TECH') AT CON-SITE HONG KONG⁶⁸

- PROJECT **GENESIS 1.0**: PROTOTYPE DIGITAL PLATFORMS FOR **GREEN BOND** TOKENISATION⁶⁹
- PROJECT **GENESIS 2.0**: PROTOTYPE USE OF SMART CONTRACTS FOR **CARBON CREDITS** ATTACHED TO GREEN BONDS⁷⁰
- PROJECT **m-BRIDGE**: CONNECTING ECONOMIES THROUGH CBDC (**INTHANON-LIONROCK** to **m-BRIDGE**: MULTI-CBDC PLATFORM FOR INTERNATIONAL PAYMENTS) CHINA-UAE⁷¹

⁶⁸ EUROSISTEM: <https://www.bis.org/about/bisih/locations/eurosystem.htm>

⁶⁹ PROJECT GENESIS 1.0: https://www.bis.org/about/bisih/topics/green_finance/green_bonds.htm

⁷⁰ PROJECT GENESIS 2.0: https://www.bis.org/about/bisih/topics/green_finance/genesis_2.htm

⁷¹ PROJECT mBRIDGE: https://www.bis.org/about/bisih/topics/cbdc/mcbdc_bridge.htm

- PROJECT **AURUM**: TWO-TIER (CRIMINAL INTRUSIVE INVASION) RETAIL CBDC SYSTEM⁷²

LEGAL CONCLUSION

Based on this FORMAT: GENESIS and m-BRIDGE are computer systems explained in Tier 1 Criminal Variants Model in Section 11. The legal conclusion (in conjunction with PERP quadrant x4 nations' CHIP): is that X4 illegal FIN-districts are reduced to a computer CHIP.

8.1.2. COMPUTER PROGRAMMABLE 'YUAN' (FALSE VERSION):

2. EVIDENCE OF PROGRAMMABLE SOFTWARE & META-CORE INSIDE COMPUTER 'CONTROLLER': CRIMINALLY ACCURATE NEUROMORPHIC SYSTEM SYNAPSE-YUAN (CO-VAX CHIP POP-100) (DIAGRAM OF COMPUTER NEURAL E-WALLET BLUEPRINT)

DIAGRAM: M-BRIDGE PLATFORM LAYERS PROGRAMMABLE SOFTWARE (FALSE VERSION) OF: THE CRIMINALLY ACCURATE NEUROMORPHIC SYSTEM: SYNAPSE-YUAN (CO-VAX CHIP NEUROGRID POP-100: META-CORE INSIDE COMPUTER 'CONTROLLER')

Here is the (FALSE) BIS⁷³ diagram of its suggestive programmable software of electronic banks linked to BIS (FALSE VERSION) of what appears to be the criminally accurate version of neuromorphic system / neural CHIP (IBM-TYPE).

⁷² PROJECT AURUM: <https://www.bis.org/about/bisih/topics/cbdc/rcbdc.htm>

⁷³ BIS duped by BIS 'global Indian' conmen duped 100+banking since his technical brochure contains vague to none technical details / blueprints as the erroneous (FALSE) 'global tech chair' i.e. infra-chip of existing infrastructure of 100+banking.

FIG. 8.1.2. CLASSIFICATIONS OF INFRA-CHIP: CRIMINAL EVIDENCE OF TYPE 2 AND TYPE 1 UNDER COMPUTER SYNAPSE YUAN (CRIMINALLY ACCURATE VERSION) BRIEF

DUAL-MULTI-CRIME		LEGAL ANS: CITIZENS' b + ETERNAL LAND PLOT @ WLC MILITARY Annual 'Take-out' simulation + JUSTICE BOARD Computation AMT: Loot X 60 Y (All industries: Shareholders' Hearing, Vote PERP-ID offsprings + Eternal LAND + Pre-Med Eternal LAND Amt
TYPE 1	PERP infra-CHIP b existing (illegal containers of nations' loot: 'B') computerized network infrastructure.	<p>Participating commercial banks in the pilot Graph 5</p> <p>COMPUTE</p>
TYPE 2	IBM-TYPE CO-VAX CHIP (Organs / Bodily cells) of SYNAPSE-Currencies: data bank of neural cells 'laced' with Graphene / Silicon Oxide / Circuitry transmitters	USMCA PLOT
		SG-PHOENIX 1965 PLOT PLUS 3 PLOT: CN JP K (GLYPH GROUP)

So what happens is: in addition to TYPE-1 Pilot testing New York-TYPE banking district by using perpetrator's (e.g. infra-)chip of the existing computerized network infrastructure of (illegal container) banks (containing loot of and) embedded in A-Z nations, [(THE CRIMINALLY ACCURATE AND COMPREHENSIVE VERSION)]

Whereas. TYPE-2 IBM-TYPE CHIP also contains electronic banks of SYNAPSE-Currencies e.g. SYNAPSED-DOLLAR (PERP refers to: Americans' / Australians' CO-VAX CHIP data bank of neural cells 'laced' with Graphene / Silicon Oxide / Circuitry Transmitter),

SYNAPSE-YUAN (PERP refers to: GLYPH group CO-VAX CHIP data bank of neural cells 'laced' with Graphene / Silicon Oxide / Circuitry Transmitter) etc.

RE-CAP OF CRIMINAL EVIDENCE OF TYPE 2 AND TYPE 1:

The (1) circuitry of transmitters micro-constructed by micro-bots remotely programmable by wifi, (2) publicly admitted (public admission) by IBM-INTEL-TYPE publications and conferences and EEG-TYPE CHIP (3) BIO-W 1 CO-VID [LAB DESIGN] WIV NIH journal publications, mRNA Cancer Indian Research Institute NUS global blacklisted with Indian 'Thiru' Event 201 pocket by foreigners NOT SINGAPORE-PHOENIX

NATION (4) MASTERCARD 1-2 'global indians' infiltration 'diseased' criminal PER pilot test NY banks / merchants with the strongest concentration based on the New York heat map hence reflecting: the Neural Net of CHIPPED organs cells (for example, in New York). Further documented by: 1. medical photographic evidence 2. lab reports on graphene oxide GO and SiOx 3. Other academic lab results: ionized membrane potentials 4. Neurogrid IBM gating variables. (Another example, Bangalore, Eroude (criminal 'global indians') satellite infiltration into LONDON (illegal banks') banking district. The point is the infiltration itself is without approval / illegal and with criminal intent against the public).

RE-CAP:

8.1.2. CLASSIFICATIONS OF INFRA-CHIP: CRIMINAL EVIDENCE OF TYPE 1

FIG. 8.1.2. CLASSIFICATIONS OF INFRA-CHIP: CRIMINAL EVIDENCE OF TYPE 2 AND TYPE 1 UNDER COMPUTER SYNAPSE YUAN (CRIMINALLY ACCURATE VERSION) EXPANSION VERSION

DUAL-MULTI-CRIME		<p>CRIMINAL EVIDENCE</p> <p>LEGAL ANS: CITIZENS' b + ETERNAL LAND PLOT @ WLC MILITARY Annual 'Take-out' simulation + JUSTICE BOARD Computation</p> <p>AMT: Loot X 60 Y (All industries: Shareholders' Hearing, Vote PERP-ID offsprings + Eternal LAND + Pre-Med Eternal LAND Amt</p>
TYPE 1	PERP infra-CHIP b existing (illegal containers of nations' loot: 'B') computerized network infrastructure.	
<p>TYPE 2</p> <p>USMCA PLOT</p> <p>SG-PHOENIX PLUS 3 PLOT: CN JP K (GLYPH GROUP)</p>	<p>IBM-TYPE CO-VAX CHIP (Organs / Bodily cells) of SYNAPSE-Currencies: data bank of neural cells 'laced' with Graphene / Silicon Oxide / Circuitry transmitters</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Lab reports on Graphene Oxide / Silicon Oxide (inside shots / injectables) 2. Ion-ized membrane potentials: matches IBM NeuroGrid POP100+ gating variables. 	<p>TRANSMITTER CIRCUITRY: MICRO-CONSTRUCTED BY MICRO-BOTS (REMOTE PROGRAMMABLE WIFI)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Medical Photographic Evidence
	<p>BIO-W 1: CO-VID</p> <p>LAB MADE WIV WITH PETER DASEK + FAUCCI: GLOBLA NEWS + NIH JOURNALS EVIDENCE WITH NAMES</p> <p>mRNA INDIAN PHOTOS CANCER RESEARCH INSTITUTE NUS (NOT SINGAPORE: FOREIGN POCKET)</p>	<p>BIO-W 2: CO-VAX</p> <p>PUBLIC ADMISSION: IBM-INTEL TYPE EEG-TYPE CO-VAX CHIP</p> <p>Organized IEEE Conferences and Publications (New York)</p>
		<p>MASTERCARD 'GLOBAL' INDIANS Trespassers</p> <p>INFILTRATION: Indian Name</p> <p>New Delhi</p>

		'DISEASED' CRIMINAL PER PILOT TEST @ NY BANKS SHOWS: LARGEST CONCENTRATION HEAT MAP REFLECTS NEURAL NET OF CHIPPED ORGAN CELLS.
		LONDON IBM: Indian Names Bangalore, Eroude
		T-MOBILE USA / NASDAQ / T-SYSTEM EUR T-Mobile: Indian Names
		THE FOUR: AMAZON / SPACE X / GOOGLE / MICROSOFT The Four Co.: Indian Names

8.1.2. COMPUTER PROGRAMMABLE 'YUAN' (FALSE VERSION):

3. EVIDENCE OF CONSTRUCTION GANG ROBBERY + 'W'B' + 'A'D'B': ('B' FAST CASH) STACKING (SINGAPORE / NEW YORK / HK) BULLDOZE LAND PERP STATUS EQUIVALENT TO MURDER UNDER INTERNATIONAL CRIMINAL LAW: WAR CRIME (NOT WAR IS MURDER STATUS)

LEGAL DIAGRAM: PROGRAMMABLE SOFTWARE (FALSE VERSION)⁷⁴ TERMINATION OF ALL SUCH PLOTS:

1. COMPUTER PERP CHIP THE CONSTRUCTION GANG 'B' (LAND THIEVES) BY FUNCTION:

HK-STACKED (e-HKD), CN-LAND (e-CNY), UAE-LAND (e-AED) AND THAI-LAND (e-THB):

SYNAPSE-CURRENCIES (CRIMINALLY ACCURATE) (INCLUSIVE OF CHIP BOTH CONTAINER, CONTAINER BANK-OWNERS' IN-BRAIN AND USERS' IN-BRAIN)

Participating commercial banks in the pilot

Graph 5

LEGAL ANALYSIS

Here is the (FALSE) BIS⁷⁵ of electronic banks in listed con-sites: HK, CN, UAE and Thailand, but factor in the IBM-INTEL-TYPE CHIP of computers data retrieval, access and 'controller' of TYPE-1 (False version) TYPE-2 (Criminally Accurate) of Neural cells CO-VAX CHIP. In theory, the computer base stations con-sites need not necessarily be only situated in such stated locations.

⁷⁵ BIS 'Innovation' HUB (2022) Project mBrige: Connecting Economies Through CBDC (Involving e-CNY / e-HKD / e-UAE / e-THB) Available: <https://www.bis.org/publ/othp59.pdf>

Also, the genocidal act of CO-VAX CHIP data bank of neural (organ) cells refers to including that of illegal containers' bank owners' and users of such banks.

LEGAL DIAGRAM: PROGRAMMABLE SOFTWARE (FALSE VERSION) ⁷⁶ OF:

2. COMPUTER CIRCUIT BOARD CHIP ILLEGAL FIN-DISTRICT X4: OF CHIP CONSTRUCTION GANG 'B' (LAND THIEVES) BY FUNCTION: 'contruction' 'agriculture' 'transport' 'Communications' etc HK (e-HKD), China-LAND (e-CNY / synapse-China PP), UAE-LAND (e-AED / Synapse-Emirates) AND THAI-LAND (e-BHT / Synapse-Thai) (CHIP: CONTAINER b, CONTAINER BANK-OWNERS' AND USERS')

LEGAL EXHIBIT: EVIDENCE OF PERP

PLACING X 4 ILLEGAL DISTRICTS ON CIRCUIT BOARD (QUADRANT CHIP)

LEGAL ANALYSIS: NOTICE THE COVER PAGE - CIRCUIT BOARD: X4 ILLEGAL DISTRICTS

Careful observation, one will realise PERP-placed X4 illegal districts OR LANDMARKS (dispersed geographically): on a (QUADRANT-)CHIP.

The (COPIED) Trilateral Commission ('RECYCLE') LOGO is also = Dulce Base (Monk-) 'Tau' ('/Dao') Stars-Stepper Jinxed U.S.\$1 bill, assembles the ('RECYCLE') LOGO pasted on the 'PP Bank of China' (NOT the people of China).

CIRCUIT BOARD: PENTAGON WASHINGTON D.C.

t city | computer circuit board - A

CIRCUIT BOARD: NEW YORK CITY (PARTIAL EXPLANATION BEHIND: 9/11)

So based on the Quadrant (computer-tracked money data-)CHIP: PERPs were calculating how much they can ROB from x4 NATIONS⁷⁷ (SAMPLES), namely: (The Judgment document will examine AMT perp targets of WHITE GROUP): EUR-SWISS-NORDIC PLOT / USMCA PLOT.

⁷⁷ (The Judgment will examine AMT perp targets of WHITE GROUP): EUR-SWISS-NORDIC PLOT / USMCA PLOT.

SUPPOSE BOLLYWOOD SIMULATION B4 INVASION
NYC

USD STASH V RUPEE ESC (FRENCH 1-MC)

PPT 11 SATELLITE LOG-ON 9/11 NEW YORK CITY
CIRCUIT BOARD CHIPPED: COMPUTER DOLLAR

PPT 8 COMPUTER YUAN

PERP ID: e-HKD, e-CNY, e-BHT, e-AED

Project mBridge: Connecting economies through CBDC

So, computer PERP-Tom had been secretly tracking the (QUOTE) access-controlled central bank real-time gross settlement (RTGS) systems (inter-bank domestic payments) and exception (QUOTE) Continuous Linked Settlement (CLS) settles FX transaction. For example, the given private sector estimates (2020) \$23.5 trillion cross-border transactions flows and calculated transaction charges (perhaps % theft per transaction @ PoS) of 0.5% equals to \$120 billion (which explains the murderers 'Pay-'gang TYPES, wireless Wave chip bank cards OR terminal groceries % theft).

For explicit example, even PERP admits its identity here: according to WB data, PERP thieves calculated that merchandise exports: 18%, 46%, 93% and 159% of GDP in 2020 (Mainland China) (L-Top), Thailand (L-Bottom), UAE (R-Top) and Hong Kong SAR (R-Bottom). Loot AMT PERP is seeing: US\$8.7 trillion merchandise trade (2021) which constitutes 19% which gives criminal motive to rip-off this Full AMT or Partial % percentage theft @PoS. (If CO-VAX CHIPPED: cant ripped off brains, low iQ PERPs figure.)

So, PERPs [mental thieves n genocidal paxs] advocate **mBridge** to target: global trade (monies) flow join the platform for robbery and (CHIP Murder). mBridge explained details: in Section 11 BoE CHIP sample.

PILOT TEST SUBJECTS GLYPH & EMIRATES VERSION (PILOT TEST: NEW YORK VERSION)

The background is that PERP knows: for cross-border transactions, required are internet / wireless transmission / CO-VAX CHIP eventual PLOT radio frequency transmission, they tabulated the amount

based on a time-frame of six weeks, how much PERP can rob (Fully on their platform or Partial percentage) as follows:

TABLE 1: PILOT 6-WK TRANSACTION PERP-(EYEING TO ROB) STATS

Issuance	HK (e-HKD)	CHINA-LAND (e-CNY)	Saudi Arabia: UAE (e-AED)	THAI-LAND (e-THB)
US\$12.1 Million	\$8.5 Million (e-HKD)	11.8 Million (e-Yuan)	31 Million (e-AED)	32.1 Million (e-THD)
164 Cross-border Pay and FX PvP transactions				
US\$22.1 Million	\$13.2 Million (e-HKD)	23.6 Million (e-CNY)	60.1 Million (e-AED)	23.5 Million (e-THB)

PERP also realizes they can be electronic money changers (akin e.g. Indians singh trespassers in world cities: GLYPH nations 'Singapore-Phoenix' setting up money changer of currencies shop). This is another reason why pilot transaction of differing currencies statistics. So what PERPs' saying is: HK SAR and CHINA banks (illegal container of CHINA-LAND: Tier 2) were (Either: forced OR secretly tracked online) 'to participate' in Phase 1. UAE banks (Tier 2) only joined the pilot in Phase 2. Then Thai banks (Tier 2) joined starting in Phase 3.

PERPs were only concerned about explaining why they may have missed out robbing a lucrative e-AED and e-THB as they joined only in Phase 2 and Phase 3 thus reflected in the e-HKD and e-CNY transactions outnumbered (those of e-AED and e-THB). ALL such PLOTS: TERMINATED.

AMERICAN JUDGEMENT (SHORT): LEGAL AMERICA NATION EVIDENCE (TAX STATS)

Since PERP e-invasion attempt is evidence here: 1. PERP will attempt (in addition to percentage online theft) eventual conversion of all digital monies of Tier 2 and Tier 1. 2.

The legal approach: GLYPH GROUP @WLC might as well compute the total AMT of illegal containers of GLYPH nations' loot (of all industries / PER state district / PER nation) x time-frame, UPLOAD AMT on WWW for conversion back to paper cash first.

Also, land thieves ETERNAL LAND worth that cannot be counted, discussion @ WLC.

Report

The ATF (Americans For Tax Fairness) report⁷⁸ on (legally suspicious / international murder: genocidal) “Americans (computerized digits or theft) Billionaires Got 62% Richer During Pandemic”, listed above had reached \$18 Trillion (computerized digits) 62% e-‘richer’:

1. \$3 Trillion (CO-VID start: 18 March 2020) to
2. \$4.8 Trillion (17 August 2021) over 17 months for the duration of the pandemic
3. collective computerized digits increment by: 62%
4. computerized digits: \$1.8 Trillion e-‘richer’

AMERICANS FOR TAX FAIRNESS REPORT: PAY-GANG AND OTHERS INCREMENT DURATION CO-VAX CHIP CIRCUITRY [AMERICAN VERSION (PANDEMIC BIO-W VAX CHIP, NOTICE: FB-META-‘GLOBAL’ ‘INDIANS’ MURDER BUILDINGS 9/11 COLLAPSE DRAWINGS: THREAT TO ROB]

SUSPICIOUS LIST: ELECTRONIC PRESS: 000 = COMPUTE INTO TRI-SOLAR CITIZENS’ B ATM
ELON MUSK NEURAL ‘LACE’: GO SHOTS RF-KILL + COPY BIS ‘MINIMALLY INVASIVE’ BROCHURE
CONMAN

⁷⁸ (2021) American Billionaires Got 62% Richer During Pandemic – Almost All That Wealth Growth Will Go Income-Tax free, Showing Need For Biden’s Tax Reforms & Investment Plans. Available:

Billionaire	Net Worth Mar. 18, 2020 (\$ Billions)	Net Worth Aug. 17, 2021 (\$ Billions)	17 Month Wealth Growth (\$ Billions)	17 Month % Wealth Growth	Source
Jeff Bezos	\$113.0	\$188.0	\$75.0	66.4%	Amazon
Elon Musk	\$24.6	\$175.4	\$150.8	612.8%	Tesla, SpaceX
Bill Gates	\$98.0	\$130.6	\$32.6	33.3%	Microsoft
Mark Zuckerberg	\$54.7	\$128.9	\$74.2	135.7%	Facebook
Larry Page	\$50.9	\$117.4	\$66.5	130.6%	Google
Larry Ellison	\$59.0	\$117.3	\$58.3	98.9%	Oracle
Sergey Brin	\$49.1	\$113.4	\$64.3	131.0%	Google
Warren Buffett	\$67.5	\$105.0	\$37.5	55.6%	Berkshire Hathaway
Steve Ballmer	\$52.7	\$85.9	\$33.2	63.0%	Microsoft
Jim Walton	\$54.6	\$69.4	\$14.8	27.0%	Walmart
Alice Walton	\$54.4	\$68.4	\$14.0	25.8%	Walmart
Rob Walton	\$54.1	\$68.1	\$14.0	25.9%	Walmart
Phil Knight	\$29.5	\$61.6	\$32.1	108.9%	Nike
Michael Bloomberg	\$48.0	\$59.0	\$11.0	22.9%	Bloomberg LP
Mackenzie Scott	\$36.0	\$54.5	\$18.5	51.4%	Amazon
SUBTOTAL	\$846.1	\$1,543.0	\$696.9	82.4%	
ALL OTHERS	\$2,101.4	\$3,222.9	\$1,121.5	53.4%	
U.S. TOTAL	\$2,947.5	\$4,765.9	\$1,818.4	61.7%	

This report was focused on the (cruel profiteering off intentional murder: genocidal) the \$1.8 Trillion (e-)'richer' not taxable (unless they sell their assets).

I will elaborate to fill the gaps that this American report (missed out):

1. Electronic digits e-increment: could have been offered to parties to prevent taxable amount (illegal legislation: criminal signature / pattern identified)
2. It did not occur to Americans (part of the USMCA PLOT / SG-PHOENIX PLUS 3 PLOT) that electronic 'banks' (e.g. E-PAY-GANG / Retail: E-cashier / Transport: computerized store of value / % theft off largest F&B, groceries etc @ PoS by physical banks issued manufactured CHIP wireless 'wave' card / eventual PERP 'intent' 'act' of CO-VAX microchip as replacement wifi 'wave' card) i.e. that ALL electronic counters (e-cashiers: e.g. LED screen / computer digits PoS) are subject to: a. PRESS: 000,000,000 (unlimited no.) b. UP/DOWN etc.
3. This electronic e-cashier counter can include: physical banks linked 'casino'-like 'trading' numbers.

Most importantly, this e-PAY-Gang increment tallies with the Phase 1 Phase 2 duration pilot testing (in PERP context: CO-VAX microchip WB doc) of the X4 QUADRANT-CHIP on BIS doc: e-HKD, e-CNY, e-AED, e-THB.

8.0.4. TIER 2 PEDO- DRUGS-RING-b-HSBC: INFRA-CHIP-E-SHOCK (BRAIN EXPERIMENTATION E-SHOCK USA) TIER 2 PEDO-b-HSBC Legal Confirmation by 1. U.S. Military and US INTEL 2. Civilian Intel USA Ex-Military) LEGAL MATCH WITH: 1. IBM Synapse Axon Dendrites (CO-VAX GO SiOx) Neurosynaptic CORE, Meta-CHIP: Neuromorphic System / Neural Network / Neurogrid-POP100PLUS 2. IBM CHIP 'ARM-Y' DEPLOYABLE INFERENCE (LEGAL SECTION 11: TIER 1 CRIMINAL VARIANTS FAKED) 3. NASA CORONA DUNAR BIS COPIED

(HSBC = HONG KONG CONSITE: NO BLUEPRINT WHITE PERP)

1. U.S. Military and US INTEL

Joachim Hagopian, U.S. Army Officer and Robert David Steel ex-CIA spy / founder of Marine Corps Intelligence / Commissioner for the International Tribunal of International Justice, that is very familiar with blackmail, bribery, assorted perversions of the “elite to the basest rogues” controlled by the Deep State construct (FALSE) legalization of bestiality and pedophilia documented the rape of children as young as two to four years old abused by pedophiles kidnapped and sold into slavery, bred from birth from birth to sale for pedophilia and the connection with illegal container banks.

He also documented accounts of illegal experimentation programs of using children substituted for chimpanzees (also document by Fritz / Sherry Shriner of such in CA 51) and long-range space mission (as disposable children).

1. U.S. Military and US INTEL (Table 8.0.4a)

PEDO-HSBC-DRUGS-RING: INFRA-co-vax wb CHIP b TYPE 3 SPORTS CONSTRUCTION FREE-FLOW THEFT with TIER 2 'b' SEX TOURISM VICES 'BANKS'-IN

	Criminal Act	INTERNATIONAL LAW
NASA Kidnap (grown from stem cells + Medical Experimentation + 20 Y SSP) Pedo & Empire c.9 (Documentation: Hagopian J. ⁷⁹ / Verified: Robert David Steele Ex-Military, Ex-CIA)	Disposable children: SSP Bio-Electromagnetic frequency brain research (near death experimentation).	
TRAFFICK RING ('Network') Blood Marrow, Organ Harvest	Baby sodomizer / trafficker: China Lake Naval Weapons (1950s) near Death Valley	The Judgment: specific names.

⁷⁹ Hagopian J. () Pedo & Empire: Satan, Sodomy & The Deep State. Verified: Robert David Steele Ex-Military, Ex-CIA

<p>Pedo & Empire c.7, c. 12, (Documentation: Hagopian J. / Verified: Robert David Steele Ex-Military, Ex-CIA)</p> <p>UN 2016 Global Report on Trafficking: 106/193 nations Trafficked (1.8 Million X 10 Y = 13 Million)</p>	<p>California: babies thousands locked in cages deliver high voltage shocks + China Lake pedo-torture chamber</p> <p>Blood Marrow, Organ-bone Marrow Harvest</p> <p>Illicit Arms, Drugs pusher: Electro-shock</p> <p>1987 Traffick Child Sex Slaves (c. 12)</p>	
<p><u>ARMS TRAFFICK</u></p> <p>Super-Soldier Assassins</p> <p>Pedo & Empire c.6, c.11 (Documentation: Hagopian J. / Verified: Robert David Steele Ex-Military, Ex-CIA)</p>	<p>Suggested by document: Oswald and George Griggs government super soldier assassin. (I don't think so)</p>	<p><u>NEW (NASDAQ) SEC EXCHANGE LAW</u> Complete shut down: PRESS: 000</p> <p>Set-up Alternate: ALL INDUSTRIES into Citizens' b. (global monitor: 'take-out' e- b, trading-'casino'-b & offsprings)</p>
<p><u>O-lympic / 100PLUS Military DUPED X 60 Y ADB body bag</u></p> <p>Pedo & Empire c.17 (Documentation: Hagopian J. / Verified: Robert David Steele Ex-Military, Ex-CIA)</p>	<p>Sexual abuse / sexual assault / sex tourism Tier 2 card advert (suspicious)</p>	

2. Civilian Intel USA Ex-Military (Table 8.0.4b1: Programming, Chemicals, E-Shock)

	Programming	E-Shock
<p>NASA (Springmeier F. I-Formula c. 8)</p>	<p>Computer Example: ALEX, Amalgamated Logarithmic Encrypted Transmissions, UNIX systems</p>	<p>Brain stem (Reticular formation: electronically + scarring: drugs + E-shock torture + MPD = Photographic Memory claim)</p> <p>RNA piles up: to break continuity of signals = matches CO-VID mRNA</p>
	<p>Chemical Example:</p> <p>Enzyme i.e. Horseradish Peroxidase (HRP) 'marker' or 'highlighter' = PET scan</p> <p>Amino acid Identified Glutamate: Neurotransmitter (memory storage)</p>	
	<p>Drug Example: UpJohn (American co.): Liquid cortisome Depo-medrone</p>	

	<p>implant for radio-transmitting material.</p> <p>Histamines (molecule) used to defend against alien cells + lower blood pressure and flare-up skin thus immune system.</p> <p>Bone marrow produce → stem cells → grow into different types of cells:</p> <p>Myeloid → Polymorpho nuclear granulocyte → basophil or mast cells = leukocytes (carriers of histamine)</p>	<p><u>Abusers: 'magically' make (i.e. trigger command) invisible scars appear (patterns / pictures) + disappear</u></p>
	<p>Histamine: dilation blood vessels = permeable (leaky = allow chemicals / fluid enter blood vessels into area between cells & tissues)</p> <p>Change ratio of stem cells → To increase Histamine → increase basophils + mast cell</p> <p><u>Ethylamine</u> core of the histamine molecule</p> <p><u>Anti-histamines</u> molecules that resemble histamines → attach themselves to the histamine receptors → prevent the histamine molecules from attaching (when histamine molecules don't attach) → body disposes of them</p>	<p><u>IBM: Leaky Integrate Fire</u></p>
	<p><u>Theory:</u> breast implants → agitate into higher immune cells' production (plausible: mast cell & basophils) raising histamine production levels (histamine-carrying cells)</p>	<p>I.G. Farben, DuPont, and Dow Chemical: Silicon Implant (1956 x 35 Y) for Silicon leak through membrane</p>
	<p><u>Re-write Genetics</u> Stressed Brain → Convert nerve signals into "messenger molecules" → direct endocrine system → product steroid hormones → reach nucleus of cells → cause nucleus to</p>	<p>Dr. S.M. Lambert of the Rockefeller Foundation studied how voodoo could cause death by creating certain thoughts in the mind.</p>

	change way body's genes written out (e.g. immune system)	
	<p><u>Immuno-transmitters</u> Hypothalamus bridges (part of the Limbic-hypothalamic system)</p> <p>The immune system communicates directly with the hypothalamus part of the brain with its own "messenger molecules" known as "immune-transmitters" i.e. mind-brain link.</p>	
	<p><u>Hippocampus</u> Hippocampus stores memory in the cortex to be encoded into long term memory (holographically)</p> <p><u>Re-Wiring</u> Neurons (nerve cells: brain 10 billion) meet each other at junctions (gaps) called synapses.</p> <p>At the synapses (gaps), neurotransmitters allow them to communicate.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. As a person gathers information, the brain changes the synapses, in a sense rewires itself. 2. Part of memory is how the brain "rewires" itself. 	<p>There are 60 trillion synapses.</p> <p>IBM Synapse Axon Dendrites (CO-VAX GO SiOx) Neurosynaptic CORE, Meta-CHIP: Neuromorphic System / Neural Network / Neurogrid POP-100PLUS</p> <p>As the mind consolidates info, it fires neurons in harmony (in phase) called a "binding" process.</p>

2. Civilian Intel USA Ex-Military (Table 8.0.4b2: Programming, Chemicals, E-Shock)

	Programming	E-Shock
(Springmeier F. I-Formula c. 6)	<p><u>Microwave Tower</u></p> <p>(False) 'Military' research to control the brain via microwaves.</p> <p>Walter Reed Army Institute of Research (WRAIR) (Patent no. 4,858,612: ELF microwave tech)</p>	<p>'Global' Strategy Council paper entitled, "Nonlethality: Development of a National Policy and Employing Nonlethal Means in a New Strategic Era" (Janet Morris, 1991)</p> <p>USAF School of Aerospace 'Medicine', Brooks Air Force Base, TX report USAFAM-TR-87-30 entitled: "Behavioral</p>

	<p>Pulsed microwave audiograms also called analogs of the sounds of spoken words, could be transmitted to a target: IBM Pulse PCM (Phase Change Memory-CHIP)</p> <p>(Questionable) Texas Dept. of Criminal Justice TDCJ-ID: Implants (high-tech listening)</p>	<p>response of rats exposed to high-power microwave radiation</p> <p>Report USAFAM-TR-83-3 entitled: "Retrograde Amnesia in Rats Produced by Electron Beam Exposure" (T. Wheeler, et. al., Feb. '83)</p> <p>Report "Classical conditioning of Microwave-Induced Hyperthermia in Rats." Radio Sci. 14 (6S): 201-207, 1979 (R. Bermant)</p>
	<p><u>Electricity: E-Shock</u></p>	<p>Electric Shock Prod Marks 1981 (e.g. staff, stun guns 120,000 DC Volt – 200,000 DC Volt)</p> <p>Manufacturer: Farrall Instrument Co. (Grand Island) adjustable voltage CTRL box + Distance wireless shocker called Personal Shocker</p> <p>Electronic firm Tujung, CA: shock box</p> <p>Larger Electroshock Machines + Computer Guided:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Conmed (315-797-8375) ('CON-MED = BIO-W') Electrodes: Portable Monitoring. 2. Sentry 'Medical' Products: Skin Mounted Conductive 'Medical' Electrodes for Tense Unit Machines. Address 17171 Murphy, Irvine, CA 92714 (714-250-0233) 3. Vivo Metric: Silver Chloride Electrodes placement on human skin. Address Healdsburg, CA. 4. Electro-Cap Inter: produces BEG placement systems. 5. Uni-Patch 'Medical' Products: All kinds of Electrodes with some into machines for shocking people. Address 13 13-T Grant Blvd. W, Wabasha, MN. 6. Classic Medical Products: Make electrodes for 'diagnostic' Address 582-T W 19246 Apollo Dr. Muskego, WI (Note. CDC patented profitable process: 'diagnostic') and shock purposes. 7. Arndt Automation & Assoc., Inc.: Make electrodes for ECG and

		EKG machines. Address 17770 Liberty Lane, New Berlin, WI. 8. 'Biomedical': CO makes 'medical' electrodes. Address: at Evergreen, Colorado.
	<u>Directed Energy: Electricity (E-Shock) Torture</u> Men's genitals: ELF waves simulate rape	Artificial sodomy via directed energy was first tested in male prisons.
	<u>Crime site: Impromptu Programming Site</u> Hypnotic Drug injected (CO-VAX CHIP IBM Neurogrid 100PLUS Military duped X 60 Y): Quick Induction	Metal band: 100,000 volts 5 sec Day Care Centres: Neuroelectric Research: Electro-Neuroprosthesis, Electroanesthesia, and Nonconvulsive Electro-'therapy' (David V. Reynold) (Note. CDC patented profitable process 'therapeutic')
	<u>Tracking ID Implants</u> Space Biology Lab/Brain Research Institute of the UCLA Center for Health Sciences, Address: Los Angeles, California 90024: "An eight channel micropowered PAM/FM biomedical telemetry system" Electronically report on person's body and the person monitoring.	"Biotelemeter" consists of a signal conditioner(s), multiplexer (for multichannel systems), and a transmitter. IBM Multiplexer CHIP.
	<u>Tracking ID Implants</u> Frequency shift signals of brain implants modulation: Modulating through a given spectrum of frequencies. EDOM -- Electronic Dissolution of Memory EEOM--Electronic Enhancement of Memory ESB --Electronic Stimulation of the brain RHIC -- Radio Hypnotic Intra-cerebral	Frequency shift modulation: IBM CHIP
	<u>Tracking ID Implants</u> Control Terms: 'Controller' Data Protection Law	

	<p>PREMA: Personal Radio & Electro-Magnetic Frequency Allocation. This is an individual's personal frequency which is scanned by a hand-held device.</p> <p>VITAL HUMAN BRAIN FREQUENCY: This is a frequency vital for humans, (the 800 MHz band) manipulated for mass mind-control.</p>	<p>VISA: Graph ID Cities (Scam)</p>
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TYPE 3 PEDO-HSBC-DRUGS-RING: INFRA-CHIP b SPORTS CONSTRUCTION FREE-FLOW THEFT with TIER 2 'b' SEX TOURISM VICES 'BANKS'-IN

3. Canadian Judge: 'Pedo-Criminal Abuse': Pedo-World Legal Confirmation

1977 CARTER WHITE HOUSE EXTRATERRESTRIAL STUDY

- "The 1977 Carter White House ET Study, had it not been terminated by the Pentagon & Men in Black (MIBs), may have led to the treaty abrogation of the Greeda Secret Treaties by US President Jimmy Carter.
- "US President Dwight D. Eisenhower originally signed these treaties with the Draco reptilians, Orion greys and Anunnaki Reptilians in 1954. These ETs abused the treaties into a planetary & Galactic pedocriminal trade of millions of human children and adults annually for ritual sacrifice, loosh, cannibalism, body parts, all enforced by the US government, and pedocriminal institutional NWO worldwide. Because the Pentagon unlawfully terminated the 1977 Carter White House Extraterrestrial Study, US President George HW Bush signed the Tau9 Treaty with the Draco, Orion Greys & Anunnaki and the pedocriminal abuses on Earth have become exponentially worse."
- Alfred Lambremont Webre, director 1977 Carter White House Extraterrestrial Study

Image: Judge Alfred Lambremont Webre, KL War Crimes Tribunal "Bush, Blair found guilty of war crimes in Malaysia tribunal" Mahi Ramakrishnan, Press TV, Kuala Lumpur, Tue Nov 22, 2011 6:51PM GMT

JUDGE, excellent materials, dedicated. He didn't know about 'SINGA' LIE. Fabricated altered GLYPH text: altered states AUTHENTIC ORIGINAL. SE (RF-CHIP-kill). STACKING-'OC' CEMENT-RUPEE repeat WAR ID UP 500Y. SATELLITE-TOMS: EM LOGO & H.E. ORGAN, pre-med BEYOND.

[MISSION UPLOADS @WLC \(PERP-PEDO-'e-b' IMPLANTS MAPPING ANALYSIS\)](#)

INSERT: IBM / WB / INFRA-CHIP MAP ANALYSIS - PEDO-RING-HSBC OLYMPICS VILLAGE
IBM CHINA INFO. CENTER: 8 BEICHEN E RD, ASIAN GAMES VILLAGE, CHAOYANG, BEIJING

MAP ANALYSIS: SEE: IBM, WB, (INFRA-B) FORCED CONSTRUCTION DEBT: STADIUM CONTRACT DEBT SPORTS EXCUSE: 'OLYMPICS (SEX TOURISM HSBC-CARD OFF EUR: BAN)

ANY CONNECTION BETWEEN:

1. ION-(IZED MEMBRANE POTENTIALS SUGGESTIVE TO BLATANT (MALL ARCHITECTURE, IBM CHIP)
2. USING MOSFET INJECTIONS BIO-W 2 CO-VAX) MALLS IN ORCHARD RD SINGAPORE (WITH NEW ORCHARD RD NEW YORK
3. AND USING NAME OF HONG KONG STAR BUYER JACKIE CHAN PURCHASE OF UNIT NEAR ION-(NIZED MEMBRANE POTENTIALS DISTRICT, ORCHARD RD SINGAPORE)
4. AND WHO CONNECTION WITH HONG KONG MARGARET CHAN AND CDC PATENTED PROFITABLE 'PANDEMIC' LAB-MADE BIO-W 1 CO-VID

'THE WORLD BANK' 'RE-CONSTRUCTION' 'INFRA-CHIP' 'DEVELOPMENT' (THEFT OF NATIONS' CONCEPT:

The land thieves: self-titled WB (perp defined geographic location of theft likely satellite theft / murder) / 'Construction'-B synonymous with 'Development'-B (function) / 'infra-CHIP'-B (function) etc.

Construction B land thieves are low IQ PERP that engage foreign (e.g. Indian) construction workers to dig soil i.e. theft of ETERNAL (worth billions in years and uncountable) land (that belong to generational

offsprings) thus with murder status equivalent war crime land thieves self-titled B (B = short for banks-in are criminals that rob land as landless) with severely disabled 'beyond' for example, Singapore-phoenix.

Another example, illegal slogan of 'wall-in' trap by Trump and LKY (pap are illegal persons since 1965 PLOT for land thieves B-in). The constructed US border walls were abandoned halfway. Also, Trump was arrested.

LAND THIEVES MATRIX (PERP-b-TOM & offsprings): MISSION DETONATE @ WLC TELCOM PPT INTRO 'TAKE-OUT'

LAND THIEVES SELF-TITLED B ILLEGAL Container of Nations' Loot	GEOGRAPHIC (THEFT / MURDER)	FUNCTION(AL THEFT AS LAND THIEVES)	EVENTS (EXCUSE AS LURE: OFFICIALS 1-SHOT 100PLUS LOOT INTENT / MURDER)	THIEVES
USMCA PLOT EUR-SWISS-NORDIC PLOT	World (World Land: 100PLUS Neurogrid) WB	Construction B 'Development' B 'Infra-' B	'OLYMPICS' BIDDING CONTRACTUAL THEFT SCAM 'WINNING' BID SIGN A COMPULSORY CONTRACT TO BIND THE VICTIMIZED NATION IN DEBT multiplied by X NO. OF YEARS I.E. 'INDEBTED' W/O CITIZENS CONSENT ROB FROM CITIZENS)	IBM Address: 'Olympics Village' Beijing
SG-PHOENIX PLUS 3 PLOT	Asia (GLYPH GROUP: Proof bombed with body bag U.S. soldiers stuffed with heroin) ADB	'Agricultural' B	Wuhan military 100PLUS 'sports' excuse: synapse-100PLUS invasion murder / loot	WB (cost of excellent cheap stone + set of computers): Singapore Marina Bay Sands

RE-CAP: ('b' pedo-b e-b infra-b Types 1-6 ADB WB All 'b' Tier 1 BIS chipped)

All Self-Titled B- short for 'B-anks' are PERP because their existence itself is criminal (i.e. war crime thus with murder status equivalent).

The only key reason is because: 'B' self-title their way to becoming illegal containers of nations' (100PLUS nations) loot AND land thieves (i.e. war crime i.e. murder status equivalent). Thus, there is no such thing as 'money' 'authority' i.e. conman as lord over monies. He lies (to rob nations' money / arrest warrant

waiting). If (whichever land thieves monies thieves) uses CON-word 'mas-(_fill-in blanks themselves as excuse):

Just cite this: ...

They operate full-time (then shorten operating hours since 9/11 targeting illegal district: containers of nations' loot) as thieves waiting for nations' (labour: hard-earned toil, easy, difficult savings, life savings depend on for survival etc) monies, inheritance, business accounts to enter random PERP-Tom Dick Harry containers (OR own pockets). Their operations are illegal:

1. land thieves (i.e. war crime = murder status equivalent) Land is worth ETERNAL (billions of years etc offsprings' inheritance, cannot count the value of Land thus, murder status attached and is war crime)
2. container of entire nations' monies /
3. business a/c turned 'casinos' erroneously called 'trading' /
4. inheritance monies etc.

	'B' Self-title: Illegal containers of nations' (100PLUS nations') Loot & Land Thieves
	1. Land Thieves: i.e. war crime = murder status equivalent, LAND is worth ETERNAL, can't count the value of Land
	2. Container of Entire nations' monies
	3. Business a/c turned 'casinos' erroneously called 'trading'
	4. Inheritance monies etc
	No such thing as 'money' 'authority' i.e. conman / lies to rob nations' money / arrest warrant any random-PERP.
	No such thing as 'land' (transport log-on electricity loot) 'authority' = computer ETERNAL Land robbed AMT UPLOAD: WWW per nation + pre-med + 'B'-ID @ WLC Mission UPLOAD: citizens justice military shareholders of all industries + global monitor of GLYPH monies

Another example, 'Olympics' bidding contractual theft scam 'winning' bid to sign a compulsory contract to bind the victimized nation in debt (UPLOAD AMT @WLC) multiplied by no. of years i.e. indebtedness. See: same Olympics committee illegal persons @Wuhan 100PLUS military 'sports' excuse post-plandemic (lab-made in Wuhan).

For example, Singapore-Phoenix (billion years bloodline) is a land-robbed nation (with land-less descendants and military genocided by PERP intent: kill-off post-loot add RACE). PERP owe land: so computer Singapore is already illegal since 1965: all have land ETERNAL per SLOT / live on land / are

land-owners with properties. This means someone's been intentionally traffick-in to populate for fast cash from stacking 'shoeboxes' (unlawful housing) for fast-cash from stacking etc x (multiplied by) various schemes scams devices x no. y. So, PERP has converted eternal land to 'the now' thus PERP has stolen in 'the now'. Due to repeat criminal signatures openly expressed by self-title WB / ADB / 'Infra-excuse'-B TYPES (land thieves lab made bio-w children experimental, computer currency rob etc) confirmed all-B PERP, that is why I advocate some adjustment of currencies value returned to land robbed GLYPH (@ WLC GLYPH meet to discuss) as the superior method, manage (global monitor and alert) monies and (guarded) land slot (e.g. inheritance / allocated) PER China Japan Korean (dragon GLYPH GROUP. GLYPH blood targeted by PERP same as Singapore-Phoenix intermarriage mix Dragon robbed: GLYPH GROUP) @ WLC PERP-ID exit or eradication

1. Anti-land thieves (e.g. self-titled B) system global alert: military take-out missions UPLOAD against intruders
2. Citizens (includes military): as shareholders of all industries (e.g. ports against infiltration random-tom dick harry) new banks (simple booklet with New ATM Singapore-phoenix)
3. Military INTEL (World Evidence Contributors against PERP-ID): sign-up @ WLC Doctors of Laws program with thesis submission (quick programs on laws, world intelligence: correct version)
4. Singapore-Phoenix (superior than MAC PRO) LAPTOP (due to insufficient battery, it is time for the side tracked Phoenix born) (anti-thieves) tablet cellphones called LOCUST / SCORPION (to load GOD's GLYPH bible text) for GLYPH military and banking purposes: and (superior than LG LED - my favourite) LED production running on free electricity for Singapore-Phoenix (PERP found a way to charge monies for free thunder using circuitry meter: coins for transport around the island).
5. With telcom products PPT introduction if interested in joining the fight against PERP-ID @WLC Singapore-Phoenix ALL GLYPH nations meet and @WLC Americas (WB / ADB / Infra-free flow-B / All B-types land thieves containers etc ID-PERP vote).
6. Compute loot amt (self-titled 'gov' as PERP building of containers of loot e.g. various schemes scams, severely disabled insurance (BIO-W CO-VAX CHIP) theft by computer force at national level / loot PER district / PER con-'B'-site: online spawn unlimited (and 'free-flow' (void) bill by self-titled PERP) and physical location site cost of stone self-titled B conmen etc) x no. y (specific period esp. crucial point e.g. land thieves robbed island-wide).

LEGAL EXHIBIT: NEUROMORPHIC SYSTEM / NEURAL NETWORK / NEURAL CIRCUIT (e.g. G30 mRNA: X 60 Y 'b' pedo-'b' 'e-b' ALL 'b' Tier 1)

IBM ('GREAT' BRITAIN): 'CHINA' 'INVESTMENT' CO. PEDO-Neuro drugs circuitry CHIP E-shock (MAPPING ANALYSIS)

'NEURAL (LINKED) NET'

'NEURAL CORE (CO-VAX) CIRCUITRY'

(10) International Publication Number
WO 2014/080300 A1

PCT

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(74) Agent: **LITHERLAND, David**; IBM United Kingdom Limited, Intellectual Property Law, Hursley Park, Winchester Hampshire SO21 2JN (GB).

(54) Title: NEURAL NETWORK

FIG. 2

(19) World Intellectual Property Organization
International Bureau

(10) International Publication Number
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(43) International Publication Date
20 March 2014 (20.03.2014)

WIPO | PCT

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650 Harry Road, Almaden Research Center, San Jose, CA 95120-6099 (US). **CASSIDY, Andrew, Stephen**; IBM Corporation, 650 Harry Road, Almaden Research Center, San Jose, CA 95120-6099 (US).

(74) Agent: **LITHERLAND, David**; IBM United Kingdom Limited, Intellectual Property Law, Hursley Park, Winchester Hampshire SO21 2JN (GB).

(81) Designated States (unless otherwise indicated, for every kind of national protection available): AI, AG, AL, AM, AO, AT, AU, AZ, BA, BB, BG, BH, BN, BR, BW, BY, BZ, CA, CH, CL, CN, CO, CR, CU, CZ, DE, DK, DM, DO, DZ, EC, EE, EG, ES, FI, GB, GD, GE, GH, GM, GT, HN, HR, HU, ID, IL, IN, IS, JP, KE, KG, KN, KP, KR, KZ, LA, LC, LK, LR, LS, LT, LU, LY, MA, MD, ME, MG, MK, MN, MW, MX, MY, MZ, NA, NG, NI, NO, NZ, OM, PA, PE, PG, PH, PL, PT, QA, RO, RS, RU, RW, SC, SD, SE, SG, SK, SL, SM, ST, SV, SY, TH, TJ, TM, TN, TR, TT, TZ, UA, UG, US, UZ, VC, VN, ZA, ZM, ZW.

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Published: with international search report (Art. 21(3))

(54) Title: NEURAL CORE CIRCUIT

FIG. 2

The word 'china' 'investment' just means (in PERP terms): to invade china (NOT investment) or invade (IBM CHIP Murder) the people of china (GLYPH GROUP). Furthermore, its replicated i.e. ancient CHINA replica technology copied (logo paste on murderous land thieves banks-in).

(e-(PAY-)-b)

'PAY'-GANG (JUDGE LYNETTE) / 'XYZ-PAY' (JAPAN BANK GOVERNOR) PPT 7 COMPUTER YEN PPT 8 COMPUTER YUAN (PAY-GANG) RUSHING TO MURDER GLYPH GROUP: E-PAY (e-b)
INSERT PHOTO PERP-ID: ALI-PAY WITH PAY-PAL / FED-PAY FED-WIRE
(WB CO-VAX E-KILL USMCA PLOT, ADB BODY BAG E-GLYPH PLUS 3 PLOT: 'B' LAND THIEVES)

Money Collection	PAY-FORMAT OUT CHANGE TO divide PER PHOENIX, glyph: Theft e.g. CEMENT-x 60 FRAUD	Transport War Facility Systematic Elimination SE, CEMENT-recruit size etc
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COMPUTE x-y-z-PAY	REPLICATED PAY-	COMPUTE WB-CHIP-genocide WT-ports-Disconnect- PERP-ID
State: x, y, z ... x time-frame	REPLICATED PAY x no. states names PASTE	Satellite-TOM Telcom-TOM
Money Collection: Military comp sci Circular + Retrieve Assets etc. Licensed.	PAY-FORMAT OUT PER PHOENIX, glyph: Theft e.g. CEMENT-x 60 FRAUD	Transport War Facility Systematic Elimination SE, CEMENT-recruit size etc

Pay-pal (Pay-now) (Space X of Elon Musk Propagator of Neural 'Lace'). Also, title of conference: (PERP-psycho-genocidal) can mean CO-VAX CHIP controlled brain functions thus becoming robotic AI (in-brain) with binary codes programmed into space-satellite from base station 'controller' 'processor' computers.

This criminal reason why these PERP-ID are linked to WB (CIA-Obama-)ADB body bag: WB doc stated clearly 'CO-VAX'-financing' (Either: funds roll-out to CHIP-genocide / scan micro-barcode in-brain @ shop outlets using (software: S/W programmable) APP on E-cashier touch button LED:

INSERT PHOTO PERP-ID: ALIPAY (JACK MA) INVADE THE PEOPLE OF CHINA / 'FAST-PAY' ZUCKERBERG WITH META-INDIAN DENOTE DRAWING – PEDO-RING CONNECTION

OLD What if 'Ali' in 'Ali-pay' is Malaysian as in Fabricated altered-'Malay' (sub-replacement for mumtha: NEW plausible cross-over sharing of inventor Ali-rezar Mahanfar short-form) with record of self-titled 'B' n 'gov' (1965 PLOT) land thieves of Malaysian-'Singa'-pore-(Phoenix LAND-PHOENIX DOLLAR)? COMPLETELY HYPOTHETICAL: Using Huawei land scan by 1-Malaysian inside California. NEW reveals SATELLITE-TOM ID: _ (Likelihood) agency 'military'-wrong label / Illegal-indians -RUPEE CEMENT WAR ID x 60 + 2023 COPY NANO GO SHOTS experimental Large conglomerate of illegal-indians: EXPLAINED in separate Judgment paper briefing. Matches pre-med x 60 EM LOGO MILITARY illegal summon by sri-lanka ANTI-RAJAH + H.E. ORGAN damage: 'drawing'.

EEG-'invade' the People of China Ali-Pay products in Computer Yuan Model (Section 8). Furthermore, FIN-(GER-)TECH FEST of TIER 2 'B' includes: (ANT GROUP short for Antenna of Microsoft Bill Gates' FIN-TECH FEST SWITCH X). ANT is involved in Elevandi thus involving Swiss (Maurer Ueli seen with Pope).

RE-CAP:

NEURAL 'LACE' CO-VAX CHIP (SCAM ONLINE MEDICAL JOURNAL)

The Pay-Gang likely made a replication of the same APP format programming using Java and Node.

FIG. 6A. Cortical surface thread implantation with visible bleeding. Elon Musk's "System B" packaged sensor device chronically implanted in rat (NEURAL 'LACE' CO-VAX CHIP POP-100+) likely the 'False Version'.

The criminal intent: 5/6G Neural Linked (remotely programmable (1) micro-bots circuitry chip i.e. neurogrid under International (Binary) Space and Criminal Law: (2) drugged cells mutation payload release under Pharma Law) thus international murder 5/6G test sites predator (Criminally Accurate Version)

Thus, a robot sewing threads in-brain depiction ABOVE with visible bleeding is likely the FALSE version since all that is required for microchipping includes: Graphene Oxide / Silicon Oxide / Radio Frequency WiFi (short for Wireless FIN-ance) and Wireless NFC (hence the term 'Fed-Wire').

LEGAL EXHIBIT: 4. PERP EVEN PUT DIGITAL POINTS/NODES ON GLOBAL MAP ('INTENT': WB / DB -TYPE LAND THIEVES)

Participating commercial banks in the pilot

Graph 5

According to Legal Exhibit: ABOVE, it is seen clearly that PERP even placed digital points (for nodes in-brain CO-VAX CHIP / OR cellphone digital robbery / OR satellite land scam digital robbery): This matches the digital points that appear in, for example, invaded national library (SINGH the construction loot: yin yang manufactured chip card theft): (The functional crime that 'b' self-titled: is laid out clearly, so, PERP-ID which PERP-Tom pockets from robbing CHINA-LAND.)

INSERT PHOTO: DIGITS POINTS 'ATTEMPT' NATIONAL LIBRARY

INSERT PHOTO: SINGH CONSTRUCTION LOOT 'YIN YANG' MANUFACTURED CHIP CARD THEFT

The illegal indians since inception: set-up 'party' asked for money, stacking on death penalty (rob money) and targeted the ATM-tom (that opened the library) or complicit pending investigation.

LEGAL ANALYSIS:

THE GREAT ROBBERY CONSTRUCTION: LAND LEFT OLD AND UNTOUCHED (FAST-CASH STUPID CRIMINALS)

Participating commercial banks in the pilot

Graph 5

UAE	CN	HK	TH
ICBC 中国工商银行 中国銀行 BANK OF CHINA HSBC FAB FIRST ABU DHABI BANK standard chartered	ICBC 中国工商银行 中国銀行 BANK OF CHINA 交通銀行 BANK OF COMMUNICATIONS 中国农业銀行 AGRICULTURAL BANK OF CHINA 中国建设银行 China Construction Bank	ICBC 工銀亞洲 中国銀行(香港) BANK OF CHINA (HONG KONG) 交通銀行 BANK OF COMMUNICATIONS HSBC standard chartered	Bangkok Bank ธนาคารกรุงเก่า ธนาคารกสิกรไทย KASIKORN BANK HSBC SCB krungsri กรุงศรี A member of CMBPS, a global financial group

INTERNATIONAL CRIMINAL LAW: WAR CRIME (NOT WAR IS MURDER STATUS)

It is clear from the diagram also, the pre-meditated crime by (1) group of illegal container 'construction' 'land'-robbery-TYPE banks against the People of China [taken from the BIS 'global' Indian that duped 100+ nations (illegal container) banks with infra-chip as 'global' tech chair with vague to no tech details]

which is just 1 example out of 100+ nations embedded illegal container banks, duped by the same BIS

in conjunction with completely genocidal 'W' 'B' (implants in Singapore, Beijing, Washington D.C.):

INDIA-LAND PEOPLE AS RECRUITS

obvious plot typically utilizing 'global' Indians is divided into functions:

construction workers (Tamil / Bangladesh perhaps some coincidental connection to Dr. Peter Deszak's ½ million multiple times for virus grant and New York Court case: Intercept suspicious 'over-spending' by Singapore party member as a money siphoning 'excuse' with excessive amount briefly mentioned in the New York Courthouse / Sri Lanka: Rajaratnam @ IISS duped nations x > 10 Y include singh (RACE) as DEF-CARD (illegitimate), LSBF traffick out USMCA PLOT nations / Eroude / Bangalore / New Delhi) as infiltration perpetrators' recruits for illegal purposes (construction for low intelligence level lacking wisdom or sense-TYPE perp fast cash:

1. stacking housing (itself is illegal) at over-priced exorbitant rate unfit for human consumption /
2. cell tower CO-VAX circuitry murder in-brain billing / electricity meter charging circuitry loot / fridge billing etc).
3. land thieves: murder status equivalent.

World Land, China Land (is World Land) and Phoenix-Land (Singapore) is worth eternal and have to be left old and untouched.

At this point, 'W' 'B' by self-title: designated location to rob / murder is 'world' (which matches the digital nodes / points on BIS con doc), it is important that targeted: USMCA PLOT LAND / CHINA-LAND with precedent stacking SG HK NY Tokyo Japan [tiny square inch allocated] completely illegal (ban worldwide), should come-up with LAND-safe proof system to be guard a CHINA-LAND slot (piece of land) v illegal containers banks' to enrich the PERP's pockets (for 'fash cash').

Also, thunder lightning electricity is free (as PERP found a way to charge using meter circuitry) meaning PERP will be stealing electricity (as replacement for oil) to rob transport.

Also, electricity / electronics (transaction) cannot be substituted for 'money' itself because PERP has already shown signs of robbing @ PoS and @ Trade with foreign exchange a percentage (eventual increment / full) off per transactions e.g. ride-off largest F&B, pilot test NY / Quadrant GLYPH mix UAE etc.
5 EVIDENCE OF (BIS) NEUROMORPHIC SYSTEM OF THE (CRIMINALLY ACCURATE VERSION):
NEURAL SYNAPSE 'RESET' PHASE 1,2 ARRAY (BEAM-FORMING)

NEUROMORPHIC SYSTEM (FALSE VERSION):

The keyword 'reset' gives conclusive legal confirmation of IBM-INTEL-TYPE Neural CORE micro-'circuitry' / Neuromorphic CHIP / Neurogrid of SYNAPSE-POP-100+ with gating variables remotely accessible by programmable software and 'global' time-step.

LEGAL EXHIBIT: NEURAL SYNAPSE 'RESET' PHASE 1, 2 ARRAY (BEAM-FORMING)
(CRIMINALLY ACCURATE VERSION)

SG-PHOENIX CO-VAX GENOCIDED MILITARY DUPED INJECTED PLUS 3 PLOT: THE PEOPLE OF CHINA-LAND / SINGAPORE-PHOENIX-LAND / JAPANESE EXPRESSLY PREFERRED CASH (ELECTRONIC NOT LEGAL TENDER)

Pilot timeline

Graph 6

LEGAL EXHIBIT: CO-VAX CHIP TIME-FRAME with 'PHASE' 'MULTI-PHASE' 'PROGRAMMATIC'
(WB DOC) COMPUTE

mBridge journey

Graph 1

8.1.3. COMPUTER MONEY YUAN MODEL: PEOPLE'S BANK OF CHINA (NOT CHINA) (FALSE VERSION / SYNAPSE-YUAN CRIMINALLY ACCURATE)

International Computer YUAN Model: PP BANK OF CHINA (NOT CHINA) (Criminal Technical Analysis)

RADIO FREQUENCY ID PRODUCT

[UNDER DATA PROTECTION LAW \('BODILY' CELLS: FUNCTION\)](#)

[INTERNATIONAL CRIMINAL LAW: CIRCUITRY GENOCIDE](#)

UTXO

8.1.3A (COMPUTER) **PP BANK OF CHINA PATENTS:** (NOT CHINA-GENOCIDED): Transaction Method and Device Based on Block Chain UTXO Model 高阳

In order to free 1. the duped 100PLUS Tier 1 Tier 2 (by BIS 'global' Indians with vague or no technical details as BIS 'global tech chair' AND falsely using the word 'Singapore' (NOT SINGAPORE) 2. The duped 'People's Bank of China' (NOT China) such as Fan, Mu and Yi Gang and 3. the plot to dupe or duped people of china (state-by-state aborted in the propagation of Synapse-Yuan), I selected three pieces for this academic work.

In the 'PP Bank of China' (NOT China-GLYPH people genocided) paper, "Transaction Method and Device Based on Block Chain UTXO Model", I simplify the criminal operational steps as follows:

UTXO

This invention with the application Filed by the People's Bank of China (NOT the People of China) Digital Cash (NOT money) Research Institute, "Transaction Method and Device" based on blockchain UTXO⁸⁰ model comprises of the computerized steps:

1. Creating a **transaction public address** of a UTXO model (Main chain of a blockchain) wherein **transaction public address** is used for **storing** UTXO transferred by a user
2. **Receiving** a UTXO **transaction request** sent by a user: used for performing transaction operation on the UTXO stored (in **transaction public address**)
4. Carry out **transaction accounting** through **accounting nodes** of the blockchain to carry out transaction operation.

⁸⁰ 姚前, 狄刚, 钱友才, 黄烈明, 陈海波, 赵新宇, 王继伟, 张大伟 (2017) Transaction Method and Device Based on Digital Currency. (Application Filed by the People's Bank of China (NOT the People of China) Digital Cash Research Institute. United States Patent Office. Patent No. CN107358424B. Available:

TRANSACTION OPERATION

The **transaction operation** refers to: (1) Main chain amount transfer-in/out, (2) **Transaction request** includes: **UTXO number** transferred to **transaction public address** (3) user **identifier** (4) **Transaction locking script** which is used to **lock** transaction operation (on transferred UTXO) and includes **unlocking condition**.

TRANSACTION OPERATION: Accounting Node of Blockchain

MAIN-CHAIN AMT ROLL-OUT AMT, USER ADDRESS, USER SIGNATURE

The transaction accounting node of blockchain comprises of: 1. **verifying UTXO number** and **user identification ID** (on a/c accounting node of a blockchain side chain), 2. **updating** amount of money transferred to the **transaction public address** by user (in a/c book after **UTXO number** and **user identification ID** verified i.e. verification passed), (1) **verifying** the **transfer amount**, receiver identifier and **user signature** through accounting node of a blockchain side chain, (2) returning **accounting node signature** to the user after verification passed so that **user generates** a **combined signature** when a **transaction unlocking condition** is met (*according to accounting node signature*) and (3) **sending combined signature and transfer amount to a receiving party** (4) updates account book record after receiving combined signature broadcasted by user.

UPDATE LEDGER RECORD

After updating the ledger record, the method include: (1) Selecting UTXO to be transferred from **transaction public address**, (2) signing the UTXO to be transferred (3) sending the UTXO to a user, so that user constructs a transaction **unlock script** according to **signature** of accounting node and performs money transfer transaction with main chain.

According to the Digital Cash (NOT money) Research Institute, the 'Fast-Pay' cross-border payment project Libra is led by Facebook Co. meant for distributed (computer) accounting. It claims 'efficient' 'Fast' referring to transaction processing per second (TPS) reaching 80,000 which exceeds traditional settlement system e.g. Visa or Mastercard.

However, the problem with 'Fast-Pay' is (according to: People's Bank of China (NOT the People of China) Digital Cash (NOT Money) Research Institute) based on 1. the '**account' a/c model** whereas 2. the '**current transaction' models** of digital currency belong to UTXO (i.e. **Open Transaction** outputs) models e.g. bitcoin, rendering 'FastPay' non-applicable. So, the proposed version is follows:

FIG. 1 TRANSACTION STEPS BLOCKCHAIN UTXO MODEL

图1

FIG. 1 shows a schematic diagram of transaction steps based on blockchain UTXO model.

In Step S101: creating a transaction public address of UTXO model (on main chain of blockchain where **transaction public address** is used for storage of user transferred UTXO).

In Step S102: receiving UTXO **transaction request** sent by user, wherein transaction request is used for performing transaction operation on UTXO (stored in **transaction public address**)

In Step S103: carry out **transaction accounting** through account nodes of blockchain (side-chain) so as to carry out transaction operation.

The invention designs (a variation of) UTXO-Fast-Pay system that references design idea of the original a/c-based Fast-Pay scheme, maintains high efficiency yet simultaneously supports UTXO transaction model.

The system comprises of dual roles of (1) user (2) UTXO-Fast Pay committee, wherein the committee consists of accounting nodes.

UTXO FASTPAY Transaction Public Address

To meet the transaction model of UTXO-FastPay **transaction public address** created on blockchain (main chain), the UTXO-FastPay **transaction public address** is responsible for storing all **UTXOs** of users [transferred into the main chain: information like transfer-in-out, transaction request includes: UTXO number of transfer **transaction public address**, **user identification**, **transaction lock script** for *locking transaction operation of the transferred UTXO and transaction unlock condition*].

UTXO POOL-FASTPAY

and a committee stores the UTXO pool (on account book record) which records all UTXOs of users stored in UTXO-FastPay **transaction public address** (to transfer transaction)

The transfer transaction between user and public address is realized using M/N multiple signature (technology) which is a plurality of users that simultaneously sign-one digital asset OR a plurality of users in one account with signature and payment 'rights' script.

FIG. 2 PRINCIPLE OF BACKBONE INTRUSION

图2

FIG. 2 is a schematic diagram showing Principle of Backbone Intrusion assume committee has total $(3f+1)$ of which at most f malicious billers. The **principal chain deposit** (i.e. **transferring funds to main-chain** of blockchain is implemented as follows:

LOCK SCRIPT

(1) User 1. **designates** UTXO, 2. transfers it to FastPay **transaction public address**, 3. **locks** the transferred UTXO, 4. **unlocks transaction operation** (to the transferred UTXO) when 'unlock condition is satisfied'.

The **locking** script: $2f+1 < \text{Public Key } 1 > < \text{Public Key } 2 > < \text{Public Key } 3f > < \text{Public Key } (3f+1) > 3f+1OP_checkkultisig$, where Pulic Key N is biller in committee, where N is $1, 2, \dots (3f+1)$;

of deposit transaction, is realized by **M/N multiple signatures**,

and **unlocking** condition is set to pass the verification of $2/3$ two-thirds $(2f+1)$ signatures of the number of billers.

(2) User sends posting information to committee, which comprises of: a **UTXO number** specified by user, **user identifier** (e.g. user address or a user **public key** in a blockchain) and **locking script**;

(3) Bookkeeper verifies the posting information of user: primarily **verifies user identification** and **UTXO number** and updates the amount of money **stored** in FastPay **transaction public address** by the user in an account book of a (side-chain)

For example, if transaction operation is a transfer, the **transaction request** includes: transfer **amount**, **recipient identification** and user *signature*.

Transaction Accounting: Node of Blockchain (Side-chain)

The Transaction Accounting through accounting: node of blockchain (side-chain) includes: (1) **verifying** transfer amount, user signature through accounting node of blockchain (side-chain), (2) returning **accounting node signature** to the user after verification passed, so user **generates a combined signature** when transaction **unlock condition** is met (according to node signature) (3) **sending combined signature** and **transfer amount** to receiving party and (4) **verifying the joint signature verification request** sent by receiver through the accounting: node of blockchain (side-chain) and updating account book record after verification has passed. Under (1) **verifying** transfer amount: verifying whether the balance of mapping account corresponding to transaction public address generated on side chain is sufficient or not (according to transfer amount).

FIG. 3 SIDE-CHAIN TRANSACTION PRINCIPLE
Committee of (3f+1) Billers

图3

FIG. 3 is a schematic diagram of side-chain transaction principle. It assumes that the committee has a total of (3f+1) billers, of which at most f are malicious billers.

FIG. 3 shows a transfer transaction that needs to be made e.g. user transfers funds to recipients, implemented by side-chain accounting:

1. User broadcasts a A. **transfer transaction request** to committee, the B. transfer information comprises of **transfer amount**, C. **receiver identification** e.g. **address of receiver** in blockchain or receiver **public key**, D. **user signature** etc.

2. Accountant **receives, verifies** transfer information: whether user signature is correct, full (sufficient) account (mapping account generated on side-chain which corresponds to **transaction public address**) created by user.

3. Accountant signs and returns signature to user: after verification passed.

4. After user collects: $(2f+1)$ signatures spliced the received $(2f+1)$ signatures into a combined signature and broadcasting the combined signature to book-keepers so as to update the book.

5. User sends transfer information and joint signature to receiving party to confirm transfer by receiving party. The receiver broadcasts join signature to all bookkeepers to verify the joint signature; and bookkeeper confirms transfer is successful and updates book record.

If the transaction operation is main-chain amount roll-out, transaction request includes: roll-out amount, user address, user signature:

The accounting node of blockchain (side-chain) for transaction accounting include: **verifying** transferred amount, user signature through accounting node of blockchain (side-chain) and **returning** the accounting node signature to user after verification passed, so that the user generates a **combined signature** when transaction **unlock condition** is met, and updates account book record (after receiving combined signature broadcasted by user).

UPDATE OF LEDGER RECORD

After updating the ledger record, 1. **selects** the UTXO to be transferred from **transaction public address**, 2. **signing** the UTXO to be transferred, 3. **sending** the UTXO to user so that user **constructs a transaction unlock script** according to signature of accounting node and 4. performs **money transfer transaction with main chain**. Verifying withdrawal amount includes: **verifying balance of mapping account** correspond to **transaction public address** generated on side-chain *sufficient* according to transfer-out amount.

FIG. 4 PRINCIPLE OF CHAIN OUT-GOLD

图4

FIG. 4 is a schematic diagram of principal chain out-gold principle. Assume committee has total of $(3f+1)$ billers of which there are f malicious billers. User needs to roll-out the amount in the transaction public address (of the main chain).

(1) user broadcasts money request to committee which comprises of information e.g. transfer amount, user address, user signature.

(2) biller **receives request** for making deposit, **verifies** request: signature (correct?), **sufficient** balance (mapping account generated on side-chain and corresponding to **transaction public address**)

(3) accountant signs + sends: information to user (after passing verification).

(4) after user collects: $(2f+1)$ signatures are spliced to generate combined signature broadcasted to book-keeper updates book (inquires: all latest available UTXOs in FastPay **transaction public address** and selects: UTXO to be paid out)

(5) biller signs: UTXO number to be paid and sends UTXO number to user.

(7) user constructs **unlocking script** according to signature $(2f+1)$ accountants required when **unlocking** condition met,

generates **cash-out transaction** information,

Thus, the method comprises of: 1. User address, 2. UTXO number, 3.unlocking script, 4. **transaction public address** created by user, then 5. cash-out transaction information sent to main-chain to initiate cash-out transaction: The **unlock script** is the **signature** of $(2f+1)$ billers on cash-out transaction using **private keys**.

BYZANTINE FAULT-TOLERANCE CONSENSUS

The invention does not need to carry out consensus among accounting nodes for transaction verification but adopts: Byzantine Fault-Tolerance Consensus mechanism. According to the patent writer, he believes that despite $(3f+1)$ billers co-exist in the system wherein at most f malicious billers exist, as long as $(2f+1)$ billers are 'honest' (questionable assumption), the system will be able to prevent attacks such as 'double flowers' and 'bifurcation'. There is mention of "double-blossom" and 'split' to a fund repeatedly operable to be explored in a separate paper.

**8.1.3. COMPUTER MONEY YUAN MODEL: PEOPLE’S BANK OF CHINA (NOT CHINA)
(FALSE VERSION / SYNAPSE-YUAN CRIMINALLY ACCURATE)**

International Computer YUAN Model: PP BANK OF CHINA (NOT CHINA) (Criminal Technical Analysis)

RADIO FREQUENCY ID PRODUCT

UNDER DATA PROTECTION LAW (‘BODILY’ CELLS: FUNCTION)

INTERNATIONAL LAW: CIRCUITRY GENOCIDE

CIPHER, QUADRANT ALOGORITHM MODEL

8.1.3B (COMPUTER) **PP BANK OF CHINA PATENTS:** (NOT CHINA-GENOCIDED):

Transaction Method and Device Based on Digital Currency (Quadrant Model) (狄刚)

CIPHER, ALGORITHM EQUATIONS

This invention with application Filed by the People’s Bank of China (NOT the People of China) Digital Cash Research Institute, “Transaction Method and Device Based on Digital Currency”⁸¹ refers to a collection end and a payment end encrypt plaintext amount related in the transactions to obtain ciphertext amount and generate a corresponding verification information for verifying or decrypting the ciphertext amount.

There appears to be a methodology, first authentication information comprises of a first transaction proof which is an authentication step where the receiving end generates the **first verification** information used for verifying the cryptograph transaction amount. The **receiving end** carries out **binary splitting** on the **plaintext transaction** amount **m** according to a **preset digit n** to obtain:

$$m = \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} m_i$$

Where *i* represents index bit, and $0 < i < n$, and the receiving end **randomly splits** the **transaction private key x** according to **preset digit n** to obtain the transaction private key *x*:

⁸¹ 姚前, 狄刚, 钱友才, 黄烈明, 陈海波, 赵新宇, 王继伟, 张大伟 (2017) Transaction Method and Device Based on Digital Currency. (Application Filed by the People’s Bank of China (NOT the People of China) Digital Cash Research Institute. United States Patent Office. Patent No. CN107358424B. Available: <https://patents.google.com/patent/CN107358424B/en?q=CN107358424B>)

$$X = \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} X_i$$

Wherein x_0 to x_{n-2} are all generated at random:

$$X_{n-1} = X - \sum_{i=0}^{n-2} X_i$$

The digital currency or computer currency-based transaction apparatus that comprises of: 1. **transaction amount encryption module** is used for encrypting the A. received plaintext transaction amount to obtain a B. ciphertext transaction amount. 2. **First verification information generation module** is used for generating **first verification information** used for verifying cryptograph transaction amount 3. **Collection request sending module** is used for **generating a collection request** and **broadcasting** the collection request. 4. The **receiving** request comprises the ciphertext transaction amount and first verification information. The receiving module for receiving the receiving request; 5. The **transaction amount decryption module** is used for **decrypting** the **ciphertext transaction** amount according to first verification information to obtain A. plaintext transaction amount.

There is some mention of computation logic that sounds like (hyper-ledger) fabric-like: For instance, **S_i Stitching is performed to obtain first proof of transaction.**

For each index bit, according to $P(x)_i$, $m_i = x_i G + m_i H$

$$P(x)_i, m_i - k_i = x_i G + (m_i - k_i) H$$

For each index bit, use the x_i , the $P(x)_i, m_i$ and $P(x)_i, m_i - k_i$ generate **ring signature S** of index bit i .

The collection request verification module is configured to: split the first transaction certificate to obtain all index bits i , $P(x)_i, m_i$, $P(x)_i, m_i - k_i$, and S_i is $P(x)_i, m_i, P(x)_i, m_i - k_i$,

The **transaction amount encryption module** starts off by (1) generating a **transaction private key** used for collection, (2) storing a **base point** value (3) carrying out **encryption calculation** on the base point value: using base point **encryption algorithm** to obtain a base point check value (4) calculating the cipher text transaction amount according to formula $q = xG + mH$; q = **ciphertext** transaction amount, x = **transaction private key**, m = **received plaintext** transaction amount, G = **base point** value, H = **base point verification** value. The base point encryption hash algorithm can be SHA 256 algorithm, RIPEMD-160 algorithm or Base58 encoding.

The **transaction amount decryption module** (2) storing a **base point** value (3) carrying out **encryption calculation** on the base point value: using base point **encryption algorithm** to obtain a base point check value (4) **generate fixed private key** of payment end, **acquire a fixed public key** of collection end, carry out **encryption calculation** on **product of fixed private key** of payment end and **fixed public key** of the collection end by **using base point encryption algorithm** to obtain a shared key (5) **splitting result** by carrying out **decryption calculation** on first communication message by using **shared key** to obtain **plaintext transaction amount**.

There is some mention of 'hash' (as in cryptocurrency hash in Microsoft 060606 patent): the A. collection request comprises of 1. transaction currency, B. the transaction currency comprises of 1. ciphertext transaction amount and the 2. first verification information, C. the payment request comprises of 1. change making currency, the D. change making currency comprises of 1. ciphertext change making amount and second verification information, the E. transfer data structure generation module is further configured to generate a transfer data structure containing the 1. Hash value of the transaction currency 2. Hash value of change currency 3. Hash values of each digital (computer) currency in the subset of currencies.

8.1.3. COMPUTER MONEY YUAN MODEL: PEOPLE'S BANK OF CHINA (NOT CHINA) (FALSE VERSION / SYNAPSE-YUAN CRIMINALLY ACCURATE)

International Computer YUAN Model: PP BANK OF CHINA (NOT CHINA) (Criminal Technical Analysis)

RADIO FREQUENCY ID PRODUCT

UNDER DATA PROTECTION LAW ('BODILY' CELLS: FUNCTION)

INTERNATIONAL LAW: CIRCUITRY GENOCIDE

8.1.3C HASH 'MICROSOFT'-060606-TYPE ALGORITHM MODEL

8.1.3C (COMPUTER) PP BANK OF CHINA PATENTS: (NOT CHINA-GENOCIDED): Method and System For Providing Digital Currency (Hash Algorithm mirrors Microsoft Cryptocurrency 060606) (姚前)

HASH ALGORITHM

This invention with application Filed by the People's Bank of China (NOT the People of China) Digital Cash Research Institute, "Method and System for Providing Digital Currency"⁸² , it states that, H(M) is hash

⁸² 姚前, 李会锋, 温信祥, 李连三, 王栋兵, 刘浩, 赵欣, 唐晓雪, 刘文舒 (2016) Method and System For Providing Digital Currency. (Application Filed by the People's Bank of China (NOT the People of China) Digital Cash Research Institute. United States Patent Office. Patent No. CN107230049B. Available: <https://patents.google.com/patent/CN107230049B/en?q=CN107230049B>

operation performed on M to obtain a value, where M = mobile phone number, an organization code or a string of characters and numbers.

CERTIFICATE AUTHORITY

There is some discussion on certificate authority. This is relevant to the CO-VAX CHIP circuitry since VAX-CERT such as mentioned in (FALSE) WEF VAX-CERT certification 'technical specification' is NOT a technical and is more akin to a brochure. Certification system is suggested to be introduced into the D-RBM (NOT MONEY, just computerized digits) for utilization between the central bank and financial institution and social (presumably media) users (individuals and business owners) that utilize IBC (Identity-Based Cryptography) authenticational center to perform Identity Authentication.

For private keys and public keys in a central row generated in IBC and PKI, Secure Element (SE) is required to be stored in a Secure exclusive area of a mobile phone. The secret key is downloaded to the SE area of the mobile phone in the card change application process.

In the construction process of authentication system, PKI (Public Key Infrastructure) system is designed according to traditional PKI authentication system, uniformly established, CA (certificate authenticity) provides a strong digital signature. The PKI system is designed according to IBC (Identity based certificate) and user mobile phone number is taken as a **public key**.

图2

FIG. 2 is schematic for registering a D-RMB a/c by user,

图3

FIG. 3 is schematic of D-RMB transaction process: after identification information sent by terminal equipment used by user, the 1. Central Bank Digital Currency system **sends applications s/w** suitable for terminal equipment to terminal equipment; the 2. Central Bank Digital Currency system **sends IBC Public Key and IBC Private key** to terminal equipment **running application s/w** and then 3. **performs** (1) **identity authentication** session and (2) **session key negotiation** with terminal equipment 4. the CBDC system receives **user a/c** sent by terminal equipment running the application s/w and then sends a **user password** to the terminal equipment.

For instance, user 1 decides to make a 50-dollar digital currency D for online payment to user 2 coin 50. The transaction process security protocol is: (1) User 1 logs in to user mobile phone APP to complete **identity authentication** of two parties (with D-RMB system) and executes transaction protocol after session key negotiated in SSL mode. (2) Mobile phone number is the **IBC public key**: Mobile phone client selects 50-yuan digital currency D coin 50. M is organized according to transaction rules where M is designated as: m = mobile phone no., D = transaction code D coin 50.

Again, the mention of a 'hash' operation (like the WO060606 Microsoft Crypto-currency Patent, Crypto GLYPH means: 加-add 密-honey (on mountain), The payment steps comprises of mobile phone number 2 that carries out '**hash operation**' on an information segment to **obtain a message H (M), signing message H (M)** using **private key** that corresponds to mobile phone number 1 to obtain M and sending M to D-RMB system in an **encryption** mode.

On the (illegal) D-RMB (NOT MONEY) system end: **Decrypt** the message according to **protocol** to obtain M | M, verify message validity namely verify **M and H (M)** using a **public key**, namely **mobile phone number**

1 and prevent the message from being tampered in the transmission process; verification D coin 50 to decipher if it is 'legal' (valid), the transaction rule and related information read and corresponding operation executed, which includes change of registration center after service verification of D coin 50. The owner changes from Mobile Phone No. 1 (H) to Mobile Phone No. 2 (H) given the D coin 50 and the 'successful transaction' prompt prompted to both parties.

Again, the mention of a 'hash' operation (like the WO060606 Microsoft 'Crypto-currency') the Mobile Phone No. [that corresponds to the RIGHT of registration center] changed into hash of mobile phone no. i.e. borrowing address of bitcoin wallet that consists of Public Key Hash, described as follows:

The client side organizes the message unchanged and the mobile phone client user 1: automatic selection of 50-dollar digital currency D coin 50. The related information M I I M is organized into **transaction rule**, where M is designed as M - transaction code I I mobile phone number 1 I I I D coin 50. The method comprises of steps of: I I I payment amount I I I mobile phone number 2, carry out 'hash operation' on an information segment to obtain a message H (M), signing message H (M) using private key corresponding to mobile phone number 1 to obtain M and sending M I I I M to D-RMB system in an **encryption** mode.

To summarize, the core [META-CORE / CHIP / SERVER] elements of D-RMB comprises of **2-libraries**: issuing bank and banking bank of D-RMB. Digital currency is expressed as **digital [COMPUTER] currency** fund at the central row in a. **issuing bank**; the b. Digital currency is presented in **bank vault** as **digital [COMPUTER] cash** in **stock** by **commercial bank**. And the three centers: (1) **Registration center** e.g. currency generation, circulation, counting, check and death whole process record and other **two certification centers** (2) **CA certification center** based on PKI system, centralized management of certificates of organizations and users such as CFCA and **IBC certification center** based on **Cryptographic Technology of Identification** (Identity-Based Cryptography):

Two tables designed in registration center:

1. Digital currency ownership registration table: To record attribution of digital currency
2. Transaction flow meter

The owner of digital [COMPUTER] currency extracted by commercial bank digital [COMPUTER] currency system into a **wallet address** of the user, wherein the wallet address is a **public key** which is a **hash code**. The user represents the public key by a string of (QUOTE) 'nonsense codes'.

TABLE 1

Digital currency name	Owner of an animal	Remarks for note	Pbc100adfk109987766670	138xxxxx 001	D _{Coin 100}
.....	Pbc50cadfk109987766670	137xxxxx 002	D _{Coin 50}

(SUSPICIOUS) WALLET ADDRESS

User 1 (cell phone no 188xxxx001) paying D to user 2 (cell phone no. 199xxxx002) Coin 100. D-RMB system registers central ownership registration form: modification of D Coin 100. Now, what happens is: The wallet address of the original mobile phone number (cell phone no 188xxxx001) is changed into the wallet address of the original mobile phone number (cell phone no. 199xxxx002). Or the computer PERP changes the code of the merchant bank into the wallet address of the user: Public Key Hash Code.

TABLE 2

数字货币名	属主	备注
Pbc100adfk109987766670	1Xadcfgdgdadg	D 币 100 H (138xxxxx001)
.....
Pbc50cadfk109987766670	2xcfdald3xgdf	D 币 50 H (138xxxxx002)

Corresponding to owner change, 1Xadcfgdgdadg in the owner field to 2xcfdald3xgdf, if user 1 wants to use D coin 100.

The **identity-based cryptosystem IBC** directly use the **user's identity** as **Public Key**, [the authentication of Public Key is NOT dependent on a certificate] the use and management of secret key simplified.

For the **identity-identification** (use **Public Key**), the individual user adopt a **mobile phone number**, adopt **E-mail address matched with mobile phone number**, and other **converted character strings**.

(SUSPICIOUS) COMPUTER CENTRAL BANK MAIN FUNCTIONS: MONITOR COMPUTERIZED DIGITS / SYNAPSE-VAXED CHIP

The D-RMB system is a hierarchical system: **central bank** digital currency system / **commercial bank** is a computer system operated and maintained by the central bank / **commercial bank** or designated

organization of central bank / **commercial bank** and used for processing information about digital (COMPUTERIZED DIGITS/OR SYNPASE-)currency. The main functions of the central bank digital currency system comprise of the responsibility of issuing, verifying and monitoring the digital (COMPUTERIZED DIGITS/OR SYNPASE-)currency and illegal propagation, erroneously duped as 'circulation' of. To recall, all central banks are specifically targeted with financial institutions (and merchant banks) with pilot tests conducted.

To sum-up, the steps involved: (1) user logs into the mobile phone APP, **selects** a **function** such as "extracting digital [COMPUTER] currency", **selects** a **designated** commercial bank, such as the illegal construction-TYPE (under international law: subject to the return of total amount of money gained off land robbery i.e. war crime under Article 8) Chinese Construction Infrastructure Bank, inputs a **bank a/c number** and a **password** corresponding to **user a/c** and an **amount** e.g. 250 yuan of digital currency (NOT MONEY) to be **extracted** and **clicks 'send'** to send the first request to a commercial bank digital currency system of the Chinese Construction Infrastructure Bank.

Final Legal Note: Google is a translation device meaning translate 1-American (or / 1-Indian murder) document into multi-languages and since it is the patent registration online 'office' anything approved by unknown voteless recruits will be **UPLOADED**.

COMPUTER MONEY YUAN Model: PP BANK OF CHINA

In relation to unknown Mastermind-PERP using Wuhan for the 100PLUS military 'sport' excuse; port drill (matches the Beijing Convention (Meaning using Location Name) drafted intentionally by Mastermind-PERP / matching Sri Lanka Rajaratnam Train Bomb Singapore 2010 GLYPH GROUP) with Wuhan infiltration of Bat Journal NIH publication of BIO-W 1 CO-VID ('infectious diseases' lab-made),

The following exemplary patents reveals some clear connections:

The picked Inventors (copied) in the following brands are the one and same persons and were picked due to some links with China and/or Wuhan as exemplary role model inventors.

For example,

TENCENT = Apple Inc. (Matthew Mow) / ('Cow' 牛華寧) = Intel Inc. = Huawei (Wen Tong + Jianglei Ma) / Futurewei (Qian Chen) = Samsung = Facebook-Meta (#Hongyu Zhou 华中科技大学 + 中国人民解放军国防科技大学 + 电子科技大学) = Wuhan China Star Optoelectronics Semiconductor Display Model

It is important to note: that the (1) scientists picked as exemplary illustrations (e.g. satellite log-on crafts etc) (2) factories locations (of all your favourite products: MAC PROP LAPTOP) (3) scientists connections to USA perps recruiters MAYBE different from loot all kill all King-Pin PERP-ID (e.g. USURP weapons patent online office for stocklist and Softbank copied)

Also, notice that the Apple Guangdong Oppo Guangdong ocean line is drawn straight to california:

EEG SENSOR PRODUCTS TYPE

Guangdong Oppo Model: Brainwave

Huawei Model: Brainscience

Futurewei Model: Brainscience

COMPUTER MONEY DOLLAR Model: BANK OF NEW YORK

Apple (Guangdong) Model:

EVIDENCE EXAMINATION: PROGRAMMABLE E-WALLET SYNAPSE-YUAN (NOT MONEY) (WI-FI) PROGRAMMABLE SYNAPSE (THE CRIMINALLY ACCURATE VERSION)

Programmable E-Wallet (NOT MONEY) Synapse-YUAN Model: China Chinese Group (Criminal Technical Analysis)

8.2. COMPUTER SYNAPSE-YUAN MODEL: PP BANK OF CHINA (NOT CHINA) (CRIMINALLY ACCURATE VERSION) CRIMINAL MODEL USING

[UNDER DATA PROTECTION LAW: \('BODILY' 'BRAIN' CELLS: FUNCTION\)](#)

[INTERNATIONAL LAW: CO-VAX CIRCUITRY \('FREQUENCY WAVE'\) GENOCIDE](#)

EEG SENSOR PRODUCTS TYPE

8.2 GUANGDONG OPPO EEG MODEL: BRAINWAVE

8.2.1. Oppo Mobile Model EEG #Lock: Electronic Device, Brain Wave Unlock Method and Related Product (CN108519810A) (#Zhang Hai Ping 张海平) (GUANGDONG, CN) (FIELD PROGRAMMABLE GATE ARRAY, FPGA)

CN 108519810 A 说明书附图 2/7页

图1B

图1C

Personally, I examined Oppo Tablet: it contains the special feature of incorporating Japanese branded component for the photographic part increases its capability somewhat compared to other equally superior Huawei tablet. However, this is in conjunction with my advisory note earlier on the legitimate space-law rationale why GLYPH group manufactures cell phones for the same GLYPH zone.

This Guangdong Oppo Mobile Telecommunications Corp. Ltd Patent⁸³ electronic device shows the process of EEG signal detection (nervous system activity) acquired by a brain wave sensor for an 'unlock event'. The brain wave unlock is completed with the (i) parallel match of EEG signal of second operation with that of the default brain wave template of the first operation being successful (ii) 'the focus' exceeding the target predetermined threshold value.

⁸³ 张海平 (2018) Electronic Device, Brain Wave Unlocking Method and Related Product. United States Patent Office. China IP Patent No. CN 108519810A. Available:

The OPPO invention comprises of: (i) brain electricity of 'the processor' in the electronic device connected to the Wave sensor and (ii) memory for storing default brain wave template and target **predetermined threshold** value. FIG 1C. diagram shows a brain wave sensor chip type signal picker.

The 'unlock event' refers to, for instance, payment wait for file destination 'unlock event' for payment scene such as being directed to Alipay and payment scene applications such as We-chat waits (solving Lock event). Now, the problem is if 'the unlock' is done in-(CHIP) brain: clearly in diagram FIG. 1C, CO-VAX CHIP IBM/INTEL/SNAPDRAGON-TYPE transmitted (squared dimensions CHIP transmitter) embedded / implanted / injected on the right-side of neural surface / in-brain. Also, 'the EVENT' in perpetrator's context evidenced thus far (EVENT 201, WUHAN PORTS DRILL WUHAN MILITARY GAMES LED 8K PIXEL) in locations west e.g. Americans WHITE, East GLYPH GROUP refers to in-brain CO-VAX GRAPHENE CHIP programmable remotely by WIFI neurogrid e.g. gating variables of POP-100 / neuromorphic system / neural linked net.

The OPPO method for recording brain activity: (i) electrophysiological index (ii) electric wave variation (iii) overall reflection of bioelectrical activity in the cerebral cortex or scalp surface of cranial nerve cell. Thus, the brain wave signal is considered the collective nervous activity signal generated by the common electric discharge of many nerves i.e. the collection of nerves signals by the brain wave sensor of active signals.

LAB REPORT - OPPO

图2B

FIG.2B shows diagrams of electroencephalogram analyzed provided by multiple waveform repetition periods obtained being identical.

图2C

图2D

The (eye) focus of the user is determined according to the number of repetitions of the waveform repetition period. The watching area is the display area showing: the (i) amount of money to be paid (ii) to execute unlock operation and the (iii) wait for the 'unlock event'.

Upon detecting the watching duration and attention given to (sense decipher) if it is greater than or equal to the target (of the display area of the amount of the money to be paid). If lengthy attentive watching duration is detected, the **unlock operation** is executed.

The target **predetermined threshold** value is a preset value chosen according to the amount of money to be paid.

The focus is a default value more than the **target threshold** value, obtained from user's pupil relative to the location parameter of the eye socket and the opening degree of the eyelid. The **watching area** is determined according to the **location parameter** and **the opening degree**.

Thus, when the EEG signal and default brain wave template matches successfully and the focus is more than the target predetermined threshold value, then 'unlock' execution operation occurs.

EVIDENCE EXAMINATION: PROGRAMMABLE E-WALLET SYNAPSE-YUAN (NOT MONEY) (WI-FI) PROGRAMMABLE SYNAPSE (THE CRIMINALLY ACCURATE VERSION)

Programmable E-Wallet (NOT MONEY) Synapse-YUAN Model: China Chinese Group (Criminal Technical Analysis)

8.2. COMPUTER SYNAPSE-YUAN MODEL: PP BANK OF CHINA (NOT CHINA) (CRIMINALLY ACCURATE VERSION) CRIMINAL MODEL USING

UNDER DATA PROTECTION LAW: ('BODILY' 'BRAIN' CELLS: FUNCTION)
INTERNATIONAL LAW: CO-VAX CIRCUITRY ('FREQUENCY WAVE') GENOCIDE
FIN-(GER) TECH LAW: SPACE LAW

EEG SENSOR PRODUCTS TYPE

8.2 **GUANGDONG OPPO EEG MODEL: BRAINWAVE**

8.2.2. Oppo Mobile Model EEG #Dialing: #Dailing Method And Related Product (CN108600502A) (#Zhang Hai Ping 张海平) (GUANGDONG, CN) (Field Programmable Gate Array FPGA)9

图3

This OPPO Patent, "(OPPO) Electronic Device, Dailing Method and Related Product"⁸⁴ shows 'the processor' for (i) determining the current type of emotion according to EEG signal analyzed and is operable: (ii) to dial the person by matching the contact person with the emotion type from the address list. FIG. 3 shows brain wave sensor conductive e.g. intrusive electrode such the in-brain injected CO-VAX CHIP circuitry as transmitter.

⁸⁴ 张海平 (2018) Electronic Device, Dailing Method and Related Product. United States Patent Office. China IP Patent No. CN 108600502A. Available:

The (programmable) computer program can 'make' the calculating Machine (computation logic configured) to execute some / all steps described and can be a software installation packet.

The details on 'the processor' being additionally operable to dial the contact person is as follows:

'The processor' obtains multiple contact persons of correspondence of multiple communication process and establishes call mood stored in the memory. For instance, the call mood model is matched with contact person of a specific emotion type to form a recommendation list. The front camera captures the user's facial expression to determine the type of emotion according to EEG signal analyzed with preliminary (computer machine learning for real time remote kill shot as real motive) judgment based on emotion type determination.

The memory operably contains a storage of electroencephalogram template library with the corresponding emotion type of each electroencephalogram template. The electroencephalogram is generated based on: (i) the EEG signal that determines the wave character (ii) divided into multiple segmentation (electroencephalogram according to the wave character period) (iii) the resulting multiple segmentation electroencephalogram and template library of row compares, to obtain matched electroencephalogram **template of segmentation** electroencephalogram (iv) Finally, the highest electroencephalogram template of multiplicity (in corresponding multiple electroencephalogram templates of multiple segmentation electroencephalogram) with the corresponding type of emotion is determined as the preliminary (computer liable / subject to erroneous) judgment knot of the type of 'emotion Fruit' (Chinese terminology).

图5

Each segmentation electroencephalogram corresponds to wave character periods e.g. 61-80, 81-100.

The electroencephalogram is drawn according to wave character period divided into multiple segmentations compared to templates stored in library.

FIG. 6 OPPO-FLOW OF DAILING METHOD

图6

FIG. 6 shows the flow of dial-ing method.

601: depicts case where (i) the electronic device gets instruction to start dialing interface (ii) ('the controller') to control brain wave sensor to obtain EEG signal.

602: determines the TYPE of emotion based on EEG signal.

603: depicts the contact person selected according to emotion type. The call mood model will be memory stored based on 'emotions-TYPES: The determined mood corresponding to contact person-TYPE so as to dial that contact person.

604: the TYPE of emotion from address list is matched with contact person selected to make dial actions.

图7

701: brain wave sensor obtains EEG signal; 702: determines the type of user emotion based on EEG signal; 703: select contact person according to emotion type; 704: dial the contact person.

EVIDENCE EXAMINATION: PROGRAMMABLE E-WALLET SYNAPSE-YUAN (NOT MONEY) (WI-FI) PROGRAMMABLE SYNAPSE (THE CRIMINALLY ACCURATE VERSION)

Programmable E-Wallet (NOT MONEY) Synapse-YUAN Model: China Chinese Group (Criminal Technical Analysis)

8.1. COMPUTER SYNAPSE-YUAN MODEL: PP BANK OF CHINA (NOT CHINA) (CRIMINALLY ACCURATE VERSION) CRIMINAL MODEL USING

UNDER DATA PROTECTION LAW: ('BODILY' 'BRAIN' CELLS: FUNCTION)

INTERNATIONAL LAW: CO-VAX CIRCUITRY ('FREQUENCY WAVE') GENOCIDE

FIN-(GER) TECH LAW: SPACE LAW

EEG SENSOR PRODUCTS TYPE

8.2 **GUANGDONG OPPO EEG MODEL: BRAINWAVE**

8.2.3. Oppo Mobile Model EEG Analysis: Brainwave Information Transmission And Control Method And Related Product (CN108498094) (#Zhang Hai Ping 张海平) CO. IBM-INTEL-CHIP-TYPE SILICON SUBSTRATE)

CN 108628445 A

说明书附图

3/6 页

图1E

This OPPO Patent, “Brain Wave Information Transmission and Control Method and Related Method”⁸⁵ shows electroencephalography (EEG) using evoked responses and brain wave information transmission and control method.

⁸⁵ 张海平 (2018) Brain Wave Information Transmission and Control Method and Related Method. United States Patent Office. China

IP Patent No. CN 108498094A. Available:

图1E

图1F

图1G

FIG. 1E shows a kind of electrode-array. The brain wave sensor that acquires EEG signal of active brain, captures large amounts of neurons that synchronize physical signs note

that the postsynaptic potential occurred formed after summation of Record: recorded electric wave variation / bioelectrical activity of cranial nerve cell in cerebral cortex or scalp surface over-all reflection.

图3

FIG. 3 flow depicts: 301 shows EEG signal of 'first user' acquired by brain wave sensor.

302 refers to the electronic equipment determining (at least one brain wave information sent) to the first receiving device (e.g. CO-VAX CHIP circuitry programmable remotely via WIFI) of the brain wave stimulating apparatus and the second user's brain in a stabilized adaptation state as a reference zone. (The second user connects via the brain wave stimulating apparatus in first receiving device.)

303 depicts the electronic equipment inquiring confirmation of (matches between) predicted EEG signal extraction (storage bank of preset brain wave information that corresponds with the human brain region) and the associated (at least one) brain wave information from the reference zone.

304 shows the electronic equipment inquiring **preset information extraction algorithm** library, confirms **reference brain wave** information with the target **brain wave information extraction algorithm** (of connection)

305 depicts the **electronic equipment extracting EEG signal (i) executing information** according to the target information **extraction algorithm operation**, (ii) obtain in the EEG signal with the associated brain wave information of the reference zone.

306 shows the electronic equipment sending at **least one brain wave information** to the **first receiving device** (on standby) by the brain **wave stimulating apparatus** (that reference zone is stimulated) so that the second user receives at least one brain wave information.

图2

S201: The electronic equipment acquires the EEG signal of user 1 via the brain wave sensor.

S202: The electronic equipment determines the brain wave stimulating apparatus [such as (i) transcranial magnetic stimulation (TMS) device that utilizes magnetic field pulse (ii) Neural Spike train of induction brain specific region, where the device is suitably positioned to form matching status with the human specific region and magnetic field changes so the second user can receive corresponding brain wave information e.g. perception of motion] of the first receiving device and second user brain in a 'stabilized reference zone of adaptative state'.

S203: Electronic equipment according to EEG signal extraction associated with at least one brain of the reference zone e.g. visual / auditory / taste information.

S204: Electronic equipment sends one brain wave information to the first receiving device. The brain wave stimulating apparatus stimulate the reference zone so the second user receives at least one brain wave information

EVIDENCE EXAMINATION: PROGRAMMABLE E-WALLET SYNAPSE-YUAN (NOT MONEY) (WI-FI) PROGRAMMABLE SYNAPSE (THE CRIMINALLY ACCURATE VERSION)

Programmable E-Wallet (NOT MONEY) Synapse-YUAN Model: China Chinese Group (Criminal Technical Analysis)

8.2. COMPUTER SYNAPSE-YUAN MODEL: PP BANK OF CHINA (NOT CHINA) (CRIMINALLY ACCURATE VERSION) CRIMINAL MODEL USING

UNDER DATA PROTECTION LAW: ('BODILY' 'BRAIN' CELLS: FUNCTION)

INTERNATIONAL LAW: CO-VAX CIRCUITRY ('FREQUENCY WAVE') GENOCIDE

FIN-(GER) TECH LAW: SPACE LAW

EEG SENSOR PRODUCTS TYPE

8.2 GUANGDONG OPPO EEG MODEL: BRAINWAVE

8.2.4. Oppo Mobile Model EEG: Advertisement Broadcast Method and Related Product (CN 108391169A) (#Zhang Hai Ping 张海平) (GUANGDONG, CN)

In this OPPO Patent, "Advertisement Broadcast Method and Related Product"⁸⁶ discloses a TYPE of "playback method" meaning when an electronic equipment plays video content, the (insidious) **preset** time period: (i) acquires the **EEG signal** of the brain wave sensor (ii) determines the user is **directed** to the **interest-degree** of currently playing video content based on the EEG signal 'currently acquired' (meaning 'captured' UNDER DATA PROTECTION LAW), (iii) if the interest degree **meets** preset condition (detected by embedded 'sensor'), played in **current timing node** and **present ad** content. Detection is based on the continuous acquisition of at least one EEG signal determination and at least one interest-degree higher than or equal to **predetermined threshold value**, to confirm that detection of that **interest-degree meets preset** condition. The perpetrator's conceptual ideal is that the interest that user that watches the advertisement is risen, the dispensing effect of advertisement is promoted.

CUSTOMER PARAMETER

The electronic equipment database obtains at least one advertisement of a matched customer parameter associated with at least one advertisement classification to launch. The electronic equipment that plays the specific implementation for preset ad content in current timing node obtained using corresponding keyword of currently playing video content: obtained from the database, using keywords matching at least one advertisement played in current timing node.

The customer parameter i.e. EEG signal (frequency range increase or slow wave) can be counted in advance (including mapping relations of differing age ranges / stars: characters' recognition and lable) in advance by the electronic equipment includes; age of user / gender / names of public figures or 'stars actresses / actors' taking into consideration that different age groups have different 'likes'.

⁸⁶ 张海平 (2018) Advertisement Broadcast Method and Related Product. United States Patent Office. China IP Patent No. CN 108391169A. Available:

The electronic equipment can be in time domain or frequency domain (i) brain wave data analyzed (ii) converted into electroencephalogram (iii) analysis of brain electricity (by equipment) in time-domain analysis (iv) brain wave data converted into spectrogram i.e. frequency spectrum of analysis spectrum figure by electronic equipment in frequency-domain analysis. The meter analysis (in electronic equipment) contains a large amount of male user and brain wave data of female user that obtained the brain wave characteristic in EEG signal.

图3

Now here is conclusive (CLEAR) evidence of the psychopathic perpetrator's criminal flow as follows:

301: Electronic equipment plays the video content and **at every preset time period** periodically acquires the EEG signal of the user via the brainwave sensor.

302: The interest degree of currently playing video content is based on EEG signal acquired in real-time.

303: If the interest degree exceeds or equates to 'predetermined value', the electronic device will obtain currently playing video content corresponding keyword

304: Electronic equipment obtains one advertisement in the pre-set video content database using pre-set video content matching keywords

305: When interest degree matches the preset condition, the electronic equipment plays at least one advertisement (video content) played in current timing node (from the preset ad content).

Web advertisement dispensing using video on-demand system: (1) First way: Advertisement is played (launched in net cast) before video program play, passively received by the user. (2) Second way: Advertisement insertion during video program play i.e. it 'breaks' for commercial in the playing process of 'frequency ('the show') program'. OPPO inventor states that the time the advertisement plays is of "most importance".

EVIDENCE EXAMINATION: PROGRAMMABLE E-WALLET SYNAPSE-YUAN (NOT MONEY) (WI-FI) PROGRAMMABLE SYNAPSE (THE CRIMINALLY ACCURATE VERSION)

Programmable E-Wallet (NOT MONEY) Synapse-YUAN Model: China Chinese Group (Criminal Technical Analysis)

8.2. COMPUTER SYNAPSE-YUAN MODEL: PP BANK OF CHINA (NOT CHINA) (CRIMINALLY ACCURATE VERSION) CRIMINAL MODEL USING

UNDER DATA PROTECTION LAW: ('BODILY' 'BRAIN' CELLS: FUNCTION)

INTERNATIONAL LAW: CO-VAX CIRCUITRY ('FREQUENCY WAVE') GENOCIDE

FIN-(GER) TECH LAW: SPACE LAW

NEUROMORPHIC PRODUCTS TYPE

8.3. HUAWEI NEUROMORPHIC MODEL:

8.3.1. HUAWEI **NEUROMORPHIC** PATENT in conjunction with SHANGHAI INSTITUTE OF MICROSYSTEMS and INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY (SIMIT): Phased-Change Memory Material / Phased-Change Memory Cell / Phased-Change Memory (郑龙 SERIES, 宋志棠, 宋三年, 宋文雄, 唐文涛, 赵俊峰, 罗时)

In this selected special Huawei Patent on “Phase-Change Memory Material, Phase-Change Memory Cell and Phase-Change Memory”⁸⁷, the phase change memory

NEURAL NETWORK: 'PROCESSOR' ALGORITHM COMPUTATION⁸⁸

⁸⁷ 郑龙, 宋志棠, 宋三年, 宋文雄, 唐文涛, 赵俊峰, 罗时江 (2022) Phase-Change Memory Material, Phase-Change Memory Cell and Phase-Change Memory. United States Patent Office. China IP Patent No. CN 116,940,221A. Available:

⁸⁸ SIMIT: <http://english.sim.cas.cn/Home2017/>

GRAPHENE NANORIBBON (/METAL LEAD): PHASE CHANGE MEMORY CELL

SILICON CARBIDE (OR SILICON OXIDE / CARBON GRAPHENE: CO-VAX CHIP IN-BRAIN PHOTOGRAPHIC PURPOSES)

memory material comprises of $Nb_{\delta} (Ge_x Sb_y Te_z)_{1-\delta}$ wherein the value range of atom content delta of Nb is $0 < \delta < 1$, $nb_{\delta} (Ge_x Sb_y Te_z)_{1-\delta}$ wherein $x / y / z$ is > 0 and ≤ 10 . The PCM material is prepared by (1) sputtering / (2) evaporation / (3) chemical vapor deposition / (4) molecular beam epitaxy / (5) atomic vapor deposition / (6) atomic layer deposition method.

LEGAL ANALYSIS

It is stated very clearly: that the phase-change memory material can (1) realize **multi-state memory** of phase-change memory and meet the requirement of (2) high-precision neuromorphic calculation. I repeat to re-emphasize: (QUOTE) “**high-precision neuromorphic calculation**”. At this point, it is evident CO-VAX in-brain CHIP of SILICON SUBSTRATE / CARBIDE OF GRAPHENE is for “**high-precision neuromorphic calculation**” of neuromorphic system of a neural linked network (evidence confirmed in: San Jose, New York: THE AMERICAS / CHINA JAPAN KOREA / EUROPE / AUSTRALIA).

LAB REPORT: (HUAWEI X-RAY PHOTOELECTRON SPECTRUM)

图5

FIG. 5 is an X-RAY PHOTOELECTRON SPECTRUM (which echoes the ‘Spectrum (CRIMINAL) Act of no authority illegal agency FCC) of a phase change (amorphous to polycrystalline) memory film after annealing at 280 ° C.

The **nb** element **participates** in (1) **crystallization** and (2) **amorphous transformation** process: Nb effectively change Ge-Sb-Te **crystal structure** i.e. binding energy change of Ge-Sb-Te caused by Nb doping. The nb combine with atoms in Ge-Sb-Te to form a stable lattice structure so a stable intermediate resistance state structure is realized.

LEGAL ANALYSIS

Manipulation of an intermediate resistance state is achieved by doping different amount of Nb elements resulting in phase change memory materials with different phase change curves obtained.

LAB REPORT – AMORPHOUS RESISTANCE / VOLTAGE / PULSE

FIG. 11 HUAWEI TOTAL AMORPHOUS RESISTANCE OF PCM

FIG. 12 HUAWEI VOLTAGE (WRITTEN TEXT: 电压)

FIG. 13 HUAWEI PULSE WIDTH 200NS

FIG. 14 HUAWEI PULSE VOLTAGE INDUCED PARTIAL AMORPHOUS RESISTANCE: CELL TO THIN FILM

图11

图12

图13

图14

FIG. 11 shows graphical PROOF of time dependence of fully (total) amorphous resistance (with drift coefficient) of phase change memory cell wrt time. It concludes the doping of Nb that effectively reduce the

resistance drift characteristic of GST system thus summarily 'beneficial' (to remote 'controller' PERP's computation) accuracy and stability of neuromorphic calculation.

FIG. 12 shows PROOF of voltage utilization (expressly stated in GLYPH TEXT 电压) for a 1. phase change memory cell versus **GST Phase Change Memory film (Nb 0.035) plot of resistance (ILLEGAL / CRIMINAL) testing (for human implementation / or implantation e.g. CO-VAX SILICON CARBIDE GRAPHENE pre-meditated crime).**

FIG. 13 shows the voltage for a phase change memory cell versus **GST Phase Change Memory film at Pulse Width of 200 ns (Nb 0.035) plot of resistance.**

FIG. 14 shows **Phase Change Memory cell to Phase Change Memory thin film versus time for corresponding pulse voltage induced partial amorphous resistance (Nb 0.035).**

FIG. 4 HUAWEI PROOF CHART OF 10-Y RETENTION OF PCM

图4

FIG. 4 shows a test chart (proof) of a (1) 10-year data retention of Phase Change Memory film and (2) as the atomic content of Nb (Niobium) changes, the data of the 10-year data retention temperature of Phase Change Memory film also varies. In addition, the doping concentration of Nb is increased, the crystallization temperature of the phase-change memory film is higher, so phase change memory film can be used in different temperature environments.

Rule: The higher the Nb content, the higher the data retention temperature for 10 years and retention temperature of range 148-230 ° C.

FIG. 3 HUAWEI RESISTANCE OF PCM FILMS

图3

FIG. 3 shows a **graph of resistance** of phase change memory PCM thin films as shown: as temperature increases, phase change memory film undergoes phase change from **amorphous to polycrystalline** accompanied by reversible transition from high to low resistance.

The report conclusion: PCM material has data retention of temperature 87 ° C. Comparative, FIG. 4 PCM film has 1. better stability in high-resistance state 2. More gradual change with temperate 3. Better amorphous state stability. Thus, PCM film of present HUAWEI application achieve a more durable data-holding performance (in-brain). (Note. Plausible temperature range can be substituted with invisible waves: RF)

FIG. 2 HUAWEI T-SHAPED PHASE CHANGE MEMORY CELL: ELECTRODES⁸⁹

FIG. 2 is a schematic of a T-shaped Phase Change Memory cell includes: a plurality of upper electrodes 10 and lower electrodes 20 connectable to common electrode 50 through conductive layer 60 and transmission of electrical signal (by common electrode 50).

LEGAL EVIDENCE: Legal Confirmation

It is clearly stated, that T-shaped structure Phase Change Memory cell / films comprises of: 1. Si / Si O2 = Silicon / Silicon Oxide (CO-VAX material) on conductive layer 60 (consists of: Al, tiN etc clearly stated as, “tunable below micron level” e.g. CO-VAX micro-circuitry: DR. NIXON) deposited on (silicon) substrate (no. 11-FIG. 6). 2. deposit layer of electrode material (TiN, W, etc clearly stated as, “tunable below micron level”) conductive layer 60 to form electrode layer (no. 12-FIG. 7) 3. etching electrode layer (no. 12-FIG. 7) and filling in a dielectric material SiOx by etching process, remaining portions of electrode layer (no. 12-FIG. 7) form lower electrode 20 and common electrode 50 and the filled dielectric material forms insulating dielectric layer (no. 40-FIG. 8) 4. depositing **Phase Change Material film layer (no. 13)** and upper electrode layer (no. 14 e.g. TiN) on the etched substrate (no. 11-FIG. 9) 5) etching Phase Change material film layer (no.13)

⁸⁹ See: Fritz’s books on electrode shock slaves ‘medical products’ sold in California.

by adopting an etching process to form a **Phase Change Material layer (no. 30)** etching **upper electrode layer (no. 14)** to form **upper electrode 10**, in order to create T-shaped Phase Change Memory Cell (FIG. 10).

图10

图9

It is clearly stated, the preparation method is compatible with existing preparation process of “complementary metal oxide semiconductor ...” (CMOS) i.e. CHIP circuitry manufacturing.

The sole criminal purpose of phase change material layer 30 (is **Ag / Cu / Zn metal doped-Ge-Sb-Te** based phase change material) for undergoing a resistance change is to enable writing and reading of information. Attributing to unstable intermediate state, PCM can realize only three-state storage at most and NOT meet requirements of a neuromorphic CHIP because more multi-state (ten-state) storage cannot (according to HUAWEI) be realized. (The phase change memory cell 100 is where data is stored.)

CRIMINAL PURPOSE

The criminal purpose of doping different amounts of Nb is so that the 1. manipulation of an intermediate resistance possible and to obtain 2. PCM materials with different phase change curves.

LEGAL ANALYSIS

1. Historic precedent clearly shows: Exemplary Shanghai (Port gateway: apparently, import-export of opium DRUG trade was meant to devastate CHINA-DRAGON GLYPH GROUP with PEDO-RING CONFIRMED HSBC and had since become a tactical invasion strategy and prime location target as gateway into China (means to rob / murder the people), so it is not surprising (in fact, totally in sync with the criminal precedent of a CHIP-CHEMICAL-DRUG genocidal criminal infiltration trade tool to murder a nation or island-wide i.e. SINGAPORE-PHOENIX GLYPH GROUP) such as GRAPHENE / SILICON CARBIDE.
2. Since phase change memory cell material are (obviously / noticeably) the EXACT IBM CHIP (COPIED Ancient Replica) in-location: San Jose in USMCA PLOT / PLUS 3 PLOT, CO-VAX CHIP POP-100PLUS NEUROGRID nations by KING-PIN PERP-ID un-confirmed.
3. Also, the suspicious rush to patent (dated 2022) in the immediate 'successful genocide / organ damage' aftermath of GLOBAL CO-VAX, can mean that the 'encouraged' KING-PIN PERP 'confidently' decided to 'make a quick move' to patent

the PCM material (bypass judges / the law and 'the people': ALL CO-VAX chipped or organ damaged / dead) using (in conjunction with) the HUAWEI brand (telcom brands including DIY 'global' india chip all replicable).

4. KING-PIN PERP resort to stealing electricity (off 100PLUS PLOT) to A. steal electrical configurable-'e-money' or B. to commit CHIP-genocide / CHIP-systematic crime / CHIP-war crime under international law remotely programmable by WiFi (short for Wireless Finance) chipped POP-100+ and **vegetables / meat / eggs / water / salt / refrigerator stock monitoring theft / in-house meter circuitry** etc. meaning A. CO-VAX GRAPHENE injection and B. cell towers erection are not a necessary requirement for killing (although it accelerates the speed of death by WiFi / frequency waves).
5. Mankind is a born a transmitter to outer-space. The neuromorphic (criminal) system is modelled after the human brain. It is an illegal device under international criminal law (postponed / rejected until safety protocols: CHIP remodelled UPLOAD set-up physical booklet new banks etc confirmed by Nations-100+ / every state in large states: permission / every citizen's comfort zone: consent). Currently, there exists expressly outright rejection 5G ban and outlawed.

EVIDENCE EXAMINATION: PROGRAMMABLE E-WALLET SYNAPSE-YUAN (NOT MONEY) (WI-FI) PROGRAMMABLE SYNAPSE (THE CRIMINALLY ACCURATE VERSION)

Programmable E-Wallet (NOT MONEY) Synapse-YUAN Model: China Chinese Group (Criminal Technical Analysis)

8.2. COMPUTER SYNAPSE-YUAN MODEL: PP BANK OF CHINA (NOT CHINA) (CRIMINALLY ACCURATE VERSION) CRIMINAL MODEL USING

UNDER DATA PROTECTION LAW: ('BODILY' 'BRAIN' CELLS: FUNCTION)

INTERNATIONAL LAW: CO-VAX CIRCUITRY ('FREQUENCY WAVE') GENOCIDE

FIN-(GER) TECH LAW: SPACE LAW

NEUROMORPHIC PRODUCTS TYPE

8.3. HUAWEI NEUROMORPHIC MODEL

8.3.2. HUAWEI MODEL: The Method and Apparatus of Model **Predictive Control** ('Controller') (Computation Logic) (Neuromorphic Computing Chip) (闫正SERIES)

In the Huawei Patent, "Method and Apparatus for Model Predictive Control"⁹⁰ (available in European Patent and CN China Patented versions) shows a Model Predictive Control (MPC) system as a control strategy (applied to automatic control of robot, drone flight control, overall energy consumption e.g. temperature, power, air-conditioner which is free e.g. etc).

For the **general discrete** system model: $x(k+1) = f(x(k), u(k))$,

where x is n -dimensional state variable,

u = m -dimensional control signal,

⁹⁰ 闫正 and 毕舒展 (2017) Method and Apparatus For Model Predictive Control. WIPO Patent No. WO2017/024583A1. Available: [https://patents.google.com/patent/WO2017024583A1/en?q=\(NEUROMORPHIC+VECTOR\)&assignee=HUAWEI&oq=NEUROMORPHIC+VECTOR+HUAWEI+](https://patents.google.com/patent/WO2017024583A1/en?q=(NEUROMORPHIC+VECTOR)&assignee=HUAWEI&oq=NEUROMORPHIC+VECTOR+HUAWEI+)

CN 107615186A. Available: [https://patents.google.com/?q=\(NEUROMORPHIC+HUAWEI+VECTOR\)&oq=NEUROMORPHIC+HUAWEI+VECTOR](https://patents.google.com/?q=(NEUROMORPHIC+HUAWEI+VECTOR)&oq=NEUROMORPHIC+HUAWEI+VECTOR)

F = system model

K = at current sampling instant

K + 1 = next sampling instant.

The MPC problem of the system is reduced to a mathematical equation:

$$\min_{u(k)} J(k) = \sum_{j=1}^N x^T(k+j)Qx(k+j) + \sum_{j=0}^{N-1} u^T(k+j)Ru(k+j) + F(x(k+N))$$

Where J(k) = performance index of 'the control' system,

Q and R = Coefficient Matrix, set to the corresponding matrix (according to actual application)

$$\text{S.t. } x(k+j+1) = f(x(k+j), u(k+j)), j=1, \dots, N-1$$

F(x(k+N)) = is about the state variable x(k+N) Function

$$u_{\min} \leq u(k+j) \leq u_{\max}, j=0, \dots, N-1$$

U max and U min = upper and lower bounds of constraint of **control input**

$$x_{\min} \leq x(k+j) \leq x_{\max}, j=1, \dots, N$$

X max and X min = upper and lower bounds of constraint of 'the system' state

N = prediction step size

The core idea of MPC is 1. to predict the state of the next N finite moments of the controlled system (at each sampling moment) then 2. solve the finite time domain optimal control problem 3. to obtain the optimal control signal at the current moment.

This Huawei model predictive control method is implemented by using a neural network architecture of prediction process of determining 3. parameter variable $\theta(k)$ and **online optimization process of determining 4. control increment $\Delta u(k)$** completed by neuromorphic computing chip.

This Huawei method for model predictive control implemented by: 3. parameter variable $\theta(k)$ at time ('moment') k (S110) by means of single layer recurrent neural network algorithm i.e. training a model of hidden layer neural network according to: 1. **state variable $x(k)$** and 3. **parameter variable $\theta(k)$** at k (S120) determining a sum of 2. **Control variable $u(k-1)$** at time k-1 and determining 4. **control increment $\Delta u(k)$** of the predictive model to the **control variable $u(k)$** of the predictive model (S140).

The law of the physical motion of controlled system that the Huawei prediction model formula:

$$x(k+1) = A(\theta(k))x(k) + Bu(k) \dots\dots\dots \text{(Equation 21)}$$

The general representation of controlled object model: (Equation 21)

The 2. control variable $u(k)$ satisfies the performance index of a predictive model by means of a **single-layer recursion neural network algorithm according to state variable $x(k)$** and 3. parameter variable $\theta(k)$ at current moment i.e. moment k and control variable at time (k-1) at previous moment, model predictive control is performed according to control variable $u(k)$. The 4. control increment $\Delta u(k)$ satisfies a performance index of a predictive model according to 2. control variable $u(k-1)$ and 3. parameter variable $\theta(k)$.

Huawei Model Predictive Control (PI = Performance Index)	Recurrent Neural Network Algorithm	Time
	1. State variable $x(k)$	k
	2. Control variable $u(k-1)$	k-1
	3. Parameter variable $\theta(k)$	k
	4. Control increment $\Delta u(k)$	

S110 shows parameter variables $\theta(k-1)$ to $\theta(kq)$ of prediction model at time k-1 to kq, 1. **state variable $x(k)$** at time k, 2. **control variable $u(k-1)$** at time k-1 and determining 3. parameter variable $\theta(k)$ at time k.

S120 shows **quadratic programming** problem solved online by single-layer recurrent neural network algorithm and determining 1. **state variable $x(k)$** at time k, 2. **control variable $u(k-1)$** and 3. parameter variable $\theta(k)$ thus satisfying the performance index of prediction model 4. control increment $\Delta u(k)$.

S130 determines according to 2. control variable $u(k-1)$ of prediction model and 4. control increment $\Delta u(k)$, 2. control variable $u(k)$ of prediction model at time k, where $u(k) = u(k-1) + \Delta u(k)$.

S140 performs model **prediction control** based on: 2. **control variable u(k)** of the prediction model. The 1. **state variable x(k)** of prediction model at time k 2. **control variable u(k-1)** at time k-1 are acquired.

In other words, the **control variable u(k) at time k is subjected to model prediction control based on control variable u(k).**

HUAWEI FIG. 2 SINGLE HIDDEN LAYER NEURAL (HUAWEI) NETWORK

The model function $\theta(\alpha)$ of single hidden layer neural network nerve (FIG. 2): $n + m + pq$

First, offline analysis of controlled object can obtain 2 sets of data

Output data: $\theta = [\theta_1, \dots, \theta_2]$ and

Input data: $\alpha = [\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_2]$, where $s =$ number of sample data.

$n =$ dimension of **state** variable $x(k)$

$m =$ dimension of **control** variable $u(k)$

$(p,p) =$ number of neurons in **output layer**

The dimension of $\theta(k)$

$L =$ number of hidden layer of neurons (L value defined by user)

$g(\cdot) =$ excitation function of hidden layer neurons

$w_i =$ weight vector of i -th input layer to hidden layer w_i (random generation)

$b_i =$ offset bias vector of neuron is b_i (random generation)

NEURON MATRIX H

By substituting input parameter $\alpha = [\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_2]$, neuron matrix H below:

$$H = \begin{bmatrix} g(w_1\alpha_1 + b_1) & \cdots & g(w_L\alpha_1 + b_L) \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ g(w_1\alpha_s + b_1) & \cdots & g(w_L\alpha_s + b_L) \end{bmatrix}$$

By substituting obtained matrix θ and output $\theta = [\theta_1, \dots, \theta_s]$, in s samples, the weight parameter β of single hidden layer neural (HUAWEI) network neuron connected to output layer:

WEIGHT PARAMETER β

The weight parameters:

$$\beta = H^T (I + HH^T)^{-1} [\theta_1, \dots, \theta_s]$$

are connected to output layer,

$$H = \begin{bmatrix} g(w_1\alpha_1 + b_1) & \dots & g(w_L\alpha_1 + b_L) \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ g(w_1\alpha_s + b_1) & \dots & g(w_L\alpha_s + b_L) \end{bmatrix}$$

COMPLETE TRAINING

The model function $\theta(\alpha)$ of single hidden layer neural network that completes training is expressed as

$$\theta(\alpha) = \sum_{i=1}^L \beta_i g(w_i\alpha + b_i)$$

Determining the Model Function $\theta(\alpha)$:

Where β_i = i th row of Matrix of Weight Parameter β .

CONTROL INCREMENT

The **control increment $\Delta u(k)$** single hidden layer recursive neural network algorithm

of time k to $k+N-1$ is determined according to formula:

$$\Delta \bar{u}(k) = [\Delta u(k); \dots; \Delta u(k + N - 1)]$$

$$\frac{d}{dt} \Delta u = -W \Delta u - p - \lambda \sum \nabla \max(0, [E \Delta u - b; \Delta u - \Delta u_{\max}; -\Delta u + \Delta u_{\min}])^2$$

CONTROL VARIABLE

The control variable from time $k-1$ to $k+N-2$:

$$\bar{u}(k-1) = [u(k-1); \dots; u(k + N - 2)]$$

Then, determine the control variable from time k to $k+N-1$:

$$\bar{u}(k) = u(k) + \Delta \bar{u}(k)$$

Finally, perform model prediction control.

EVIDENCE EXAMINATION: PROGRAMMABLE E-WALLET SYNAPSE-YUAN (NOT MONEY) (WI-FI) PROGRAMMABLE SYNAPSE (THE CRIMINALLY ACCURATE VERSION)

Programmable E-Wallet (NOT MONEY) Synapse-YUAN Model: China Chinese Group (Criminal Technical Analysis)

8.2. COMPUTER SYNAPSE-YUAN MODEL: PP BANK OF CHINA (NOT CHINA) (CRIMINALLY ACCURATE VERSION) CRIMINAL MODEL USING

UNDER DATA PROTECTION LAW: ('BODILY' 'BRAIN' CELLS: FUNCTION)

INTERNATIONAL LAW: CO-VAX CIRCUITRY ('FREQUENCY WAVE') GENOCIDE

FIN-(GER) TECH LAW: SPACE LAW

EEG SENSOR PRODUCTS TYPE

8.4. HUAWEI EEG MODEL:

8.4.1. HUAWEI MODEL: Neural Network Model Update Method And Device (YUAN PENG SERIES袁鹏) (DNN / CNN / RNN)

HUAWEI CNN DEFINITION

Huawei's definition of CNN or Convolutional Neural Network is a deep neural network with convolutional structure. The deep learning architecture refers to: (i) an algorithm updated through a neural network model (ii) feed-forward neural network. For instance, each neuron in the CNN feed-forward artificial neural network responds to an input image. FIG. 3 is a flow of the application of automatic machine learning to a neural network model.

HUAWEI DNN DEFINITION

Huawei's definition of Deep neural network (DNN) is multi-layer neural network i.e. NN with multiple hidden layers divided according to the positions of different layers namely, (i) input layer (ii) hidden layer (no. of layers) and output layer. The simple rule: Any neuron in the i-th layer must be connected to any neuron in the i+1th layer.

HUAWEI RNN DEFINITION

The RNN Recurrent Neural Networks aims to (in author's words) "make machines have memory capabilities" and 2. to process sequence (of any length) data: It is called recurrent neural network RNN because current output of sequence is related to previous output. It will memorize the previous information and apply it to the calculation of current output. Thus, nodes between hidden layer are no longer unconnected but connected. The input of hidden layer includes output of input layer and output of hidden layer (of the previous timeslot).

HUAWEI DEFINITION OF LOSS FUNCTION

The loss function is the 'objective function' used to measure difference between predicted value and targeted value. Thus, higher the output value (Loss) of loss function, the greater the difference, the training of deep neural network is a process of reducing this loss to a minimum amount.

HUAWEI DEFINITION OF BACKPROPAGATION ALGORITHM

The neural network uses:

the (1) backpropagation (BP) algorithm to modify the **size of parameters** in the neural network model during the training process so **reconstruction error loss** of neural network model becomes smaller.

(2) Forwarding the input signal to the output causes error loss (3) parameters in neural network model is updated by (4) backpropagating the error loss information 1. to converge error loss 2. To obtain optimal parameters of neural network model such as weight matrix.

(3) The convolutional layer 221 consists of many convolutional operators:

1. convolutional operator is called a kernel function is image processing equivalent to a filter that extracts specific information (from input image matrix).
2. Convolutional operator is essentially the weight matrix (pre-defined) which is one pixel after one pixel (or two pixels after two pixels) along horizontal direction.

The depth dimension of weight matrix and depth dimension of input image are equivalent.

The output of each weight matrix is stacked to form the depth dimension of convolutional (extends to enter entire depth of the) image.

HUAWEI FIG. 2 CONVOLUTIONAL NEURAL NETWORK (CNN)

CHIP CHINA = TERMINATED

COMPUTER BANK OF ENGLAND ('CHIP')

图 3

图 4

In the Huawei Patent, “Neural Network Model Update Method and Image Processing Method and Device”⁹¹, discloses a neural network update method which acquires (1) structure of neural network model (2) parameter of neural network model (3) training / trained neural network model

FIG. 3 is a diagram of a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) 200 that includes: (i) input layer 210 to obtain image to be processed (ii) pass the obtained image to be processed to the convolutional layer / pooling layer 220 and (iii) subsequent neural network layer 230 for processing, (iii) if evaluation result of trained neural network do not meet preconfigured condition, then update 2 items in the A. parameter and B. structure of neural network model until an evaluation result of updated neural network model meets preconfigured condition and preconfigured value.

Legal Analysis: Computer CHIP of Tier 1 showing resemblance is legal proof that it is NOT a ‘b’ but a CHIP. Due to the reference to the word ‘neural’ it refers to in-brain device (e.g. CO-VAX CHIP or WiFi = Wireless Fi-short for finance).

FIG. 9 HUAWEI NEURAL NETWORK MODEL USING (HYPER-) PARAMETERS

⁹¹ 张新雨, 袁鹏, 方慕园, 钟钊 (2022) Neural Network Model Update Method, and Image Processing Method and Device. WIPO Patent No. WO 2021/120719 A1. Available: <https://patents.google.com/patent/WO2021120719A1/en?q=WO2021120719A1>

FIG. 9 shows a method for updating a **neural network model** such as a **cloud service device** or **mobile terminal (server / computer with sufficient computing power)**.

910: Acquire the structure of the neural network model and related **parameters e.g. weights / bias**, includes: **hyper-parameters e.g.** 1. learning rate 2.a. weight decay coefficient 2.b. smooth coefficient 3. loss function and 4. evaluation method.

920: **Input training data** into the neural network model, perform processing and obtain a predicted **label** called 'PREDICTION TAG'.

921: **NN model** applied to image processing, training images and translating training images.

930: Determine **function value of a loss function** according to predicted **label (PREDICTION TAG)** of training data (**label**) and train the neural network model according to the 1. function value of the loss function, 2. Hyper-parameter of the Neural Network Model to acquire a 3. Trained Neural Network Model.

HUAWEI: TRAINED NEURAL NETWORK MODEL PROCEDURE

Train the neural network model based on: 1. **function value of the loss function** 2. **hyperparameter** of the **NN model** 3. to obtain a trained **neural network model** by **modifying parameters size** 4. corrected by the **error back propagation algorithm** 5. to make error loss smaller and smaller.

940: **Evaluation** method: Evaluate the result of trained neural network model that does not meet 1. the preset (meaning **PERP configured**) **condition**, (update 2. at least 2 items in the) the relevant (related) parameters and 3. + structure of the NN model are checked and updated 4. until the evaluation result (of updated neural network model) meets the preset (preconfigured) condition (value) and/or ('number') of updates.

For example, the evaluation index includes the target reasoning accuracy.

FIG. 10 ENVIRONMENTAL OBSERVATION / HISTORICAL INFO. STORAGE / N-AGENTS

图 10

FIG. 10 and 11 are alternate block diagrams for neural network models update. The HUAWEI **environmental** observation module is used 1. to collect / input environmental state information to 2. (one or multiple) Training inference module(s) (is the device for updating neural network model). The environmental state (status) information includes: 1. Training resource e.g. total number of training (and current available training) machines and 2. evaluation result of trained neural network model.

The HUAWEI **historical information** storage module is used: 1. to store / input historical information and 2. network state e.g. **probability distribution** of multiple candidate options: corresponding to each item 3. into the training reasoning module.

Multiple agents form multi-agent system (MAS) to jointly implement the update task: at least 2 items include one agent to update updating neural network model and one agent to update preprocessing method. FIG. 10 include N agents: each agent includes: A. environment state observation module (computer processor + storage memory) B. training reasoning module (computer processor + controller: for computation logic) C. output module (computer data output). In other words, the so-called N agents: are a set of computers with 'controller', 'memory storage' and 'processor'.

[COMPARE: SEE PPT 11](#)

[FIG. 11 MULTIPLE AGENT SYSTEM \(NNM UPDATE\)](#)

[JP MORGAN \(AGENT\)](#)

图 11

FIG. 11 shows neural network model update with exemplary three agents: agent 1 (update / output: preprocessing method), agent 2 (structure of neural network model) and agent 3 (update / output: loss function).

FIG. 12 MLP Long Short Term Memory LSTM

图 12

FIG. 12 is highly suspicious and obvious: it states “frequency of exchange of other agent information between ‘agents’ (computers ‘processors’, ‘controllers’, frequency transmission of data into ‘storage memory’).

1211: Input the 1. collected environmental state information 2. Historical related information 3. Other ‘Agent’ information A. spliced into a vector and B. input into a multilayered perceptron MLP network

1212: MLP network processes 1. environmental state information 2. Historical related information 3. Other ‘Agent’ information, A. obtains mapped vector B. enters into Long Short Term (LSTM) memory network.

1213: The LSTM network processes mapped vector to obtain ‘Feature Map’: output and input dimension of fully connected layer.

1214: The fully connected layers (in three agents) obtain **probability distribution** of their (output) actions, **probability distribution** of 1. Preprocessing method 2. Structure of Neural Network Model 3. loss function, according to ‘Feature Maps’.

1215: perform actions sampling according to **probability distribution** (of each **action** of three agents to obtain **output actions**): Agent 1. Preprocessing method (pie 1), Agent 2. Structure of (e.g. untrained) Neural Network Model (pie 2), Agent 3. loss function (pie 3).

Actions output by current (not terminated yet) Agent 1. Rep by discrete numerical values / set of actions output: $A = (1, 2, 3, \dots, N)$ and according to probability distribution set is $P = (P_1, P_2, P_3, \dots, P_N)$, where $N =$ positive integer, N rep. no. of actions selected by Agent 1.

1220: Evaluate the actions (Or strategies) output by three agents in environment: is strategy group pie = pie 1, pie 2, pie 3.

Preprocessing method (pie 1) + Structure of (untrained) Neural Network Model (pie 2) + loss function (pie 3) are applied to (dubious-TYPE) 'business' process. Training the structure (pie 2) of neural network model purpose is to modify **parameters** in structure (pie 2) of **neural network model** i.e. train neural network model to obtain trained neural network model. Evaluating actions output by the three agents refers to evaluating the performance of trained neural network model: e.g. inference accuracy, inference delay.

1230: Determination of whether updated result meets termination condition (NOT met), steps 1210 – 1220 repeated.

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FIN-(GER) TECH LAW: SPACE LAW

EEG SENSOR PRODUCTS TYPE

8.4. **HUAWEI EEG MODEL:**

8.4.2. HUAWEI MODEL: Identity Recognition Method and Device Based on Electroencephalogram Signal Method

(#Yuan Peng 袁鹏)

STEADY-STATE VISUAL EVOKED POTENTIAL SSVEP

The Huawei Patent, "Identity Recognition Method and Device Based on Electroencephalogram Signal"⁹² in FIG. 1 identity recognition method 100 and device 200 based on electroencephalogram signal.

The methodology: S110 determines a target stimulation frequency sequence (6 Hz to 100 Hz).

For example, FIG. 1 flow shows Method 100 for EEG-based identity recognition that requires authentication (with identity device installed in an interesting entity called: 'HUAWEI safe' (OR/AND, in my legal opinion: in-brain CO-VAX computing circuitry that has memory storage or a transmitter device that transmits data to cloud using HUAWEI frequency bandwidth satellite linked remotely programmable)

Method 100: determines target stimulation frequency sequence [f1, f2, f3 fn] where n is a positive integer.

If stimulation frequency [f1, f2, f3, ... fn] belongs to the initial (TARGET / PRE-SET) stimulation frequency sequence [f1, f2, f3, ... fn] set by (question: which user), the identification is passed.

HUAWEI SAFE IDENTIFICATION SYSTEM: BRAIN ELECTRICAL SIGNALS HZ AS TARGET STIMULATION SEQUENCE

To identify an EEG based signal, collecting / saving a user's EEG signal (is required) = as a pre-set EEG signal, in advance. Then, collecting the brain of the user to be detected when performing identity verification or identity recognition is carried out. The real brain electrical signals X (12, t), X (8, t) and X (20, t) are saved to the (HUAWEI) safe identification system. The user selects [12, 8, 20] Hz as the target stimulation sequence.

For example, when the user initializes the identification system, the user selects [12, 8, 20] Hz as the target stimulation sequence, and the real brain electrical signal X (12, t), X (8, t) and X (20, t) under three frequency stimulations are saved to the safe identification system.

When the user to be detected requests for identity authentication, the system requests the user to input the stimulation frequency sequence instruction and end it with the # key. If a user inputs a sequence of non-

⁹² 袁鹏, 薛希俊, 姚骏 (2017) Identity Recognition Method and Device Based on Electroencephalogram Signal. WIPO Patent No.: WO2017/201972A1. Available:

set frequency sizes e.g. [6, 12, 15 #] or enters a wrong sequence of [12, 20, 8#] or short of one [12, 8#], the sequence indicates that the user authentication failed and identification process ends.

Only the user that correctly inputs [12, 8, 20#] then will it indicates the identity of the user to be detected wrt stimulation frequency sequence input is successful and identity verification about SSVEP signal can be continued.

1. The electrical signal will compare the EEG signal with the saved preset EEG signal: If it matches, the preset (EEG SIGNAL), it is an indication that the user identity detected is correct, thus passing the identity verification.
2. If it does not match the preset (EEG SIGNAL), it is an indication that user identity errors are detected thus the authentication failed.

STEADY STATE VISUAL EVOKED POTENTIALS (SSVEP) SIGNAL

The EEG SIGNAL to be obtained for identity verification refers to: a Steady-State Visual Evoked Potentials (SSVEP) SIGNAL. The identity is (confirmed) 'identified' based on the SSVEP SIGNAL, induced by a stable periodic visual stimulus recorded in the occipital region of the human brain.

Compared to other EEG SIGNALS: such as Event Related Potentials (ERP) SIGNALS or Visual Evoked Potentials (VEP), THE SSVEP is more stable and has a higher signal-to-noise ratio.

It is necessary to determine the frequency of at least one visual stimulus: SSVEP signal is generated by a stable periodic visual stimulus (whether preset SSVEP signal input by user or detection), a stable cycle is required.

LEGAL ANALYSIS

SSVEP brain signals partially explains the simultaneously timed EVENT 201 GAMES NY and WUHAN MILITARY GAMES inserts a suspicious inaugural LED 8K PIXEL which projects 1. Image for visual stimulus SSVEP signal capture (in CO-VAX CHIP CHINESE and AMERICANS) in addition to 2. the global time step discussed earlier in the IBM-CHIP. Furthermore, LED 8K PIXEL is a 3. (frequency) beam function that is connected to WiFi from cell tower and space satellite remotely programmable (i.e. 'programmatic approach' in WB document).

120 displays for the user (to be detected): n-segment stimulation signal corresponding to the target stimulation frequency sequence [f1, f2, f3, ... fn].

为待检测用户显示该目标刺激频率序列 $[f_1, f_2, f_3, \dots, f_n]$ 对应的 n 段刺激信号, 该 n 段刺激信号中第 i 段刺激信号的显示频率为该目标刺激频率序列 $[f_1, f_2, f_3, \dots, f_n]$ 中第 i 个频率 f_i

S120

The display frequency of the i -th stimulation signal (in the n -segment stimulation signal) is = The target i -th stimulus frequency sequence $[f_1, f_2, f_3, \dots, f_n]$ with i -th frequency with f_i where i is $1, 2, 3 \dots n$.

130 acquires n -stage steady-state visual evoked potential (SSVEP) signal generated by the user to be detected due to the n -segment stimulation signal.

获取该待检测用户由于该 n 段刺激信号产生的 n 段稳态视觉诱发电位SSVEP信号

S130

For example, the first segment of the stimulation signal is displayed at a frequency of f_1 for a period of time, and then the second segment of the stimulation signal is displayed for a period of time at a frequency of f_2 and the third segment of the stimulation signal is displayed for a period of time at a frequency of f_3 until the n th segment stimulation signal is displayed at a frequency of f_n for a period of time and then a corresponding n -segment SSVEP signal generated by the user to be detected according to n -segment signal.

Thus, the display frequency of the i -th segment stimulation signals in the n -segment stimulation signals is the target stimulation frequency sequence $[f_1, f_2, \dots, i$ -th frequency.

当该 n 段SSVEP信号与 n 段预设SSVEP信号的相似度大于或等于阈值时, 确定该待检测用户身份正确; 当该 n 段SSVEP信号与该 n 段预设SSVEP信号的相似度小于该阈值时, 确定该待检测用户身份错误

S140

140 determination of user identity is dependent upon similarity between n -segment of SSVEP signals and n -segment preset SSVEP segments: For example, if preset SSVEP signals is greater than or equal to a threshold, the identity of the user is determined to be correct.

FREQUENCY OF STIMULATION SIGNAL

For the collected n-segment SSVEP signals, each collected n-segment SSVEP signal corresponds to a frequency of a stimulation signal i.e. i-th SSVEP signal can be represented as $X_i(f_i, T_i)$

f_i represents the i-th SSVEP signal obtained according to the stimulation signal whose:

Display frequency = f_i

TARGET STIMULATION FREQUENCY SEQUENCE: SSVEP n-SEGMENT

the target stimulation frequency sequence = $[f_1, f_2, f_3, \dots, f_n]$ corresponds to the SSVEP signal X_1 of the n-segment.

PRESET n-SEGMENT SSVEP SIGNAL

Pre-set SSVEP signal set by the user in advance is expressed as $X'_i(f_i, T_i)$ i.e. the Target Stimulation Frequency sequence $[f_1, f_2, f_3, \dots, f_n]$ corresponds to n segments of pre-set SSVEP signals $X'_1(f_1, T_1)$ $X'_2(f_2, T_2)$... $X'_n(f_n, T_n)$.

TIME DOMAIN CORRELATION COEFFICIENT

Identity recognition is determined by calculating:

Similarity / correlation coefficient between the n-segment SSVEP signal and the n-segment pre-set SSVEP signal can be calculated by time domain angle:

Time domain correlation coefficient $r_x(f_i)$ of i-th SSVEP signal $X_i(f_i, T_i)$ and i-th segment pre-set SSVEP signal $X'_i(f_i, T_i)$.

LINEAR CORRELATION COEFFICIENT

The correlation coefficient can be a linear e.g. Pearson linear correlation coefficient to measure the degree of similarity between input signal and real user signal. The correlation coefficient will only be larger when the input SSVEP signal is the real user's own EEG signal. For instance, a given same stimulation frequency, differences in e.g. physiological structure of the brain / visual pathway delay / spectral response of the visual systems leads to large differences between SSVEP signals induced.

TRANSFORM DOMAIN ANGLE: T DOMAIN / F-DOMAIN

The transform domain correlation coefficient of n-segment SSVEP signal and n-segment preset SSVEP signal is calculated by transforming the domain angle.

The acquired SSVEP signal is = a plurality of electrodes, $X_i(f_i, T_i)$ or $X'_i(f_i, T_i)$ which can be a matrix. So, $X_i(f_i, T_i)$ or $X'_i(f_i, T_i)$ can be reduced to one-dimensional (classical data dimension reduction methods: **Principal Component Analysis PCA** or **Canonical Correlation Analysis CCA**, Time domain signal).

The transform domain refers to other domains different from the Time Domain (T domain) for example, frequency domain is F domain etc.

FOURIER ALGORITHM TRANSFORMS

For instance, the i -th (Time domain) SSVEP signal $X_i(f_i, T_i)$ in the n -segment SSVEP signal (is) transformed into the transform domain by an algorithm to obtain $Z_i(f_i, Y_i)$.

For example, the SSVEP signal $X_i(f_i)$ is obtained by the Fourier algorithm T_i transforms into the **frequency domain** and obtains $Z_i(f_i, F_i)$.

For example, the SSVEP signal $X_i(f_i, t)$ can be transformed into the **frequency domain** by the Fast Fourier algorithm to obtain another $Z_i(f_i, F_i)$

For example, the SSVEP signal $X_i(f_i, t)$ is transformed into the S domain by the **Laplace algorithm** to obtain $Z_i(f_i, S_i)$.

SUM-UP

Therefore, the method for EEG signal identification is based on: (i) the displaying of a stimulus signal for the user according to the target stimulation frequency sequence and (ii) collecting the SSVEP signal generated by the user.

Then, compare the SSVEP signal with the preset SSVEP signal.

LEGAL ANALYSIS

The SSVEP signal is primarily concentrated in the human occipital region, requiring only a few electrodes (such as in my legal opinion: CO-VAX CHIPPED POP-100+). One electrode can collect a rich amount of information signals. The SSVEP signal is a primary visual cortex inducing signal that does not require participation of human advanced cognitive activities (thus, unaffected by human mental state).

The signal comprises of (i) amplitude frequency response and (ii) phase frequency response of the SSVEP signal that correspond directly to the system physiological characteristics of the human primary visual cortex for (ILLEGAL) **identification**.

In order to use SSVEP signal for identification, SSVEP signal generated is required via a stable periodic visual stimulus to induce (at least one SSVEP frequency of one visual stimulus) SSVEP signals in the human brain.

For example, a dry electrode (or vaxx-chip in liquid form solidified circuitry, injected into) the user's occipital region to facilitate acquisition of the user's SSVEP signal induced in the user's cerebral occipital region by looking at the stimulation signal with his eyes and the collection of the SSVEP signals wirelessly transmitted to the corresponding signal analysis for processing.

EVIDENCE EXAMINATION: PROGRAMMABLE E-WALLET SYNAPSE-YUAN (NOT MONEY) (WI-FI) PROGRAMMABLE SYNAPSE (THE CRIMINALLY ACCURATE VERSION)

Programmable E-Wallet (NOT MONEY) Synapse-YUAN Model: China Chinese Group (Criminal Technical Analysis)

8.2. COMPUTER SYNAPSE-YUAN MODEL: PP BANK OF CHINA (NOT CHINA) (CRIMINALLY ACCURATE VERSION) CRIMINAL MODEL USING

UNDER DATA PROTECTION LAW: ('BODILY' 'BRAIN' CELLS: FUNCTION)

INTERNATIONAL LAW: CO-VAX CIRCUITRY ('FREQUENCY WAVE') GENOCIDE

FIN-(GER) TECH LAW: SPACE LAW

EEG SENSOR PRODUCTS TYPE

8.4. HUAWEI EEG MODEL:

8.4.2. HUAWEI MODEL: Visual Evoked Potential-Based Identity Verification Method and Device.(WO2017/201972

A1) (YUAN PENG SERIES袁鹏)

图 1

It is documented with evidence: MAC random number generator is the barcode CO-VAX injected. This Huawei Patent, “Visual Evoked Potential Based Identity Verification Method and Device”⁹³ for identifying an evoked potential based on visual evoked potential comprised of: (i) generating a user-supplied M-sequence stimulation signal to the user (ii) collecting the user-generated EEG signal (iii) correlation coefficient between the collected EEG signal and authenticated EEG signal (iv) the **authenticated electroencephalogram** signal of the user is an EEG signal generated by the user for the corresponding **M-sequence stimulus signal**; is a visual signal that changes in the form of M-sequence and **induces** the user to generate an EEG signal by stimulation for a certain period of time and obtaining the M-sequence stimulation signal corresponding to each shift EEG signal for identification (v) by **calculating the EEG signal** corresponding to each **acquired M-sequence stimulation signal**, the user’s **correlation coefficient** of the **EEG signal** is **verified**. The correlation coefficient calculated each time summed according to the **corresponding weight**. The correlation coefficient is the **degree of similarity** between the two signals measured. For example, if the correlation coefficient is greater than the matching coefficient threshold, the identity authentication passed.

Thus, FIG. 1 **M-sequence stimulus signal** 1. is used to cause the user to generate a specific electroencephalogram signal pattern, the 2. correlation coefficient between **acquired** electroencephalogram signal and **authentication** electroencephalogram signal of the user is used 3. to determine an **identity verification** result.

STIMULUS SUB-UNIT

Huawei states that the stimulation generation unit is an ‘electronic device’ that produces 1. a stimulus signal that changes in the form of M sequence 2. visualizes the display to the user (hypothetically and practically speaking, in-brain display),

SIGNAL ANALYSIS (CALCULATION) SUBUNIT

The signal analysis unit includes: 1. ‘processor’ that executes the computer to execute instruction for calculating collected EEG signal and user’s certified EEG signal.

2. ‘memory’ to store the computer execution instruction

3. The **signal analysis unit** is called the ‘**calculation sub-unit**’ which means computation logic (function / instruction). It calculates the correlation coefficient between collected EEG signal and user’s certified EEG signal (VAX-CERT WEF).

⁹³ 袁鹏, 薛希俊, 姚骏 (2018) Visual Evoked Potential Based Identity Verification Method and Device. WIPO Patent No. WO 2018/112799 A1. Available: <https://patents.google.com/patent/WO2018112799A1/en?q=WO+2018%2f112799+A1>

The correlation coefficient determines whether greater than matching coefficient threshold, then identity authentication passes. The identification device include: input/output (sounds like a transmission device i.e. CO-VAX CHIPPED transmitter) unit for 1. **receiving T-digits sequentially input** by user then 2. generates **M-sequence stimulation** signal (corresponds to user) 3. The processor further configured to determine the **input T-numbers**. The input order is the same as shift number and shift order of the T-time shift.

Using the sequence of the number of shifts of the M-sequence stimulus signal (corresponds to user), as the password input by user (using the identification system), the input/output unit receives password input by user. Upon the sequence of shift number input by user verified correct, the user enters subsequent identification process.

AUTHENTICATION SUB-UNIT

The 4. **authentication subunit** is configured (computation logic) to decipher whether the correlation coefficient is greater than a matching **coefficient threshold**, then identity authentication passed. If not, the identity authentication fails.

It is documented that CO-VAX CHIPPED circuitry is an electronic device, in fact, a transmitter, an LED beam display and MAC random number generator.

T-TIME SHIFT

Huawei states that the M-sequence stimulation signal corresponding (meaning frequency logged unto) user is obtained: by performing T-time shift on the original M-sequence stimulation signal (length of: N) when $0 < T < N-1$

It is documented a worldwide express 5G ban in conjunction with courtroom judgments on T-Mobile U.S.A. NASDAQ / I-T-Systems European Gateway / Sprint (Tech BIS duped pilot tested NY banks), this Huawei section on T-shift is of importance.

Huawei:

1. K_i of the shift of the T-ith shift in the T shift and $0 < K_i < N-1$, the M-sequence stimulus generating unit (used for the original M sequence stimulation signal) sequentially shifts K_i to generate T-th M-sequence stimulation signal.
2. Using T-th M-sequence stimulation signal to stimulate the user, the signal acquisition unit includes sub-unit for collecting user's stimulation for M-sequence.

INTERCEPT SUBUNIT

The EEG signal generated by the signal: The intercepting subunit is configured: to intercept 1. the **acquired** EEG signal according 2. to stimulation sequence of the **M-sequence stimulation signal** of the T-shift and 3. obtain the EEG corresponding to M-sequence stimulation signal per signal shift.

The stimulation generating unit is configured 1. to generate a synchronization signal when starting to stimulate the user with the **M-th order stimulation** signal of the T-ith shift. Then, the intercepting sub-unit is used for 2. the collected brain electrical signal intercepted according to the synchronization sequence of the M-sequence stimulation signal of the T-shift. Finally, the 3. EEG signal corresponding to the M-sequence stimulation signal of each shift is obtained.

WEIGHT MANAGEMENT SUB-UNIT

The weight management sub-unit is configured to influence the accuracy of the user's identification based on 1. **correlation coefficient** between: **EEG signal** corresponding to A. **M-sequence stimulus signal** (acquired) and B. authenticated EEG signal. Then adjusting the weight of correlation coefficient that corresponds: to the EEG signal that corresponds to M-sequence stimulation signal of each (T-)shift.

KEY AUTHENTICATION SUB-UNIT

The identity identification (CO-VAX Electronic) device includes: key authentication unit configured 1. to receive T-digits sequentially (USER INPUT) 2. determine the input T-digits and input sequence and 3. generate user-supplied M-sequence stimulation signal to stimulate the user.

To conclude, the M-sequence stimulus signal is used to induce a user to generate a specific mode (pattern) of EEG signals, calculate the collected EEG signals and the user's certified EEG signals and the correlation coefficients for identification results.

EVIDENCE EXAMINATION: PROGRAMMABLE E-WALLET SYNAPSE-YUAN (NOT MONEY) (WI-FI) PROGRAMMABLE SYNAPSE (THE CRIMINALLY ACCURATE VERSION)

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INTERNATIONAL LAW: CO-VAX CIRCUITRY ('FREQUENCY WAVE') GENOCIDE

FIN-(GER) TECH LAW: SPACE LAW

NEUROMORPHIC PRODUCTS TYPE

8.5. ALIPAY NEURAL NETWORK MODEL:

8.5.1 ALIPAY MODEL: Target Recognition and Neural Network Model Processing Method Based on Image (WO2017/201972 A1) (JING DA KAI 金达开)

In this Alipay Patent, “Target Recognition and Neural Network Model Processing Method Based on Image”⁹⁴, the medical image refers to an reflecting the internal structure or internal function of an anatomical region presented in two-dimensional pixels (2D) or three-dimensional voxels (3D) obtained from a variety of medical images such as: Angiography, Angiogram (Cardiac Angiography), Computed Tomography CT (computerized Tomography), Positron Emission Tomography PET (is Nuclear Medicine Imaging technique), Nuclear Magnetic Resonance Imaging NMRI (to detect emitted electromagnetic wave by externally applied gradient magnetic field), Medical Ultrasound CT (UCT) Examination (Medical Ultrasonography), gamma-ray (gamma-CT).

Angiogram involves usage of x-ray CT and adopted rays: (i) to irradiate the insides of the human body to observe blood vessels distribution (ii) rapidly inject **contrast agent** into **heart cavity** or **blood vessel** through **cardiac catheter**: to make heart and blood vessel cavity develop under X-ray irradiation.

Positron Emission Tomography PET is a **nuclear medicine** imaging technique that provides: (1) 3D and (2) functionally functioning images of the whole body.

Nuclear Magnetic Resonance Imaging NMRI is the detection of **emitted electromagnetic** wave by externally applied **gradient magnetic field** thus drawing internal structure of the human body.

Medical Ultrasonic Examination is a non-invasive examination mode for judging: physical Characteristics, morphological structure and functional state of human soft tissues (by utilizing Physical Characteristics of Ultrasonic waves: transmitting, receiving and converting the Ultrasonic waves and rapidly analyzing, processing and visualizing the Ultrasonic waves by an electronic engineering technology).

⁹⁴ 郭大洲, 金达开, 吕乐, 王普阳, 闫轲, 周靖人, 吉张鹤轩 (2023) *Target Recognition and Neural Network Model Processing Method Based on Image*. United States Patent Office. Patent No. CN 116167990A. Available: <https://patents.google.com/patent/CN116167990A/en?q=CN+116167990A>

ALIPAY FIG. 1: WHOLE BODY MEDICAL IMAGE CT SCAN IN DATA SET FOR TRAINING SET

图1

The whole-body medical image data sample includes conventional diagnostic CT scan of 1204 different body parts, includes 103 marked whole-body organs (26 main organs, 59 bone instances, 10 muscles, and 8 blood vessels) in total. Post-deleting the face class (privacy) medical image samples in the dataset is used as training set and verification set according to ratio 4:1.

The execution body refers to (an application / service / functional module): e.g. in s/w form, VM ('Virtual Machine'), cloud server, h/w device (e.g. server, or terminal device), h/w chip (e.g. CPU, GPU, FPGA, NPU, AI accelerator card or DPU) with a data processing function.

CLOUD COMPUTING PLATFORM

The device for organ recognition (medical image) deployed on computing device of an application side provides a corresponding service or (1) cloud computing platform e.g. computing power, storage and network resources (2) mode of externally providing service by cloud computing platform e.g. IaaS (Infrastructure as a Service), PaaS (Platform as a Service), SaaS (Software as a Service) or DaaS (Data as a service). Under SaaS, for example, the cloud computing platform (1) utilizes its own computing resources to provide **training** of a model or (2) deploy an image-based **target recognition** device (3) medical image **organ recognition** device and (4) **specific application** architecture.

LEGAL ANALYSIS

ALIPAY FIG. 2: IMAGE-BASED OBJECT ('ORGAN') RECOGNITION

图2

SEE SEPARATE JUDGMENT BRIEFING PAPER ON illegal-indians nano-BW-INDIA-(CRIMINAL TECHNICAL ANALYSIS & EVIDENCE-BASED, BIO-MEDICINE LAW & PHARMACEUTICAL MEDI-CRIME LAW)

FIG. 2 of the Alipay Model provides an image-based (meaning Organ) recognition method (UNDER BIO-MEDICINE LAW e.g. Organ Transplantation Sale / Tissues etc).

In step S201, an encoder inside the Neural Network Model is trained for feature extraction (Of a plurality of targets meaning at least one organ of a biological object) invoked, to extract full-scale feature data of the image to be recognized or feature extraction of all targets i.e. all organs in the whole body region (of the human body contained in the medical image). Identification refers to marking (e.g. shape, size, position, environment) and further identification refers to target organ damage (e.g. lesion, lesion type, severity, stage of development etc).

ALIPAY STIMULATING BRAIN NERVE: NEURONS PROCESSOR

The 'application' has capability of adopting a Neural Network Model i.e. information processing system: realizes intelligent activity function of the human brain by simulating brain **nerve** structure formed by a large number of simple processing units called neurons connected to each other with capabilities of large-scale parallel, distributed storage and processing ('processor'), with emphasis on "self-organization / self-adaption / self-learning" for target (organs) recognition on image recognition. Alipay obtained its Neural

Network Model for its application through pre-training e.g. 'organs' as objects identification in medical images.

ALIPAY NETWORK STRUCTURES (/ MODEL)

Network structures are used (unlimited): (1) Radial Basis (RBF – Radial Basis Fuctio) Neural Network (2) PERCEPTRON Neural Networks, (3) Linear Neural Networks, (4) Self-Organizing Neural Networks, (5) Feedback Neural Networks, etc.

(1) Radial Basis (RBF – Radial Basis Fuctio) Neural Network: is 3-layer feedfwd network with a single hidden layer, which simulates A. the Neural Network Structure of Local Adjustment and B. mutual coverage of receiving domains (or receptive fields) in the human brain [is a local approximation network / Can approximate any continuous function with any precision, and is suitable for solving classification problem]

(2) SENSOR Neural Networks: is a neural network with single-layer calculations neurons. The **transfer function** of network is a **linear threshold** unit and is mainly used for simulating the PERCEPTION characteristics of the human brain.

Only two values can be output due to the fact that the **threshold unit** is adopted as the transfer function, so the **sensor neural network** is suitable for the problem of simple mode classification.

(3) Linear Neural Networks: composed of **one or more linear neurons** and only process **linear mapping** relation of reaction input / output sample vector space. In other words, it can only process linear separable problems by adopting a linear function as a **transfer function**.

(4) Self-Organizing Neural Networks: comprises of a. self-organizing **competition** network, b. self-organizing **feature mapping** network, c. learning **vector quantization** network and other network structure forms.

ALIPAY INPUT SIGNALS

The neural network **adaptively** learn the characteristics of **input signals** and then self-organize into different areas with different response characteristics to input modes (in each area).

ALIPAY OUTPUT SIGNALS

In the output space, the neurons form a map which (1) functionally identical neurons are closer together and (2) functionally different neurons are farther apart.

ALIPAY COMPETITION LEARNING

The self-organizing mapping process is completed through competition learning which refers to the process that (1) neurons in the **same layer** compete with each other, and (2) neurons in competition win, modify the connection weight connected with the neurons, so that the **self-organizing mapping process** is an unsupervised learning method.

ALIPAY COMPUTER MACHINE LEARNING PROCESSING

In the learning process, only a (1) few learning samples are provided for the network without providing ideal target output and (2) the network performs **self-organizing mapping** based on input samples' characteristics. Thus, the samples are automatically ordered and classified.

In the network structure, the feedback neural network transmits information in **forward direction** and transmits information in **reverse direction**.

The feedback of information occurs between A. **different network layers** or can be B. **limited to** neurons of a **certain layer**.

Only if the **stable condition** is met: feedback network belongs to a dynamic network, the network reaches a stable state after a **period** of operation only.

ALIPAY ENCODER

The encoder is an **APPLICATION module** for extracting image features in an **input** neural network model and **extract full-scale** feature data of medical images identified, wherein encoder (in a **trained** Neural Network Model) is commonly used for **feature extraction** of the **whole body region** of human body in medical images, and the encoder suitable for **feature extraction** of the **whole body region** obtained by training, using **whole body medical image** data set, so that feature data of extracted medical images recorded as full-scale feature data.

The encoder can **extract enough features** on targets ('organs') in the image to be **identified**: to meet the (1) requirements of a plurality of decoders for **identifying different area ranges** on feature data, meaning there's no need to retrain the encoder when a new decoder is added. This enables the **target range** to be identified by Neural Network Model to be wider with expandability.

For example, the encoder extracts (1) full-scale feature data of medical image sample in data set one by one from total segment data set, then (2) uses feature data input to the first decoder by encoder and (3) organ recognition result marked in the medical image sample (in the total segment data set: to train organ recognition capability of decoder i.e. feature data output by encoder = input of decoder which calculates by using input feature data) (4) further **recognizes** the **marked organ** in medical image sample, uses the organ recognition **result marked** in the medical image sample in the training to **verify** the **accuracy** of decoder recognition result, (5) continuously adjusts the **network parameters** of decoder to achieve better recognition effect.

The encoder include: a **plurality of encoding** units, each correspondingly **extract feature data** within a range of partial area, then a sum of feature data extracted by all encoding units used (as feature data of all areas) and if **plurality of encoding** units **execute action** of **feature data extraction** in parallel, the **extraction efficiency** of feature data further **improved**.

ALIPAY INPUT TO PLURALITY OF DECODERS

In step S202, at least part of the **full-scale feature data** is **input** to a **plurality of decoders** (in the Neural Network Model) and a **target identification** result of corresponding decoder is obtained, and **different decoders** identify **different target** types. Since plurality of decoders are used for identifying different target types, each decoder is a **dedicated** decoder for **identifying** certain **part of targets e.g. organs**.

ALIPAY DECODER PLATFORM

The Decoder is a module for identifying a corresponding target based image feature extract by Encoder in a neural network model. For example, the Decode performs further **processing** and **recognition** on **feature data** in target medical image obtained from the Encoder that: predicts position, shape size, and (clearly stated in Alipay) 'corresponding organ' based on content represented by 'features data' or 'organ features' data **within range of corresponding body region** learned in advance and obtain the **corresponding organ recognition** result.

ALIPAY PARTIAL DECODER

The obtained full-scale feature data is **partially or fully input** into the decoder and since partial **decoder** is used only for **identifying** a partial **target**, e.g. divide **organ** of a partial body region, **ONLY** corresponding **region** or ('organ') feature data that **exceeds** the **region** can be **input**. The amount of data depends on the overlap ratio of range of region that **decoder** can **identify** and **range of region** displayed in the image identified.

ALIPAY TARGET TYPES: ORGAN

The so-called 'target' types corresponds to (based on the identification of different decoders) medical images i.e. (2) the **range of body area corresponds** to the **identification of different decoders**: For example, the body is divided into several different regions by dividing body region of the human body (in the 'medical image'). Then, the decoder is used to perform organ recognition to 'correct' error of region of organ generated by decoder.

(3) **identification range preset** to 'needs': to **reduce** the **number of feature data** processed by single decoder.

When the decoder is trained, the (4) **image sample set** in range of area is used for **training**, so identification result of decoder is more accurate.

For example, the abdominal organ is recognized as an organ with a certain head shape, so as to further improve organ recognition accuracy.

ALIPAY (IBM-TYPE) TARGET ANALYZER / IMAGE RECOGNITION

The first region range corresponds to different regions types obtained by performing A. region recognition on image to be recognized and B. local feature data (corresponds to the first region range used, as the partial full-quantity feature data as input into a plurality of decoders in the Neural Network Model, so that the target recognition result of the decoders obtained).

ALIPAY INPUT CHARACTERISTIC DATA

The (range of) input characteristic data is determined according to: A. target types identified by different decoders B. Range of body area identified by different decoders. (This is to reduce the quantity of characteristic data processed by a single decoder.) Then, the medical image sample set in a certain body area range is used for training when decoder is trained so that identification result of decoder is more accurate.

There are decoders for identifying all organs of the whole body region e.g. abdomen and overlap of organ ranges identifiable between different decoders e.g. decoder for identifying head and neck organs. For example, decoder B for identifying oesophageal (oesophagus) and thoracic organs.

Different decoders trained using different data sets, first decoder trained using first set of image samples e.g. using total segment data set, second set of image samples used e.g. using head neck organ data set, third decoder trained using e.g. chest organ data set, fourth decoder trained using dedicated esophageal cancer data set. The training process entails: encoder (1) **extraction** of **full-scale feature data** of medical image sample in the data set, one by one, from **total segment data** set, (2) use **feature data input** to first decoder by encoder, (3) **organ recognition** result *marked* in **medical image** sample in **total segment data** set, to **train** organ recognition **capability** of decoder (4) the **feature data output** by encoder = input of decoder, the **decoder calculates** by using input feature data, further **recognizes marked organ** in the medical image sample, (5) uses **organ recognition** result **marked** in medical image sample in training to **verify accuracy** of decoder recognition result, and continuously adjusts the network parameters of decoder to achieve better recognition effect.

It is stated, that "If the number of decoders is infinitely increased, the complexity of model is arbitrarily updated, which leads to an explosion of parameters in the model".

ALIPAY TRAINING APPROACH: ALIPAY (IBM-TYPE) MACHINE TRAINING

The **nnUNet** backbone frame (**no-new-Net**: neural network backbone frame includes encoder and decoder) in 3D full resolution set-up / high resolution for accurate segmentation. Internal structure of partial images e.g. medical images is fixed regularly, object identified by low-resolution information. The nnUNet backbone combines low resolution information (object recognition) and high resolution (accurate segmentation positioning basis). Each coding unit in framework consist of successive operations: Convolution e.g. normalization, leak ReLU units (random correction linear units), Maximum pool operators. The **encoder trained** using total segment data set e.g. training period of 2000, 1000 iterations per period and 1000 training periods per internal data set, 250 iterations per period. The optimizer adopts polynomial learning rate strategy random gradient descent, and initial learning rate set 0.01. The Nesterov momentum extension of gradient descent optimization algorithm: 0.99. The feature data enhanced with default data enhancement function in nnUNet backbone framework e.g. perform horizontal flip on feature data, 10 degree random rotation in x-y plane, intensity scaling at ratio [0.74, 1.25], adding zero mean, gaussian noise with variance [0,0.1]. Thus, total average training time is 2.5 GPU days per 1000 cycles.

The **encoder trained** in the mode obtain deeper (medical) images, features, identify wider target ('organ') range, and when a new decoder is added, this enable the Neural Network Model to have expandability. Thus, the trained encoder is used as generic encoder for subsequent training of multiple decoders. For example, when training a **general encoder** for identifying medical images, auxiliary body part division task can be supplemented: **automatic body part regression algorithm** used to **label pixels** in human body into 4 categories (head neck, chest, abdomen, buttocks and thigh) i.e. obtained by **means of linear regression calculation** e.g. label body parts at different layers belonging to categories.

The generic encoder can explicitly identify the region location of each pixel in the image (Identified) or anatomical region location of each voxel (in the target medical image) facilitates the generic encoder to learn a more accurate representation of pixel or voxel.

ALIPAY FREEZING ENCODER PARAMETERS CORRESPONDING TO ENCODER

Prior to training the plurality of decoders for performing organ segmentation using the plurality of second medical image sample sets: Freezing part of encoder parameters corresponding to encoder.

After training the generic encoder and decoder using the old data set A, if the generic encoder and decoder are retrained using the new data set B, it is likely that the training will result in the entire neural network model forgetting to learn the knowledge obtained. Thus, at least some of the encoder parameters corresponding to the encoder may be frozen to obtain a model that can be continuously learned prior to training a plurality of decoders for object recognition (using a plurality of second sets of image samples).

ALIPAY MEDICAL (2ND) IMAGE SEGMENTED INTO ORGANS

The second medical image sample set include: normal state and abnormal state. For example, the when a medical image is segmented into organs, the second set of medical image samples used include: one-healthy state and one-lesions.

Here a reasonable sample of Whole Body Image Scan (prototype-Old) LED Pixel E-Cashier Counter:

MCBRIDGE (CO-VAX CHIP IN-BRAIN: ALMOST BODY SCAN – SAMPLE ONLY)

ALI-(ANY-FED-FAST-)PAY SUPERMARKET THEFT E-CASHIER LED COUNTER: WHOLE BODY IMAGE SCAN

M-BRIDGE DIAGRAM

DIY PIXEL FULL BODY SCAN CO-VAX CHIP - SS (ALIPAY)

Several legal points behind this Whole Body Image Scan (prototype-Old) LED Pixel E-Cashier Counter:

1. PERP-ID figures that as sub-point (to main criminal point: no need for any 'gov' once e-cashier e.g. 13-States America with a e-cashier base (automated by any computer-Tom EVEN outside of USA) in San Jose / Washington D.C. etc): For instance, space-binary code (is BAR-glyph means 'big-snake' space-CODE) via satellite scan in-brain CO-VAX CHIP.

2. There is no need to sell food if PERP of all E-Cashier counters e.g. 1. Illegal container Tier 2 'b' etc can PRESS: 000,000,000 or 2a. LED Pixel encouraged (using s/w programmable) Wal-Mart to twitch their numbers OR 2b. 'pretend' to let illegal Tier 2 'b' steal % off per groceries OR 3. 'ride-off' the largest F&B per transactions e.g. 'wave' WiFi = Wire-less Finance manufactured chip card progressed to 4. CO-VAX CHIP in-brain. (There was a case that entire populations were starved to death.)

In conjunction with m-Bridge discussed in EMV, there exists drawings of CO-VAX CHIP in-brain graphical ID of entire state / city (hence perhaps the world cities scam by global blacklist Indian 'Thiru' sharing with 'Indranee rajah').

Furthermore, no one knows who is 'Ali-Pay': could be Malaysian Indian-Muslim that does programming of LED Pixel s/w or he could be computer-Tom infiltrate replicated Pay-Gang LED Pixel s/w format (steal some electronic digits) etc. It is a programmable s/w APP with satellite log-on by computer-tom. It is NOT a legitimate entity that ensures every human being has sufficient food.

INSERT PHOTO: SUPERMARKET #1, #2 % THEFT off GROCERIES (Physical-'b' manufactured 'Wave' chip card: NFC WiFi-CO-VAX Micro-Chipped, Satellite-b / e-b)

SCENARIO ONLY: ALL-(ANY-FED-FAST-)PAY SUPERMARKET THEFT: WHOLE BODY IMAGE SCAN E-CASHIER LED COUNTER

M-BRIDGE DIAGRAM

1. Largest SUPER-MART CHAIN STORES WORLDWIDE (PERP knows largest SUPERMART based: No. of Chain-Stores and Size of Supermarket / volume of food supplies): to commit Pixel Scan Micro-Chip (CO-VAX CHIP: RF KILL)
2. E-Cashier Theft: For example, software programmable E-cashier theft just by pressing: 000 (Thus, motive to be complicit as it has become pointless to sell food for money when PERP-F&B Supermarket can just press: 000)

SUPERMART 1:

Rows of E-Cashier Programmable Software (with Ali-PAY+: E-b, Satellite-b, NFC Scan Micro-chip): Here: Scanned (CO-VAX CHIPPED chip-transmitter: RF Data Transmission) customer checked receipt

Rows of E-Cashier Programmable Software (with Ali-PAY+: E-b, Satellite-b, NFC Scan Micro-chip): Here: Scanned customer scanning process (CO-VAX CHIPPED himself and food item)

Rows of E-Cashier Programmable Software (with Ali-PAY+: E-b, Satellite-b, NFC Scan Micro-chip): Here: barcode scan customer (himself and food item) (overhead: scan CCTV, is possible if installed)

SUPERMART 2:

Rows of E-Cashier Programmable Software (with Ali-PAY+: E-b, Satellite-b, NFC Scan Micro-chip): Here: Scanned customer scanning process (CO-VAX CHIPPED himself and food item)

Micro-Chip scan RF Kill (data transmission CO-VAX chip-transmitter + scanned item): TERMINATED

SUPERMART Theft Programmable Software E-cashier (A) (Indians Trespassers X 60 Y: World Cities' Theft Example: Indraneer Rajah)

1. Largest SUPER-MART CHAIN STORES WORLDWIDE (PERP knows largest SUPERMART based: No. of Chain-Stores and Size of Supermarket / volume of food supplies): to commit Pixel Scan Micro-Chip (CO-VAX CHIP: RF KILL)
2. E-Cashier Theft: For example, software programmable E-cashier theft just by pressing: 000 (Thus, motive to be complicit as it has become pointless to sell food for money when PERP-F&B Supermarket can just press: 000)
3. If PERP intent to commit: additional criminal evidence of traffick e.g. Indians committed = TERMINATED.

Micro-Chip scan RF Kill (data transmission CO-VAX chip-transmitter + scanned item):

SUPERMART Theft **Programmable Software E-cashier** (B) (Indians Trespassers X 60 Y: World Cities' Theft Example: Indranee Rajah)

Micro-Chip scan RF Kill (data transmission CO-VAX chip-transmitter + scanned item): TERMINATED PLOTS (REVERSE RF-KILL on 'GLOBAL' 'FIN-Thieves' PERP offsprings: Land War Declaration)

RENTAL (ABOLISHMENT) X COMPUTE 60 (DISTRICT-BY-DISTRICT)	STASH	SUPERMARKET CHAIN-TERMINATION: RF- (S/W PRESS: 000) RET. LANDED + VEG FARMLAND + TEMPLE: NO CHIP- CLOUD-PORTS
--	-------	--

	<p>Ret. Sheng Siong building rental stash (abolished + computation expert islandwide on rental stash x 60 in addition to my checking: x 60) stash illegal malaysians = (rf scanner chain = reassessed) eliminate 1 sewing + 1 cleaner x2 (like pick fights, attack, put half indian wear color, many rental stash ringgit-but have put illegal indian rajaratnam) = illegal recruits.</p> <p>another subordinate expert for diffusion system stacking 'oc' unto landed (applicable to other stacking 'oc' states) conmen cheat money</p> <p>no claim over 'phoenix' cn 'hk include ports + all illegal 'A' Ita-mpa compute etc.</p>
	<p>MALAYSIAN-SET-UP: LOCATION, HORSE-PP-EVACUATE</p>
	<p>include diffusion of horse-atm-pap x 60 conmen Malaysian gov set-up place for them-chinese-pap-HORSE-ATM stay = ret. landed district by district 1965 satellite controller = also contact me whether funded by phoenix-star x 60 + whether can do diffusion (cannot stacked) Malaysia big = many ports.</p>
	<p>INDIAN GOV-SET-UP: CLAIM PIECE INDIA-LAND</p>
	<p>diffusion of illegal indians x 60 = india gov If INDIAN GOV set-up place: all ILLEGAL INDIANS x 60 (shoeboxes priority + pap-unapproved un + rajanaratm + ringgit-nu's' etc) go over landed. + report worldwide on their status.</p> <p>ILLEGAL PAXS ENTRY X 60 APPROVED BY ATM-CONMEN = TEMASEK PLS RET. ALL INDIANS X 60 OFF PHOENIX 1ST (include half, trace indian, those publicly malay speaking chinese = not phoenix islanders)</p> <p>those like fabricated-malay false aboriginal = pls ret., those illegal traffick likes to sit with indians = ret. india with them = factories office buildings relocate (stash not phoenix-take but use name + land + take-up space x 60 compute</p> <p>(include rajaratnam headed) cannot involved in phoenix-land = tiger is usa-13 (entire migrated alternate populations) not (n never be) equated with x2 illegal Indians wearing red t-shirt = = indians, indian trace classified india-land (ETERNAL = duration) belong to india-land</p> <p>no one ('party' self-title official conmen 'businessmen' rental stash etc ATM-TOM CONMEN = no one = ID-PERP signature which guy which country) (cannot use any 1-nationality no approval entering = not function of begin with just conmen stealing money with no claim over anything) today using indo-(chinese face no approval I do not know never interview x 60 full illegal paxs no approval)</p> <p>wrong insert-put indian = no approval (ret. district by district landed + farm + temple + exotic etc) no nobody approved HIMSELF-thieves-commercial-ATM & ILLEGAL INDIANS by any land (no ne-sians knew about this indian = so they could not approval) basically stalking me (which perceive Ringgit-whole island as criminals conmen owe money using CCTV also require computation money collection becoz used to rob</p> <p>no other nations will spare them (include whole of asia) south-phoenix east-dragons (pre-med ILLEGAL INDIANS stacking 'oc' x 60 illegal summon</p>

	nations) south-east global asia (no india-land). (malaysians cannot spare = still speak malay ret. Malaysia + add illegal indians x 60 = then malaysians ret. with indians to india. (indians in india not malay speaking: POINT can speak indian, r classified india x 60 - ETERNAL duration)
	TEMASEK
	TEMASEK also owe alot of money = upload ID + basic amt discussion, if ok with all glyph states = go ahead (if nations satellite controller = actually want diffuse indians off phoenix star + consider compute ATM for that state inside white states, there's glyph) the whole world chinese = only malaysians use indians (becoz think speak malay = means v big) = after thiru infra-'asia' with infra-chip genocide + chew Gek Khim theft \$90b co-vax 'research' + Halimah 90b etc = whole world know (chinese originally = land + farm + temple = no such thing illegal indians cement stacking) = cheat money (rajaratnam premed x 60 (waiting for day to genocide) EM LOGO military H.E. Organ damage ANTI-glyph grouped wrong label + BEYOND stacking cheat money chip-genocide PHOENIX-SOUTH + PLUS 3 DRAGONS PLOT
TEMASEK Medicorp HORSE-ATM-CONMEN-infocomm: chip-genocide	TEMASEK-dbs stacking ANTI-'oc' using illegal Indians x 60 + construction e.g. cement + transport Indians 1-location + self-title buildings (over robbed land: ret. district-by-district) to rob
	at least granite: stacking dangerous, cannot charge money, landed per citizen (illegal not citizen of any nation but ATM-conmen) 3. if all glyph states, ok, go ahead arrest ringgit-MalAySia + all Ringgit-'sg'-something illegal paxs x 60 = ret. money + arrest all illegal indians x 60
	WB, WT
	2. if all glyph states ok, go ahead x 60 theft amt = WT WB + all HIMSELF-'trading' HERSELF press: 000 = ret. keys
	FIN-ATM-CONMEN-'STATEMENT'
	1. require someone collect trillions from tharman s 1-sum can UOB = 600M KAMALA -HARRIS ATTEMPT = pass me, set-up
	SHELL
+ get rid of urself + airplanes from stalking daily	perp himself deleted shell but evidence is up: WWW https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=brZTLhOkBoI CHIP-genocide shots in-brain: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=nSQ6NymJ9qs (criminal methodology explained in WLC DOCTOR OF LAWS materials & evidence + pre-med plots BEYOND PHOENIX stacking 'oc' x 60 PLUS 3 DRAGONS etc x 100PLUS MILITARY EM LOGO (rajaratnam conmen x 60 using ILLEGAL INDIANS stacking ANTI-'oc') + HE ORGAN DAMAGE grouped ANTI-glyph wrong label DONT WHOLE WORLD JUST BOMB UK SHELL + RINGGIT-LEE RUBBER-pap x 60 + SLD NOW = NAPIER INVESTMENT ID UP (WITH ALL SHAREHOLDERS ATM-TOM UP OF RINGGIT-STACKING 'OC' OFFSPRINGS) + WIPE CLEAN INDIA + ALL INDIANS Shanmugam + Tharman + CAVINDER BULL DAVINDER SINGH + bala Vivian + rajaratnam chew Gek Khim etc = all u r ILLEGAL INDIANS inside phoenix x 60 = conmen = no claim over any land = need claim india-land evacuate ALL INDIANS shoeboxes now. shell so Good at genocide = y dont u wipe clean india. cease

	<p>operation completely. u can ask chew Gek Khim to press: 000 for u inside Malaysia, evict her + ringgit-'sg'-(something)-pap out of phoenix + flood-in since 1965 shoeboxes.</p>
	<p>PASTE 'SHELL LOGO' (electricity will always be FREE) with 'i-tron' etc RF chip genocide pre-med + Rajaratnam illegal Indians x 60 = behind trilateral 'rockefeller' + COPIED LOGO UN not authentic logo (= maybe arrest with TERMINATION just make statement of all bank a/c & why think he's a rocket (which land e.g. phoenix star base funding satellite- launches include space x + airbus thuraya + INMARSAT VIASAT HARRIS) = ret. keys (re-assign etc wWW reports 247 surveillance) SHELL location inside phoenix star = ret. keys (see what's going on inside computers)</p>
	<p>SBI CLUSTER</p>
	<p>required phoenix + glyph collection SBI money + cluster s/w upload www = funding ?</p> <p>(rush complete prior chip-genocide): I PICK relevant european to join.</p> <p>preferred to take-in glyph experts quota 1st (nordic will never equated with 1-stalking indian or color outfit: SUM UP nonsense criminal self-definition x 60)</p> <p>if fill 1-whole building using e.g. cement etc (over robbed phoenix no claim) filled with illegal-indians self-title building nordic = supposed close it = ret. keys. (question k-pin criminal indians intentionally = rapist indian)</p> <p>(small location, all pilots satellites funded from phoenix-star: all aircrafts ret. + computers ret. dbs-HORSE-ATM arrange: details of pilots crafts illegal-indians inside phoenix what doing inside bank x 60)</p>
	<p>I know white like this kind = to extort money = but only need PRESS: 000,</p> <p>imply x 2-illegal-indians (if lay claim to ILLEGAL INDIANS = have to transport to ur white location) when supposed ret. to india-land</p> <p>= never equated with migrant usa-13 tiger (Or any nordic) but if like to claim illegal indians with illegal malaysians-ATM over robbed phoenix</p> <p>= transport indians over (Love white states, dont like chinese, just place convenience over dislike of india).</p> <p>if shell to shell home (hv explain all crimes COMPUTE AMT)</p>
	<p>I know white like this kind = to extort money = but only need PRESS: 000, imply x 2-illegal-indians (if lay claim to ILLEGAL INDIANS = have to transport to ur white location) when supposed ret. to india-land = never equated with migrant usa-13 tiger (Or any nordic) but if like to claim illegal indians with illegal malaysians-ATM over robbed phoenix = transport indians over (Love white states, dont like chinese, just place convenience over dislike of india). if shell to shell home (hv explain all crimes COMPUTE AMT)</p> <p>otherwise, illegal Indians themselves e.g. Rajaratnam warwick etc (BUT STILL cavinder bull WB d.c. all from horse- x 60 = india-land. Classification india-Duration = eternal)</p>

	<p>if indian INSIST white endorse = transport indians over white states. (require white states signature USA-13 EUROPE = confirm for indians = not nordic not allowed phoenix) WHICHEVER refuse to sign = know who</p> <p>(additional confirmation = in addition to 'shell-logo paste-i-tron etc) saying only need PRESS: 000, fellow criminals</p> <p>electricity free forever. (no claim = cannot touch soil of any land, transport illegal-indians + cement etc)</p> <p>(anyway = time = eventually, ret. india</p> <p>say require white states signature USA-13 EUROPE = confirm for indians = not nordic not allowed phoenix e.g. cement building filled illegal indians self-title NORDIC = signed then confirm = not nordic, ban from whole asia = know who culprit + end-illegal indians, if insist = transport over that white)</p> <p>this signed document = is legit evidence contribution.</p>
	AIIB
	<p>required per nation collection money = AIIB is illegal criminals NOT any nation x 100plus CONFIRMED.</p> <p>1 criminal record x 60 consistent format = transport illegal indians 1-location + cement + vehicles = x100plus (repeat crime x 60 compute inside phoenix star base)</p>
	CORRECT COMPUTE = DIFFUSION
	<p>correct compute of stolen money key to diffusion</p> <p>correct money approval based on economy compute for selected states = correct ATM (cn hk phoenix etc</p>
	LURE HORSE-STACKING 'OC' CHIP-genocide: PRETEND HIGH DEMAND
	<p>correct compute of stolen money key to diffusion</p> <p>correct money approval based on economy compute for selected states = correct ATM (cn hk phoenix etc</p> <p>USE money lure HORSE-PP = trap then chip-genocide (y stacking 'oc' BAN ALL-'c' = change to landed with veg fruit = no more supermarket chain stash anyway s/w press:000)</p> <p>thus, 1 way (correct dollar base on theft x time-frame + per c-state + diffusion system) = no more stash.</p>
	LURE HORSE-STACKING 'OC' CHIP-genocide: PRETEND HIGH DEMAND
	<p>pretend 'high demand' for malaysians transport Illegal-indian illegal stacking over robbed DISTRICT-BY-DISTRICT RET. evacuation unto landed = then</p>

	<p>criminals planning = transport illegal Indian + cement + vehicles + put HIMSELFHERSELF-only PRESS: 000 ATM-CONMEN repeat crime other locations (also no claim)</p> <p>(copy hk but also no claim over hk)</p> <p>so LAW-LESS INSOL-illegal indians AUTO-VOID criminal paperwork consistent record x 60 -100 (BAN WHOLE ASIA x eternal) malaysian office x 60 in all glyph listed no claim over = can GUN DOWN close files = change back landed</p> <p>EXAMPLE: AIIB is illegal criminals NOT any nation x 100plus CONFIRMED.</p> <p>required per nation collection money = ONE way to increase size cn ret. homeland (until all diffusion complete back phoenix per house farm temple) = becoz same TRAP use money lure out.</p> <p>(legitimate way to do CORRECTION MONEY per state based on theft etc)</p> <p>then 'excuse (very exceedingly) high demand' for malaysians (use flood-in x 60, then chip-genocide HORSE) & fabricated-'sg'-official-conmen-from robbed (not phoenix no claim over 'phoenix-cn-hk-any land' = thus conmen robbers) x 60 'excuse' transport Illegal-indian illegal stacking (into HIMSELF-ATM) over robbed = SORRY CAN GUN DOWN THEIR WHOLE illegal indian + malaysian etc family.</p>
	<p>(legitimate way to do CORRECTION MONEY per state based on theft etc)</p>
	<p>ATM-per cn state COMPUTE COMPLETE = no more 'pretend high demand for illegal + cement' = also, same change back landed per cn state</p> <p>EXAMPLE: CORRECTION MONEY per state based on theft = 'stacked' + WRONG LABEL 'b'-function / paste 'location name' etc CAN COMPUTE to adjust etc becoz HIMSELF-B-('self-title') no claim</p>
	<p>ID-PERP-Kpin (pre-med cement x 60)</p>
	<p>behaviour something wrong = kill own pp (questionable: HV 2 ID-PERP-Kpin pre-med cement x 60)</p>
	<p>[only official duty = 1 y TEMASEK or pap or tharman & Illegal-indians urself claim 1 piece Indian-land remove ALL-indians x 60 escort back india = settle permanently. COMPUTE all ringgit-'sg'-(something) whole island = closed = evacuate unto landed (based on robbed x 60) + ret. DISTRICT-BY-DISTRICT = No more stash.</p> <p>(then, see how adjust size CORRECTION MONEY based on theft-stash by HIMSELF-PRESS or stacked etc for glyph states evidence)]</p>
	<p>compute conglomerate theft x 60 + ret. satellite keys = relaunch rebuild per state protection + correct compute per glyph (use = lure into tiny space =</p>

illegal shoeboxes nonstop over robbed land x 60 NO CLAIM OVER 'phoenix-star x 60' 'cn' 'hk' all glyph states etc =

pretend 'high demand' for malaysians transport Illegal-indian illegal stacking over robbed DISTRICT-BY-DISTRICT RET. evacuation unto landed = then criminals planning = transport illegal Indian + cement + vehicles + put HIMSELFHERSELF-only PRESS: 000 ATM-CONMEN repeat crime other locations (also no claim)

(copy hk but also no claim over hk)

so LAW-LESS INSOL-illegal indians AUTO-VOID criminal paperwork consistent record x 60 -100 (BAN WHOLE ASIA x eternal) malaysian office x 60 in all glyph listed no claim over = can GUN DOWN close files = change back landed

let say no such white is alleged k-pin = then white just ask criminal malaysian even press: MONEY over inside Malaysia or inside ny or whichever = no claim over any x eternal + and no need touch any soil (transport indians cement etc) = required evacuate ALL INDIANS eventually + also required collect money back equivalent to theft amt per press x time-frame (large scale large sums collection) + diffusion into landed with veg (re-built) (then alleged 1-2 illegal Indian-use ATM machine is alleged k-pin = 1st place stay inside india) or cn = alleged touch ATM-so adjust size based on theft amt + landed (no more stacking 'oc') consider size country

INSERT PHOTO: **LARGEST F&B % THEFT OFF 'WAVE' CHIP CARD (FREQUENCY: NFC, WIRELESS WIFI)**

MACDONALDS / KFC (OR E-CASHIER S/W MANIPULATION COMPLICIT) ('e-b' / 'b')

KFC-HALF BODY PIXEL SCAN MICRO-CHIP (NFC)

MACDONALDS-HALF BODY PIXEL SCAN MICRO-CHIP (NFC) (USA-13: USD + SGD)

LEGAL ANALYSIS:

4. Largest F&B (PERP knows largest volume of fast-food traffic based on sales revenue): to commit Pixel Scan Micro-Chip (CO-VAX CHIP: RF KILL)
5. E-Cashier Theft: For example, software programmable E-cashier theft just by pressing: 000 (Thus, motive to be complicit as it has become pointless to sell food for money when PERP-F&B Supermarket can just press: 000)

JAPANESE BURGER-HALF BODY PIXEL SCAN MICRO-CHIP (NFC)

Compare 1. Female head size with pixel scan micro-(CO-VAX)-chip (NFC, WiFi = Wireless 'Finance' Theft (Data Transmission) Kill-off Post-Loot (Murder)

Compare 1. Male head size with pixel scan micro-(CO-VAX)-chip (NFC, WiFi = Wireless 'Finance' Theft (Data Transmission) Kill-off Post-Loot (Murder)

Micro-Chip scan RF Kill (data transmission CO-VAX chip-transmitter): whilst paying to play (WiFi = Wireless 'Finance', Infra-Chip: \$5 x killer shots x no. y AMT Time playing)

1. Easy manufacture LED PIXEL DIY brandless: lorry to 'transport' (/ wrong ICAO) over (India / Malaysian Indians used to target SG-PLUS 3 USMCA PLOT / Factories labelled GLYPH)

Summation Equation: 1. Supermarket Theft (e.g. LED Pixel APP programmable S/W), 2. Theft of Pay-Gang Supermarkets, F&B i.e. all electronic-counters (e.g. satellite log-on) + 3. M-Bridge

To sum-up, there is high potential for electronic theft (all types: Wal-Mart monopoly Supermarket ('food'), largest F&B franchise burgers & fries, pizzas, ice-blended coffee rip-off or complicit F&B ('food') in the M-Bridge example

also, becomes pointless meaning there is no more need to sell anything if product sellers can get (electronic-)'money' without making a sale. So there is Supermarket theft F&B: pizzas / burger & fries theft / Tier 2 self-titled 'b' container of nations' loot bank: all with LED full body image (organ / neural) scan electronic (APP s/w programmable) e-cashier LED payment counter in conjunction with M-Bridge type of CO-VAX CHIP in-brain graphical network of nodes (in-brain: end-user and all mentioned E-counter stalls selling products).

LEGAL ANALYSIS

The preliminary assessment based on the criminal blueprint mapping analysis of the 'MCB-PLATFORM' is to commit the robbery of the largest F&B (with the click of a button). This criminal act means: For example, in FIG. 1B, highlighted brands are: MacDonalds, Starbucks, are no longer owners since the checkpoint cashier's computer screen DIY brandless include Italy / India (recruits) [because criminal Italian ('Fish'-)Dagon (any random pax) host of large supermarkets (/ chain-store 7-11) sudden influx (with a sticker-on') / infiltration of LARGE PIXEL DIY brandless cashier's screens': typical options include 'ALIPAY'.

The first criminal act: to steal a percentage (%) off per groceries / steal a percentage (%) off per MacDonald's meal. This is illegal. The whole idea is supposed to be a 1. One-time installation in order to for convenience's sake 2. facilitate chipped-card transactions. But perpetrator decided by himself to go ahead: additionally configured a per transaction percentage (%) theft. Thus, this is criminal (theft: stealing x multiplied by the no. of the largest F&B sales).

The second criminal act: the methodology to get all (illegal container and obviously greedy) banks hooked into a global trap. The wireless connection transfers all chip data [of whichever bank issued / factory manufactured with bank shops' name printed on the physical chip-card] to a computer chip / core with 'controller' / 'processor' tracking transaction and chip data thus effectively eliminating the (eventual) need for any (illegal container) bank. A remote computer in any con-site: which is also why the DIY brandless make with criminal purpose to conceal information about PERP i.e. illegal intent to be 'trace-less' is against protocol.

PERP already stated his intent: all central banks, financial institutions ... because he figures all banks contain monies for all required transactions by criminal methodology of remotely capturing all chip data via wireless (frequency band) transmissions (I figured).

The third criminal act: all perpetrators (such as illegal container banks / card-imposters looting nations) fight to 1. Steal 'electricity' (free-of-charge) 2. get devices installed for meter (circuitry) charging.

In contrast, an established brand can be identified, or the department of justice can request for an 'unlock' and is comparatively more socially responsible compared to an intentionally 'trace-less' criminal with intent to commit large global (F&B) sales (chip-card) theft.

EVIDENCE EXAMINATION: PROGRAMMABLE E-WALLET SYNAPSE-YUAN (NOT MONEY) (WI-FI) PROGRAMMABLE SYNAPSE (THE CRIMINALLY ACCURATE VERSION)

Programmable E-Wallet (NOT MONEY) Synapse-YUAN Model: China Chinese Group (Criminal Technical Analysis)

8.2. COMPUTER SYNAPSE-YUAN MODEL: PP BANK OF CHINA (NOT CHINA) (CRIMINALLY ACCURATE VERSION) CRIMINAL MODEL USING

UNDER DATA PROTECTION LAW: ('BODILY' 'BRAIN' CELLS: FUNCTION)

INTERNATIONAL LAW: CO-VAX CIRCUITRY ('FREQUENCY WAVE') GENOCIDE

FIN-(GER) TECH LAW: SPACE LAW

NEUROMORPHIC PRODUCTS TYPE

8.5. ALIPAY NEURAL NETWORK MODEL:

8.5.2. ALIPAY MODEL: (Brain-based) Shopping Method and device based on Brain-computer and Brain-Nerve Signals and E-Equipment (CN113421141A) (裴龙凯)

FIG. 1 ALIPAY SHOPPING PROCESSING METHOD BASED ON BRAIN-COMPUTER NERVE SIGNALS ELECTRONIC EQUIPMENT

图1

In this Alipay Patent, “Shopping Processing Method and Device based on Brain-Computer and Brain Nerve Signals and Electronic Equipment”⁹⁵ consists of a display of steps by acquiring: (1) **consciousness content** information containing the item information to be purchased through a **brain-computer signal extraction interface** (2) sending the **item information** to server (interaction module) and receiving commodity content information returned by the server, (3) generating and sending back **feedback signal** according to item content information through brain-computer signal feedback interface, through a **brain-computer signal feedback interface** for user (4) to **perceive** item in order to acquire ‘consciousness content information’ containing **ordering decision** (through a **brain-computer signal extraction interface**) (5) sending ordering instruction to server according to ordering decision.

图4

图5

FIG. 4, for instance, the brain-based shopping process comprises of steps: (1) acquiring first cranial nerve signal, decoding the first cranial nerve signal and generating (and acquiring user first **consciousness content information** by the consciousness content information acquisition module used) of user X (through a consciousness processing module of brain-computer signal extraction interface); (2) suppose the first consciousness content information contains a **purchase decision** of a specified commodity e.g. textbook X, the commodity information of specified **commodity** (in the first consciousness **content**) is contained in commodity **query request** and sent to server (3) **receiving** commodity content information **returned by server** (4) **encoding** commodity content information to generate second cranial nerve signal (5) **inputting**

⁹⁵ 裴龙凯 (2020) *Shopping Processing Method and Device Based on Brain-Computer and Brain Nerve Signals and Electronic Equipment*. United States Patent Office. Patent No. CN 113421141A. Available: <https://patents.google.com/patent/CN113421141A/en?q=CN113421141A>

the second cranial nerve signal to a cranial neuron and stimulating brain of user to generate perception content (PERCEPTRON)

LEGAL ANALYSIS

Firstly, it is clearly stated that the intrusive method comprises of electrodes (/ in my legal opinion: CO-VAX CHIPPED INJECTED CIRCUITRY of TRANSMITTERS) directly implanted into the cerebral cortex in order to obtain high-quality nerve signals. The brain nerve signals (illegal acquisition) identified by collecting the brain waves emitted. Alternatively, the brain-machine interface meaning CO-VAX CHIPPED INJECTED (electronic device) CIRCUITRY of LED micro-cellphones micro-constructed by micro-bots 1. (neuro-)transmitters of data brain waves emitted (NOT necessarily sensed by sensors since this is not required) 2. Brain-machine interface implanted inside cranial cavity (SEE: DR. NIXON'S MEDICAL EVIDENCE) / cerebral cortex based on cortical electroencephalogram (ECoG).

Secondly, it is also clearly stated that the computer device is a microchip (CO-VAX: MICROCHIP CIRCUITRY) which is a small computer device in-brain (IBM-TYPE 'processor' 'controller') micro-constructed by micro-bots programmable by WiFi (frequency waves) that performs coordination control (neuromorphic) system with a 'processor' of (OBVIOUSLY ALIPAY) transaction processing on a (NEURAL PAYPAL LACE NETWORK platform) with A. acquired information (SENSOR) by the brain signal acquisition module B. Transmitter transmission of brain nerve signal data fed back module criminally accomplished by (ALIPAY QUOTE) 'independent hardware circuits or chips' which matches perfectly the C. CO-VAX: MICROCHIP CIRCUITRY with hardware and software module D. remotely programmable by WiFi (frequency waves) E. with wireless connection to cloud server, cell tower, space satellite F. running on computer equipment.

Thirdly, ALIPAY explains that the original brain nerve signals come from 2-WAY implanted transmitters (for example, injected in-brain CO-VAX CHIP CIRCUITRY): Suppose an example of an implant of the CO-VAX CHIP is in fact for the criminal purpose to 1. Output brain nerve signals to the brain (e.g. input electric signals / magnetic signals / electromagnetic signals) to the neurons of the brain to trigger the brain to present some information ('contents') ALIPAY explains that 2. The brain controls sense organs e.g. signal acquisition and information feedback (from multiple senses e.g. visual information seen by user generated) acquired by stimulating neurons of the brain. (SEE FIG. 1: SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE OF BRAIN-COMPUTER DEVICE)

Fourthly, the signal pre-processing unit is used for amplifying acquired cranial nerve signals, signal feature extraction for extracting (time domain / frequency domain) features of the cranial nerve signals. Then the feature analysis unit processes using 'machine learning' and convert the brain neural signal features into

computer data (and to brain nerve so that feedback information is sent to the brain which the user can perceive). Then, perform, as clearly stated by ALI-PAY for OBVIOUS “subsequent transaction” processing. There is guarantee the electronic payment transaction is not conducted in-brain. It states, “the processing (of transaction) is by using a computer device” with interaction with a server (network) or transmission to other brain devices in a (neural) network (POP-100 CO-VAX CHIPPED circuitry constructed by micro-bots programmable by WiFi). Thus, explaining how the consciousness of shopping from the thinking activity of the brain user can generate a brain nerve signal collected through a brain-computer interface 2. Brain computer equipment further analyses consciousness content through processing logic 3. converted into computer readable format sent to a server of online shopping platform that displays commodity pictures, price information etc and content information includes sensory information, which 4. the brain machine encode to generate a brain nerve signal output back to the human brain as feedback signal (to stimulate the brain nerve to generate feedback of various senses). The user then 5. Selects and confirm the commodity to be purchased through brain consciousness and ordering decision confirmed.

INTENSITY OF BRAIN NERVE SIGNAL AS CRITERION

The strength of the brain wave signal or brain nerve electrical signal is used as auxiliary judgment for identification and confirmation of purchase decision. The willingness of the user to purchase decision is confirmed or not is determined according to the strength of corresponding brain nerve signal: When the strength of brain nerve signal is determined to be greater than a preset threshold, the shopping operation is triggered.

Thus, the brain-computer interface collects brain nerve signals of consciousness content information identified for ordering decision with order instruction sent to the server to complete commodity transaction.

The key reason why extensive write-up was offered under ALIPAY ‘shopping operation’ is obvious: it is a PAY product, so it concentrates on making a user pay and likely obtains electronic tokens per pay transaction. However, this is an illegal transaction. Inserting circuitry for transmission of brain signals to facilitate electronic payment in-brain is illegal. The criminal purpose is IBM-TYPE Neurogrid CO-VAX CHIPPED POP-100 genocide / systematic crime / war crime (mass murder) under international criminal law.

EVIDENCE EXAMINATION: PROGRAMMABLE E-WALLET SYNAPSE-YUAN (NOT MONEY) (WI-FI) PROGRAMMABLE SYNAPSE (THE CRIMINALLY ACCURATE VERSION)

Programmable E-Wallet (NOT MONEY) Synapse-YUAN Model: China Chinese Group (Criminal Technical Analysis)

8.2. COMPUTER SYNAPSE-YUAN MODEL: PP BANK OF CHINA (NOT CHINA) (CRIMINALLY ACCURATE VERSION) CRIMINAL MODEL USING

UNDER DATA PROTECTION LAW: ('BODILY' 'BRAIN' CELLS: FUNCTION)

INTERNATIONAL LAW: CO-VAX CIRCUITRY ('FREQUENCY WAVE') GENOCIDE

FIN-(GER) TECH LAW: SPACE LAW

NEUROMORPHIC PRODUCTS TYPE

8.5. ALIPAY NEURAL NETWORK MODEL:

8.5.3. ALIPAY (ALIPAY HANGZHOU INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY CO.) MODEL: (Disease Insurance by Computer Force) Event Investigation Method and Device (曲春雨)

LEGAL ANALYSIS

This is just an exemplary model specially chosen in light of the controversial 'severely disabled' insurance computer theft 'beyond' Singapore-phoenix military (CO-VAX CHIP) PLUS 3 scam: (> 1 such insurance)

Here, this Alipay Patent, "Event Investigation Method and Device"⁹⁶ speaks of 'insurance' being integrated into people's lives as a "guarantee mechanism" and spotting user's willingness to buy insurance to compensate for losses caused by accidents: For example, life insurance / injury insurance / health insurance e.g. medical insurance, disease insurance as an Alipay opportunity, and spotting a new opportunity, 'mutual insurance' which Alipay refers to as individuals with **homogeneous risk guarantee requirements**, by contracting, (1) pay premiums to form **mutual insurance funds** (suspicious) that claims to "bear responsibility for losses caused by contractually agreed accidents" or pay insurance funds when the insured dies / disabled / diseased e.g. (major) diseased mutual insurance e.g. engineered co-vid / contractually agreed death age e.g. elderly mutual insurance e.g. binary keys programmed frequency bandwidth waves synapse death (by co-vax chipped emitting MAC) from cell towers.

In other words, lab manufactured disease / disabled Insurance by Computer Force PERP intent by BIO-W (synonymous with 'H' = 'Health') CARD-imposter at the national level.

⁹⁶ : 廖梓函, 李楠, 曲春雨 (2021) *Event Investigation Method and Device*. United States Patent Office. Patent No. CN 113221529A. Available: <https://patents.google.com/patent/CN113221529A/en?q=CN113221529A>

FIG. 1 ALI-PAY (OR ANY-PAY GANG: REPLICATED FORMAT) 'DISEASE INSURANCE' PROGRAM

图1

图2

FIG. 1 shows a claim application initiated on the user terminal by a user participating in a disease insurance program. For example, user can simply apply for a 'claim' on user terminal / WeChat public number / Payment Account / Browser webpage / dialling a hotline phone.

The event information includes: user identity, (for health insurance settlement): medical records, diagnostic books, lab test sheets, admission / discharge off XX hospital.

CONTRAST:

8.5. **AMERICAN EXPRESS MODEL:**

8.5.4. **AMERICAN EXPRESS: (SEVERELY DISABLED INSURANCE APPLICABLE THEFT BY COMPUTER FORCE)**

Manging Insurance Product With an Insurance Value Chain (US2015/0206250A1) (Michael Concannon, John Anthony Levin)

FIG. 1

This American Express Patent, “Managing An Insurance Product With An Insurance Value Chain”⁹⁷ speaks of a once-off or recurring (DISEASE APPLICABLE INSURANCE THEFT BY COMPUTER FORCE) monetary payment⁹⁸ from the insured to the insurer, showing in FIG. 1, a network diagram including the API (Programmatic Interface: WB, Computer Bank of England) depicting client-server system with embodiments deployed. For example, application 106 ‘web client’ and 108 ‘programmatic client’ are coupled to multiple payment applications associated with multiple payment processors e.g. Visa, MasterCard and American Express. It describes the insurance co. seller’s user interface that include boxes for specifying age calculation basis e.g. Birthday, expiry age xx-xx-xx days (termination date / no longer available), min. max premiums per day, sums assured, ownership of product transferrable, increasing coverage allowed, renewal, converted into a different product, date which coverage becomes effective e.g. future date, additional set of product variables e.g. risk premium rates, coverage calculations or value maintenance, creation date set automatically by insurance value chain application e.g. system clock.

⁹⁷ Michael Concannon, John Anthony Levin (2012) *Managing An Insurance Product with An Insurance Value Chain*. United States Patent Office. Patent No. US 20150206250A1. Available: <https://patents.google.com/patent/US20150206250A1/en?q=US20150206250A1>

⁹⁸ Further details: The Judgment on CARD-IMPOSTERS insurance recurring theft by computer force e.g. severely disabled from BIO-W2 CO-VAX)

IBM MODEL: ANATOMICAL SEGMENTATION

8.5.5. IBM PATENT: System And Method For Virtual World Biometric Analytics Through The User of A Multi-Modal Biometric Analytical Wallet (AARON K. BAUGHMAN) (ANATOMICAL SEGMENTATION)

CONTRAST:

In the IBM Patent, "System and Method For Virtual World Biometric Analytics Through The Use of A Multimodal Biometric Analytical Wallet", shows obvious intent targeted at using biometrics (organ analysis etc) in order to rob by presenting the 'biometric analytic wallet' by proposing a pervasive repository for biometric data storage combination of e.g. biometric layer, genomic layer, health layer, privacy layer, and processing layer.

FIG. 2

FIG. 3

FIG. 4

FIG. 5

FIG. 6

FIG. 7

LEGAL ANALYSIS

Since FIG. 7 contains neural networks, this means there must be in-brain connection. Also, (IBM) k-clustering explained in previous examples: visual image digits formation.

It is clearly stated, that the (criminal purpose) of Bank of Algorithms 710 includes: genetic algorithms 750 used for bio-informatics / gene expression profiling / protein folding etc. This matches the gene-editing mRNA (global blacklisted: Indians recruits) under 'pretext' 'cancer' research institute, public 'health' (synonymous with BIO-W) and (wrong) 'medicine' (counter-feit medi-products) output e.g lab-made CO-VID.

FIG. 9 BIOMETRIC ANALYTIC INTERFACE KNOWLEDGE REP

Biometric Analytic Interface
Knowledge Representation

Type 1	.9 meters	Output (a1, a2, ..., ak)	Input (I1)
Type 2	.01 miles	Output (z1, t4)	Input (a1)
Type 3	2 feet	Output (z9, t7)	Input (a12)
...

↑ ↑ ↑ ↑
 900 910 920 930

FIG. 9

It is clearly stated that Events are used to determine when or how frequently biometric information is obtained from **virtual biometric wallet's biometric analytical interface**:

1. The input column 930 represents information sent to one or more algorithms, communication rules etc (included in processing layer of pervasive information) based on biometric analytic interface type. For example, under TYPE 1 (representative of virtual kiosk with a biometric analytical interface), it acquire and process information obtained from an 'avatar' e.g within 0.9 meter activation range (virtual-k).
2. There is an output column 920 that represents knowledge sent from and is: part of biometric analytical interface to acquisition device. The biometric analytical interface send information about the avatar as output.

EVIDENCE EXAMINATION: PROGRAMMABLE E-WALLET SYNAPSE-YUAN (NOT MONEY) (WI-FI) PROGRAMMABLE SYNAPSE (THE CRIMINALLY ACCURATE VERSION)

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UNDER DATA PROTECTION LAW: ('BODILY' 'BRAIN' CELLS: FUNCTION)

INTERNATIONAL LAW: CO-VAX CIRCUITRY ('FREQUENCY WAVE') GENOCIDE

FIN-(GER) TECH LAW: SPACE LAW

NEUROMORPHIC PRODUCTS TYPE

8.6. TENCENT NEURAL NETWORK MODEL:

8.6.1. TENCENT 'HEALTHCARE' SHENZHEN CO. LTD MODEL: (Brain) Image (Using Cloud) Segmentation Method, Device, Equipment, Program Product and Medium (黄雅雯, 黄慧敏, 王红, 李悦翔)

It is clear by now (global witness) that CARD-IMPOSTER 'Heath' of 'children' criminally accurate meaning is interchangeable with (perpetrator's contextual meaning): BIO-W in conjunction with GRAPHENE [NEURAL NET] CIRCUITRY by Ex-and-repeat criminal record: 'BIG-PHARMA' so this Tencent 'Healthcare' is specially picked as exemplary model with application filed by in-location Shenzhen Co. Ltd.

In this TENCENT Patent, "Image Segmentation Method, Device, Equipment, Program Product and Medium"⁹⁹, under international law, the steps: acquire a characteristic image of a target object 1. Extraction of image features (according to image features in category) 2. Obtain (a block) sequence of (characteristic) image through convolution calculation (according to image characteristics in category) 3. Calculate a pixel set (according to image features in category) to obtain category central features of feature images 4. Interact **block sequences** and category central features to obtain enhanced category central features 5. **Splicing** the enhanced category central features and image features (in categories) to obtain image features between categories 6. Segmenting the characteristic image (according to image characteristics between categories to obtain a segmentation result of characteristic image of **target object**). The purpose is to improve image segmentation accuracy and adapt to different image segmentation scenes.

DEFINITION OF TENCENT CNN

Tencent defines convolutional neural networks (CNN) as a class of Feed-FWD Neural Networks that contain convolutional computations with deep structure / learning (shift-invariant classification) algorithms.

Deep learning frames for example, Tensor Flow, Torch etc constructs the model. The multi-segmentation network is formed by combing multiple layers of Neural Network Layers CNN. Input for the model is a three channel or original channel matrix by reading images through e.g. OpenCV and other tools. Output of the model is multi-classification probability. Final output of image segmentation result from e.g. softmax and other algorithm. To approach the correct trend, target functions, use e.g. cross entropy.

DEFINITION OF TENCENT CNN

Tencent defines convolutional neural networks (CNN): Artificial Neural Network is a computational (mathematical) model that imitates the function / structure of the biological Neural Network of the central nervous system / brain. It is classified under the field of machine learning and cognitive science used for estimating (approximating) functions.

⁹⁹ 黄雅雯, 黄慧敏, 王红, 李悦翔 (2023) *Image Segmentation Method, Device, Equipment, Program Product and Medium*. CN115965785A. Available (Google Patent):

TENCENT FIG. 2 IMAGE SEGMENTATION USING TRANSFORM NETWORK CONVENTIONAL SCHEMATIC

图2

FIG. 2 transform network includes 2 structures: Multi-head attention Mechanism (MHA) and one-site fully-connected feed-forward network (FFN). Firstly inputting a characteristic diagram, obtaining 3 non-linear mappings: **Query (Q)**, **key value (K)**, **value item (V)**. The dot product between Q and K transpose is first calculated then resulting **attention matrix (HW x HW)** normalized to a probability distribution using SOFTMAX operation and multiplied by matrix V to obtain a representation of the sum of weights. The enhanced images are input into FFN learning more non-linear r/s between features.

LEGAL ANALYSIS

FIG. 2 can be captured from endoscopic video which is pathological information of a video state formed by image-capturing a body region of different organs of a human body or an in-vivo lesion by an image-capturing device. Now, this is very close to my (extremely accurate or in fact) criminal hypothesis (factual perpetrator's obvious intent) of the global CCTV (DIY brandless) LED PIXEL e.g. in public right-of-way. Secondly, it matches perfectly the criminal intent and criminal act of real-time remote kill-shot aim capability of the IBM-TYPE CO-VAX CHIPPED POP-NEUROGRID 100+ of INJECTED TRANSMITTERS connected to WiFi cell towers and space-satellites, remotely programmable [with delay or timeslot configured] in a computer 'controller' 'processor' 'memory' base station. Also, filming is illegal in public places (worldwide law).

FIG. 2 medical images is proof of capability to analyze (NOT just X-RAY capture) target regions e.g. regions of lesion tissues (brain tissues). TENCENT confirms the following:

The data transmission (e.g. CO-VAX CHIPPED POP-NEUROGRID 100+ of INJECTED TRANSMITTERS) is implemented by using a wireless link (matches my criminal hypothesis: criminal intent / criminal act / criminal method of operation 'modus operandi').

FIG. 1 TERMINAL 10-1, 10-2: MEDICAL IMAGES OF TARGET OBJECTS

图1

SEE: SEPARATE JUDGMENT BRIEFING PAPER	INTL LAW BIO-MEDICINE LAW & PHARMACEUTICAL MEDI-CRIME LAW)
-(CRIMINAL TECHNICAL ANALYSIS & EVIDENCE-BASED,	illegal-indians nano-BW-INDIA

LEGAL ANALYSIS UNDER INTERNATIONAL LAW:

The **TYPES** of medical images of **TARGET OBJECTS** (meaning specific **ORGANS/TISSUES** which matches the pharma crime / medi-crime product / international law: **CHIP-genocide, systematic CHIP-crime, CHIP-war crime: of the CO-VAX GRAPHENE fluid of transmitters dispersed throughout the body (brain) in conjunction with programmable WIFI. SEE: BLOOD CLOT Medical evidence documented**). TENCENT confirms and clearly states, “image segmentation [using deep convolutional neural network algorithm] of a focus tissue region” (etiological diagnosis). Also, TENCENT highlights that the convolutional neural network technology adopts illegal encoder-decoder technology. It opts to adopt reversible residual error network RevNet technology (intermediate calculation Microsoft 060606-TYPE parameters increased).

Also, TENCENT clearly states, (QUOTE) ‘obtained by terminal 10-1, 10-2’ which means cellphones. TENCENT confirms that terminals 10-1, 10-2 can acquire ‘pathological image or medical image set (CT image) matched with the target object’ from SERVERS 200 (storage of auxiliary analysis, endoscopic images) through NETWORK 300 (Either: wide area network / local area network / combination of) (even ‘for browsing’ by unknown perpetrator being the implication). This is the reason why illegal TELCOM CO. with coverage of T-MOBILE US / NASDAQ / I-T-SYSTEM EUR GATEWAY were called to U.S. courthouses to obtain illegal licensing through criminal agencies FCC (IEEE) and outlawed in Italian Court (European coalition ban on 5G). TENCENT clearly stated that terminal 200 is located in institutions e.g. (QUOTE) “hospitals and medical research institutes” with medical attributes (for the criminal purpose) of acquiring with image acquisition device terminal 200 (or acquisition device terminal 400 which is a functional blood ‘sucking’ extraction device) e.g. a fundus image “i.e. blood vessel image to be processed” of a (e.g. CO-VID / CO-VAX) patient” (SEE: FIG. 1, 13) in order to perform blood vessel segmentation / classification of fundus image and output the results in graphical manner to get doctors 1. to perform the (criminally profitable CDC patented processes of) ‘diagnosis, re-diagnosis and (ILLEGAL CO-VAX CIRCUITRY INJECT) treatment methods of (LAB MANUFACTURED CO-VID) diseases” and 2. (QUOTE: TENCENT) ‘Morphological performances of different types of blood vessels” which totally matches the IBM-INTEL-TYPE neuro-morphic systems documented.

TENCENT even confirms the **capability of blood vessel characteristic** image segmentation. For instance, the (1) shapes / densities of diverse tumor capillaries (tissue) (2) plurality of signal paths participating in regulation and controlling the growth of capillaries and in response to (3) prognosis and ‘treatment’ of patient (4) micro-vessels / mature vessels separation (mutually distinguished) with intra-class variations reduced / inter-class variations improved and overall vastly improved accuracy of image segmentation. In other words, (criminal psychopathic) perpetrators of neuromorphic systems know / believe in blood-morph (meaning blood mutation) as a key element thus the emphasis on ‘regulating / controlling’ growth of capillaries which matches the SAMSUNG discussion on engraftment into capillaries.

Furthermore, exemplary TENCENT (PAY-GANG-TYPE / electronic devices / TELCOM / EMV pilot tested NY Tier 2 banks) confirms that data protection law (GDPR) is continually illegally breached since it admits, “images are continuously [FREQUENCY PENETRATED] generated as different time points are required” claiming [CO-VID, CO-VAX CHIPPED] patients’ [BLOOD CLOT / ORGAN DAMAGE] condition are “continuously shot” thus accumulating a large amount of data therefore illegally justifying the urgent need to implement large-scale classification and identification’ with classification prediction.

Thirdly, TENCENT confirms

Fourthly, TENCENT confirms that this image segmentation apparatus comprises of hardware decoding processor of integrated circuit chip with signal processing capabilities (in my legal opinion, CO-VAX transmitter in-brain matches description) e.g. (1) Application Specific **Integrated Circuits (CHIP)** (ASICs) (2) Digital **Signal Processor** (DSP) (3) Programmable Logic Device (PLD) (4) Complex Programmable Logic Devices (CPLDs) (5) Field-Programmable Gate Array (FPGAs) (6) Programmable Logic Device, (7) Discrete Gate (8) Transistor Logic (9) Microprocessor and any convention processor.

TENCENT FIG. 3 EFFECT OF IMAGE SEGMENTATION USING TRANSFORM NETWORK CONVENTIONAL SCHEMATIC (DIAGRAM)

图3

TENCENT FIG. 12 MONU SEG DATA SET AND RELATED ART TESTS (COMPARISON)

图12

FIG. 3 (a) and (c) shows segmentation results: TransUNet and FIG. 3 (b) and (d) shows segmentation results: SwinUNet. The relationship between PIXEL points on the liver and organs e.g. stomach / left right kidney (QUOTE) TENCENT clearly states, “can be captured at a long distance”.

TENCENT states the conventional transform acts on feature map without distinguishing the classes and edge of division result is blurred (all class objects highlighted at once). The weighted set of all these salient regions (based on multiple object inference) results in (DIRECT QUOTE) exactly called, “confusing pixel-to-pixel” relationships that compromise intra-class consistency learning thus incomplete stomach segmentation in FIG. 3.

To solve this program FIG. 4 alternative flowchart is executed using various electronic devices operating segmentation network: 1. Server with medical image processing terminal 2. Image segmentation function or 3. server cluster to implement accurate segmentation for complex images adapted in different usage scenarios.

FIG. 4 IMAGE SEGMENTATION (FLOW)

图4

FIG. 5 TENCENT MODEL STRUCTURE OF A CLASS-AWARE NETWORK
 INTRA-CLASS DYNAMIC TRANSFORMER INTER-CLASS INTERACTIVE TRANSFORMER

图5

FIG. 5 is a TENCENT model structure of a class-aware network (ClassFormer):

1. Intra-Class Dynamic converter network model (IDT Intra-Class Dynamic converter) and Inter-Class Dynamic converter network model (IIT Inter-Class Interactive) Transformer

2. Sequentially processing through IDT (LEFT) and IIT module (RIGHT). 3. Finally, enhanced image characteristics X between categories are output inter. A complex image segmentation segmented utilizing image characteristics in categories and segmentation result with clear edges and accurate segmentation obtained.

TENCENT FIG. 6 INTRA-CLASS DYNAMIC TRANSLATOR NETWORK MODEL (OPERATION)

图6

FIG. 6 is schematic of intra-class dynamic Transformer Network model with global relationship for feature map of each class.

FIG. 6 is a 1. decoupled Class C feature image X with input c ; 2. Query feature Q obtained by linear projection $c = X c W_q$. 3. Query features are input into a simple saliency sense network θ_{SN} (includes: convolutional layers and active layers) 4. PIXELS of TARGET CLASS feature image re-weighted i.e. weights of salient pixels increased, while weights of irrelevant pixels suppressed.

The aware network θ_{SN} , input features subjected to: 3×3 convolution operation and GELU activation function to extract local features.

Pooling along channel dimension can effectively activate the information region, maixma and means on channel side can be pooled and then connected. The stitched features are processed through 3×3 convolution layer (in FIG. 6) to obtain saliency perception map: where H/W = height and width.

Here, p is the position of each pixel. Thus, a set of significant positions Λ is formed over entire space Λ .

$$\hat{p} = \arg \max_{p \in \Lambda} M(p)$$

Saliency map M is first (1) divided into a set of non-overlapping sub-regions Λ uses a sliding window of size δ_s .

to achieve dynamic key value K selection across space Λ .

$$M = \theta_{SN}(Q_C) \in \mathbb{R}^{H \times W}$$

Each sliding window matching the target object is determined according to the total scale number and δ_s . δ_s clearly states, FIG. 6 is a pyramid mechanism adopted to adaptively sample salient points from multiple scales.

For each scale, a different significance aware network θ is used SN. Corresponding 1. δ_s (i.e. size of sliding window) 2. Unique patterns of different scales adaptively learned. Thus, the pyramid (shown below):

$$\tilde{P} = \{P_s\}_{s=1}^S$$

Information extracted from different scales is fused wherein S is the total scale number. From the salient position P , X is input c .

Extracting significant features further obtains key value K through linear projection c Sum term V c :

$$K_C = \tilde{X}_C W_k, \quad V_C = \tilde{X}_C W_V \circ$$

Continuing to capture remote dependency, via multi-headed attention mechanism:

$$Z_c = \text{softmax}(Q_c K_c^T / \sqrt{D}) V_c。$$

Combining enhance sequences from different classes:

$$Z = \{Z_c\}_{c=1}^C$$

Converting the image into a 2-D feature, splicing the 2-dimensional feature with original input feature, inputting the 2-dimensional feature into a convolutional layer of 1*1 size, and generating a final image feature or of the image in the output class):

$$X_{\text{intra}} \in \mathbb{R}^{H \times W \times D}$$

Where H/W/D = is height, width, feature dimension (corresponding to feature image).

TENCENT FIG. 7 INTER-CLASS DYNAMIC TRANSLATOR NETWORK MODEL (OPERATION)

图7

FIG. 7 is (high-level) schematic diagram of TENCENT network model of INTER-CLASS DYNAMIC TRANSFORMER convolutional step size of H/r W/r D [obtained using 1-maximal pooling layer with convolution step size r and 2 consecutive convolution layers with size 3*3 and its shape further transformed into] [matching with an image feature in-class first determined performing convolution processing on image

features (in-category) according to convolution step length to obtain] block sequence [with rich semantics / patch sequence] of feature image meaning specific inputting of image features in-category.

Thus, the intra-class dynamic transformer network model completes image processing process and outputs the intra-class image features to inter-class dynamic transformer network model.

Thus, the active layer uses (1) GELU activation function, (2) SOFTMAX activation function (3) ReLU activation function.

TENCENT FIG. 10 IMAGE SEGMENTATION METHOD IN SYNAPSE DATA SET AND RELATED ART TEST (SEGMENTATION EFFECT)

图10

TENCENT FIG. 11 IMAGE SEGMENTATION METHOD IN ACDC DATA SET DATA SET AND RELATED ART TEST (SEGMENTATION EFFECT)

图11

FIG. 10 and FIG. 11 are evidence of image segmentation method in synapse data set and test of related technology.

CRIMINAL EVIDENCE

TENCENT FIG. 8 IMAGE SEGMENTATION METHOD SYNAPSE DATASET AND RELATED ART TEST

Method	Params	DSC	HD	Aorta	Gallbladder	Kidney(L)	Kidney(R)	Liver	Pancreas	Spleen	Stomach
V-Net	45.60	68.81	-	75.34	51.87	77.10	80.75	87.84	40.05	80.56	56.98
U-Net	31.04	76.85	39.70	89.07	69.72	77.77	68.60	93.43	53.98	86.67	75.58
AttUNet	34.88	77.77	36.02	89.55	68.88	77.98	71.11	93.57	58.04	87.30	75.75
R50 ViT	103.77	71.29	32.87	73.73	55.13	75.80	72.20	91.51	45.99	81.99	73.95
TransUNet	105.28	77.48	31.69	87.23	63.13	81.87	77.02	94.08	55.86	85.08	75.62
SwinUNet	27.17	79.12	21.55	85.47	66.53	83.28	79.61	94.29	56.58	90.66	76.60
UCTransNet	66.43	78.23	26.75	88.86	66.97	80.19	73.18	93.17	56.22	87.84	79.43
MTUNet	79.08	78.59	26.59	87.92	64.99	81.47	77.29	93.06	59.46	87.75	76.81
AFTerUNet	41.50	81.02	-	90.91	64.81	87.90	85.30	92.20	63.54	90.99	72.48
MISSFormer	42.46	81.96	18.20	86.99	68.65	85.21	82.00	94.41	65.67	91.92	80.81
ScaleFormer	111.58	82.86	16.81	88.73	74.97	86.36	83.31	95.12	64.85	89.40	80.14
ClassFormer	35.43	84.40	12.22	89.04	72.91	88.95	85.68	95.55	69.25	90.70	83.09

图8

TENCENT FIG. 9 ACDC DATA SET AND MONUSEG DATA SET (COMPARISON)

Methods	DSC	RV	Myo	LV
R50 UNet	87.55	87.10	80.63	94.92
R50 AttUNet	86.75	87.58	79.20	93.47
R50 ViT	87.57	86.07	81.88	94.75
TransUNet	89.71	88.86	84.53	95.73
SwinUNet	90.00	88.55	85.62	95.83
TransUNet*	89.63	86.70	86.96	95.33
SwinUNet*	89.16	87.04	86.22	94.24
MTUNet*	89.84	86.06	88.14	95.32
UCTransNet*	90.11	88.01	87.29	95.02
ScaleFormer*	90.17	87.33	88.16	95.04
ClassFormer	90.99	88.35	89.08	95.54

Methods	DSC	IoU
U-Net	73.97	59.42
UNet++	75.28	60.89
AttUNet	76.20	62.64
MedT	79.24	65.73
MISSFormer	76.04	61.58
MTUNet	77.97	64.30
TransUNet	79.20	65.68
SwinUNet	78.49	64.72
UCTransNet	79.87	66.68
ScaleFormer	80.06	66.87
ClassFormer	80.75	67.88

图9

ADDITIONAL LEGAL ANALYSIS ON TENCENT In addition, the TENCENT Patent, “Image Classification Method, Device, Equipment, Storage Medium and Medical Electronic Equipment”¹⁰⁰, in FIG. 3 reveals a somewhat illicit coordination with GOOGLE NET:

¹⁰⁰ 揭泽群, 赵波, 冯佳时 (2022) Image Classification Method, Device, Equipment, Storage Medium and Medical Electronic Equipment. CN110276411B. Available:

TENCENT FIG. 3 ILLICIT COORDINATION WITH GOOGLNET

图3A

FIG. 3A shows schematic process of image classification method with illicit pre-meditated coordination with GOOGLE NET against CO-VAX CHIPPED GRAPHENE NEURAL LINKED NEUROGRID POP-100+.

FIG. 3B LOSS OF MAMMARY GLAND: TENCENT COMPUTATION LOGIC WITH GOOGLE NET (NEURAL GRAPHENE NET LINKED-IN WB)

图3B

FIG. 3A shows cc-bit image, mlo-bit image of left / right breast of human body. TENCENT clearly states, “googlenet network sharing parameters” and “vectorized image features” of each image. This is a perfect match with the MICROSOFT 060606 Patent on ‘parameters’ and ‘vectors’ of bodily (ELON MUSK NEURAL LACE NET) cells.

TENCENT based on the breasts images, could even give a computation logic mathematical elaborate expansion on MICROSOFT'S 060606 'parameters' and 'vectors' of bodily cells: For example, 1024-dimensional vectorized feature generated for each input image using pool 5/7 x 7 \ u s1 layer in googlenet (likely ILLEGAL usage of CLOUD) network. Fusion of four 1024-dimensional image features:

$f_{cc}^l, f_{mlo}^l, f_{cc}^R, f_{mlo}^R$. Thus, creating a 4096-dimensional fusion characteristic $F = [F]$ obtained.

The fusion characteristics pass through a full connection layer to obtain 4-dimensional vector (VECTOR) which represents confidence scores of (TENCENT QUOTE) 'left mammary gland and right' of so-called health (PERP's translation: BIO-W2) category and 'disease' (PERP LAB MANUFACTURED: CO-VID / CO-VAX circuitry payload release / frequency damage) categories:

$s_+^l, s_-^l, s_+^R, s_-^R$.
Then, the by now familiar TENCENT SOFTMAX function to pair with s_+^R, s_-^R .

1. Normalization is then performed to obtain probability p that (TENCENT QUOTE) the left breast belongs to health (BIO-W2) category and (LAB DESIGNED) 'disease' category: p_+^l, p_-^l .
 p_+^l denotes the probability that left breast image belongs to 'health' category. $d = 0$ when true category to which left breast image belongs to health category.
2. p_-^l denotes the probability that left breast image belongs to 'disease' category, $d = 1$ when true category to which left breast image belongs to 'diseased' category. $d =$ annotation true value.

Thus, TENCENT COMPUTATION LOGIC / MATHEMATICAL EQUATIONS:

$$p_+^l = \exp(s_+^l) / (\exp(s_+^l) + \exp(s_-^l))$$

$$p_-^l = \exp(s_-^l) / (\exp(s_+^l) + \exp(s_-^l))$$

S can be paired with TENCENT'S SOFTMAX FUNCTION:

$$s_{+}^R, s_{-}^R$$

3. Normalization is then performed to obtain right side probability of mammary gland belonging to

health (BIO-W) and (LAB DESIGNED) 'disease' class: p_{+}^r, p_{-}^r .

4. p_{+}^r denotes the probability that left breast image belongs to 'health' category. $d = 0$ when true category to which left breast image belongs to health category.

5. p_{-}^r denotes the probability that left breast image belongs to 'disease' category, $d = 1$ when true category to which left breast image belongs to 'diseased' category. $d =$ annotation true value.

Pertaining to breast medical image, the first fully connected network outputs a probability representing that the left / right breast image belongs to 'health' (BIO-W) and (LAB DESIGNED) disease category.

3. The loss of left breast image calculated by TENCENT using the formula:

$$L_{left} = d \log(p_{+}^l) + (1 - d) \log(p_{-}^l)$$

The loss of right breast image calculated by TENCENT using the formula:

$$L_{right} = d \log(p_{+}^r) + (1 - d) \log(p_{-}^r)$$